

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D3.3

A co-created portfolio of mission-relevant pilot activities to support evaluation of project tools and methods

Planned delivery date: 31/01/2025 [M32]

Actual submission date: 2.0

Deliverable leader: 12- CSIC

Authors: Josep L. Pelegrí (report coordinator), Carine Simon, María Elena Carbajal, Noemí Fuster, Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini, Gustavo González Hurtado (CSIC); Caecilia Managò (ERINN); Maria Vittoria Marra (GAA); Elisabeth Morris-Webb (NRI); Francesco M. Falcieri (CNR); David Whyte (UCC)

Type of deliverable: Report

Work package Leader: WP3 - UCC

Version: 2.0

Project funded by the European Commission within the HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO Confidential, only for member of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2022

www.Prepare4Blue.eu

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DISCLAIMER

“PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters” has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call *“Preparation for deployment of ‘lighthouse demonstrators’ and solution scale ups and cross-cutting citizen and stakeholder involvement (HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01)”*, Grant Agreement n° 101056957.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This document contains information on PREP4BLUE core activities. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation, and publication date. The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the PREP4BLUE Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). *“PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters”* has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01, Grant Agreement n. 101056957.

VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Authors (Institution)	Notes
1.0	30.11.2024	Josep L. Pelegrí (report coordinator), Carine Simon, María Elena Carbajal, Noemí Fuster, Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini, Gustavo González Hurtado (CSIC); Caecilia Managò (ERINN); Maria Vittoria Marra (GAA); Elisabeth Morris-Webb (NRI); Francesco M. Falcieri (CNR); David Whyte (UCC)	Preliminary draft submitted to the coordination.
1.1	02.12.2024, 03.12.2024, 05.12.2024, 06.12.2024	Cécile NYS (IFREMER)	Layout & Headings numbering review
1.2	02.12.2024	Cécile NYS (IFREMER)	Coordination content review
1.2.1	03.12.2024	David Whyte (UCC)	WP leader review
1.2.2	05.12.2024	Eirini Apazoglou (EuroMarine)	Coordination content review
1.3	21.01.2025	Josep L. Pelegrí	Final draft submitted to WP leader
1.4	22.01.2025	David Whyte (UCC)	Final review by WP leader
1.5	27.01.2025	Cécile NYS (IFREMER)	Final review by Coordination
1.6	28.01.2025	Josep L. Pelegrí	Integration of final reviews
2.0	29.01.2025	Josep L. Pelegrí (report coordinator), Carine Simon, María Elena Carbajal, Noemí Fuster, Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini, Gustavo González Hurtado (CSIC); Caecilia Managò (ERINN); Maria Vittoria Marra (GAA); Elisabeth Morris-Webb (NRI); Francesco M. Falcieri (CNR); David Whyte (UCC)	Final version (to submit)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS	9
1 INTRODUCTION TO NETWORK BUILDING AND MOBILISATION TO ENGAGE CITIZENS WITH THE MISSION ..	11
2 METHODS	15
2.1 ANALYSIS OF MISSION REQUIREMENTS.....	16
2.2 EXPLORATORY CONTACTS	17
2.3 TYPES OF NETWORKS	18
2.4 KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER.....	19
2.5 COLLABORATIVE CO-CREATION AND ENGAGED RESEARCH.....	19
2.6 PILOT ACTIONS: ENGAGING CITIZENS IN MISSION OCEAN.....	20
2.7 COMMUNITY BUILDING	21
3 RESULTS	23
3.1 NETWORK DEVELOPMENT.....	25
3.1.1 <i>Ocean Literacy Networks</i>	25
3.1.1.1 Irish Ocean Literacy Network.....	26
3.1.1.2 Catalan/Spanish Ocean Literacy Networks	28
3.1.1.3 BlueMed Network / Italian Ocean Literacy Network	29
3.1.2 <i>Coastal communities</i>	30
3.1.2.1 Barcelona City Network	31
3.1.2.2 Other Networks	34
3.1.3 <i>Art-Science Communities</i>	35
3.1.3.1 Blue Genes Community.....	35
3.1.3.2 Other Creative Activities	38
3.1.4 <i>Ocean Decade</i>	39
3.1.4.1 TransOcean: citizen engagement in the Decade and the Mission	40
3.1.4.2 The 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference	41
3.1.4.3 Ocean Cities Network and Cities with the Ocean Platform.....	41
3.1.4.4 Empowering Science, Policy and Society through Co-Design.....	44
3.1.4.5 Diving from Local to Global Ocean Literacy	45
3.1.4.6 Enbluement: Connecting Science and Art.....	47
3.2 PILOT ACTIONS.....	48
3.2.1 <i>Selection Process</i>	48
3.2.2 <i>Preparatory Sessions and Follow-up Support</i>	50
3.2.3 <i>PA1: Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship Training Course for Early Career Ocean Professionals</i>	52
3.2.3.1 Methodology.....	52
3.2.3.2 Outcomes.....	53
3.2.3.3 Good Practices	53
3.2.3.4 Lessons learned.....	53
3.2.3.5 Contribution to the Mission.....	53
3.2.4 <i>PA2: The BlueScape2024 Baltic Hackathon</i>	53
3.2.4.1 Methodology.....	54
3.2.4.2 Outcomes.....	54
3.2.4.3 Good Practices	54
3.2.4.4 Lessons Learned.....	55
3.2.4.5 Contribution to the Mission.....	55

3.2.5	<i>PA3: The Sea of Sounds</i>	55
3.2.5.1	Methodology.....	55
3.2.5.2	Results.....	55
3.2.5.3	Good Practices	56
3.2.5.4	Lessons Learned.....	56
3.2.5.5	Contribution to the Mission.....	56
3.2.6	<i>PA4: Sea Synergy Oyster Project</i>	56
3.2.6.1	Methodology.....	57
3.2.6.2	Results.....	57
3.2.6.3	Good Practices	58
3.2.6.4	Lessons Learned.....	58
3.2.6.5	Contribution to the Mission.....	58
3.2.7	<i>PA5: Blue Genes Giant Collaborative Puzzle</i>	58
3.2.7.1	Methodology.....	60
3.2.7.2	Outcomes.....	60
3.2.7.3	Good Practices	61
3.2.7.4	Lessons Learned.....	61
3.2.7.5	Contribution to the Mission.....	61
3.2.8	<i>PA6: Sustainable Coastal Futures</i>	61
3.2.8.1	Methodology.....	62
3.2.8.2	Outcomes.....	62
3.2.8.3	Good practices	63
3.2.8.4	Lessons Learnt.....	63
3.2.8.5	Contribution to the Mission.....	64
3.2.9	<i>Pilot Actions In-Person Final Meeting</i>	64
4	LEARNINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS ON CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT WITH THE MISSION	65
4.1	LEARNINGS	65
4.2	RECOMMENDATIONS	68
4.2.1	<i>Practical Project and Network Recommendations</i>	68
4.2.1.1	Project-Oriented Recommendations	68
4.2.1.2	Network-Oriented Recommendations.....	69
4.2.2	<i>Strategic Mission Recommendations</i>	71
4.2.2.1	Specific Mission recommendations	71
4.2.2.2	Collaborative Trust Missions.....	72
5	CONCLUSIONS	75
6	BIBLIOGRAPHY	76
7	ANNEXES	79
	ANNEX A. AN ALL-ISLAND OCEAN LITERACY NETWORK STRATEGIC PLAN 2024 – 2030.....	80
	ANNEX B. OCTOBER 2024 IOLN MEETING	87
	ANNEX C. THE BARCELONA CITY NETWORK.....	106
	ANNEX D. PROFILE OF MOODS STATE TEST	116
	ANNEX E. SHORT REPORT ON THE ESPAI MEDITERRANI NETWORK.....	119
	ANNEX F. OCTOBER 2022 BLUE GENES VIRTUAL MEETING.....	126
	ANNEX G. JUNE 2023 BLUE GENES VIRTUAL MEETING	131
	ANNEX H. DECEMBER 2023 BLUE GENES IN-PERSON MEETING	151
	ANNEX I. FEBRUARY 2024 BLUE GENES RETREAT - PROGRAM.....	166
	ANNEX J. FEBRUARY 2024 BLUE GENES RETREAT - REPORT	170
	ANNEX K. THE OCEAN CITIES NETWORK (OC-NET) PROGRAM	184

ANNEX L. SUMMARY OF OC-NET ACTIVITIES DURING ITS FIRST TWO YEARS	186
ANNEX M. OCEAN CITIES MONTH.....	194
ANNEX N. PREP4BLUE CALL FOR PILOT ACTIONS	202
ANNEX O. LIST OF PROPOSALS SUBMITTED TO THE PREP4BLUE CALL FOR PILOT ACTIONS	205
ANNEX P1. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA1: OCEAN LITERACY FOR BLUE CITIZENSHIP TRAINING COURSE	209
ANNEX P2. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA2: THE BLUESCAPE2024 BALTIC HACKATHON.....	225
ANNEX P3. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA3: THE SEA OF SOUNDS.....	250
ANNEX P4. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA4: SEA SYNERGY OYSTER PROJECT.....	267
ANNEX P5. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA5: BLUE GENES GIANT COLLABORATIVE PUZZLE	281
ANNEX P6. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA1: SUSTAINABLE COASTAL FUTURES.....	313

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS USED IN PREP4BLUE AND THE DOCUMENT.....	9
TABLE 2. EXPECTED OUTCOMES BY 2025 (1ST PHASE) AND BY 2030 (2ND PHASE) OF MISSION OCEAN & WATERS WITH RESPECT TO CITIZEN PARTICIPATION. THOSE OUTCOMES SPECIFICALLY ADDRESSED IN THIS REPORT ARE SHOWN ITALICISED (EDITED FROM THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION, IMPLEMENTATION PLAN FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS.).....	12
TABLE 3. OBJECTIVES/TARGETS ADDRESSED AND STRATEGIES USED BY THE PREP4BLUE PILOT ACTIVITIES (ON NETWORK BUILDING AND MOBILISATION TO ENGAGE CITIZENS WITH MISSION OCEAN & WATERS). THE COLOURS SHOW THE LEVEL OF ACCOMPLISHMENT AND THE CONTENTS INDICATE THE PREDOMINANT STRATEGY USED TO REACH THE OBJECTIVES AND TARGETS OF NETWORK BUILDING AND MOBILISATION. A FULL DESCRIPTION OF THESE ACTIVITIES IS SHOWN IN SECTIONS 3.1 AND 3.2.	23

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. CONNECTIONS BETWEEN THE FIVE MISSION OCEAN OBJECTIVES/ENABLERS AND THE 10 OCEAN DECADE CHALLENGES, REPRODUCED FROM PELEGRÍ ET AL. (2025B).	16
FIGURE 2. MAP SHOWING THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE IOLN MEMBERS MEETINGS ORGANISED OVER 2023 AND 2024.	27
FIGURE 3. BLUE COMMUNITIES MUST INCORPORATE PARTICIPANTS FROM ALL SIX DIFFERENT AREAS: HEALTH, SPORT, ADMINISTRATION, CIVIL ASSOCIATIONS, ACADEMY AND ECONOMY.	31
FIGURE 4. SOCIAL ACTORS PARTICIPATING IN BCN-NET, GROUPED BY TYPES OF ASSOCIATIONS OR BUSINESS ACTIVITIES. THE COLOURS INDICATE THE PROJECTS THAT HAVE GROUPED SEVERAL OF THESE ACTORS AND THE ARROWS SHOW THE INTERCONNECTIONS AMONG PARTICIPANTS.....	32
FIGURE 5. BLUE GENES RELIES ON INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATION TOWARDS BRIDGING THE DISCONNECTION BETWEEN HUMANS AND THE OCEAN. THROUGH DELIBERATIVE DEMOCRACY AND SOCIAL INNOVATION, BLUE GENES CONTRIBUTES DIRECTLY TO THE PARTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE OF MISSION OCEAN & WATERS. THE CONCENTRIC CIRCLES ILLUSTRATE THE ACTORS (INNER CIRCLE) CO-CREATING AND CO-IMPLEMENTING STRATEGIES AND METHODS (FOLLOWING CIRCLES) TO HAVE AN EFFECTIVE IMPACT ON THE KNOWLEDGE AND EMOTIONAL GAP BETWEEN HUMANS AND NATURE (OUTER CIRCLE).	36
FIGURE 6. SAMPLES OF ARTISTIC PIECES CREATED DURING A RESIDENCY OF ARTIST FRANCESCA BUSCA IN MAY 2024 AT ISMAR-CNR. ..	38
FIGURE 7. (LEFT) CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF OC-NET, EMPHASISING THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN FOUR CORE PILLARS: OCEAN CAPACITY RESEARCH SYNERGY, OCEAN SCIENCE AND DATA, SCIENCE-BASED POLICIES, AND OL AND SOCIAL AWARENESS. THESE PILLARS SUPPORT THREE THEMATIC AREAS: MARINE SYSTEM HEALTH (MONITORING AND RESILIENCE), MARINE SOCIAL SCIENCE AND CULTURE (PERCEPTION, CONNECTION, AND SHARING) AND MARINE SUSTAINABILITY AND SOCIAL JUSTICE (RESOURCE SHARING AND INTERRELATIONS). (RIGHT) OC-NET CURRENTLY HAS 24 MEMBERS AROUND THE WORLD, 2 COORDINATORS (ICM-CSIC AND UTM-CSIC), 12 OFFICIAL PARTNERS DIRECTLY INVOLVED, 2 CITY NETWORKS CONNECTING WITH CITY COUNCILS, 1 LOCAL COUNCIL DIRECTLY INVOLVED AS A PARTNER, AND 7 COLLABORATORS ACTING AS ALLIES. THE ICONS REPRESENT THE SEVEN UN OCEAN DECADE CHALLENGES ADDRESSED BY OC-NET, TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE AND RESILIENT COASTAL CITIES.....	42
FIGURE 8. CHALLENGES TO INCLUSIVE CO-DESIGN, AND IDEAS ON HOW TO OVERCOME THEM AS PART OF INCLUSION STRATEGIES, AS GENERATED DURING REFLEXIVE THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF DISCUSSIONS AMONG THE PARTICIPANTS IN THE SATELLITE EVENT ‘EMPOWERING SCIENCE, POLICY AND SOCIETY THROUGH CO-DESIGN FOR SUSTAINABLE OCEAN DEVELOPMENT’. THEMES IN BOLD DOMINATED DISCUSSIONS. INFOGRAPHIC PRODUCED BY SATELLITE CO-HOSTS, EMPOWERUS HORIZON PROJECT.	45
FIGURE 9. SOME OF THE SENSORY, INCLUSIVE AND PARTICIPATIVE, ACTIVITIES HELD DURING THE ENBLUEMENT EVENT.	47
FIGURE 10. VR SESSIONS EXPLORING THE MARINE ECOSYSTEM AND SOUNDSCAPES IN THE VESTFJORD, NORWAY.	56
FIGURE 11. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING FOR THE SEASyNERGY OSTER PA.	57
FIGURE 12. (LEFT) SHOWCASE DOCUMENTARY PREMIER. (RIGHT) ARTICLE IN THE LOCAL KERRY’S EYE NEWSPAPER, PRINTED ON NOVEMBER 20, 2024.	58
FIGURE 13. PICTURES ILLUSTRATING THE CO-CREATION PROCESS OF THE BLUE GENES GIANT COLLABORATIVE PUZZLE.	59
FIGURE 14. PRESENTATION OF THE GIANT PUZZLE AND CULTURAL-ARTISTIC PERFORMANCES AT THE FES! CULTURA #ACCIÓCLIMA FESTIVAL ON OCTOBER 31, 2024.	60
FIGURE 15. SMALL GROUP DISCUSSIONS DURING A SESSION ON FUTURE SCENARIOS, USING THE ART FOR FUTURES LAB METHODOLOGY..	63
FIGURE 16. (TOP) MISSION OCEAN AND WATERS, AS AN EXAMPLE OF A TECHNICAL MISSION: FROM THE INNER GENERAL AND THEMATIC OBJECTIVES, THROUGH THEIR ENABLERS, INTO THE SPECIFIC TECHNICAL PROJECTS-OUTPUTS AND THE TARGET BASINS; THIS IS ACCOMPLISHED VIA TECHNICAL AND SCIENTIFIC METHODS AND TOOLS. (BOTTOM) THE CLIMATE-OCEAN TRUST MISSION: FROM THE INTEGRATIVE CLIMATE CHALLENGE, THROUGH CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT AND MOBILIZATION STRATEGIES, INTO THE SOCIAL ACTORS AND THE TARGET BASINS; THIS IS ATTAINED VIA CO-CREATIVE/CO-DESIGN INCLUSIVE AND DEMOCRATIC COLLABORATIVE METHODS. REPRODUCED FROM PELEGRÍ ET AL. (2025B).....	74

Executive Summary

PREP4BLUE (*Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters*) was commissioned to support the successful implementation of the EU Mission Restore our Ocean & Waters. Central to PREP4BLUE, there is the development of co-creative approaches for the active participation of citizens in the co-design and co-implementation of the Mission. This Report is *deliverable D3.3* of PREP4BLUE, *A co-created portfolio of mission-relevant pilot activities to support evaluation of project tools and methods*, which summarises most of the work done within Task 3.4 of PREP4BLUE. This work supported and engaged citizen organisations and networks with the Mission expected outcomes, in particular testing the methods for the engagement and mobilisation of citizens and facilitating the development of pilot actions where these methods and tools could be tested and applied.

We start revising the Mission objectives and enablers, and identify those 2025 and 2030 Mission expected outcomes to be considered. We further set the context to explain why the work here reported has focused on 21 initiatives belonging to three different types of networks: coastal and riparian communities, ocean literacy within and beyond the school system, and creative initiatives around ocean sciences and arts. These networks include 15 initiatives selected based on an extensive number of initial contacts – covering a variety of geographic and cultural settings mainly in Ireland, Spain and Italy – in several cases linked to the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030 (UN Ocean Decade). Additionally, six networks – from the Baltic region, Norway, Ireland, Spain, Germany and an UN Ocean Decade program – applied and obtained funding for a four-month pilot action, which included training sessions and mentoring.

The Methods section begins with an analysis of the Mission’s key requirements for citizen engagement, and follows up with a description of the diverse methods and tools used to identify, train, support, engage and build up networks and communities of practice. The section with the Results explores: first, the diversity of actions carried out with the 15 initiatives, aimed at their empowerment through the development of collaborative and innovative approaches for citizen engagement and mobilisation; second, the efforts dedicated to promote networking and democratic and inclusive co-creation during the 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference; and third, the preparation of a call of pilot actions to test methods and tools, followed by a selection of the winning projects and the support and follow-up that they received.

We end up with a section on Learnings on citizen engagement and mobilisation, and on Recommendations, both practical ones addressed to the development of projects and networks, and strategic ones addressed to the European Commission. Our final recommendation is the convenience of implementing a new type of collaborative Mission framework, aimed at logistically and financially supporting committed grassroots organisations and networks, as the best possible strategy towards a healthy and resilient socio-economic system that respects the Earth’s planetary boundaries.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
BAU	College of Arts and Design of Barcelona
BCN-Net	Barcelona City Network
BCN MdC	Barcelona Mar de Ciència (Barcelona Sea of Science)
BlueMed Network	BLUE MISSION MED Network
CCCB	Centre de Cultura Contemporània de Barcelona (Contemporary Cultural Centre of Barcelona)
CLG	Company Limited by Guarantee
CPMR	Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spanish National Research Council, Spain)
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italian National Research Council, Italy)
CoP	Community of Practice. <i>A CoP is here understood as a diverse group of people, entities and even networks that share a concern or a passion about a topic and interact among themselves to deepen their knowledge and expertise on that topic</i>
CWO-UN	Informal Working Group Cities with the Ocean, United Nations
C40	Global network of world leading cities
DHub	Museu del Disseny de Barcelona (Design Hub Barcelona)
ICM-CSIC	Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC (Institute of Marine Sciences)
IOLN	Irish Ocean Literacy Network
ISMAR-CNR	Istituto di Scienze Marine, CNR (Institute of Marine Sciences)
ECOP	Early Career Ocean Professional Programme at IOC/UNESCO
EMSEA	European Marine Science Educators Association
ERINN	ERINN Innovation Ltd
EuroMarine	EuroMarine Association
FHA	Fraunhofer Austria
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Party
GAA	Galway Atlantiquaria
CLG	Company Limited by Guarantee
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KTOSM	Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module

MedCities	Mediterranean Cities Network
Mission	EU Mission Restore Our Oceans and Waters by 2030
Mission Plan	Implementation Plan of the EU Mission Restore Our Oceans and Waters by 2030
Network	<i>A network is understood as a named group of individuals or entities that are concerned with or work on a certain topic</i>
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NRI	Nordland Research Institute
OC-NET	Ocean Cities Network, UN Ocean Decade Program
Ocean Decade	UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development
OL	Ocean Literacy
OLIta	Italian Ocean Literacy Network
PA	Pilot Action
POMS	Profile Of Mood States
QuoArtis	Quo Artis Art and Science Foundation
UNODC	2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference
PREP4BLUE	EU Mission Ocean project: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters
Reeducamar	Red y Recursos de Educación Marina (Network and Resources on Marine Education)
SDG	UN Sustainable Development Goal
SDU	University of Southern Denmark
TransOcean	EuroMarine Working Group on Transformative International Ocean Programs
UCC	University College Cork, National University of Ireland
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
WP1, WP3, WP4	Work Packages 1, 3 and 4 of PREP4BLUE
Youth4Ocean	Ocean Decade young ocean changemakers forum

1 Introduction to Network Building and Mobilisation to Engage Citizens with the Mission

The EU Mission Restore our Ocean & Waters (hereafter “Mission Ocean & Waters” or simply “Mission”) aims at protecting and restoring the health of the Ocean and waters. Mission Ocean & Waters has three central objectives: to protect and restore the marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity; to prevent and eliminate ocean pollution; and to make blue-economy carbon-neutral and circular. This is to be accomplished through research and innovation, with the help of two enablers: a digital Ocean and waters knowledge system and the public mobilisation and engagement.

Mission Ocean & Waters indeed recognizes that effective solutions to the current environmental and climatic crises call for a committed participation of society. The Mission further recognizes that this participation must be fully collaborative, democratic and inclusive: a bottom-up mobilisation that is intellectual and operational responsible of all the phases of their own initiatives, from co-design and co-development to co-implementation and co-monitoring. This requires planning a top-down strategy for the empowerment of all these bottom-up movements, a fully innovative approach to democratic participation and government, it requires outlining the fundamentals of a new program that will sail among uncharted waters of networking mobilisation and engagement.

In this context, Mission Ocean & Waters chose *Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters* (PREP4BLUE) as its very first project with the objective of supporting the Mission’s successful implementation by developing tools, guidelines and methodologies that both empower citizen initiatives and can also be used by stakeholders on all Mission funded projects. One of the central results expected from PREP4BLUE is the development of co-creative approaches that ensure the active engagement and participation of citizens in the co-design and co-implementation of the Mission activities. Work Package 3 of PREP4BLUE (WP3) – *Empowering citizens to engage with the Mission and implement activities to support the Mission* – precisely focuses on enabling stakeholders to empower citizen and facilitate community-led actions in support of the Mission, through deepening and widening citizen engagement by leveraging participatory innovations. The three main objectives of WP3 are to increase citizen participation and engagement with the Mission goals, to co-create and co-develop approaches supporting citizen participation in the Mission, and to provide critical reflection and expertise to support citizen engagement activities aligned with the Mission outcomes.

This Report - *Deliverable D3.3 “A co-created portfolio of mission-relevant pilot activities to support evaluation of project tools and methods”* (hereafter “Pilot Mission Report” or simply “Report”) – summarises most work done within Task 3.4 of WP3 (*T3.4: Network and Support Networks who Engage Citizens*), which has been aimed at supporting and engaging citizen networks at different levels of maturity, scale and geography, with the Mission expected outcomes. *[Editors’ Note: A network is understood as a named group of individuals or entities that are concerned with or work on a certain topic]*. In particular, the main goals of T3.4 have been to test diverse citizen engagement methods and tools to mobilise networks to successfully engage with Mission Ocean & Waters, and to facilitate the development of pilot actions where these methods and tools could be tested and applied. To a large extent, the T3.4 work, and hence the actions identified in the Pilot Mission Report, represent the testing and application

of resources developed as part of Task 3.1 (*T3.1: Citizen Participation and Citizen Assemblies*) and Task 3.3 (*T3.3: Citizen Action*).

Table 2 summarises the citizen engagement expected outcomes from the 1st (2025) and 2nd (2030) phases of the Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Plan (hereafter “Mission Plan”) (EC, 2021a), indicating those that are directly addressed by this report: on the development of innovative democratic, inclusive and participatory methodologies, tools and practices aimed at the preservation and restoration of the Ocean and waters, through collaborative citizen engagement and the empowerment of social actors.

Table 2. Expected outcomes by 2025 (1st phase) and by 2030 (2nd phase) of Mission Ocean & Waters with respect to citizen participation. Those outcomes specifically addressed in this report are shown italicised (Edited from the European Commission, Implementation Plan for Mission Ocean & Waters.)

Expected outcomes by 2025	<i>Tried and applied deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions for the restoration of the aquatic environment.</i>
	<i>Developed and piloted frameworks and processes for participatory governance and deliberative democracy, including an EU-wide network of assemblies to enable effective citizen and stakeholder involvement in the lighthouses.</i>
	Up-scaled the European Research Area funded pilot citizen science campaign “Plastic Pirates – Go Europe” together with further Member States.
	Involved the European solidarity corps in restoration projects.
	Promoted apps allowing citizens to collect data and observations, and promoted (digital) data collection and participatory research involving citizens for the monitoring and restoration of Ocean and waters.
	Provided knowledge and methodological frameworks to support the revision of the International Ocean Governance agenda.
Expected outcomes by 2030	<i>All European citizens have the opportunity to engage in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through participative means, volunteering and citizen science.</i>
	<i>All European citizens are empowered to be actors in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through social innovation, awareness raising, education and training.</i>
	Promoted EU-wide annual ocean literacy campaigns, in cooperation with the EU4Ocean Coalition to strengthen public awareness and overcome the emotional disconnect with the Ocean and waters.
	Launched regular citizen science campaigns as a part of novel participatory research initiatives to increase the reach, quality and impact of scientific initiatives and boost the environmental awareness of the participants.

This Pilot Mission Report has been written by the T3.4 participants from the Institut de Ciències del Mar (Institute of Marine Sciences, ICM, with headquarters at the Spanish National Research Council, CSIC), the Galway Atlantic Aquaria (GAA), the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italian National Research Council,

CNR) and the Nordland Research Institute (NRI, leader of T3.1), with the active support from the University College of Cork (UCC, as the WP3 coordinating institution and leader of T3.3), and the collaboration of ERINN Innovation Ltd (ERINN).

From the recognition that PREP4BLUE is an exploratory project aimed at preparing for the ulterior development and upscaling of the Mission, the first step consisted in identifying a limited yet representative number of networks where the available economical and human resources could be efficiently invested. Each of these networks would be actively supported towards the collaborative co-creation and co-implementation of innovative and inclusive practices in the protection and restoration of aquatic environments, in particular providing the opportunity for testing the methods and tools developed within WP3. In some instances, the networks would naturally interact and lead to a community of practice (CoP), often acting upon a certain local territory [*Editor's Note: A CoP is here understood as a diverse group of people, entities and even networks that share a concern or a passion about a topic and interact among themselves to deepen their knowledge and expertise on that topic*]. From this preliminary reflection, we identified initiatives that belonged to three different types of networks: coastal and riparian communities, ocean literacy (OL) within and beyond the school system, and creative initiatives around ocean sciences and arts.

The initial extent and degree of engagement of the networks and social initiatives with the Mission objectives varied notably, so initial efforts were largely set towards creating contacts and synergies among the different social actors. In the process of establishing these initial networks, we identified the advantages of contacting and collaborating with initiatives endorsed by the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (hereafter the “Ocean Decade”, oceandecade.org), available through the Ocean Decade forum (forum.oceandecade.org). The Ocean Decade is a mandate of the United Nations (UN) General Assembly, to run between 2021 and 2030 under the coordination of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). Indeed, the Ocean Decade shares many challenges and outcomes with Mission Ocean & Waters. Specifically, the Ocean Decade challenges 9 – *on Skills, knowledge, technology and participation for all* – and 10 – *on restoring the relationship of society with the ocean* – point at the central relevance of developing the knowledge and engagement of citizen for the protection and restoration of the Ocean; and outcome 7 of the Ocean Decade focuses *on the inspiring and engaging value of the Ocean in relation to human wellbeing and sustainable development*.

The initial contacts with the ongoing networks and initiatives were often virtual, except for local networks in those locations of the T3.4 participating institutions, so major emphasis was placed on looking for an opportunity where the networks could meet. The opportunity arose with the UN Ocean Decade Conference (UNODC), held in Barcelona on 8-12 April 2024, with the organisation and celebration of four satellite events: one on methods and tools and other three for the different types of networks previously prioritised (coastal communities, OL networks and sciences-arts initiatives). The celebration of these four Ocean Decade satellite events became a major milestone, because of both the preparative networking that would lead to these events and the possibility of building in-person contacts and synergies.

Asides from identifying and supporting, both methodologically and logistically, existing network initiatives, PREP4BLUE has also encouraged and financed the development of transformative network initiatives. Through an open call for pilot actions, T3.4 offered the possibility to propose and develop inclusive, collaborative and innovative activities, with the commitment of exploring the implementation

of the PREP4BLUE methodologies, reporting the experience of using these instruments, as well as the goals accomplished, difficulties encountered, and the extent to which mobilisation towards Mission Ocean & Waters objectives was achieved. A total of six actions were funded and supported, two for each of the three selected types of networks: Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship (PA1) and The Baltic Hackaton (PA2) for OL; The Sea of Sounds (PA3) and Sea Synergy Oyster (PA4) on coastal communities; and Blue Genes Giant Collaborative Puzzle (PA5) and Sustainable Coastal Futures (PA6) on arts and sciences. The details of these Pilot Actions are presented see Section 3.2.

The Report is organised as follows. Chapter 2 describes the methods used throughout the process, with emphasis on the need to slowly build connections and lasting synergies. Chapter 3 is the heart of the Report with two major sections: Section 3.1 explains the results obtained for the three types of networks – coastal and riparian communities, OL initiatives, and creative communities around ocean sciences and arts – and the experiences attained in connection with the Ocean Decade, while Section 3.2 is a detailed description of the endorsed pilot actions, from the support in capacity building to the outcomes and learnings obtained from the actions. Finally, Chapter 4 presents the main learnings and recommendations, and Chapter 5 ends with the main conclusions.

2 Methods

National and international programs usually follow a top-down approach that focus on technical remediation and adaptation actions aimed at reconciling a healthy environment with economic growth and development. Horizon Europe is no exception, as most of the emphasis is on the development of scientific and technical corrective and adaptative methods and tools. Remediation-adaptation methods are indeed necessary to address the environmental and climatic crises but they are not at all sufficient: they will not succeed unless there is a substantial change in an unsustainable societal lifestyle that led to such critical situations. The solutions rely on an integrative approach that must include, as possibly its most important pillar, bottom-up preventive measures.

Transformative scientific and technological preventive measures towards the conservation and regeneration of the Ocean and waters do require the collaborative analyses of scientists and technicians with all social actors. A principal actor in this transformation are the committed citizens and civil associations who often have the plural knowledge and experience that are necessary for integrative proposals that should guide policy actions (Whyte *et al.*, 2024). This collaborative analysis is time consuming but the outcomes of multiple experiences – with different personal, cultural and geographic characteristics – are certainly much richer and the impacts have much lasting effects than any individual approach.

Collaborative work is rooted in participatory practices that encourage knowledge sharing and collective action, empowering communities to proactively search a new relation with the Ocean and waters. The development of an inclusive participatory atmosphere, where diverse perspectives can be expressed and integrated as shared initiatives, is achieved by the combination of inclusive reflection (such as regular meetings, workshops and retreats) and collaborative action. The creation of spaces for dialogue and reflection ensures that every voice is heard, and that projects are shaped by the community's collective vision.

The keywords are *trust* and *collaboration*. Above all, it refers to trusting and supporting the committed citizens and associations. Listening and trusting their engagement, knowledge and experience towards identifying the building blocks of any effective preventive methodology. Supporting them strategically to create synergies that build up the transformative initiatives and financially providing some minimum operative resources. Experience has shown (see Section 3 of this report) that the combination of committed people and modest financial support does lead to significant results.

Collaboration also refers to promoting existing and creating new synergies among international programs. In the case of Mission Ocean & Waters, its natural counterpart is the UN-led Ocean Decade (Pelegrí *et al.*, 2025b). As indicated above, both Mission Ocean & Waters and the Ocean Decade aim at the conservation and regeneration of the Ocean, and they both incorporate citizen engagement and mobilisation in their route maps (Figure 1). Under the motto “*The science we need for the Ocean we want*”, the Ocean Decade aims at supporting and promoting citizens to design, develop and implement bottom-up innovative solutions towards the SDGs. Challenges 9 and 10 of the Ocean Decade are supported by thousands participatory bottom-up Ocean Decade actions around the globe (oceansdecade.org/decade-actions).

Figure 1. Connections between the five Mission Ocean objectives/enablers and the 10 Ocean Decade challenges, reproduced from Pelegri et al. (2025b).

The methodology explained next is aimed at empowering the several networks in the development of innovative and inclusive democratic practices, in some instances facilitating the interaction between networks as CoPs. In all instances, we appreciated the relevance of a participative, inclusive and collaborative bottom-up process, realising that there are no shortcuts and that it is essential to take the necessary time in order to develop strong and lasting commitments. The observed success raises the possibility of upscaling these methods to other types of communities with a different variety of links and experiences with the Ocean and waters.

2.1 Analysis of Mission Requirements

The expected outcomes from the first and second phases of the Mission Plan with respect to citizen participation, as presented in Table 2, are rather generic. Therefore, the strategy to create a portfolio of mission-relevant pilot activities started with a careful analysis of the Mission Plan, specifically of its specific objectives and targets, the delivering on key EU policies, the rationale behind the Starfish 2030 Report (EC, 2020), the intervention logic and timing, and particularly the description of the cross-cutting enabler on public mobilisation and engagement. A summary of the principal elements of this analysis follows next.

In the specific objectives and targets of the Mission Plan (EC, 2021a p. 13) we find the three overarching objectives of the Mission: ***Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity; Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters; Make the sustainable blue economy***

carbon-neutral and circular. To deliver on key EU policies, the Mission Plan (EC, 2021a, p. 15) reads *“the Mission will aim to strengthen the EU’s position as a **global leader for ocean and water sustainability.**”*

In the analysis of the Starfish 2030 Report (Lamy *et al.*, 2020), it is concluded that the Mission Plan *“takes up the Mission Board’s objective to **“fill the knowledge and emotional gap, by proposing enabling actions (section 2.3 of this plan), in particular by creating a digital knowledge system and promoting public mobilisation, engagement and awareness... a revamped ocean and water governance”** (EC, 2021a, p. 16).* This is followed by the conclusion that *“**participatory governance is a central feature of this Mission with co-design and co-implementation of solutions with citizens and stakeholders at its heart.**”*

In the intervention logic and timing, the Mission Plan (EC, 2021a, p. 18) point at the need of delivering *“public mobilisation and engagement: with **tried and tested deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices, participatory governance approaches, mobilising and empowering citizens for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions.**”*

Further, the description of the characteristics of the citizen engagement enabler of the Mission Plan (EC, 2021a, p. 35) summarises most of these aspects as follows: *“The Mission will **connect Europe’s citizens and local communities with the ocean, seas and waters, facilitate broad ownership and education and co-design the transitions within the communities that will allow the European Green Deal targets to be reached. The Mission will act as a new tool to pilot deliberative democratic decision-making that will help citizens to co-design the future of Europe, in terms of sustainable management of aquatic resources and co-implement transformative solutions supporting the restoration of EU waters... [The Mission] will leverage social innovation throughout the co-design, co-development, co-implementation, and co-monitoring of solutions for sustainable use of the ocean and waters. To promote better public understanding and engagement, the Mission will support education and training activities, and launch regular citizen science campaigns together with the Member States, building on and enhancing the EU’s work to date on ocean literacy. To create stronger public connection and engagement with the ocean and waters, the Mission will draw on the power of arts, media and culture”.***

The outcome of the above analysis has been a categorization of strategies towards network building and mobilisation, as follows: (1) filling the knowledge and emotional gap to raise citizen awareness and response; (2) supporting the EU Leadership for Ocean & waters sustainability and global ocean governance; (3) promoting full democracy in the development and piloting of frameworks and processes for participatory governance; (4) testing and applying new practices of deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for collaborative citizen engagement; and (5) supporting OL at its widest expression, encompassing capacity building, education and training, citizen science, communication and outreach. An extensive list of engaged networks and the specific actions carried out through the PREP4BLUE project fall within one or more of these five categories.

2.2 Exploratory Contacts

Initial contacts were carried out with a substantial number of initiatives and organisations, mainly during the first year of the project, selected on the base of previous and arising knowledge of their activities related to the three types of networks. Additionally, throughout the project we made use of the application, WaveLinks (wavelinks.eu), developed by the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) as part of PREP4BLUE, which maps the research and innovation landscape of the Mission.

The contacts with coastal community initiatives included Ocean Cities (an Ocean Decade program), two city networks (MedCities and C40), a number of local Foundations (Barcelona Capital Nàutica, BlueWave Foundation, Fundació OnaFutura), local coastal networks (Pla Comunitari Barceloneta, Barcelona City Network, Espai Mediterrani), plus several other initiatives on sustainability, outreach and international exchanges. The initial meetings with OL initiatives included the Spanish, Catalan, Italian and Irish OL networks, as well as a local literacy network (Barcelona OL), the BlueMed Network (the Mediterranean initiative on sustainable Blue Growth), the Early Career Ocean Professionals initiative and the Ocean Literacy for All program (both Ocean Decade programs), the Centre de la Platja (an OL initiative ran by the Barcelona City Hall), and other initiatives on capacity building and citizen science (the Blue Generation Project, Observadores del Mar, technical schools for marine and environmental capacitation). The initial sessions on arts and sciences initiatives were largely centered on the Blue Genes initiative but also included many European youth associations (OYSTER-EuroMarine, Juste 2.0, Christian Youth for Climate, ICM Young Researchers Association, Eurocean's Youth), environmental organisations (Sustainable Ocean Alliance, Surfriider Foundation, Posidonia Green Project, SANAMARES Foundation, Cetàcea Association, North Wind Sailing for Science, Sea-Tech, A Sud Foundation, Legambiente, Sea Shepherd, Ecologistas en Acción), artistic groups (La Fura dels Baus, Arka Kinari), open-waters initiatives (Club Patí Vela Barcelona, Club d'Immersió de Biologia), a number of design and artistic universities, museums and organisations (College of Arts and Design of Barcelona, Contemporary Cultural Centre of Barcelona, Design Hub Barcelona, QuoArtis Foundation), plus many artists from the EU and abroad, including individuals from the Youth4Ocean Forum.

Besides the above contacts, we connected with different stakeholders, including the Barcelona City Council, the Barcelona Chamber of Commerce, the Barcelona Port Authorities, the Barceloneta Fisherman's Guild and a number of universities and marine research institutions. A detailed description of the above initial contacts that turned into networking activities is presented in Section 3.1.

The early online meetings served as a bottom-up approach to gather initial ideas and define the community's goals. These meetings allowed members from various locations to discuss the intersection of art and science, identifying challenges such as eco-anxiety (distress relating to the future scenarios of climate and ecological crises; Hickman *et al.*, 2021) and solastalgia (the distress that is produced by environmental change impacting your home environment, Albrecht *et al.*, 2007), and the barriers to engaging youth in marine conservation efforts, including both a lack of knowledge of the behaviour and state of natural ecosystems as well as a lack of emotional connection with the environment. The flexibility of virtual sessions also made it easier to include a diverse array of voices and perspectives.

2.3 Types of Networks

Rather than trying to embrace many different types of initiatives, the project selected three types of networks that were committed to initiatives connected to the Ocean and waters: coastal and riparian communities, OL networks, and creative initiatives with interests in both ocean science and arts. The original motivation for this selection was indeed the relevance and social extension of these three themes, but was also prompted by the results of the exploratory contacts, which confirmed the existence of several meritorious and very diverse networks in each of them.

Building on the exploratory contacts, the PREP4BLUE team interacted and supported a selected number of initiatives since the very start of the project. A complete list of initiatives is provided in Section 3, three

notable examples are the following: the Irish Ocean Literacy Network as a remarkable example of a mature national network; the UN Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET) program as a growing global network of cities coordinated from Europe; the Barcelona City Network (BCN-Net) as a very active coastal community in a dynamic metropolitan area, with the sea as their common factor; and the Blue Genes initiative, illustrating the potentialities arising from the creativity of a variety of artists and scientists with the Ocean as their vertebrate theme. Their characteristics, recent evolution, and mobilisation for Mission Ocean & Waters is detailed in Section 3 of this report.

2.4 Knowledge Transfer

To foster the uptake of knowledge towards the ambitious objectives and targets of Mission Ocean & Waters, the Knowledge Transfer (KT) process in PREP4BLUE applied a tried and tested methodology, developed by ERINN Innovation, the PREP4BLUE WP4 Leader. The methodology was adapted to the needs of PREP4BLUE to build an effective tool for Mission Ocean & Waters (Manago and Ni Cheallachain, 2024). The ultimate goal of this KT methodology is to enhance the uptake of solutions and thus foster high impact, in line with the EU requirement that *“Missions put emphasis on demonstrating, scaling up and replicating existing and new solutions including social innovations.”* (EC, 2021b). To foster the uptake, application and impact of knowledge, the Mission Ecosystem Database Wavelinks (wavelinks.eu by SDU) provides the visibility to Key Exploitable Results (KER). This includes diverse types of citizen initiatives; in case targets, the users of specific KER have been both citizens and citizen science Initiatives.

Pathways to increase the impact of the KT methodology, specifically on citizen engagement through mobilisation, have been developed for KER within *Task 4.4 of PREP4BLUE. A Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM)*, which includes the identification of drivers and barriers and how they might be overcome, is embedded in [WaveLinks](#). The module is aimed at facilitating and showcasing knowledge transfer activities in PREP4BLUE (Manago and Ni Cheallachain, 2024), to foster the uptake and application of solutions, and to increase their impact towards the objectives of Mission Ocean & Waters. Towards the end of T3.4 and its network mobilisation activities, KT sessions were held to assess how to best exploit the results of the work done and how to increase and sustain the impact of this networking and mobilisation for the Mission beyond the lifetime of PREP4BLUE.

A Semantic Network (Berndt, 2023) developed by the leader of Task 4.1 of PREP4BLUE, Fraunhofer Austria, is at the core of the Module and establishes linkages across the Database. A key feature of the KTOSM is that it matches solutions with stakeholders, ensuring that the solutions is fostered and the citizen engagement and mobilisation supported.

2.5 Collaborative Co-Creation and Engaged Research

Collaborative co-creation and knowledge sharing is based on the facilitation of in-person and virtual spaces where network members can not only collaborate on projects but also learn from each other through conceptual and practical activities, from collective brainstorming to hands-on workshops. The foundation and consolidation of networks and communities builds from regular gatherings, from meetings to workshops, both online and in-person. These sessions encourage open dialogue among participants, allowing them to share experiences, ideas, and reflections on how to strengthen the knowledge and emotional connections with the Ocean and waters towards their protection and restoration. Key to this

process is the facilitation of discussions where each member can voice their perspectives, contributing to the collective vision of the community.

A central message is that activities such as workshops should not be a space for unidirectional knowledge transfer but rather an open encounter that facilitates the collaborative and inclusive exchange of ideas and practices. It implies recognizing and empowering the very distinct possible approaches to Nature, beyond the traditional (structured and cognitive based) scientific method, with particular emphasis on artistic, sensorial, traditional and popular knowledge. Publishing and sharing the outcomes and insights from these gatherings on open repositories helps ensure transparency and wider dissemination of the community's efforts (see Annexes C, E, F, G, H, J, K, L and M.)

Most virtual and in-person meetings have been limited in their temporal extent. However, the experience obtained through the project has shown that the organisation of longer (one or a few days) reunions in a periodic (*e.g.*, annual) basis can be very beneficial for the engagement and mobilisation of the citizens, organisations and networks, as shown by the numerous examples presented in Section 3 of this Report. In particular, gatherings organized within the frame of large in-person events, represent an excellent opportunity not only to deepen relationships but also to enlarge the networking. Independently of their size, these in-person gatherings allow for more intimate exchanges and the creation of shared rituals that reinforce the community's commitment, fostering collective reflection, strategic planning, and the co-creation of activities that align with the community's mission.

One excellent example of collaborative co-creation and engaged research is the satellite events co-organised by PREP4BLUE at the UNODC in Barcelona in April 2024, which gathered the networks on coastal communities, OL, and Ocean and arts. These events were: (1) Cities with the Ocean – Ocean science for the sustainable development of coastal cities and ports (UNODC, 2024a); (2) Empowering science, policy and society through co-design for sustainable ocean development (UNODC, 2024b); (3) Diving from local to global ocean literacy: Exploring, sharing and developing successful practices to know, feel and join the living ocean (UNODC, 2024c); and (4) Enbluement: Connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean (UNODC, 2024d).

Engaging with citizens evolves from the capacity of listening and building from diverse and sometimes opposite opinions, always aimed at finding the best possible approach to an issue of public concern. Engaged research with citizens employs methods that *“share a common interest in collaborative engagement with the community and aim to improve, understand or investigate an issue of public interest or concern, including societal challenges. Engaged research is advanced with community partners rather than for them”* (Campus Engage 2022, p. 2). Within PREP4BLUE, the engaged research strategy aimed at facilitating and supporting scalable initiatives as examples of citizen-engaged Mission networks, and at facilitating that this exchange of ideas and practices would support the establishment of CoPs in the different locations.

2.6 Pilot Actions: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

To capitalise on the momentum and exchanges in the UNODC events, PREP4BLUE offered small scale grants for pilot activities on citizen engagement. The call for proposals opened in June 2024, offering six grants of up to €2,250 each, with a total of €13,500 available. Proposals were asked to align with one or more of Mission's goals: ecosystem restoration, pollution elimination and sustainable blue economy. Eligibility required applicants to represent non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and civil associations,

to have attended one of PREP4BLUE events at the Ocean Decade conference, and to complete their project and reporting by November 30, 2024.

A total of 32 proposals were submitted addressing networks on OL, coastal and riparian communities, and Ocean and arts initiatives. Submitted proposals included information on their approach to Mission Ocean & Waters: objectives, engagement strategy, expected outcomes, impact assessments, communication plans, and previous experience. The organisations presenting proposals were NGOs, educational institutions and community groups, the target audiences were youth public, indigenous communities, and the general public. The proposed engagement strategies included workshops and training activities, citizen science, and collaborative events.

Six projects were selected and asked to use the draft tools available from the online resources produced from the *Toolbox for Citizen Engagement: Engaging Citizens in Mission Ocean & Waters* developed within T3.1 of PREP4BLUE (prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement). These teams were also required to assess citizen engagement outcomes, participate in CoP events, submit a progress report, and deliver a final report by November 30, 2024. Additionally, the teams of the selected proposals as well as all teams that presented a proposal were invited to attend three webinars on citizen engagement strategies that were held on 17-25 July 2024, aimed at enhancing methodologies for citizen engagement and participatory practices.

NRI and CSIC offered mentoring sessions at the start, middle and end of the pilot projects, in the form of semi-structured interviews with prior informed consent from all participants. The objective of these interviews was to support the pilots in their delivery and understanding of PREP4BLUE and Mission Ocean & Waters tools, to encourage pilots to engage more deeply with Mission Ocean & Waters, and gather feedback to refine the tools and resources available in the PREP4BLUE toolbox. In these interviews, the organisations behind the pilot actions were asked and assisted in the following aspects:

- the initial objectives of their project and how to map them onto the Mission goals,
- the dimensions of OL in their project that were beyond their knowledge and awareness,
- their experience of using the PREP4BLUE toolbox, and their likes, dislikes and barriers with respect to this tool,
- strategy and ideas to leave no one behind, and
- the support needed to best engage more in Mission Ocean & Waters, either within the pilot action or beyond.

A detailed description of the specific methodological details in the evaluation, selection, formation and follow-up of the pilot actions is presented in Sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2. Sections 3.2.3 through 3.2.8 describe the pilot actions themselves, and Section 3.2.9 briefly explains work in progress towards an in-person gathering of the pilot actions teams in March-April 2025. The complete list of submitted proposals and the self-evaluation final reports of the winning projects are included in Annexes O and P1 through P6.

2.7 Community Building

The different initiatives, and in particular the pilot actions, have been facilitated through social events and collaborative projects to strengthen local ties, build a sense of belonging among the members, and transfer knowledge and capacity to engage with the Mission. Capacity building actions are of particular importance, aimed at promoting inclusivity and ensuring a leverage of basic skills and knowledge. In particular, these actions help participants realise that their emotional connection with the ocean is also

sustained by the central role of water and the Ocean in our daily lives, a knowledge-emotion connection that eventually helps to drive sustained behavioural change (McKinley *et al.*, 2023).

Two examples of intersectoral collaboration are BCN-Net and OC-NET, the first one at a local level in the city of Barcelona and the second one at European level and beyond. These two initiatives, which are presented in detail in Sections 3.1.2.1 and 3.1.4.3 of this Report (see also the Annexes), represent movements that encompass not only the local social-oriented organisations (*e.g.*, neighbour organisations, civic centres, local business) but also incorporate actors from other fields, such as science, arts and education. In both these cases, the conducting axis is to transmit the value of a healthy ocean - be it economic, ecosystemic or emotional - to coastal inhabitants and to propose actions and activities towards its protection and restoration. These intersectoral initiatives are good examples of CoPs as they naturally incorporate different types of networks, in the above examples these being from the coastal communities, OL and arts-sciences themes.

To translate ideas into concrete projects that reinforce the communities, these groups develop proposals that blend different perspectives and approaches, including interactive events and workshops that engage local communities. This structure ensures that each project is grounded on both scientific rigour and creative expression. One BCN-Net example is Espai Mediterrani (espaimediterrani.org) (Fuster and Pelegrí, 2025), an initiative that blends organisations in science, aquatic sports and local blue economy towards developing projects with a real impact on the coast and its inhabitants (Section 3.1.2.1.) Another example, now within OC-NET, is the Ocean Cities month (ocean-cities.org) (OC-NET, 2025), a full month dedicated to raising awareness and promoting activities for the protection and restoration of the Ocean and waters, in 2024 reaching its third edition with the participation of cities from six countries (Section 3.1.4.3 and Annexes L and M.)

As a final strategy to support intersectoral community building for Mission Ocean & Waters, PREP4BLUE is currently organising an in-person encounter among the PA teams, to take place in Barcelona in late March or early April 2025 (Section 3.2.9). The main objective of this gathering is to get these teams to meet each other and promote building synergies among them – specially to discuss legacy and replication actions for Phase 2 of the Mission. This final meeting will also be an opportunity to further explain the objectives and logistics of Mission Ocean & Waters, and to point at several funding possibilities that are appearing in the frame of this program.

3 Results

On the basis of the methodological analysis, and considering the three types of networks addressed (coastal communities, OL and arts-science), Table 3 summarises the principal citizen participation and networking pilot activities that PREP4BLUE engaged with. The Table includes the status of all pilot activities and the strategies used in these activities used to reach the Mission objectives.

Table 3. Objectives/targets addressed and strategies used by the PREP4BLUE pilot activities (on network building and mobilisation to engage citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters). The colours show the level of accomplishment and the contents indicate the predominant strategy used to reach the objectives and targets of network building and mobilisation. A full description of these activities is shown in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

Network/Action Type	Network/Action	Zero Pollution in the Ocean	Protect and Restore the Marine & Freshwater Ecosystems & Biodiversity	Sustainable Blue Economy Carbon-Neutral and Circular
Ocean Literacy Networks	Irish OL Network	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy
	Barcelona OL Network	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy Ocean Literacy	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy Ocean Literacy	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy Ocean Literacy
	Catalan/Spanish OL Networks	Ocean Literacy	Ocean Literacy	
	BlueMed Network / OLIta			
Coastal and Riparian Communities	Barcelona City Network	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy
	Partnerships with Third Countries	EU-Leadership	EU-Leadership	
Arts and Science Initiatives	Blue Genes Community	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices	Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices	
	Sea It Lab	New-Practices		
	A Sea Change	Fill-the-Gap New-Practices	Fill-the-Gap New-Practices	
Ocean Decade	TransOcean	EU-Leadership	EU-Leadership	EU-Leadership
	Ocean Cities Network	Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy EU-Leadership	Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy EU-Leadership	Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy EU-Leadership

Network/Action Type	Network/Action	Zero Pollution in the Ocean	Protect and Restore the Marine & Freshwater Ecosystems & Biodiversity	Sustainable Blue Economy Carbon-Neutral and Circular
	Cities with the Ocean Platform	<i>EU-Leadership</i>	<i>EU-Leadership</i>	<i>EU-Leadership</i>
	Empowering Science, Policy and Society through Co-Design			<i>Full-Democracy New-Practices EU-Leadership</i>
	Diving from Local to Global Ocean Literacy	<i>Full-Democracy Ocean Literacy</i>	<i>Full-Democracy Ocean Literacy</i>	<i>Full-Democracy Ocean Literacy</i>
	Enbluement: Connecting Science and Art	<i>Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices</i>	<i>Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices</i>	
Pilot Actions	Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship Training Course for Early Career Ocean Professionals			<i>Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean-Literacy EU-Leadership</i>
	The Baltic Hackathon	<i>Fill-the-Gap New-Practices Ocean-Literacy</i>	<i>Fill-the-Gap New-Practices Ocean-Literacy</i>	<i>Fill-the-Gap New-Practices Ocean-Literacy</i>
	The Sea of Sounds	<i>Fill-the-Gap New-Practices Ocean Literacy</i>		
	Sea Synergy Oyster Project		<i>New-Practices Ocean Literacy</i>	
	Blue Genes Giant Collaborative Puzzle	<i>Fill-the-Gap New-Practices Ocean Literacy</i>	<i>Fill-the-Gap New-Practices Ocean Literacy</i>	
	Sustainable Coastal Futures			<i>Fill-the-Gap Full-Democracy New-Practices Ocean Literacy</i>

Colour code for degree of development: green for activities that were facilitated or directly support by PREP4BLUE and are considered as successful; yellow for those that were started in the latter half of the PRPE4BLUE project and show adequate progress; orange for those where PREP4BLUE was a collaborator and are being continued through other projects or by other partners; red for those that despite continued attempts were not successful.

*Legend for each of the five strategies used to reach the objectives and targets of network building and mobilisation: **Fill-the-Gap**, filling the knowledge and emotional gap to raise citizen awareness and response; **EU-Leadership**, EU Leadership for Ocean & waters sustainability and global ocean governance; **Full-Democracy**, develop and pilot frameworks and processes for participatory governance and deliberative democracy; **New-Practices**, tried and applied deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for collaborative citizen engagement; **Ocean-Literacy**, ocean literacy at its widest expression, encompassing capacity building, education and training, citizen science, communication and outreach*

The status of the activities has been classified in four categories as follows: (1) if facilitated or directly support by PREP4BLUE and considered as successful; (2) if started in the latter half of the PRPE4BLUE project and show adequate progress; (3) if PREP4BLUE was a collaborator and the activity is being continued through other projects or by other partners; and (4) when despite continued attempts the activity was not successful. The strategies to reach the Mission objectives and targets of network building and mobilisation belong to five categories: (1) filling the knowledge and emotional gap to raise citizen awareness and response; (2) supporting EU Leadership for Ocean & waters sustainability and global ocean governance; (3) supporting the development and piloting of frameworks and processes for participatory governance and deliberative democracy; (4) supporting the trial and application of deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for collaborative citizen engagement; (5) promoting OL at its widest expression, encompassing capacity building, education and training, citizen science and OL.

A complete description of the activities for citizen mobilisation and networking on the three thematic networks and the Ocean Decade synergies is found in Section 3.1, while the PREP4BLUE endorsed pilot actions are carefully presented in Section 3.2 (see also the Annexes.)

3.1 Network Development

Three different types of networks were selected both because of their very high relevance regarding the objectives of the Mission and their excellent potential in terms of the investment-results ratio. These networks can be classified in three thematic areas: coastal and riparian communities, OL within and beyond the school system, and creative initiatives around ocean sciences and arts (Table 3). A total of about 20 networks, including those that were incorporated during the last year of the project through the pilot actions, were supported, with an even distribution of themes and strategies.

The work done within PREP4BLUE aimed at the following:

- Help the growth and development of the network.
- Support the network to orient to, engage with and mobilise for Mission Ocean & Waters.
- Apply and test some of the PREP4BLUE tools and methods.
- In those cases where the Network started through the intervention of PREP4BLUE, to prepare the network for continued work following the end of the project.

3.1.1 Ocean Literacy Networks

The selection of OL networks arises from two main premises. First, the narrowing and eventual removal of the knowledge gap on the relevance of the Ocean and waters is central in the transformation and engagement of society towards their conservation and restoration. Indeed, all major Mission Ocean and Waters' strategies to raise citizen engagement and mobilisation do rely on a better knowledge of the role and importance of the Ocean and waters in our lives and the living planet, with the objective of reducing the knowledge and emotional gap, promoting EU Leadership for Ocean and waters sustainability, developing participatory governance and deliberative democracy processes, applying democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices, and promoting all issues related to capacitation and education.

The second reason is that Europe already has several very well developed and mature OL networks, among them the Irish and Portuguese, and other networks that are experiencing substantial growth, such as the

Catalan network. Hence, we aimed at including at least one well-developed network - the Irish Ocean Literacy Network (IOLN) - and one starting network - the Catalan Ocean Literacy Network.

3.1.1.1 Irish Ocean Literacy Network

The IOLN was established informally in 2016 to maintain and expand an original network that was developed across the Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland over the course of the EU project Sea for Society (2012-2015), which consulted youth, citizens and other previously overlooked stakeholders on marine matters for the first time in Europe. Over the years, the IOLN has gathered over 150 members representing individuals and organisations ranging from NGOs, public bodies, research and academia, education, and private enterprises who share the vision of a network to create an Ocean literate society across the island of Ireland. Between 2016 and 2021, funding came mainly through contributions from the Marine Institute, supplemented by Bórd Íascaigh Mhara (BIM) in 2020 and 2021.

Some of the highlights for the IOLN in this time frame were the all-island social media campaign 'We Are Islanders' in 2019, and the involvement of the network in initiatives such as the UNESCO Ocean Literacy With All, the EU4Ocean Platform, the EuroGOOS Ocean Literacy Working Group, and both the European and the All-Atlantic Blue Schools Networks.

Since 2022, thanks to the inclusion in the citizen engagement work carried out in the framework of the PREP4BLUE project, the IOLN has had the opportunity to significantly expand its reach on the all-island territory. In fact, the support to the Secretariat secured through PREP4BLUE not only has allowed the IOLN to resume its activities on a regular basis, but has also permitted the Network to undertake the process to become a formal social enterprise.

Based in Galway Atlantaquaria (GAA) since 2018, the IOLN Secretariat acts like a central contact and dissemination point and carries out the day-to-day activities necessary to coordinate the Network and promote its growth. These consist mostly in organising regular networking events and workshops for the IOLN members, and the distribution of information about projects and initiatives led by the same members as well as other opportunities of interest for the whole community of OL champions in the island of Ireland.

In November 2023, the IOLN was established as a Company Limited by Guarantee (CLG), a form of social enterprise which allows the Network to fund directly its Secretariat through paid memberships, sponsorships and national and international grants. In this new form, the IOLN Governance includes:

- A Board of Directors, tasked with overseeing the management of the CLG;
- working groups, which closely support the Board by discussing the most operational decisions and making recommendations. The working groups established in this first phase of the CLG focus on education, capacity building and training, understanding regional action and activism, and implementing all-island IOLN events, campaigns and celebrations; and
- an Advisory Panel, composed of senior management level representatives of private and public bodies from the marine and maritime sectors at an all-island level, who provide high level support to the Board by sharing additional expertise and knowledge on strategic matters in order to maximise the Network's impact.

In winter 2023, the IOLN Board drafted the Network's 2024-2030 Strategy eliciting the feedback of the membership, both in-person at the Annual Members Meeting held in Dublin in November and through

online consultation (see Annex A) (IOLN, 2024a). The final version of the strategy so developed focuses on five objectives:

1. Enhance network capacity.
2. Promote engagement and collaboration within IOLN membership.
3. Facilitate stakeholder engagement and coordination.
4. Champion best practices in OL and community engagement.
5. Establish a sustainable funding model.

By achieving these strategic objectives by 2030, the IOLN will accomplish its mission *“to cultivate and nurture a sustainable community of Ocean literate citizens, enabling seamless collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the effective coordination of marine outreach and OL endeavours throughout the island.”* In doing so, the IOLN plays a major role in supporting Mission Ocean & Waters to achieve some of its 2030 outcomes, in particular, the promotion of EU-wide annual OL campaigns to strengthen public awareness and overcome the emotional disconnect with the Ocean and waters.

Moreover, through the implementation of its strategy, the IOLN can play a decisive role in supporting the Mission to enable effective citizen and stakeholder involvement in the Arctic-Atlantic lighthouse, providing opportunities for multi-stakeholder dialogue from local to all-island level. A significant example are the in-person regional meetings that the IOLN Secretariat organises in collaboration with the Board in the four provinces (Connaught, Leinster, Munster and Ulster) of the island of Ireland (Figure 2). Such meetings focus on promoting discussion between IOLN members and other stakeholders on relevant topics for the area from an OL perspective, e.g., conservation, education, blue economy, renewable energy, with the intent to integrate all possible points of view (see Annex B) (IOLN, 2024b).

Figure 2. Map showing the distribution of the IOLN members meetings organised over 2023 and 2024.

Between 2023 and 2024, six regional meetings were organised: two in Connaught (Galway, April 2023, and Aughleam, June 2024), two in Munster (Cork, June 2023, and Tralee, May 2024), one in Leinster (Kilmore Quay, October 2024), and one in Ulster (Belfast, March 2023). Based on the feedback provided by the meeting attendees, the IOLN is effectively providing a space for open discussion on marine and maritime issues – a space which has been clearly missing so far – and is showing its essential role as a key intermediate actor in the development of more participatory policy-making processes, of particular relevance when considering the cross-border perspective.

3.1.1.2 Catalan/Spanish Ocean Literacy Networks

OL networking has progressed intermittently and regionally in Spain. Since the early 2010's, several Spanish research institutions had their own OL actions but these were largely independent. In 2022 the Spanish Ministry of Ecological Transition set up a space for networking but without proper human and economic mechanisms to ensure its effectivity and continuity over time. PREP4BLUE has supported these activities at the Spanish and Catalan levels, actively and successfully finding ways to ensure their future development into effective networks, as briefly described next.

Reeducamar: Red y Recursos de Educación Marina

The network Red y Recursos de Educación Marina (Network and Resources on Marine Education, Reeducamar) was promoted in 2022 by the Spanish Ministry of Ecological Transition through the National Centre for Environmental Education (CENEAM, www.miteco.gob.es/es/ceneam.html). The objective of the network is to connect the community of marine educators (public administration, aquarium, centres of environmental education, companies, NGOs, education centres, research centres, associations), bringing sea knowledge close to the general public and promoting marine awareness and citizens' responsibility for the conservation of our seas.

The main visible outcomes of Reeducamar are a webpage (CENEAM, 2025), where resources from the different stakeholders are shared, and an annual meeting with all its members, where the participants are invited to share new methodologies and ideas and to co-create new projects. The main limitation of Reducamar is that it is a top-down initiative with very limited human and funding resources. PREP4BLUE is part of this network through ICM-CSIC, having participated in the meetings and having promoted collaboration and the sharing of good practises.

Xarxa d'Escoles Marines

The Xarxa d'Escoles Marines (Catalan Network of Marine Schools) began in the frame of an earlier European H2020 project, ResBios (resbios.eu). The aim was to set the basis of a platform where the Catalan education community could meet, get trained and share resources and knowledge. The network did not become operative but the initial contacts have been continued by the ICM-CSIC team as part of PREP4BLUE with the objective of setting the network. In particular, the PREP4BLUE team has promoted and compiled the multiple existing resources in Catalan and Spanish, which are often difficult to find. Efforts are currently aimed at setting a new web platform where reliable resources are gathered and classified in a clever and simple way.

In connection with promoting the Catalan Network, the PREP4BLUE team has endorsed two OL actions. The first one is Petits Oceanographers (Small Oceanographers, petitsoceanografs.icm.csic.es), an annual voyage with half of dozen primary schools that has been active since the 2016-2017 academic course. The

initiative includes formative sessions with the school teachers and the sharing of educational materials, and an annual gathering of all schools in the form of a scientific congress at the ICM-CSIC facilities. The second one was the active participation of the PREP4BLUE team in the 11th Science Congress organised by the Consortium of Education of Barcelona, entitled El mar és vida! (The Sea is life!) with the participation of over 40 middle schools of the Barcelona metropolitan area (projectes.xtec.cat/barcelona-apren-ciencia/categoria/11e-congres-de-ciencia). The team contributed both in the opening sessions with talks and materials (projectes.xtec.cat/barcelona-apren-ciencia/general/inauguracio-de-l11e-congres-de-ciencia) and in the closing UNODC event (projectes.xtec.cat/barcelona-apren-ciencia/general/conferencia-unesco).

The growing strength of the Catalan OL networking has been recently reflected by the participation of the ICM-CSIC in two new OL Horizon Europe projects: ProBlue (probleu.school) and BueLight (blue-lights.eu). These projects will undoubtedly be the opportunity for the final deployment of the network.

[Barcelona Ocean Literacy Network](#)

In a more informal setting, an Itinerant Breakfast Network was created with the participation of a variety of stakeholders from Barcelona. The network started in 2022 through informal breakfast meetings, organised in the office of the director of the Port of Barcelona, progressively bringing together people from different companies, non-profit organisations and administrations with links to the sea from all over Catalonia. This network has developed and grown organically over the years, currently with over 340 participants that communicate mainly via WhatsApp and promote regular gathering around different sustainability topics.

Discussions about the ocean are naturally generated by breaking news and, if the topic is of great interest, organizing face-to-face meetings and debates with experts. Meetings are usually held in different parts of the city, or even during boat trips along the coast of Barcelona. The key to success is the great knowledge of the area and the marine and nautical world of the coordination, as well as the willingness of the group to discuss sea-related topics. The ICM-CSIC PREP4BLUE team has actively participated in this network, often giving conferences and workshops to its members and as part of city events, and promoting the knowledge of Mission Ocean & Waters as well as the citizen engagement tools and methods developed within PREP4BLUE. The major weakness encountered has been the volunteering character of the network, which builds from the enthusiasm and commitment of individuals.

[3.1.1.3 BlueMed Network / Italian Ocean Literacy Network](#)

In the fall of 2022, the Italian Ocean Literacy network (OLIta) was approached by the CNR to explore its willingness to be supported by PREP4BLUE to expand its network and activities. At that time, OLIta was already facing significant challenges that threatened its sustainability. The network lacked a legal entity and official institutional support, and had no permanent dedicated staff. It was created as a grassroots movement and struggled to secure consistent commitment from researchers and volunteers. The network was unable to transition from a small, dedicated group of individuals to a broader, more influential and stable movement.

PREP4BLUE proposed to support the network for two years with a budget and staff from PREP4BLUE through the CNR. The proposed idea was to create a toolkit for its partners, which would be used to organise a nationwide activity for World Oceans Day in June 2023 and 2024. Even though the network's

volunteers were highly motivated, the lack of a stable structure and institutional support resulted in the decision to drop the proposal and eventually close the network.

The interactions with OLIta, despite their unsuccessful outcome, have provided valuable insights into the barriers, challenges and opportunities associated with building and sustaining OL networks (see recommendations in Section 4). The experience showed that the landscape of organisations dealing with OL is fragmented and sometimes in competition, and highlighted the importance of integrating grassroots initiatives within a formal institutional framework.

The absence of dedicated staff and organisational structure within OLIta underscored the need for robust organisational components to ensure the long-term sustainability of OL networks. To foster such a synergistic approach, which combines bottom-up and top-down strategies, a collaborative interaction with the BLUE MISSION MED network (BlueMed Network, bluemissionmed.eu/network-of-projects) was initiated. This collaboration involved two key activities:

- a) A workshop held in Rome in January 2024, bringing together key stakeholders from the BlueMed Network. The objective was to brainstorm and develop an engaging activity for World Oceans Day 2024. This collaborative effort culminated in the creation of an educational-artistic project by Francesca Busca (see Section 3.1.3.2 for details). The art piece created by Busca is accompanied by an educational lab designed to be easily organised and replicated by different stakeholders. Two short videos were recorded and are freely available online: one explaining the art piece and another focusing on how to organise the lab effectively (see Section 3.1.3.2.).
- b) Co-organized Session at Ecomondo 2024: PREP4BLUE collaborated with the BlueMissionMed project to organise a session entitled *“Boosting technology, business models and societal engagement for the implementation of the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters in the Mediterranean”* during the Ecomondo conference (Rimini, 5-8 November 2024.) Prior to the session, a call for a Citizen Science award was launched and 19 projects applied (bluemissionmed.eu/bluemissionmed-launches-the-society4med-award), the winners were presented during the Ecomondo conference.

3.1.2 Coastal communities

The selection of networks within coastal/riparian communities arose naturally from the intricate living relation between coastal population and the ocean, as well as from recognition that these communities (a) experience the physical, economic and emotional changes in the coastal and marine spaces and ecosystems that are related to both the climatic and environmental crises, and (b) are a natural place to create intersectoral connections, among diverse areas such as health, sport, administration, civil associations, academy and economy (Figure 3).

The complexity of this task led PREP4BLUE to focus on one single coastal community from a cosmopolitan region such as the metropolitan area of the city of Barcelona. The objective was to promote synergies among the diversity of stakeholders that are driven by the coastal and marine activity, hence strengthening the networks and eventually empowering a CoP around the three Mission Ocean and Waters objectives (healthy marine ecosystems, prevent and eliminate marine pollution, and create a sustainable blue economy). Several additional mobilisation and engagement citizen actions in the city of Barcelona and other coastal communities, which have been carried out in connection with the Ocean Decade, will be presented further below in Section 3.1.4.

Figure 3. Blue communities must incorporate participants from all six different areas: health, sport, administration, civil associations, academy and economy.

3.1.2.1 Barcelona City Network

Barceloneta is a coastal neighbourhood located close to downtown Barcelona, with a long-time tradition of fishermen and small and medium boats decked in its popular harbour, which during the last decade has progressively been replaced by a combination of high-standing yacht port and massified beach tourism. Despite these dramatic changes, Barceloneta remains as a very diverse social, cultural and economic neighbourhood. In this context, the Barceloneta City Network (BCN-Net) incorporates most social agents in the area, including neighbour associations, shopkeepers, fishermen guild, restaurants, environmental education centres and the town council (Figure 4).

BCN-Net started in 2022 with the support of the PREP4BLUE at ICM-CSIC. After a preliminary selection of the main actors, representative of the different sectors and stakeholders, individual meetings were held to identify their needs, explain Mission Ocean & Waters, and explore ways to meet their needs through the Mission. These initial gatherings allowed identifying potential synergies that were then explored in multilateral meetings. In several cases, as described below, these meetings led to successful intersectoral projects; a description of the principal activities is presented in Annex C (Fuster, 2025).

The network was also articulated through the organisation of different activities related to the Ocean, which involved several actors from the network. The Profile Of Mood States (POMS; McNair *et al.*, 1981) test (see Annex D) was adapted to incorporate feelings associated with commitment and eco-anxiety, and used out to assess the change in the participants' emotions during the Ocean-related activities, aimed at identifying those that have the greatest impact and produce an increase in positive emotions among the participants. The underlying assumption is that the activities that produce the greatest physical and mental wellbeing will allow the easiest connection with the Ocean and will hence encourage a robust commitment towards its restoration by 2030. The actions within BCN-Net are divided next according to their contribution towards the three objectives of the Mission.

Figure 4. Social actors participating in BCN-Net, grouped by types of associations or business activities. The colours indicate the projects that have grouped several of these actors and the arrows show the interconnections among participants.

A - Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity

- **Espai Mediterrani** (espaimediterrani.org). This is a network of environmental and social entities (civil associations, sustainable business, aquatic activities, fishermen guild), driven by their passion for the sea, which started activities in 2019 (see Annex E) (Fuster and Pelegrí, 2025). Throughout these years the network has had annual assembly meetings and has carried several educational and ecosystem restoration actions. In 2022, following the COVID19 pandemics, the coordination was overtaken by a member of the PREP4BLUE team in order to reactivate the network. As a result, a proposal for the restoration and recovery of the coastal ecosystem with the help of citizens (*Restauración y Resiliencia con y por el Mediterráneo*, RES-MED) was submitted to an open call by the city of Barcelona. The proposal was selected and a 2-year project was funded, which has helped to activate the network. Each entity is responsible for diverse actions, but all entities participate in these activities and collaborate in the dissemination of the results.
- **MetropolifPLab**. The PREP4BLUE team facilitated the establishment of a collaboration between a foundation (Fundació BCN Formació Professional) and researchers at ICM-CSIC. The foundation supports the MetròpolisFPLab project (www.fundaciobcnfp.cat/metropolis-fplab-2), which aims at bringing young people in practical-formative cycles close to innovation companies or research institutions. ICM-CSIC launched the challenge "How to renaturalise the coastline of an urban area", which was chosen by three groups of students who visited the ICM-CSIC facilities. The students were guided through different phases: exploration, ideation, creativity, prototyping, acceleration and final presentations. In addition, the proposals were also presented to members of the BCN-Net to create synergies and support the application of the ideas to real projects in the

area. The winning proposal was a prototype of an autonomous underwater robot that would measure different parameters of the water and monitor marine species of interest. The team of this proposal was formed by three students who did a four-month internship at ICM-CSIC to further develop their work, under the supervision of the PREP4BLUE team.

B - Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters

- Sant Joan Sostenible. The activity consisted in the organisation of sustainable festivity in the beach of Barceloneta, Sant Joan Sostenible (sustainable St. John's Eve festival), during the ephemerides of Sant John. Every year, on the night of the 23rd of June, a festival takes place that leaves an average of about 25 tonnes of waste in the Barcelona beaches. The action was designed for the night of 23 June 2024, aimed at offering a zero waste and alcohol-free space within the beach with inclusive-collaborative Ocean-focused activities. The PREP4BLUE ICM-CSIC team drew up a programme of activities based on the proposals made by the organisations and citizens, and coordinated the logistics. The BCN-Net network was activated through messages, identifying those organisations that could act as sponsors and those that could provide content throughout the day. Meetings were also held with the Department of Beaches, the local Police and the City Council. The day began with a waste collection in the area and continued with free activities for citizens to help them connect with the Ocean – snorkelling, paddle surfing, ice bath, body expression lab, dance, art exhibition with recycled materials – and ended with a zero-waste dinner on the beach. The event was quite successful, with the participation of over 100 people in a space of about 500 m²; the imperious necessity of this type of activities was evidenced by the fact that during that following the day in the entire beach [a total of 57 tonnes of waste were collected](#).
- September beach sustainability event. The Sant Joan Sostenible experience was repeated in September 2024 during the Barceloneta neighbourhood festivities, expanding the network of entities and extending the activities with gymkhanas and workshops on sustainable fish consumption. The event had two objectives: to reduce pollution on the beach and to create a space for the neighbours who feel excluded from the beach during these massive celebrations. The physical space chosen was a portion of the beach and several adjacent areas, such as the promenade and jetties. A participatory mapping was carried out with the help of the evolving Toolbox on the engagement of citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters (PREP4BLUE, 2025), which allowed identifying the different uses that citizens make of each area of the beach. A talk on these two events was done in the framework of the European Week For Waste Reduction (November 2024.) The participation in the event was comparable to the participation in the June 2024 event, further allowing an organic grow of the BCN-Net network.

C - Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular:

- World Environment Day. In 2023 and 2024, on occasion of the World Environment Day, the BCN-Net network was activated to celebrate this day with the companies that make up the Barcelona Port. Following an informal proposal from this Port, the BCN-Net got organized and prepared the contents for both years. A different theme was chosen for each year: The first year was focused on biodiversity and the second one on activities and services related to the Ocean (*e.g.*, co-management of fisheries, citizen science, sailing). A full day of activities was offered by the BCN-Net to about 30 CEOs of the main companies working in the Port of Barcelona. The activities included mindfulness sessions on the beach, sailing, snorkelling, sustainable fishing, a citizen

science workshop and a talk led by the America’s Cup organisation. The success of the journey was sampled using the POMS test before and after the activities, to assess changes in their emotional state day (see Annex D.) The test indeed detected a substantial increase in their positive emotions (commitment and vigour) following the activities. Considering the high managing level of the participants, the conclusion was that this type of activities of connection with the ocean is very beneficial to raise stakeholder awareness about caring for the environment.

- **Contributions to the local magazine.** *Essència Barceloneta* (Barceloneta Essence) is a quarterly free magazine that is distributed to citizens, especially in the Barceloneta quarter, where ICM-CSIC is located. The magazine is printed with 36,000 copies and offered online in Catalan, Spanish and English (essenciabarceloneta.cat). The magazine editorial team is also part of the BCN-Net, which promotes the co-creation of contents. Preliminary meetings established a working relationship, where the PREP4BLUE team would routinely prepare a one-page opinion article for the magazine, explaining the Ocean Decade and Mission Ocean & Waters goals and the BCN-Net activities. Six articles have been written during the span of the PREP4BLUE projects (Essència, 2023, 2024a-e), a routine that is expected to naturally continue after its end.

3.1.2.2 Other Networks

One of the goals of the Mission, as expressed in the Mission Plan, it “*to strengthen the EU’s position as a global leader for ocean and water sustainability.*” With this in mind, and in the context of co-managing the Ocean as a common good, PREP4BLUE has carried out several actions with third countries, both as part of the Ocean Decade and as individual collaborations. The latter ones are briefly described next while those in the context of the Ocean Decade will be presented in Section 3.1.4.

- **Spain-Chile Knowledge Exchange.** An activity with two student groups, from the Narcís Monturiol Institute of Barcelona and the Metropolitan Technological University of Santiago (Chile), was promoted and supported for two years. These groups of students are trained in water quality analysis, both marine and continental. Through several virtual meetings, the students presented their projects and explained the methodology used and the results obtained to teachers of both institutions and ICM-CSIC researchers from PREP4BLUE. For the first year, the students showed the analysis of seawater adjacent to the Port of Barcelona and the analysis of the Maipo River in Chile. In the second year, the students exposed the analysis of water from the Barcelona city fountains and the water quality of the Puangue Estuary in Chile. The expositions were followed by debates and the exchange of ideas for further research and collaboration.
- **Spain-Gambia exchanges.** An activity with a group of students, again from the Narcís Monturiol Institute of Barcelona, and researchers from the University of The Gambia was promoted and supported for two years. In the first year, the Narcís Monturiol students carried out a chemical and microbiological analysis of Gambian seawater in contact with the mouth of a pipe coming from a fishmeal production plant, which had caused serious environmental impacts in the area. The students interviewed microbiological experts from The Gambia to share their knowledge and concerns. In the second year, this activity has been upgraded with more tools to analyse the water and was incorporated into the school year curricula. Having a positive impact on countries where the environmental conditions may be at risk, is an opportunity that has had a very positive impact on the commitment of the Spanish students and faculty with the Ocean and waters.

3.1.3 Art-Science Communities

Traditional cognitive sciences, with marine sciences among them, propose a structured cognitive approach to reality, with its important advantages of quantification and replication but with rather clear constraints related to our limited human capacity to perceive and explain reality. In contrast, creative non-cognitive sciences, such as arts, have the power to enhance our perception and interaction with the natural world. Through visual arts, music, dance and storytelling, complex topics such as biodiversity loss, climate change and marine pollution can be lived – interpreted, experienced or communicated – in a way that speaks directly to the senses and emotions.

One of the central goals of the Mission Plan is to fill the knowledge-emotional gap. It proposes that for *“stronger public connection and engagement with the ocean and waters, the Mission will draw on the power of arts, media and culture”* (EC, 2021a, p. 35.) Indeed, emotional engagement not only helps bridge the gap between scientific facts and public awareness, encouraging active participation in conservation efforts, but it is also key to fostering a robust and persistent sense of urgency and responsibility among individuals and communities with respect to the regeneration of the Ocean and waters.

The PREP4BLUE team has actively supported the development of the Blue Genes network, which has shown to be an excellent example of how a network has matured through collaborative, inclusive and democratic strategies to bridge the emotional-knowledge gap. The result has been the creation of a community that is both a think-tank and a creative space dedicated to reshaping our relationship with the ocean. Section 3.1.3.1 carefully illustrates this case, followed by Section 3.1.3.2 with a more succinct description of other ongoing initiatives that have been supported by the PREP4BLUE team.

3.1.3.1 Blue Genes Community

The Blue Genes initiative (blue-genes.org) was established in 2022, through the facilitation of ICM-CSIC and with the initial support of the College of Arts and Design of Barcelona (BAU). Blue Genes is a community of diverse individuals—including artists, scientists, educators and activists—who share a common vision of fostering a deeper connection with the ocean. This initiative recognizes that the health of our seas and oceans is not just a scientific issue but also a cultural and emotional one. By integrating artistic expression with scientific inquiry, Blue Genes aims to create a holistic approach to marine conservation that resonates with a broader audience.

Collaboration within communities of practice plays a crucial role in addressing contemporary environmental challenges, especially when diverse perspectives come together. The intersection of sciences and arts allows for the communication of complex scientific ideas through accessible and creative methods, making the message more relatable to a broader audience. Blue Genes enables participants from various backgrounds—scientists, artists, educators, and activists—to share their unique expertise, fostering an environment where knowledge exchange and interdisciplinary collaboration thrive. This dynamic space encourages individuals to explore new perspectives and develop innovative solutions to the pressing issues facing our oceans (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Blue Genes relies on interdisciplinary collaboration towards bridging the disconnection between humans and the Ocean. Through deliberative democracy and social innovation, Blue Genes contributes directly to the participatory governance of Mission Ocean & Waters. The concentric circles illustrate the actors (inner circle) co-creating and co-implementing strategies and methods (following circles) to have an effective impact on the knowledge and emotional gap between humans and Nature (outer circle).

Following initial contacts in early 2022, the development of the Blue Genes network has taken place through virtual and in-person meetings and collaborative co-creation. The principal steps in the Blue Genes roadmap have been the following:

- **First Virtual Meeting (October 2022).** This was the initial workshop, where a group of scientists and artists were invited to explore how young generations can be better engaged with marine conservation through creative activities (Alonso-Ruiz *et al.*, 2023; Annex F). Participants shared perspectives on youth awareness about the state of oceans, obstacles to involvement, and the benefits of blending artistic expression with scientific understanding. The discussion also explored strategies for raising awareness and fostering collaboration between artists, scientists and activists. The participants expressed their enthusiasm to impulse the Blue Genes initiative, agreeing that the outcomes of the meeting will help shape the vision and direction of the network, and identifying key areas for future focus and community-building.
- **Second Virtual Meeting (June 2023).** Building on the first workshop, this encounter emphasized the need for a "collaborative revolution" focusing on blending intellectual knowledge with sensory experiences (Balagué *et al.*, 2023; Annex G). It featured presentations on interdisciplinary projects that combined dance, science and activism to communicate marine issues. The event highlighted the role of young marine scientists in building support networks and emphasized the importance of initiatives like Mission Ocean & Waters and the Ocean Decade. It concluded with a call for a deeper integration of art in communicating oceanic challenges.
- **First In-Person Workshop (December 2024).** This event brought together Barcelona-based members and international participants, creating an opportunity to strengthen local connections

and refine the Blue Genes objectives (Giannoukakou-Leontsini *et al.*, 2025a; Annex H). The meeting featured discussions on eco-anxiety and solastalgia, and the breaking of old narratives in order to create new ones through art-science collaboration. Participants emphasized the importance of having diverse perspectives and transdisciplinary approaches. A key outcome was the decision to organize a three-day retreat, fostering more profound connections among community members and setting a path for future activities.

- **Costa Brava Retreat (February 2024).** The three-day retreat in Costa Brava provided a space for members to deepen discussions and align on future activities (Giannoukakou-Leontsini *et al.*, 2025b; Annexes I, J). The gathering focused on building a collective strategy for ocean engagement through art and science, resulting in a concrete plan for the upcoming Enbluement UNODC event. The retreat included group workshops, creative brainstorming and moments of sharing and reflection, aiming to blend arts and science to drive the community engagement. The participants left with a clear roadmap for the next steps of Blue Genes and a shared commitment to expand the community's reach.
- **Enbluement event.** Under the framework of the UNODC, the Blue Genes community led the organisation of the satellite event entitled "*Enbluement: connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean*". The event was attended by over 150 participants and featured inspiring workshops and participatory celebrations, including an engaging shoal of fish dance and a youth choir. Artworks such as *Inverted Earth* and a *Letter to the Ocean*, created by members of the Blue Genes community, were showcased.

The detailed reports of the above gatherings, with the complete list of participants, is available at the Blue Genes website (blue-genes.org/outputs), also enclosed as Annexes F, G, H, I and J; the Enbluement event is furtherly described in Section 3.1.4.6. These reports offer comprehensive insights into the activities and outcomes of the events, and their inclusion in open repositories ensures that they are accessible for future academic and research purposes.

Blue Genes is an excellent example for innovative ways, which break the knowledge-emotional gap, to engage citizens towards the marine conservation and restoration goals of Mission Ocean & Waters. Specifically, Blue Genes meets the following Mission Ocean & Water targets:

- *Enhancing participatory governance.* Utilize the community's artistic and scientific expertise to develop engaging campaigns that promote citizen participation in marine conservation and restoration efforts. This includes workshops, art installations and public events that break the knowledge-emotional gap and encourage individuals to take an active role in protecting the aquatic environments.
- *Implement deliberative democracy mechanisms.* Foster participatory governance by involving community members in decision-making processes related to marine conservation and restoration. This is achieved through the establishment of local assemblies that allow citizens to voice their concerns and contribute to the co-design of solutions.
- *Expand citizen science initiatives.* Collaborate with existing citizen science campaigns, such as "*Plastic Pirates – Go Europe*" to enhance data collection and monitoring efforts. Blue Genes provides new approaches that increase public awareness and can hence mobilise citizens to actively participate in these participative data-science initiatives.
- *Raising OL.* Through innovative and participative events, Blue Genes can amplify the Mission's objective to promote OL. Through the blending of scientific knowledge with sensory experiences

and artistic insights, the community can make the complexities of marine science more accessible to all publics, fostering a deeper emotional connection with the ocean.

- *Promoting youth engagement and social innovation.* The focus of Blue Genes on engaging young people through creative workshops directly supports the Mission to empower youth as active contributors to ocean regeneration. The availability of new platforms for the creative expression of young artists and scientists will empower the co-creation of innovative and transformative solutions, which can drive social innovation and inspire a new generation of ocean stewards.

3.1.3.2 Other Creative Activities

Sea it Lab

This activity was designed to support OL stakeholders – such as primary school teachers, volunteers, and environmental education organisations – by providing them with an easy-to-organise OL activity on marine litter. The lab was developed during a residency of artist Francesca Busca in May 2024 at ISMAR-CNR. The artist collected trash from ISMAR-CNR (labs, offices, research vessels and offshore research platforms) and used these materials to create an art piece titled "*Sea it!*" (Figure 6.) The piece was presented during the 2024 Venice Boat Show and, in the opening days, the artist and ISMAR scientists interacted with over 400 people. Following the Venice event, the lab activity has been promoted and is currently planned by several stakeholders.

Figure 6. Samples of artistic pieces created during a residency of artist Francesca Busca in May 2024 at ISMAR-CNR.

The artwork aims at fostering a deeper connection to the marine world through a creative and sustainable approach, presenting a stark contrast between a lifeless polluted seabed illuminated by a lighthouse and a vibrant healthy underwater world depicted in darkness. The lighthouse represents scientific research,

which reveals the devastating consequences of human impact on marine ecosystems. The use of trash from ISMAR-CNR highlights the paradoxical nature of scientific research: while aimed at protecting the environment, it can also contribute to pollution. The artwork serves as a powerful reminder of the urgent need to balance human activity with the preservation of our oceans.

Two videos were recorded to describe the art piece and to explain how to conduct the lab (introduction video at youtu.be/l4YgBpyjBJg and video with organisms at youtu.be/L_h8zN9IsTg). The videos illustrate how, by representing marine organisms with recycled materials, the lab participants stimulate their imagination and creativity while promoting environmental consciousness. The sharing and discussion of these creations deepen the participants' understanding of marine life and strengthen their communication skills. The final comparison of the handmade models with real-life photos solidifies their knowledge and provides a unique learning experience. Ultimately, the workshop aims to build a stronger sense of community and environmental awareness through shared creativity and a collective appreciation for the marine ecosystem.

Other collaborations

The PREP4BLUE team at ICM-CSIC also established many other contacts to promote artists-science collaborations. Two of these contacts took place in 2022 with the directors of two of the main communication centres in the city of Barcelona, specifically the Centre de Cultura Contemporània de Barcelona (Contemporary Cultural Centre of Barcelona, CCCB) and the Museu del Disseny de Barcelona (Design Hub Barcelona, DHub), proposing to create exhibitions around the Oceans and waters in occasion of both Mission Ocean & Waters and the Ocean Decade. Despite that these were initial contacts, the ideas were well received and likely led these two centres to organise diverse talks and events on this topic in 2024. In particular, DHub has organised the exhibition *The Ocean Speaks. New Ecologies and Economies of the Seas* (October 2024 to February 2025, www.dissenyhub.barcelona/en/exhibition/ocean-speaks-new-ecologies-and-new-economies-seas), which explores the relation between humankind and the Ocean and proposing innovative design approximations

Besides these preliminary proposals, there have also been closer collaborations and synergies with BAU and the Quo Artis Art and Science Foundation (QuoArtis). The collaboration with BAU started in the first steps of the Blue Genes network, and keeps active through a series of seminars and workshops that explore which are the (subjective) criteria that define the value of data, materials and practices, an idea that can be extended to the sustainability and regeneration of the Ocean and waters. The collaboration with QuoArtis was in the context of the project A Sea Change (2022-2024), co-financed by the EU, which focuses on creative interdisciplinary innovation on blue economy, with an emphasis on artistic resources (quoartis.org/project/a-sea-change). This collaboration was bilateral, collaborating with some of the actions of this project and receiving the Foundation's support towards the organization of the Blue Genes retreat in February 2024.

3.1.4 Ocean Decade

Both the UN Ocean Decade and the EU Mission Oceans & Waters envision science and technology as tools towards sustainability, with and for people and nature, based on collaboration, inclusiveness and equality. Indeed, the Decade and to a large extent the Mission are fully committed to all UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in particular SDG13 (Climate action) and SDG14 (Life below water), and foster the collaborations necessary for SDG17 (Partnerships for the goals). This commitment is evident in the

three overarching objectives of the Mission (protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity; prevent and eliminate pollution in oceans and waters; make a sustainable, carbon-neutral and circular blue economy) and the 10 Decade challenges (marine pollution, ecosystems and biodiversity, sustainable food sources, sustainable and equitable blue economy, ocean-based solutions to climate change, community resilience to ocean hazards, global ocean observing system, digital twin of the ocean, capacity development and equitable data access, new relation of humankind with the ocean).

The similarities in the objectives/challenges of the Mission and the Decade (Figure 1) evidence the interest of exploring and endorsing the Mission-Decade synergies, and of taking advantage of the many potential synergies. In this Section we explain how the PREP4BLUE team has followed this path, in particular by having the UNODC as a referent gathering to empower the citizen engagement and mobilisation actions within Mission Ocean & Waters. We first refer to specific actions connected with the Ocean Decade (Sections 3.1.4.1 to 3.1.4.3), followed by activities related to the UNODC offsite satellite events (Sections 3.1.4.4 to 3.1.4.6); the satellite events represented a major meeting point for individuals and organisations connected to the regeneration of the Ocean and waters, an opportunity to facilitate the PREP4BLUE goals.

3.1.4.1 *TransOcean: citizen engagement in the Decade and the Mission*

EuroMarine, an European partnership that encompasses over 50 marine research organisations from over 20 countries, represents a referent independent scientific pan-European voice that can help identify and fill the scientific knowledge gaps, foster connections with diverse existing networks (from OL to community associations and NGOs), and implement marine science and technology tools towards increased impact, with the overarching objective of achieving the UN Decade challenges and the EU Mission objectives towards the SDGs. In 2022, EuroMarine launched an internal call for Long-Term Scientific WG on the “*Ocean Decade, Mission Ocean and other international initiatives*”, opening a bidirectional pathway between the EuroMarine network and the ongoing key international programs aimed at accomplishing the SDGs.

The selected proposal was “*EuroMarine Outlook on Transoceanic, Transversal and Transformative International Ocean Programs*” (TransOcean), with the participation of 15 European marine research institutions, among them six PREP4BLUE partners (including ICM-CSIC as the coordinator)¹. TransOcean is to last between January 2023 and December 2025, with the objective of exploring how EuroMarine can take advantage of its unique position to foster the necessary societal transformative changes and promote key governance strategies and policy measures (euromarinenetwork.eu/activities/transocean). TransOcean examines how the marine scientific community can engage towards attaining the SDGs in the frame of the Ocean Decade and Mission Oceans and Waters, aiming to provide specific recommendations

¹ *OYSTER*, youth chapter of EuroMarine; Centro de Ciências do Mar do Algarve, Portugal; Ecopath International Initiative, Spain; Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Greece; *IFREMER*, France; *Institut de Ciències del Mar*, Spain; Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries, Croatia; *MaREI*, University College Cork, Ireland; Marine and Environmental Sciences Center, Portugal; Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Italy; *Nordland Research Institute*, Norway; Università degli Studi di Padova, Italy; Università di Bologna, Italy; University Le Havre Normandie, France; *University of Southern Denmark*, Denmark. The PREP4BLUE participants are italicised.

to the EuroMarine network. TransOcean has been recognized as an Ocean Decade action and is part of the Mission Charter.

In accordance with the Mission enablers, the entire TransOcean analysis keeps the double perspective of favouring increased marine knowledge and enhancing public mobilisation and engagement. This is done through quarterly virtual meetings of the entire partnership plus the development of specific actions and the repartition of diverse materials. One of these groups has explored the synergies and complementarities between the Mission and the Decade, endorsing the top relevance of mobilisation and engagement policies and proposing a new European strategy to accomplish it; the results of this analysis are to appear in a white paper and a journal article (Pelegrí *et al.*, 2025b).

TransOcean has also prepared and submitted a proposal for a two-week transformative course entitled “*Beyond global crises – On the search of new pathways to perceive and experience the living Ocean*”. The course, to be carried out in Fall 2025, will integrate ocean, social, artistic and philosophical sciences to provide a comprehensive and innovative understanding of the complex interactions between human societies and marine environments. A total of 40 participants will engage, for two weeks, in theoretical and practical sessions, collaborating on interdisciplinary projects and applying innovative methodologies. The first week will be in-person, with key lectures, open debates, field activities and the setup of interdisciplinary group-projects. During the second week, to be conducted online, the participants will dedicate several hours per day to refine these projects into actionable proposals.

3.1.4.2 The 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference

In March 2024, PREP4BLUE launched a call to fund up to 18 travel grants (prep4blue.eu/un-ocean-decade-2024-travel-grant) covering accommodation and per diem (14 burses up to 500 euros and 4 burses up to 550 euros), to facilitate participation in four UNODC satellite events co-hosted by PREP4BLUE, held in Barcelona in April 2024 (Sections 3.1.4.3 to 3.1.4.6.) The selection criteria include the following: past and current involvement with the Ocean Decade, background in activities promoting citizen engagement with the oceans and waters, being invited as a speaker at one of the four satellite events, statement of motivation.

The call attracted 28 applications from individuals across 19 countries. After evaluation, 15 participants from 11 different countries were selected. Among the selected participants, eight identified as men, six as women, and one chose not to disclose their gender. Of these 15 participants, nine attended the event “*Diving from local to global ocean literacy: Exploring, sharing and developing successful practices to know, feel and join the living ocean*”, seven participated in both “*Cities with the Ocean – Ocean science for the sustainable development of coastal cities and ports*” and “*Empowering science, policy, and society through co-design for sustainable ocean development*”, and five people attended “*Enbluement: Connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean*”.

3.1.4.3 Ocean Cities Network and Cities with the Ocean Platform

Ocean Cities Network

Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET, ocean-cities.org) is an international network of coastal communities that has been endorsed by UN as a structural Ocean Decade program (Figure 7). The principal goal of OC-NET is to expand the city boundaries beyond the shoreline, integrating the Ocean into everyday city life; see a summary poster in OC-NET (2024), also in Annex K. Rooted in scientific research, sustainability, and

community collaboration, OC-NET fosters a deeper connection between coastal cities and the Ocean, aiming to create a balanced relationship that reshapes urban landscapes and enriches residents' lives. OC-NET envisions a future where coastal cities move in harmony with the Ocean's rhythm, becoming beacons of innovation, sustainability and inclusivity. In this journey, cities worldwide are encouraged not only to recognize the Ocean's intrinsic value but also to embrace it as an essential part of urban life – a shared responsibility and a pathway to a sustainable future for all.

Figure 7. (Left) Conceptual framework of OC-NET, emphasising the interplay between four core pillars: Ocean Capacity Research Synergy, Ocean Science and Data, Science-Based Policies, and OL and Social Awareness. These pillars support three thematic areas: Marine System Health (monitoring and resilience), Marine Social Science and Culture (perception, connection, and sharing) and Marine Sustainability and Social Justice (resource sharing and interrelations). (Right) OC-NET currently has 24 members around the world, 2 coordinators (ICM-CSIC and UTM-CSIC), 12 official partners directly involved, 2 city networks connecting with city councils, 1 local council directly involved as a partner, and 7 collaborators acting as allies. The icons represent the seven UN Ocean Decade challenges addressed by OC-NET, towards sustainable and resilient coastal cities.

OC-NET is a Mission Charter action (maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/node/4929_en), with the goal of promoting citizen engagement, citizen science, youth-led projects, communities of practice, ocean and water literacy, outreach, awareness raising and participatory approaches. Through collaborative projects focused on health, culture and justice, OC-NET closely aligns with the objectives of Mission Ocean & Waters; a summary of the principal projects during the first two years of the Network is presented in Pelegrí *et al.* (2025a) (see Annex L).

The relevance of the above objectives for citizen engagement and network mobilisation, combined with the fact that OC-NET is coordinated by ICM-CIC, a PREP4BLUE partner, has led to a strong and stable relation between PREP4BLUE and OC-NET. Further, OC-NET represents a natural way for the EU to participate in the global leadership in Ocean and water and governance, as OC-NET has already established regional nodes in Latin America (including Mexico, Argentina, Colombia and Chile) and collaborates with international city networks united in action to confront the climatic and environmental crises, specifically with the Mediterranean Cities Network (MedCities, medcities.org) and the global network of many of the world's leading cities, united to confront climate change (C40 Cities, www.c40.org).

OC-NET uses several of the tools and methodologies promoted by PREP4BLUE for the protection and restoration of the ocean and waterways, through the following:

- *Active citizen engagement.* OC-NET fosters active citizen participation in Ocean-related initiatives, promoting citizen science and involvement in local activities that contribute to ecosystem health. OC-NET conducts exploratory contacts with various initiatives and communities to uncover synergies on shared themes, mapping activities that can align and multiply impact in areas such as citizen science, climate justice and coastal ecosystem restoration.
- *Education and awareness.* Through OL programs and awareness campaigns, OC-NET aims to integrate ocean knowledge into the daily lives of citizens, fostering a culture of respect and care for the sea. OC-NET strengthens local ties and fosters a sense of community belonging through events like the *Ocean Cities Month* (www.icm.csic.es/en/news/thousands-participate-second-edition-ocean-cities-month). In October 2024, this event reached its third edition, engaging thousands of people across the network in coastal cities from Australia, Argentina, México, Colombia, Portugal and Spain (OC-NET, 2025; see Annex M), capacity-building initiatives, and public awareness campaigns. These activities not only increase the knowledge of participants but also build an emotional connection, motivating citizens to view the Ocean as an integral part of their urban environment and inspiring them to contribute to its preservation.
- *Collaborative research and innovation.* The network promotes a bottom-up approach based on inclusive community goals and collaborations in Ocean and urban sustainability research. Interdisciplinary co-creation is fundamental to OC-NET's mission, driving projects that integrate science, art, and community action around the ocean. OC-NET organizes and facilitates co-creation spaces where art and science converge, as well as activities like citizen science campaigns, art exhibitions, and educational workshops. These initiatives encourage communities to engage actively and develop a deeper connection with ocean issues, fostering a lasting, emotional relationship with the ocean.
- *Participative and innovative actions.* OC-NET promotes the development of intersectoral participatory projects, in partnership with scientific and academic institutions. OC-NET applies an interdisciplinary approach where each member contributes to generate innovative and evidence-based solutions towards ocean sustainability, exchanging experiences and strengthening the connection between science and community on ocean-related themes. Participation in high-impact events, such as European Maritime Day and the UNODC, facilitates collective engagement and broadens the network for a greater impact on ocean sustainability.
- *Communities of practice.* The network promotes and supports the organisation of CoPs to share knowledge and experiences, strengthening the local capacities to address the challenges of climate change and urban development in coastal areas. Community building is essential for sustaining OC-NET's mission, fostering sustainable behavioural change and enhancing Ocean awareness in urban life.

Cities with the Ocean Platform

The *Cities with the Ocean* platform (CWO-UN), co-coordinated by OC-NET, was launched during the UNODC (April 2024) as an UN Informal Working Group formed with key stakeholders, aimed at addressing the needs of coastal cities regarding the Ocean Decade goals. This group collectively assesses the common challenges and needs of coastal cities and explores the best ways to mobilize the Ocean Decade community to invent, test and replicate science-based solutions.

The CWO-UN platform aims at enabling coastal cities to adopt a cross-cutting, science-based approach to harmonise their relationship with the Ocean, involving existing networks and initiatives that support urban development, leveraging their experience to strengthen the use of marine sciences. It promotes the access and use of interdisciplinary marine sciences to meet the challenges arising from global change and rapid urban growth, and to develop innovative solutions to achieve their sustainable development ambitions. Cities could share their experiences and challenges, while the hundreds of partner institutions leading Ocean Decade Actions would provide tools, data and capacity to meet the city needs through shared best practices and co-designed innovative solutions.

CWO-UN coordinated the organisation of the UNODC satellite event entitled “*Cities with the Ocean – Ocean science for the sustainable development of coastal cities and ports*” (UNODC, 2024a). The event brought together over 20 speakers from coastal cities around the world, representing different stakeholders. Speakers shared their experiences and participants released the *Cities with the Ocean Call to Action*, expressing their will to activate the platform towards an active participation in the UN Ocean Conference in Nice in June 2025.

3.1.4.4 Empowering Science, Policy and Society through Co-Design

Another satellite of the UNODC was “*Empowering science, policy and society through co-design for sustainable ocean development*”, with 50 participants including policymakers, coastal community members, industry, research and NGOs (UNODC, 2024b). This workshop was envisaged as a networking event for the coastal communities and OL communities of practice, and as a catalyst event to engage different networks and stakeholders towards co-design in support of the Mission citizen engagement targets. It addressed the question: *how can co-design empower science, policy and society stakeholders to better support Ocean sustainability?*

The workshop provided a space for dialogue for learning the importance of working across the science–policy–society interface for sustainable Ocean development. Comprising inspirational stories (from different perspectives on co-design) and good examples, followed by working groups, it showcased examples of how co-designed transformative Ocean science and knowledge production has contributed to building a sustainable Ocean development at the national and sub-national levels, with a focus on Small Island Developing States and Least Developed countries. The workshop then identified the potential roles, challenges and synergies of researchers, policymakers and decision-makers as well as societal actors, such as indigenous peoples, local communities, minorities, women and young people – including Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs) – in advancing sustainable Ocean development.

The specific objectives of the event were:

- To share experiences and understand and promote best practice examples in the co-design and co-delivery of Ocean science to strengthen the marine science-policy-society interface.
- To support sustainable Ocean economic development and priority actions in the framework of the Ocean Decade.
- To foster synergy between the Ocean Decade and Mission Ocean & Waters, and to chart the role and structure of co-design to help each reach their citizen engagement targets.

The workshop specifically focused on synergies between Challenge 9 of the Ocean Decade (skills, knowledge, technology and participatory decision making for all) and what Mission Ocean & Waters was trying to achieve in relation to civic participation in Ocean governance and development (*e.g.*, through

setting up direct democratic initiatives such as Mission Ocean citizen assemblies). The results from discussions were provided to the Ocean Decade Challenge 9 Working Group and contributed to the resulting Challenge 9 white paper entitled *Skills, knowledge, technology and participatory decision making for all* (Arbic *et al.*, 2024), ensuring that the PREP4BLUE Mission-focused work has become part of the official policy for the second half of the Ocean Decade. The challenges to inclusive co-design, with proposals and strategies on how to overcome them, are summarized in Figure 8. Participants in this event were informed of the upcoming PREP4BLUE call for pilot citizen engagement actions (Section 3.2) and were invited to apply for funding.

Figure 8. Challenges to inclusive co-design, and ideas on how to overcome them as part of inclusion strategies, as generated during reflexive thematic analysis of discussions among the participants in the satellite event ‘Empowering science, policy and society through co-design for sustainable ocean development’. Themes in bold dominated discussions. Infographic produced by satellite co-hosts, EmpowerUs Horizon Project.

3.1.4.5 Diving from Local to Global Ocean Literacy

The UNODC satellite event entitled “Diving from Local to Global Ocean Literacy: Exploring, Sharing, and Developing Successful Practices to Know, Feel and Join the Living Ocean” showcased a wide range of innovative OL initiatives from a global to a local perspective (UNODC, 2024c). The event was co-organised and co-hosted by GAA, ECOP, the Escola Galí Bellesguard and the Universitat de Barcelona, and co-hosted by several organisations and initiatives, among them PREP4BLUE.

After an introduction by representatives of the hosting organisations, which set the intentions for the event and provided guidance in generating the outcomes of this collaborative efforts, a short film by the OL Task Team of the ECOP Programme and the OL Asian Hub was screened to showcase “*The Ocean Literacy Series*”, as an example of a much broader portfolio of innovative practices in OL. This was followed by four interactive panels designed to explore the experiences across diverse sectors: Removing Barriers for OL, OL in Local Communities, OL in Science, and OL & Water Sports. In these panels, some 20 speakers shared their views on best practices and on how to overcome the Ocean conservation and protection challenges. Participants in this event were invited to apply for funding to the upcoming PREP4BLUE call for pilot citizen engagement actions (Section 3.2).

The outputs of the four panels can be summarised as follows:

- The *Removing Barriers for OL* panel highlighted innovative approaches, such as citizen science projects and local community engagement efforts, able to bridge gaps in knowledge and empower individuals to actively participate in Ocean conservation by removing barriers such as financial constraints, limited access to educational resources, generational gaps, and cultural and language barriers. The panellists emphasised the critical role of funding in supporting marine education initiatives and suggested local solutions to global challenges by sharing their own experiences. An example was the *Explore, Feel, Reconnect, Act methodology* proposed by the Fundación Amiguitos del Océano to successfully measure the internalisation of OL concepts within coastal communities in Ecuador.
- The panel on the topic of *OL in Coastal Communities* focused on overcoming the challenges of communicating OL. The panellists agreed that knowledge should be enhanced, but not just from a theoretical and scientific perspective, but also focusing on practical and traditional knowledge. The panel highlighted the importance of listening to the different voices within local communities to enact a comprehensive and inclusive stakeholder engagement, which is mindful of different conceptions, beliefs and perceptions of the Ocean. It was stressed that citizen engagement can be encouraged using diagnostic methodologies that highlight cultural backgrounds and personal relationships with the Ocean, and that endorsing participatory processes is particularly beneficial to all parties.
- The panel about *OL in Science* discussed challenges and solutions related to OL in the context of ocean science, which is often viewed as a difficult field, accessible only to researchers that are familiar with the scientific method. OL holds enormous strategic potential to promote the relevance of science for society and policy development. However, creativity, philosophy, sociology and behaviour sciences should all be considered in the context of OL. In this view, the panellists addressed the pursuit of Ocean intelligence, which should include qualitative aspects beyond purely quantitative scientific methods. Traditional and non-traditional approaches, from mythology to artificial intelligence, can all provide meaningful ways to reconnect the public with the environment and marine knowledge.
- The panellists of *OL and Water Sports* were four advocates of OL in sports who shared their very different projects across scuba diving, sailing and stand-up paddle boarding. Through their initiatives, these advocates enable Ocean users to understand the marine ecosystems on a much deeper level, and to incorporate OL learnings into their activities. By showcasing projects that take place globally, regionally, locally as well as online, the panel concluded that sports could give good access to OL to wider and broader audiences, helping to foster an increased connection with the

Ocean. Moreover, through the inclusion of citizen science methodologies, water sports can play a significant role in supporting the collection of Ocean and climate change data.

3.1.4.6 *Enbluement: Connecting Science and Art*

As a follow-up to their February 2024 retreat (Section 3.1.3.1), the Blue Genes network gathered to finalize the plan for a UNODC satellite event, with the goal of proposing an innovative approach for connecting with the Ocean through art-science creative and sensory experiences (UNODC, 2024d). The event was entitled “*Enbluement: connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean*” and it was designed to include workshops, participatory performances, and a public celebration blending dance, music, and sensory experiences (Figure 9). The session focused on ensuring a balance between scientific content and emotional engagement to resonate with a broad audience. Participants in this event were informed of the upcoming PREP4BLUE call for pilot citizen engagement actions (Section 3.2) and were invited to apply for funding.

Figure 9. Some of the sensory, inclusive and participative, activities held during the Enbluement event.

The Enbluement event was hosted by Blue Genes, the Barcelona City Council and the Bluewave Alliance, and co-hosted by several organisations, among them PREP4BLUE. The event aimed to deepen our cognitive-sensory connection with the Ocean. The activities included six inspirational stories on visual arts, music, aquatic sports, traditional knowledge, augmented reality and virtual networks, followed by a roundtable discussion that encouraged participants to rethink their relationship with Nature.

The second part of the event was a participatory sensory experience in the adjacent Charles Darwin Square – featuring music, silences, images and motion – created a deep emotional connection to the ocean (Figure 9). Artworks such as an *Inverted Earth*, a *Letter to the Ocean*, and a participative guitar-choir concert, designed by the Blue Genes community, were showcased; a video can be seen in the Youtube channel of ICM-CSIC, at www.youtube.com/watch?v=2HEUdy9QcSE&t=40s.

Supported by over 30 dedicated volunteers, the Enbluement event offered an immersive and interactive experience that deepened the individual and collective connection to the Ocean. By blending science and art, the event expanded cognitive-sensory perceptions and promoted a holistic belonging to the Ocean, fostering collaboration and community building among those exploring new ways to interact with and perceive the natural world.

3.2 Pilot Actions

In May 2024, PREP4BLUE advertised a Pilot Action (PA) Fund (prep4blue.eu/prep4blue-pilot-activity-funding-engaging-citizens-in-mission-ocean) for projects that aimed to capitalise on the energy and discussions during the UNODC satellite events, with the objective of facilitating or developing success stories on citizen engagement and mobilisation towards the Mission Plan goals, which could be replicated or scaled up in the future. The PA proposals were requested to aim at engaging citizens in activities relevant to the Mission citizen engagement targets and at least one of its overall objectives (see Section 2.6 and the introduction to Section 3), the text of the call is included in Annex N.

3.2.1 Selection Process

The selection process for the PA grants was structured in a multi-phase approach designed to ensure that the awarded projects align with the Mission citizen engagement targets and objectives. The process began with a public call for proposals, inviting NGOs, non-profit groups, and civil organizations to submit pilot projects aimed at engaging citizens in activities related to ocean preservation, pollution prevention, and fostering a sustainable blue economy. The call was open from May 22 to June 20, 2024, with a total fund of 13,500 EUR available, distributed in grants of up to 2,250 EUR for each selected project.

A total of 32 innovative proposals were received from applicants across Europe, targeting various demographics and geographic areas (see Annex O). The proposals reflect a strong commitment to raising awareness about marine ecosystems, often engaging youth and indigenous communities, and promoting a sustainable blue economy. The initiatives ranged from interdisciplinary workshops and citizen science projects to community clean-up events and educational programs. Many proposals emphasized the importance of co-designing activities with participants, fostering direct democratic elements, and ensuring deep participation from local communities. A summary of the characteristics of the 32 submitted proposals follows.

Target network:

- OL: 17 organizations focused on educational or awareness programs around ocean ecosystems.
- Coastal and Riparian Communities: 13 organizations working directly with communities located along coastlines or rivers, likely engaging them in conservation or educational projects.
- Ocean and Arts: 3 organizations combining artistic initiatives with oceanic themes, using creative methods to drive environmental engagement.

Type of organisation:

- NGOs: 15 proposals from various NGOs focused on environmental conservation and community engagement.
- Educational Institutions: 10 proposals submitted by schools, universities, and educational programs.
- Community Groups: 8 proposals from local community organizations and citizen science groups.

Target demographics:

- Youth: 20 proposals specifically target youth engagement through educational programs and citizen science initiatives.
- Indigenous Communities: 5 proposals emphasize the involvement of indigenous and traditional communities.
- General Public: 15 proposals aim to engage the general public in OL and conservation activities.

Engagement strategies:

- Workshops and Training: 25 proposals include workshops aimed at educating participants about marine ecosystems and conservation practices.
- Citizen Science Projects: 18 proposals incorporate citizen science components for community participation in data collection.
- Collaborative Events: 12 proposals propose organizing hackathons, clean-up events, and community gatherings.

Geographic distribution:

- Europe: 25 proposals from European countries (France, Germany, Ireland, Portugal, Spain.)
- International: 5 proposals had components of internationalization, particularly collaborations with African and Latin American countries.

Each proposal was evaluated independently by two reviewers, based on the following scoring framework, totalling 100 points across ten categories:

1. Alignment with Mission Ocean objectives (10 points)
2. Methodology and working plan (10 points)
3. Participative and inclusive strategy (10 points)
4. Specific outcomes (10 points)
5. Sustainability of the project (10 points)
6. Impact assessment strategy (10 points)
7. Budget justification (10 points)
8. Outreach and communication strategy (10 points)
9. Innovative aspects (10 points)
10. Previous experience of the applicant (10 points)

Each criterion was carefully weighted to emphasise projects that align with the Mission's goals and also demonstrate strong participatory approaches, sustainability and innovation. High-scoring proposals were those that incorporated co-design elements, direct citizen engagement and strategies to include traditionally underrepresented communities, thereby ensuring social inclusion.

After the independent reviews, the top-scoring proposals were presented to an evaluation committee for final deliberation. This committee made the ultimate selection of the six projects to be funded and prepared the evaluation feedback for all 32 proposals, including both successful and unsuccessful

applicants, to help them refine their projects and enhance future alignment with the Mission objectives. This inclusive approach ensured that all participants received constructive insights for potential improvements.

A total of six innovative projects were selected and awarded funding (prep4blue.eu/prep4blue-funding-for-pilot-actions-winners-announced). The successful projects ranged from restoration workshops and innovative educational games to creative approaches like ecological hydrogen production through art and music, a hackathon for real-world ocean challenges, a virtual reality experience tackling marine noise pollution, and a blue Citizenship training course. Activities include music, hackathons, an oyster restoration project, an interactive workshop series, a training course on blue citizenship, a giant eco-friendly jigsaw puzzle, collages designed to educate citizens on the production of ecological hydrogen and a gamified VR experience on marine noise pollution!

The PAs ran between August and November 2024. After completion of the pilot activities, by the end of November 2025, each project completed a self-evaluation form following a PREP4BLUE PA reporting template (prep4blue.eu/portfolio/prep4blue-pilot-activity-reporting-template-engaging-citizens-in-mission-ocean). A description of the PAs is presented in Sections 3.2.3 through 3.2.8, and the self-completed evaluation reports can be seen in Annexes P1, P2, P3, P4, P5 and P6.

3.2.2 Preparatory Sessions and Follow-up Support

To support the PA with the development of their activities, the PREP4BLUE partners ran a series of webinars to introduce PREP4BLUE and the Mission objectives, explore strategies for designing and implementing effective citizen engagement actions, and explain how the PAs can evaluate the impact of their citizen engagement actions to ensure effectiveness and sustainability. The participation in these webinars was compulsory for the teams of the winning proposals and open to all teams that had submitted a proposal. The seminars can be seen in the Youtube channel of ICM-CSIC (www.youtube.com/@ICM-CSIC), and are summarized next.

Webinar 1 (July 17, 2024): Introduction to Citizen Engagement for Mission Ocean

Moderator: Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini (ICM-CSIC)

Speaker: David Whyte (UCC)

(Available at www.youtube.com/watch?v=s6HkabwQ--s)

This initial session started introducing the goals of citizen engagement in alignment with PREP4BLUE and the Mission. After reviewing the essential logistics, including financial requirements and deliverable deadlines, the support team was introduced, highlighting their roles in assisting participants. A high-level overview of the Mission objectives was provided, emphasizing how citizen participation in environmental stewardship and restoration efforts is crucial to achieving long-term ecological sustainability. Key themes included the importance of structured support for citizen-driven projects and their alignment with the Mission goals. Participants also presented their own projects, on topics such as OL, coastal restoration and environmental education. The session concluded with questions and answers, and an open discussion on the Mission challenges.

Webinar 2 (July 18, 2024): Preparing for and Implementing Citizen Engagement Actions

Moderator: Noemí Fuster (ICM-CSIC)

Speaker: Liz Morris-Webb (NRI)

(Available at www.youtube.com/watch?v=96Ylr4zHYxE)

This second session introduced the PREP4BLUE Toolbox (PREP4BLUE, 2025), designed to guide citizen engagement with the Mission. The presentations discussed strategies for mapping participants, fostering inclusivity and avoiding engagement fatigue. It also explored the levels of participation and emphasized the available tools for planning, monitoring and evaluation of the engagement actions. Resources included a toolkit and guidelines on diverse approaches for community involvement.

Webinar 3 (July 25, 2024): Using Citizen Engagement Expected Outcomes as a Planning and Monitoring Framework

Moderator: Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini (ICM-CSIC)

Speaker: David Whyte (UCC)

(Available at www.youtube.com/watch?v=20ctFE3VZaU)

The third session focused on the relevance of aligning the PAs with the Mission targets, and on how to use the Mission-expected citizen engagement outcomes as a framework for planning and assessing the impact of the project. Three main resources were highlighted: the citizen engagement activity reporting template, the PREP4BLUE Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper (developed as part of Deliverable 3.2 – *A synthesis report containing bespoke legacy training resources to support citizen action*) and the PREP4BLUE Toolbox (PREP4BLUE, 2025), all designed to help project teams to plan, track and document their efforts. Emphasis was placed on using these tools not only to fulfil the project reporting requirements but also to secure future funding by showcasing project alignment with European sustainability and social inclusion policies.

PREP4BLUE also offered mentorship to the winning proposals – through semi-structured interviews and check-ins during the project development and implementation – to ensure that the PAs maximised their contributions to the Mission. These interviews and check-ins fulfilled three purposes: first to support the pilots in their delivery and understanding of PREP4BLUE and the Mission tools; second to encourage pilots to engage more deeply with Mission Ocean & Waters now and in the future; and third to inform the final toolbox to be updated in 2025. All projects have taken up the opportunities for check-ins, including a final one after project completion (December 2024).

The interviews with the PA teams detected that the PREP4BLUE Toolbox (PREP4BLUE, 2025) is useful in planning activities, particularly when considered early in their process. Considerations on inclusivity – reaching their intended audience and considering how to include less obvious and possibly marginalised stakeholders – were particularly useful. Workshops introduced participants to principles of Leaving No-One Behind, that may be integrated into the Toolbox, and these were also found to be easier to focus on throughout the project: who might be left behind, why and what can you do to minimise this risk?

PA organisers were also asked to map their specific activities onto a Mission Activity Mapper, thus visualising how each contributing part of their activity (often different tasks with different participant groups) was working towards meeting the overarching Mission objectives and citizen engagement target outcomes. Grass roots practitioners, often working directly with citizens rather than through EU calls,

found this to be a difficult exercise, and not all took up the opportunity to map their activities in the requested format. However, many were working towards these outcomes indirectly, and the PREP4BLUE team has taken good note of their comments to deliver more user-friendly mappers and guidance in future. A similar mapper was developed to help pilot activities to think about the ten known dimensions of OL in their projects. Most found this a much easier task than mapping to Mission Ocean & Waters, and again most found it useful for maximising the benefits of their work with citizen engagement.

The results from the check-in interviews have been used after completion of the projects, to individually inform the PAs action final reporting using the PREP4BLUE PA reporting template. NRI researchers will also use the results from these interviews to inform the development of Task 3.1 (T3.1) in WP3 of the project (The [PREP4BLUE Toolbox for Citizen Engagement; PREP4BLUE, 2025](#)).

3.2.3 PA1: Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship Training Course for Early Career Ocean Professionals

The ECOP Programme had identified a critical skills gap in policy engagement among its members, which affects effective ocean advocacy. This PA proposed a training course, "*Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship*", to provide ECOPs with the necessary knowledge and skills to advocate for sustainable ocean management, promote engaged blue citizenship, and influence ocean policies. The course design incorporated local experiences and leveraged findings from a comprehensive needs assessment conducted across EU and non-EU countries.

An initial need-assessment revealed that 64% of ECOP respondents lack policy engagement experience, citing barriers such as unclear processes, insufficient information and limited training opportunities. It also identified an urging need of essential skills like understanding policy processes, communication, stakeholder engagement, negotiation and conflict resolution. With insights from 104 ECOPs and stakeholder consultations, the course curriculum was co-designed with 15 selected ECOPs through focus groups and workshops to ensure relevance and practicality.

Partnership-building was central to the project, with the collaboration of organisations such as Youth4Ocean, Youth and Environment Europe, and Ocean Teacher Global Academy. Future partnerships are being negotiated with groups like the International Ocean Institute and the EMSEA. The project also involved conducting surveys and one-on-one meetings with stakeholders to map existing training resources, disseminating best practices and fostering a collaborative development process.

By integrating local experiences and expanding collaborations globally, the course has the potential to influence policy advocacy efforts beyond Europe. Future plans include awareness campaigns during the Ocean Week in Brussels and expanding the course to regions like Asia and Africa, with growing interest in the United States of America. This initiative marks a significant step towards empowering ECOPs in the leadership of ocean sustainability and policy advocacy worldwide.

3.2.3.1 Methodology

The pilot action followed a participatory and phased approach to ensure inclusivity, adaptability, and effectiveness. It began with a comprehensive Stakeholder Engagement Plan, which involved mapping key stakeholders, structuring surveys, and summarizing relevant EU policies. A Needs Assessment was carried out through surveys and interviews targeting ECOPs to identify knowledge gaps and areas for improvement. Practice assessments included interviews with key organizations to understand existing

practices and challenges. Focus groups and one-on-one meetings were held to develop course content tailored to regional needs. Knowledge sharing took place through webinars, an online resource library, and the dissemination of best practices. Finally, a feedback loop was established to refine curriculum design and develop a mechanism for continuous input and improvement.

3.2.3.2 Outcomes

The project resulted in six confirmed partnerships and active collaboration with NGOs and ECOP networks. The course content was enriched by integrating regional needs and stakeholder feedback, leading to positive participant responses emphasizing the relevance and effectiveness of the curriculum. Participants highlighted how the content was practical and well-aligned with their learning needs. The collaboration also led to the creation of new initiatives with organizations across Europe and expansion plans for Africa, strengthening the network and broadening the reach of OL efforts.

3.2.3.3 Good Practices

One of the key best practices from the project was addressing communication barriers by emphasizing the need for multidisciplinary professionals, such as science communicators, to bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and policy advocacy. Stakeholder engagement was improved by leveraging pre-existing relationships and selecting facilitators with strong networks. Resource limitations were addressed by offering official certifications through partnerships, which encouraged greater participation. OL was redefined to include "cognitive equity," focusing on actionable care for the ocean. Flexibility in planning allowed core activities to continue despite unexpected disruptions, ensuring that the project remained on track. The limitations in resources required creative solutions, such as offering official certifications through partnerships to incentivize participation.

3.2.3.4 Lessons learned

Key challenges included communication barriers, where scientists struggled to convey their findings to policymakers, underscoring the need for multidisciplinary professionals like science communicators. Pre-existing relationships were important for stakeholder engagement, while new contacts were less responsive, indicating the importance of a dedicated communication strategy.

3.2.3.5 Contribution to the Mission

This PA equipped young ECOPs with tools and knowledge to engage in effective policy-making. It fostered partnerships and supported sustainable blue economy practices through strategic collaborations. The emphasis on co-creation aimed to influence international ocean governance frameworks, promoting bottom-up actions and campaigns – both in alignment with the Mission’s participatory aims. Additionally, the project prioritized capacity-building, offering policy tools tailored to empower stakeholders for meaningful action. Ultimately, the initiative laid the groundwork for a scalable and transformative OL effort, ensuring lasting contributions to the goals of Mission Ocean & Waters. The self-evaluation PA report is presented as Annex P1.

3.2.4 PA2: The BlueScape2024 Baltic Hackathon

The BlueScape2024 Baltic Hackathon took place on 8-10 November 2024 both online and in person in Pärnu, Estonia. The event brought together participants from diverse backgrounds to tackle OL and environmental science challenges through engaging and innovative formats. The organising team,

belonging to several organisations, held weekly meetings throughout the summer to brainstorm ideas for the hackathon's structure, challenges and rules. They collaboratively designed a schedule that included workshops, mentorship sessions and flexible breaks, as well as icebreaker activities and team-building exercises to keep participants engaged.

The Hackathon included both online and in-person challenges (DigiEduHack, digieduhack.com), hence also representing a step toward realizing the vision of the EU Digital Education Plan 2021-2027. Marketing efforts included social media campaigns, as well as email outreach across Estonia that encouraged schools to send teams of 3-5 students and their teachers or mentors.

The Hackathon invited participants to work on environmental challenges to "escape" and unlock subsequent stages of the event while learning about OL. Expert talks and mentorship sessions aimed to raise awareness of marine and freshwater ecosystem issues, and to engage participants in citizen science initiatives for real-time data collection and analysis. The Hackathon culminated with presentations from the participants, and by fostering community engagement and encouraging ongoing stewardship of marine and freshwater ecosystems. This event is a good example model of actions that are replicable in other regions across Europe.

3.2.4.1 Methodology

The Hackathon employed a structured methodology aligned with the Mission's focus on citizen engagement and OL. The Hackathon design included student-centred activities focused on ocean science, marine conservation, and the use of digital applications to engage the public in environmental monitoring. Experts, mentors, and community members helped create a rich learning environment that bridged formal education with real-world applications. By integrating interdisciplinary collaboration, digital tools, and hands-on problem-solving, the event aimed to foster OL among high school students, emphasizing the role of technology in addressing marine environmental challenges.

3.2.4.2 Outcomes

The BlueEscape2024 Baltic Hackathon led to increased awareness and engagement of young participants regarding Baltic Sea challenges, such as pollution, invasive species, and overfishing. The Hackathon empowered students to develop practical solutions through digital tools, demonstrating creativity and technical proficiency. Notably, participants designed apps and interactive platforms to monitor ocean health and biodiversity, showcasing their potential to contribute to real-world conservation efforts. Additionally, the involvement of marine scientists, educators, and the local community enriched the learning experience, providing students with diverse perspectives on ocean sustainability.

3.2.4.3 Good Practices

The Hackathon exemplified several best practices in OL pedagogy, including hands-on learning through technology, collaborative problem-solving, and the creation of digital resources. Engaging "digital natives" in the process ensured high levels of participation and innovation, especially in addressing ocean-related issues. The use of mentors from the Blue Economy and marine sciences sectors proved essential in guiding students, ensuring they received valuable, real-world feedback. Furthermore, the use of an online platform (DigiEduHack.com) facilitated broad participation, overcoming geographical barriers.

3.2.4.4 Lessons Learned

A key lesson from the Hackathon was the importance of meticulous planning and risk management. Logistics, venue arrangements, volunteer coordination, and sponsorship procurement all posed challenges that required effective mitigation. Language barriers were identified as an issue, with the need for translated resources related to science in native languages of the Baltic Sea region. Another important learning was the necessity to enhance OL within the core educational curricula, as significant gaps in knowledge remain among students. The Hackathon was possible thanks to the integrated efforts of experts from various fields and sectors, reinforcing the value of interdisciplinary collaboration.

3.2.4.5 Contribution to the Mission

The Hackathon contributed directly to Mission Ocean & Waters by enhancing OL and by fostering active citizenship in marine conservation. By engaging students, educators, and the wider community, the event supported the EU's broader goals of public engagement and collective action toward restoring European waters. The creation of digital tools and resources ensured the long-term impact of the initiative, offering scalable solutions for ocean monitoring and conservation. The Hackathon turned as a clear example of the key role of interdisciplinary approaches, essential for addressing complex, interconnected environmental challenges, thus aligning with the Mission's call for cross-sectoral collaboration. The self-evaluation PA report is presented as Annex P2.

3.2.5 PA3: The Sea of Sounds

The Sea of Sounds is a sensory and digital PA aimed at raising public awareness about underwater noise pollution and its effects on marine ecosystems, particularly cetaceans like whales and dolphins. The project uses virtual reality (VR) technology to provide participants with an immersive experience of marine soundscapes in the Vestfjord, Norway, helping them understand the impact of noise pollution on marine life. The main objectives of the project are to engage the public in marine conservation, to enhance understanding of noise pollution, and to strengthen the involvement of the local community in the protection and health of the marine ecosystems.

3.2.5.1 Methodology

The project adopted a participatory and co-design approach, involving local stakeholders, scientific partners, volunteers and the general public in shaping the VR experience and the educational activities. This collaborative effort ensured that the project was both scientifically accurate and accessible to a broad audience. The project emphasized social inclusion by providing free access to events and engaging local volunteers.

3.2.5.2 Results

The project successfully attracted over 320 participants, including local residents and international visitors, who expressed surprise at the biodiversity in the Vestfjord. It featured a combination of VR experiences (Figure 10), educational workshops, live listening stations, and large-format images, effectively connecting participants to marine conservation issues. Overall, the pilot action met its short-term objectives by raising awareness of underwater noise pollution and fostering public engagement in marine conservation.

3.2.5.3 Good Practices

The initiative highlighted the high potential of immersive technology, such as virtual reality, to engage participants in environmental issues. The combination of diverse activities, including educational workshops and live listening stations, facilitated a multi-faceted approach to the public. The free access to all events emphasised social inclusion, another good practice that ensured broader community involvement.

Figure 10. VR sessions exploring the marine ecosystem and soundscapes in the Vestfjord, Norway.

3.2.5.4 Lessons Learned

The project laid a strong foundation for long-term impact and highlighted the need for continuous involvement of local stakeholders early in the preparation process. It also indicated the importance of expanding outreach through diverse activities to attract a wider audience.

3.2.5.5 Contribution to the Mission

The Sea of Sounds project contributed to Mission Ocean & Waters by raising public awareness about underwater noise pollution and its effects on marine ecosystems, particularly cetaceans like whales and dolphins. It effectively engaged the public in marine conservation and strengthen local community involvement, aligning with the broad Mission of protecting and recovering the health of the marine environments. The self-evaluation PA report is presented as Annex P3.

3.2.6 PA4: Sea Synergy Oyster Project

The Sea Synergy Oyster Project is an initiative that focuses on citizen science, aimed at enhancing the understanding of marine biodiversity, particularly the role of the European Flat Oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) and its associated ecosystems. The project explores the ecological value of the marine environment, showcasing the presence of diverse species and habitats. The active participation from the community emphasises the role of citizen science in driving awareness and engagement in marine conservation.

3.2.6.1 Methodology

The methodology of the Sea Synergy Oyster Project employed a variety of strategies for data collection and community involvement:

- Observations are made using the iNaturalist platform (www.inaturalist.org), which has efficiently captured extensive species data.
- Community engagement occurs through diverse channels, including social media, public posters, and workshops. The strategy for public engagement considered not only the general public but also all local stakeholders (Figure 11).
- Surveys and public feedback mechanisms designed for both in-person and online participation are being implemented to gather insights from the community, ensuring inclusive involvement regardless of event attendance.

Figure 11. Stakeholder mapping for the SeaSynergy Oyster PA.

3.2.6.2 Results

The project, launched in early summer, has garnered over 1,000 observations contributed by 43 observers and has facilitated the involvement of 180 identifiers. The project continues to analyse survey data, revealing key findings such as the identification of 241 distinct marine species, with 57 serving as epibiota of *O. edulis*, and the recording of 830 oysters, providing a tangible foundation for study and conservation efforts in the region. Events include a showcase at the Skellig Experience Centre (Ireland) on 10 November 2024, alongside with workshops organised with local organisations like Inbhear Sceine and the Galway University Dive Club. Furthermore, a documentary trailer has been released to raise awareness and promote the showcase, evidencing the high project's reach and community interest (Figure 12).

Figure 12. (Left) Showcase documentary premier. (Right) Article in the local Kerry's Eye newspaper, printed on November 20, 2024.

3.2.6.3 Good Practices

The active participation from the community emphasises the role of citizen science in driving awareness and engagement in marine conservation. The project's primary objectives include:

- Documenting marine biodiversity in the channel, particularly species associated with *O. edulis*.
- Analysing species data to identify patterns and assess biodiversity.
- Engaging the community through events, workshops, and feedback mechanisms to foster a collaborative approach to marine exploration.

3.2.6.4 Lessons Learned

The initiative highlights the importance of community involvement in marine conservation efforts. Engaging the public through various channels and ensuring inclusive participation can significantly enhance data collection and awareness of biodiversity. The project also illustrates how citizen science can effectively contribute to understanding and protecting marine ecosystems.

3.2.6.5 Contribution to the Mission

The Sea Synergy Oyster Project has contributed to Mission Ocean & Waters by enhancing the understanding of marine biodiversity and the role of the European Flat Oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) within its ecosystem. Through citizen science, the project has raised awareness and has effectively promoted community engagement in marine conservation, supporting broader conservation goals and fostering a collaborative approach to marine exploration. The self-evaluation PA report is presented as Annex P4.

3.2.7 PA5: Blue Genes Giant Collaborative Puzzle

The Giant Puzzle was a Blue Genes community project, which consisted in the co-creation of a giant puzzle board with magnetised components that illustrate the interconnectedness of humans and the Ocean, a large-scale interactive arts-driven approach to community engagement that emphasises the essential role of collaboration (Figure 13) The co-creation of the puzzle allowed participants to symbolically piece together the components of a healthy Ocean, fostering a visual and tactile learning experience that serves as an educational tool and a community engagement activity on the relationship with the Ocean and the broader marine ecosystem.

Figure 13. Pictures illustrating the co-creation process of the Blue Genes Giant Collaborative Puzzle.

The key components of the co-creative process included:

- Diagnostic pre-event surveys assessed the Ocean-related concerns and OL level of participants, ensuring that the puzzle is aligned with the interests of the audiences. An initial survey with 48 participants highlighted concerns on pollution and biodiversity loss, underscoring the need for collective responsibility in addressing these issues. This feedback configured the puzzle themes, framing each piece within the context of shared environmental challenges.
- Collaborative workshops to fabricate the puzzle. The Blue Genes community worked together in small groups to assemble sections of the puzzle.

Real-time feedback tools and post-activity feedback and evaluation surveys assessed how the activity shifted the views of the participants from individual towards collaborative approaches, impacting on attitudes towards Ocean conservation. Rather than focusing on individual achievements, the project highlights how collective action is necessary to tackle complex environmental challenges. Through this symbolic assembly, participants experience first-hand the power of working together toward a shared goal, reinforcing the message that change is often beyond individual capability and relies on community collaboration. The methodology fostered cooperative engagement, using the puzzle to demonstrate how each contribution is essential to the whole. The puzzle was presented at the Fes! Cultura #AccióClima Festival (fescultura.org), a one-day event on 31 October 2024, in Barcelona, Spain, that gathered artists, cultural managers and environmental activists dedicated to eco-social transformation (Figure 14). The Festival, which aimed at inspiring sustainable creativity and fostering a committed community, positioned the puzzle within a dialogue table on the role of culture in environmental action.

Figure 14. Presentation of the Giant Puzzle and cultural-artistic performances at the Fes! Cultura #AccióClima Festival on October 31, 2024.

3.2.7.1 Methodology

The development of the project was based on four pillars: P1, project management and coordination; P2, participatory process of the community; P3, information: data for activity; and P4, communication, dissemination and legacy. Each pillar involved distinct tasks to achieve the defined objectives. P1 included administrative and financial management and general project coordination; P2 included stakeholder meetings and the elaboration process. P3 involved designing, creating and processing information, gathering and selecting data, and creating reports. Lastly, P4 focused on dissemination and communication of activities, and on improving audience engagement.

3.2.7.2 Outcomes

The event had both quantitative and qualitative significant results, engaging participants with Ocean-related topics. A total of 48 individuals participated, primarily from Spain, representing diverse backgrounds. A survey revealed that most participants were interested in the activity but preferred a more passive role, particularly in artistic or aesthetic components. The Kahoot quiz highlighted the audience level of OL indicating areas where knowledge-gap could still be addressed. Word clouds and feedback from the survey revealed the emotional connection with the Ocean, with participants expressing concerns about plastic pollution and the impact of industrial consumption. These outcomes guided the activity, emphasizing the importance of fostering understanding, dialogue, and artistic engagement.

3.2.7.3 Good Practices

One of the key best practices was the use of surveys to personalize the event and tailor the content to the participants' interests. These surveys enabled to gather valuable data, enhance engagement, and create an activity that resonated with the audience. Another best practice was the interactive use of Kahoot, which encouraged participation and dialogue, while maintaining a playful and non-competitive atmosphere. Additionally, involving participants in discussions about their concerns helped shape a deeper connection between their perceptions and the challenges faced by the Ocean. Ensuring a positive atmosphere and reducing the focus on competition were also vital in achieving the event's goals.

3.2.7.4 Lessons Learned

Budget constraints and dependence on external suppliers limited flexibility in certain areas, especially in terms of material and logistic planning. Weather conditions, particularly rain, also posed challenges, reducing visibility and potentially affecting attendance. Limited participant mobilization due to timing conflicts or commercial events, like Halloween, contributed to lower attendance than anticipated. These setbacks highlight the importance of pre-event coordination, clear communication, and adaptability to unpredictable factors.

3.2.7.5 Contribution to the Mission

The PA contributed to the Mission Ocean & Waters goals by promoting citizen engagement in addressing ocean-related challenges. Through raising awareness and fostering a connection with the Ocean, the PA aligned with two key objectives: preventing pollution and promoting a sustainable Blue Economy. The activity encouraged participants to reflect on their consumption habits and the environmental impacts associated with them, contributing to the reduction of pollution and supporting a more circular economy. Additionally, the event sought to inspire collective action, emphasizing that individual and community efforts are integral to achieving the Mission goals. The methodology remains scalable, offering potential to replicate and expand, ensuring broader participation and sustained engagement with Ocean stewardship. The self-evaluation PA report is presented as Annex P5.

3.2.8 PA6: Sustainable Coastal Futures

Sustainable Coastal Futures was an interdisciplinary initiative that addressed the long-term resilience of coastal areas through community-led scenario planning. This project brought scientists, policymakers and local communities in an interactive workshop setting to collaboratively envision sustainable futures for coastal regions. The methodology emphasised collaborative scenario planning, allowing participants to explore realistic pathways for resilient coastal futures. The approach was rooted in interactive techniques that merged science, art and community engagement, promoting a shared vision for coastal sustainability. The workshop took place on November 15, 2024, at the UNESCO's Wattenmeer Visitor Center in Wilhelmshaven (Germany), providing an excellent setting within a protected ecosystem.

The participation of key stakeholders – including experts from renewable energy initiatives like the hydrogen flagship project H2Mare (www.wasserstoff-leitprojekte.de/projects/h2mare), local government representatives and researchers on public acceptance of regenerative technologies – ensured that the discussions captured technical, social and environmental perspectives essential to addressing coastal challenges. The project adapted Art For Futures Lab creative techniques: *future-prototyping*, where participants visually model potential sustainable futures; *world-building*, where

groups collaboratively create narratives around sustainable development; *backcasting*, from a desired future, where the participants outline the necessary steps to reach the utopia; and *concept Art*, where visual products make complex topics accessible and engaging. Moreover, through *participatory mapping and scenario planning*, participants charted resources, challenges and possible futures for their coastal areas. Scenario planning encouraged stakeholders to envision alternative futures, emphasizing that sustainable solutions require collective effort and adaptability. Finally, facilitated discussions prompted participants to consider shared insights and to refine ideas together.

Post-workshop surveys assessed shifts in the participants understanding of sustainable coastal futures. Outcomes, including scenario maps and visualisations, were shared through a touring exhibition and social media, ensuring broader community engagement and fostering ongoing dialogue around sustainable coastal development. The co-created coastal scenarios were also shared through an exhibition and digital platforms to inspire further community engagement.

3.2.8.1 Methodology

This PA employed the *Art for Futures Lab* methodology, which was pivotal in creative, collaborative, and futures-thinking approaches to sustainability and societal transformation. Tailored specifically for this pilot's context, the methodology facilitated the co-creation of four future scenarios centred on coastal sustainability by 2050, addressing critical issues such as green hydrogen energy production, ecosystem restoration, and community empowerment. The methodology integrated tools like scenario planning, systems thinking, backcasting, and design thinking with creative techniques such as world-building. These tools allowed participants to navigate complex challenges and generate actionable pathways toward sustainable and regenerative futures.

Through participatory engagement, diverse perspectives were synthesized, leading to innovative solutions that balanced environmental, social, and economic priorities. Key outputs of the pilot action included visual and narrative elements—mood boards, drawings, AI-generated images, and compelling future narratives—that made abstract ideas more accessible. These tangible outputs served as both tools for continued engagement and as means of advocacy and education, ensuring that the insights gained from the workshop extend beyond the PA and contribute to broader efforts in coastal sustainability. The PA emphasized collaborative scenario-building, ensuring that diverse stakeholders—including policymakers, scientists, industry representatives and local citizens—were actively involved. By leveraging participatory methods such as Backcasting, Future Prototyping and World-Building, participants were able to empathize with different perspectives, fostering a sense of shared ownership over the scenario outcomes. This inclusive approach not only enhanced systemic understanding but also encouraged the co-creation of actionable solutions for coastal management, ensuring a holistic and collaborative vision for sustainable futures.

3.2.8.2 Outcomes

The PA successfully engaged diverse stakeholders in co-creating future scenarios for sustainable coastal management by 2050. Key findings highlighted the value of empathy and perspective-sharing, with participants gaining a deeper understanding on complex topics and the role of different stakeholders. Short-term outcomes included co-creating four future scenarios and strengthening cross-sectoral networks. Long-term impacts, such as policy and community engagement, touring exhibitions, and enhanced OL contribute to sustainable development and advocacy in coastal regions.

3.2.8.3 *Good practices*

The PA demonstrated several best practices, crucial for ensuring the effectiveness and sustainability of participatory engagements. First, interdisciplinary collaboration played a key role in integrating diverse perspectives, fostering innovative solutions. The *Art for Futures Lab* methodology proved effective in translating abstract concepts into actionable visions, emphasizing the importance of visual narratives in stakeholder engagement (Figure 15). Clear communication, transparency, and the inclusion of residents were instrumental in maintaining trust and participation, despite logistical challenges. Leveraging participatory tools ensured that all participants could empathize with stakeholders, promoting an inclusive and systemic approach to coastal management.

3.2.8.4 *Lessons Learnt*

The PA faced several challenges that offered important lessons for future projects. Late venue confirmation at the UNESCO-Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer Besucherzentrum limited outreach, reducing participation from younger, under-represented groups. Targeted outreach through digital channels helped, but earlier venue confirmation would have broadened engagement. A key debate on green hydrogen highlighted misconceptions, which were addressed by expert-led discussions, fostering a shift towards more holistic, inclusive future visions. The technical complexity of topics like green hydrogen and coastal sustainability posed barriers for non-experts, but the *Art For Futures Lab* tools helped simplify these challenges, making complex ideas more accessible. Limited regional participation was another challenge, particularly from neighbouring areas, emphasizing the need for broader outreach efforts. Lastly, resource constraints led to an in-person format, highlighting the need for hybrid options in future projects to enhance accessibility and engagement.

Figure 15. Small group discussions during a session on future scenarios, using *The Art for Futures Lab* methodology.

3.2.8.5 Contribution to the Mission

The PA was very well aligned with the Mission Ocean & Waters citizen engagement goals. The PA enhanced OL by raising awareness of the link between coastal ecosystems, green energy transitions, and sustainable development. The participatory methodologies empowered citizens with knowledge and tools to influence policy decisions, promoting a stronger connection between scientific, societal, and policy-driven approaches. Additionally, the PA encouraged collaboration across sectors, fostering partnerships that will continue to support sustainable coastal management in the long term. By promoting inclusivity and systemic thinking, the PA contributed to the Mission objectives of sustainable coastal futures. The self-evaluation PA report is presented as Annex P6.

3.2.9 Pilot Actions In-Person Final Meeting

At the time of writing this Report, PREP4BLUE is organising a final in-person meeting in Barcelona for the six teams that successfully developed the PAs. The main objective of this meeting will be that these teams get to know each other, explain their interests and previous work, share their experiences with the PAs, and explore the potential synergies among them. For the PREP4BLUE team it will be an excellent opportunity to learn from their experiences, as well as to use networking tools and observe and support the possible the birth of a CoP.

The meeting is planned to last two days in late March or early April 2025, open to the entire six PA teams with travel and subsistence support provided for up to two representatives for each of them. Besides the expositions of these teams on the PAs and other initiatives, there will be PREP4BLUE presentations on: best networking practices, coastal regeneration initiatives, and the Mission objectives, strategy and funding opportunities. This will also be an opportunity for the teams to visit the Barceloneta coastal neighborhood, where the participants will learn about ongoing community initiatives.

4 Learnings and Recommendations on Citizen Engagement with the Mission

4.1 Learnings

The Ocean and waters are the principal and essential component of the living Earth, and nowadays they are at stake. Indeed, the climatic and environmental crises are causing changes that are difficult to predict, with the thermodynamic state of the Earth possibly approaching a threshold towards another state of equilibrium and our ecosystems degrading and experiencing a massive loss of biodiversity, a new mass extinction. These are facts that most population recognize yet ignore in their daily attitudes. The reason is a dramatic disconnection between knowledge and emotions, and possibly also other feelings such as denial (changes are difficult to detect at daily scales), fatalism (nothing can be done) or an uncertain trust that nothing will happen, that humankind can keep overexploiting planet Earth because there will always be miraculously bioengineering solutions.

The Mission explicitly recognises the extraordinary importance of these circumstances. In its communication and engagement section, the Mission Plan (EC, 2021a, p. 52-53) states the importance *“to create a stronger emotional connection between society and aquatic ecosystems... rather than simply attempting to ‘plug’ the knowledge gap. A focus on knowledge alone often is not sufficient for achieving communication goals. Framing messages in terms of science and evidence failed to move people to be more concerned about the health of the ocean – or towards support for pollution reduction policies.”* The Mission Plan continues pointing at the need to avoid *“fuel feelings of fatalism: the bleak but pervasive notion that little can be done to address the multiple crises our world faces... citizens need to understand that they can “do something about it”, thereby increasing their awareness that they are agents of change”*.

A possibly essential aspect related to the emotional connection with the Ocean and waters is the power – physical, intellectual and emotional – of working together. Citizen engagement with the Ocean and waters is, above all, a fully collaborative process, in the sense that it cannot become effective without citizens joining in participative, inclusive and democratic networks. Endorsing and promoting the emotional connection necessarily implies endorsing and promoting the creation and growth of people together, the formation of resilient and mature citizen organisations. It implies supporting the activities of individuals and organisations through a diversity of strategies and actions that facilitate the setup, development and mobilisation of citizen networks. Learning how this can be done has precisely been one of the driving axes for PREP4BLUE.

There are possibly many different types of networks – from a diversity of places and peoples, and around an immense variety of topics – but for this learning process PREP4BLUE has chosen three types of networks (coastal communities, OL networks and art-science initiatives). Despite their differences, all three types are connected, to a lesser or greater extent, with the three overarching Mission objectives (healthy ecosystems, ban contamination and sustainable blue economy). For each of these networks, we have explored how to facilitate citizen engagement through networking and mobilisation, taking into consideration five strategies:

- **Fill the Gap:** filling the knowledge and emotional gap to raise citizen awareness and response.
- **EU Leadership:** EU Leadership for Ocean & waters sustainability and global ocean governance.

- **Full Democracy:** develop and pilot frameworks and processes for participatory governance and deliberative democracy.
- **New Practices:** develop, try and apply deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for collaborative citizen engagement.
- **Ocean Literacy** at its widest expression: OL that encompasses capacity building, education and training, citizen science, communication and outreach.

Through our PREP4BLUE work with many committed citizen associations, organisations and networks we have learnt that the differences are in details, possibly in where the emphasis is, but at the core they are all mainly moved by emotions such as empathy, sensibility and generosity, possibly much more than by scientific knowledge. Remarkably, to be engaged with Nature (with the Ocean and waters as the essential and central element) is also to be engaged with each other, as we are all part of Nature. This spirit is always present in all committed networks. Again, from the Mission Plan (EC, 2021a, p. 53), *“to change hearts as well as minds on this issue, communication actions will seek to inspire awe and wonder, and connect with the things people deeply value...”*

One significant instance of the relevance and potential of developing these harmonic values arose during the plenary sessions of the UNODC (oceansdecade-conference.com/speakers.php). The Conference had four plenary sessions in a room with a capacity of over 1000 people: session 1 on Science and Solutions for a Clean, Healthy and Resilient Ocean, session 2 on Science and Solutions for a Sustainable and Resilient Ocean Economy, session 3 on Science and Solutions for a Safe and Predicted Ocean, and session 4 on An Inspiring and Engaging Ocean for All. Remarkably, the single plenary session that received a standing ovation was session 4, where the speakers extensively addressed the intangible values of the Ocean (webcast.unesco.org/events/2024-04-IOC-ODC).

The principal learnings arising from the work on citizen engagement and mobilisation done within PREP4BLUE are the following:

1. **Citizen organizations can provide very significant outcomes with limited resources.** Our work with bottom-up organizations has shown that they can be extremely productive, attaining substantial results with small economical and capacity-building support. This has been clear with the several types of networks that have been advised and logistically supported through PREP4BLUE, and has become most evident when considering the formative and economical support to the PAs and their very significant outcomes.
2. **The crucial role played by individuals leading community initiatives.** Inspirational network and community leaders are essential for fostering engagement, maintaining momentum, and ensuring the long-term success of participatory initiatives. Their ability to connect with diverse stakeholders, facilitate meaningful dialogue, and adapt strategies to local contexts has proven invaluable.
3. **From the citizen perspective, there are no clear differences between the three overarching objectives of the Mission.** On the contrary, for associations, organisations and networks working on topics related with the environment, these objectives are fully interconnected: healthy ecosystems cannot exist with pollution, which itself is the outcome of unsustainable practices. Emotional connection is indeed the linkage between apparently different approaches, such as OL, coastal communities and art-science approximations. Bridging the knowledge-emotional gap

requires the working together of scientists, innovators, artists, philosophers and all creative people.

4. **There are no substantial geographical differences in the commitment of citizen organisations, the major differences are in historical structural support.** No EU country seems to have an adequate structural support to grassroots movements in Ocean sustainability and literacy, but some countries have benefit from large projects that set the right basis for creating an organized bottom-up structure. Our experience has shown that these minimum maturity and confidence levels are necessary for the continuity of a joint collaborative initiative beyond the temporal frame of a project. This is clearly the case of Ireland, with its very active and mature IOLN, and something similar is now happening in Catalonia. In other countries, such as Italy, the community was possibly not diverse and mature enough, as shown by the dissolution of initial attempts at establishing an OL network.
5. **There is a need to develop connections and trust between local, regional and national stakeholders.** There is a lack of knowledge and often a lack of trust between small local organisations and larger national entities, including research institutions. Large entities often get major funding from public calls and high prominence from the media, while small and medium-size civil organisations get very little support and visibility, giving rise to a sense of neglect. Further, administration requirements are often too demanding to properly be handled by these civil organisations. An increase in the provision of Financial Support to Third Parties in the form of cascade grants would provide a connection between the small and large organisations, between the on-the-ground initiatives and those ones with much larger structural public funding.
6. **Robust motivated networks rely on real connections, they rely on shared live experiences with people and Nature.** Virtuality may help but will never replace reality to create an emotional and lasting connection with Nature: for a mature and robust network there is a prime need of joint conceptual reflection and sustained practical activities. Online sessions allow for a wide array of perspectives, while in-person meetings facilitate stronger connections and more in-depth collaborative work. The hybrid approach is an alternative, showcasing the importance of flexible engagement, maximizing reach and fostering closer bonds within the network.
7. **Collaborative networking is a principal way towards innovative solutions that can be incorporated by most citizens.** Working in diversity introduces significant challenges for maintaining a clear focus during discussions but is the only pathway towards innovative interdisciplinary and intersectoral approaches. Diversity enriches conversations but also occasionally drives away the focus from key Mission Ocean & Waters targets, highlighting the importance of setting clear goals for every engagement activity.
8. **Citizen networking is an antidote to negative feelings of despair and impotence.** Eco-anxiety may emerge as a common concern among participants, as marine conservation topics can evoke feelings of despair, and solastalgia (the distress caused by environmental change) is a clear signal of a lack of harmony with our environment. Positive thinking and reflective practices, such as guided meditations and rituals to open/close sessions, can help to process emotions constructively. Addressing emotional aspects is essential for sustained citizen engagement in environmental projects.
9. **An outstanding variety and quantity of committed people and organisations.** The number and quality of citizen organisations committed with the conservation and regeneration of the Ocean and waters is simply amazing. This certainly provides the necessary critical mass to move towards

sustainability, it shows up as an extraordinary opportunity for a societal transformation, possibly only requiring the setting of the right priorities and strategies in public funding.

4.2 Recommendations

The main feeling that arises after working during 32 months in PREP4BLUE together with organisations and networks is of serene satisfaction: of appreciation of the extraordinary enthusiasm of many individuals and organisations wonderfully committed with the Ocean and waters; of hope that our work has supported and nurtured a significant number of these organisations and networks; and of trust that we can now provide some significant practical and strategic feedback to the Commission for the development and upscaling phase of Mission Ocean & Waters. This section precisely addresses this last aspect, providing both practical recommendations that can be useful to the organisations and networks as well as strategic recommendations that can possibly help the Commission when moving towards phase 2 of the Mission.

4.2.1 Practical Project and Network Recommendations

Practical recommendations to the civil initiatives arise from the very diverse experiences gained throughout PREP4BLUE, both in specific capacity building and logistic support to the PAs as well as in backing the establishment and development of networks. A summary of these recommendations is provided next, structured into project- and network-oriented recommendations.

4.2.1.1 Project-Oriented Recommendations

The work done in launching and supporting the execution of the PAs brought many useful experiences, which were confirmed by the responses of the PA teams in informal interviews. These relate to the capacitation and support of individual organisations and small networks that carry out projects related to citizen engagement and mobilisation towards the conservation and restoration of the Ocean and waters, as presented next.

1. **Knowledge transfer sessions.** Workshops can effectively introduce participants to the objectives and tools within Mission Ocean & Waters, as well as the gender equality, OL and Leaving No-One Behind frameworks. These workshops can also help develop best practices in collaboration, inclusion and democracy within an organisation and particularly in the frame of ongoing projects. They can also serve to prepare the organisations in the logistic aspects of a project, from the planning and preparation of a proposal, to the follow up and justification.
2. **Investing on leadership.** As explained in Section 4.1, skilled and engaged leaders are central to the success of participatory initiatives. All resources dedicated to the formation of these leaders will certainly be a very good investment.
3. **The benefits of 1:1 mentoring.** Many organisations are already highly motivated towards the conservation and restoration of the Ocean and waters, and often have vast previous experience. Despite so, some of these organisations have not carefully or have not recently considered the diversity of ways they can engage or broaden the inclusion of citizens, and were often not familiar with the Mission and its targets. Engagement is frequently done with a friendly audience or through an existing list of participants. Interviewees found that early mentoring on the different available tools – particularly during the pre-bidding stages of planning – was useful in breaking

down their project objectives, explicating and further aligning them with the Mission, and bringing up new pathways towards diverse and inclusive audiences.

4. **Support Toolbox.** The interviews with the PA teams detected that the PREP4BLUE Toolbox (PREP4BLUE, 2025) is useful in planning activities, particularly when considered early in their process. Of particular use were considerations regarding inclusivity – reaching beyond the initial target audience by considering how to include less obvious and possibly marginalised stakeholders. The Toolbox should be simple yet comprehensive, incorporating democratic and participatory principles such as Leaving No-One Behind. These tools help identify conflictive situations and minimise the associated risks.
5. **Developing simple planning habits.** Mapping the proposed activities onto a user-friendly mapper, can be very useful. The use of the PREP4BLUE Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper not only encourage the use of citizen engagement target outcomes but also helps to visualise how the diverse tasks of a project contribute towards meeting the overarching Mission objectives.
6. **Need to diversify toolboxes.** Often the organisers of citizen engagement projects come from non-science backgrounds, so that the tools provided need to be written in easy-visual ways that are easy to understand by these end users. It would be convenient to use a range of accessible languages that meet the needs of different types of citizen engagement organisers (e.g., large European bidders, planners or local projects).
7. **Minimize reporting demands.** Projects are recurrently under-resourced, which does not allow to hire dedicated personnel, and many small and medium-size organisations do work on a voluntary basis, without the capacity of dedicating extensive time to reporting demands.
8. **Building emotional resilience through in-person group reflection.** Engaging with environmental challenges can bring up tough emotions, including eco-anxiety and solastalgia, which will be best addressed through reflective practices like group discussions and meditations. These simple but indispensable support systems help maintain the group’s enthusiasm and commitment.

4.2.1.2 Network-Oriented Recommendations

Multiple learnings have also arisen from the work done with very diverse coastal communities, OL initiatives and arts-sciences networks. These are summarized next.

1. **Simple and innovative virtual tools.** Virtual tools are necessary for developing joint projects, contacting potential partners and collaborators, minimising displacements and optimizing time and resources. Virtual collaborative games and immersive reality tools can also provide innovative ways to reach, explore and participate in remote places, such as the deep ocean and the polar regions. Tools, however, must be clear and simple, adhering to the frame of Leaving No-One Behind.
2. **Building community through hands-on interaction.** Virtual tools are essential for multiple purposes, from initial contacts to the everyday logistics, but it is through in-person gatherings that a robust and bond community is created. There is a wide range of possibilities, from short meetings to structured workshops and retreats, for sharing ideas towards common goals as well as to co-create and co-design innovative and transformative approaches. Starting with in-person interactions strengthens bonds, builds trust, creates enthusiasm and generates a sense of ownership, and further leads to transformative new ideas.

3. **New non-cognitive tools for public engagement.** Standard OL is necessary but not sufficient for a robust engagement of organisations and networks: to create such a robust commitment it is indispensable to raise an emotional connection. This can be brought about through sensory experiencing of the Ocean and waters, either via immersion in the aquatic natural environments or through artistic experiences and evocations of the natural world. The necessary conditions for a resilient engagement are that these in-person activities be fully creative but also relatable, accessible, and maintained through time (a one-time experience usually has a passing impact).
4. **Empower youth and marginalized groups.** Make sure to involve young people as well as participants from marginal communities, giving them the opportunity to shape the conversation and bring new, fresh ideas to the table. The underlying idea is inclusivity, so that everyone's voice is heard, creating a diverse and richer approach to addressing the complex environmental issues.
5. **Build partnerships with local institutions.** Reach out to scientific, social and artistic organizations within towns, cities, countries and regions to create dynamic partnerships that help the network grow. A network will strengthen through collaboration with local institutions, hence deepening its roots in the local community, through both their difficulties and goals.
6. **Favour the engagement of networks with private companies.** Sustainability has become a social trend, which brings numerous opportunities to create effective complicities between networks and private companies that do believe and search for an environmentally and climatically respectful way of doing business. This includes favouring that the employees of these companies participate in literacy and sensory Ocean and waters related activities.
7. **Search connections with other analogous or complementary networks.** Local networks can benefit in many ways by establishing connections with local networks from other regions and countries. These benefits include sharing resources and perspectives, as well as building enthusiasm and resilience.
8. **Create spaces for collaboration.** Bring together a diversity of social agents and stakeholders in co-creating workshops that drive collaboration, the sharing of ideas, and the development of innovative methods and proposals to address the pressing Ocean and water challenges. These workshops shall foster conversation and understanding, so that everyone can contribute their unique perspectives.
9. **Promoting open spaces and activities for citizen engagement.** Promote citizen participation by creating open spaces and activities for dialog, such as theatre groups, reading clubs, art classes, *etc.* These activities could take place in local sites of easy access and high visibility – such as schools, libraries and civic centres – and have open sessions that would promote further citizen engagement.
10. **Partnering with schools.** Middle and high schools are often searching for ideas and places where their students can develop different types of projects. This partnership can have numerous benefits: engage the students, create innovative ideas, and permeate to the entire school and the students' families.
11. **Incorporate an interdisciplinary scientific perspective to the networks and projects.** The collaborative spaces will benefit mostly by incorporating a diversity of scientists. Marine sciences are certainly indispensable, but networks will benefit largely by incorporating the social dimension through the social sciences, and by exploring new imaginaries through innovative artistic and philosophical approaches.

4.2.2 Strategic Mission Recommendations

We conclude this Report with a critical reflection on the requirements of strategies that can effectively empower citizen initiatives. We provide next a list of bullet points for improving the actual strategy that promotes citizen participation and engagement in the Mission, and conclude with some general considerations on the main limitation of this general strategy and the proposal of an alternative citizen-oriented type of Missions.

4.2.2.1 Specific Mission recommendations

1. **A need for integrative calls.** The climatic and environmental crises reflect an unfair socioeconomic system, they cannot be addressed without a joint consideration of causes and effects. The Mission should help bridge this gap, fostering a holistic understanding that incorporates the social, ethical, and emotional dimensions of marine science.
2. **A need for interdisciplinary transformative sciences.** For the Mission to be fully innovative and transformative, it must continue to prioritize truly interdisciplinary calls, which integrate areas that are traditionally viewed as separate — ocean, social, artistic and philosophical sciences. Recent Mission calls that integrate art and ocean science have been well received and have led to very innovative projects that will be exciting to watch. These creative calls should consider developing a holistic perception of our environment — one that includes sensory, intuitive and collaborative associations and resonances — going beyond a purely cognitive Cartesian approach.
3. **Promote interaction between civil organisations and interdisciplinary sciences.** The benefits of interdisciplinary thinking must reach down to the civil organisations and networks, promoting the interaction of marine and social scientists, as well as artists and philosophers, with the civil organisations.
4. **Address the emotional wellbeing of citizens.** The Mission also stands as a unique frame to address the relation between harmony with Nature and emotional wellbeing. The concept of *Harmony with Nature* was promoted by the UN in 2009 and its philosophy of searching a just balance between the economic, social, and environmental needs of the present and future generations strongly connects with the core message in the Mission Ocean & Waters (www.harmonywithnatureun.org). The development of transdisciplinary approaches through the combination of scientific cognitive and sensory-artistic perceptions can be a very impactful instrument towards individual and collective harmony and wellbeing.
5. **Mirror the Mission targets in local to national funding.** Local networks usually participate in projects and initiatives with relatively small budgets. These initiatives often find difficulties to upscale their goals and budgets towards EU citizen engagement targets. One pathway to this could be to lobby so that the Mission targets be included as criteria in the setup of local and national calls. This may nudge smaller projects that incorporate the same goals of Mission Ocean & Waters.
6. **Make more use of Financial Support to Third Party (FSTP) provisions in funding calls.** A need remains for a broader and deeper communication of Mission Ocean & Waters and its value beyond the core stakeholder groups, reaching across the European society at large. The Commission's aim of having on-the-ground communities taking ownership of the Mission in a meaningful way has yet to be achieved. A key issue here is that communities do not perceive a tangible benefit or added value from the Mission. A remedy would possibly be to stipulate a much

greater use of FSTP in Mission Call Topics, so as to provide consistent and tangible benefit to the communities and small organisations that engage with research projects but are not yet capable of becoming involved in project consortia. This FSTP provision could be made mandatory in some or most of the remaining work programmes for Phase 2 of the Mission, which could provide small grants (*e.g.*, representing 5%-10% of the total call value) for different activities, depending on the project's focus. This would give small groups, communities and citizen science initiatives, a reason to consistently engage with the Mission, investigate what the projects are, who is providing funding, what is the Mission doing, and overall to see its benefit via small scale funding.

7. **Promote national structural funding.** Citizen engagement and networking shows very different levels of development in diverse countries. One clear example is the success of the OL community in Ireland and the difficulties it has experienced in Italy. This is the result of many factors, among them, past individual and institutional leadership in the frame of successful EU projects, which did set the solid foundations to build a resilient network. The challenge is to create proper structures at regional or national levels, which are now lacking in most of the EU, so as to guarantee the continuity of these networks. Research institutions or a single citizen organisation are possibly not the best option to lead these structures, as there may be some jealousy and lack of confidence among participants. Rather, national structures could coordinate networks, providing basal resources and ensuring that bottom-up funding is sustained in time through open calls.
8. **Promote and support synergies with the Ocean Decade.** The Ocean Decade shares many goals and values with Mission Ocean, with the advantage of very high visibility, particularly among civil organisations. Promoting and supporting joint Ocean projects with the UN on citizen engagement and mobilisation would have a high impact and would further position the EU as a world leader in Ocean sustainability.
9. **Recognize and celebrate excellence in sustainability.** It is important to recognize individuals and organisations that have a committed and effective role at different levels, from local to international, in developing good practices and initiatives for the protection of the Ocean and waters. Networks can support the recognition of local initiatives, but the public and private stakeholders are the ones that should provide the tools for recognition at national and international levels.
10. **Facilitate transnational civil partnerships.** Provide mechanisms and funding to facilitate the establishment of EU connections and networks, particularly among local networks that address similar problems but from different perspectives. Provide also the basis for reaching beyond Europe, turning the EU as a world-leader in citizen engagement and mobilisation.
11. **Create communication channels that reach the civil organizations.** It is imperative to develop effective ways for reaching the civil organisations and networks, with clear and simple information on possibilities for collaboration and funding. Most local organisations are still unaware of the EU programs and the possibilities that these programs provide to bottom-up organisations.

4.2.2.2 Collaborative Trust Missions

The Mission Plan (EC, 2021a, p. 35) states that *“The Mission will **connect Europe’s citizens and local communities with the ocean, seas and waters, facilitate broad ownership and education and co-design the transitions within the communities ... [The Mission] will act as a new tool to pilot **deliberative democratic decision-making that will help citizens to co-design the future of Europe, in terms of*****

sustainable management of aquatic resources and co-implement transformative solutions supporting the restoration of EU waters... [The Mission] will leverage social innovation throughout the co-design, co-development, co-implementation, and co-monitoring of solutions for sustainable use of the ocean and waters.”

The above statements recognise an imperative necessity for supporting bottom-up movements capable of promoting a transition towards an environmentally and climatically sustainable society. Only these movements can set the transformative pathway towards a new socio-economic model, which recognizes that humankind is overexploiting Planet Earth and that, as a consequence, we have already crossed most planetary boundaries. However, the truth is that the Mission still predominantly proposes the development of scientific and technical remediation and adaptation actions rather than the advancement of preventive new societal behaviours.

The Mission has progressively adapted to become more interdisciplinary and intersectoral, continuously diversifying both on strategies and number of calls. Now, there are also plans for cross-Mission calls. Ocean and waters/aquatic research is also present in many calls within the EU clusters on environment, climate, society and others, possibly creating substantial overlapping. The Commission is constantly calling for the creation of synergies among the diverse programs, but is this efficient to engage and mobilise citizens?

An alternative is to develop a new type of Missions, focused on the empowering of civil organisations towards the development of the new societal model that Planet Earth demands. Pelegrí *et al.* (2025b) have called them *Trust* collaborative missions, a name that reflects both hope and care. Mission Ocean & Waters is essentially a scientific-technical Mission: it starts from a general idea, call it objective or challenge, and mainly focuses on developing and implementing remediation or adaptation measures. In contrast, *Trust Missions* would focus primarily on the engagement and mobilisation of people through networks and CoPs, ensuring that most of the Mission’s funding arrives to these civil organisations for designing, testing and implementing the preventive measures (Figure 16.) The technical Mission prioritizes short- or mid-term sustainable growth and innovation, while the *Trust Mission* would be a long-term investment towards overall and harmonious human and Nature development.

Trust Missions could be implemented around the climatic and environmental emergencies. We cannot ask citizens to address these crises by engaging solely with the Ocean and waters, as all components of the living Earth (hydrosphere, atmosphere, cryosphere and biosphere) are interlinked and people experience so in their everyday lives. Hence, *Trust Missions* should also be Earth-system oriented, possibly allowing some geographical or thematic structuring for sole practical reasons.

Figure 16. (Top) Mission Ocean and Waters, as an example of a technical mission: from the inner general and thematic objectives, through their enablers, into the specific technical projects-outputs and the target basins; this is accomplished via technical and scientific methods and tools. (Bottom) The Climate-Ocean Trust mission: from the integrative climate challenge, through citizen engagement and mobilization strategies, into the social actors and the target basins; this is attained via co-creative/co-design inclusive and democratic collaborative methods. Reproduced from Pelegrí et al. (2025b)

5 Conclusions

In this Report we have presented the experiences of the PREP4BLUE team working with a variety of citizen initiatives in three different themes: coastal and riparian communities; ocean literacy within and beyond the school system; and creative initiatives around ocean sciences and arts. This work goes from the identification and exploratory contacts with numerous initiatives all the way to support a selection of them in many different aspects, such as searching for synergies with other organisations, capacity building through formative virtual and in-person sessions, setting and implementing workshops, looking for funding sources, and the preparation and development of sessions at an international conference. It also includes preparing and launching a call for small pilot actions, evaluating and selecting the winning proposals, running the formation and mentoring of the pilot actions teams, and evaluating their performance, including assets and limitations.

We have worked with 21 initiatives belonging to the three different types of networks. These networks include 15 initiatives selected after an extensive number of initial contacts, plus six networks that applied and obtained the pilot actions funding. The final goal of our work has been to develop and test methods and tools for citizen engagement and mobilisation. The methodology that has been applied includes knowledge transfer and individual mentoring, the use of a support toolbox, the backing in strategies for emotional support, the development of virtual tools, the realization of hands-on sensory and artistic experiences, and the organization of activities and workshops for the growth of networks into communities of practice, among others. The general appraisal is very satisfactory, with the explicit recognition that all methods revolve around collaborative co-creation, and that successful networks largely respond to a combination of good preparation, high emotional motivation, robust commitment and generous collaboration.

Throughout the entire project, we have lived many experiences with these very different teams, some of them very personal and intense, which have provided a number of remarkable lessons. These are here expressed in a section on Learnings and Recommendations, many of them revolving around the relevance of searching synergies and creating opportunities for partnering: with public and private stakeholders, in innovative settings, through interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaborations. Additionally, we have provided a number of strategic recommendations to the EU Commission, such as supporting interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity, favouring national and EU structural funding, and promoting and supporting synergies with the Ocean Decade. Our final recommendation has been on the convenience of implementing a new type of collaborative *Trust Missions*, aimed at logistically and financially supporting committed grassroots organisations and networks, as the best possible strategy towards a healthy and resilient socio-economic system that respects the Earth planetary boundaries.

6 Bibliography

Albrecht G, *et al.*, 2007. Solastalgia: the distress caused by environmental change. *Australasian psychiatry* 15, S95-S98.

Alonso-Ruiz M, *et al.*, 2023. Blue Genes: Synopsis of the workshop organized by ICM-CSIC and BAU to increase engagement and collaboration for Our Ocean and Waters. Digital CSIC, <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/15328>

Arbic B, *et al.*, 2024. Ocean Decade Vision 2030 White Papers—Challenge 9: Skills, Knowledge, Technology, and Participatory Decision-Making for All <https://doi.org/10.25607/k5ptfp54>

Balagué V, *et al.*, 2023. Synopsis of the second virtual meeting of the Blue Genes community: In search of new ways to increase our connection with Nature. Digital CSIC, <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/16057>

Berndt, R., 2023. PREP4BLUE D4.1: Report on INITIAL VERSION of Mission ontology and semantic network and guidance for use. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944474>

Campus Engage, 2022. A Framework for Engaged Research: Society and Higher Education Addressing Grand Societal Challenges Together. https://www.iaa.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Guide-IAA-Engaged-Research-Framework-2022_V7-11.pdf

CENEAM, 2025. Reeducamar Red y Recursos de Educación Marina. Centro Nacional de Educación Ambiental. <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/ceneam/recursos/mini-portales-tematicos/reeducamar.html>.

EC, 2021a. European Commission. *Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030: Implementation Plan*, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_for_publication.pdf.

EC, 2021b. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on European Missions https://cor.europa.eu/en/events/Documents/COTER/ec_communication_eu_missions.pdf

Essència, 2023. 70 years in Barceloneta (#5/2023, Innovation) <https://essenciabarceloneta.cat/en/70-years-in-barceloneta/>

Essència, 2024a. Gorgonias Project (#8/2024, Sustainability) <https://essenciabarceloneta.cat/en/gorgonias-project/>

Essència, 2024b. La Barceloneta, important enclave for the Decade of the Oceans (#8/2024, Sustainability) <https://essenciabarceloneta.cat/en/la-barceloneta-important-enclave-for-the-decade-of-the-oceans/>

Essència, 2024c. La Barceloneta, a strategic point of connections with and through the ocean (#9/2024, Education) <https://essenciabarceloneta.cat/en/la-barceloneta-a-strategic-point-of-connections-with-and-through-the-ocean/>

Essència, 2024d. Reconnecting with the sea in Barceloneta (#10/2024, Sustainability) <https://essenciabarceloneta.cat/en/reconnecting-with-the-sea-in-barceloneta/>

Essència, 2024e. Do you know what ocean culture is? (#11/2024, Sustainability) <https://essenciabarceloneta.cat/en/do-you-know-what-ocean-culture-is/>

- Fuster N, 2025. Report on the Barcelona City Network. Digital CSIC, <http://hdl.handle.net/10261/377020>
- Fuster N, Pelegrí JL, 2025. Short Report on Espai Mediterrani. Digital CSIC, <http://hdl.handle.net/10261/377021>
- Giannoukakou-Leontsini I, Pelegrí JL, Carbajal, M-E, *et al.*, 2024. Synopsis of the First In-Person Meeting of the Blue Genes Community: Strengthening a Local Community of Practice <http://hdl.handle.net/10261/377591>
- Giannoukakou-Leontsini I, Pelegrí JL, Carbajal, M-E, *et al.*, 2024. Synopsis of the Second In-Person Meeting of the Blue Genes Community: The Retreat Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles, Girona, Spain <http://hdl.handle.net/10261/377601>
- Hickman C, Marks E, Pihkala P, Clayton S, Lewandowski RE, Mayall EE, Wray B, Mellor C, van Susteren L, 2021. Climate anxiety in children and young people and their beliefs about government responses to climate change: a global survey, *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 5, e863-e873, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(21\)00278-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00278-3)
- IOLN, 2024a. An All-Island Ocean Literacy Network Strategic Plan 2024 – 2030.
- IOLN, 2024b. IOLN REGIONAL MEMBERS’ MEETING – WEXFORD, Stella Maris Centre.
- Kelly R, Elsler LG, Polejack A, van der Linden S, Tönnesson K, *et al.*, 2022. Empowering young people with climate and ocean science: Five strategies for adults to consider, *One Earth*, 5, 861-874, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2022.07.007>.
- Lamy P, Citores A, Deidun A, Evans L, *et al.*, 2020. *Mission Starfish 2030 – Restore our ocean and waters*, European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/70828>
- Manago C, Ni Cheallachain C, 2024. PREP4BLUE D4.2: Customized Knowledge Management Method for Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12527756>
- McKinley E, Kelly R, Mackay M, Shellock R, Cvitanovic C, van Putten I, 2022. Development and expansion in the marine social sciences: Insights from the global community, *iScience*, 25, 104735, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.104735>.
- McNair DM, Lorr M, Droppleman JF, 1981. Profile of Mood States. San Diego Educational & Industrial Testing Service.
- OC-NET, 2024. The Ocean as a Common Language For Coastal Communities, 2024 Ocean Decade Conference, Barcelona, Spain. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14224486>
- OC-NET, 2025. Ocean Cities Month 2024 Third Edition, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14644182>
- Pelegrí JL, Talone M, Carbajal ME, Salvo VS, 2025a. Ocean Cities Network: Summary of Activities 2021-2023. Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/14671684>
- Pelegrí JL, Bojanić N, Pinto PIS, Whyte D, *et al.*, 2025b. Trust collaborative bottom-up Missions: long-term strategies with and for people and Nature. Research Square, submitted 28 January 2025.

PREP4BLUE, 2025. Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters: A Toolbox of Approaches <https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/>

UNODC, 2024a. Cities with the Ocean – Ocean science for the sustainable development of coastal cities and ports. [https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024 Ocean Decade Conference - Satellite Event Report - 937.pdf](https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024%20Ocean%20Decade%20Conference%20-%20Satellite%20Event%20Report%20-%20937.pdf)

UNODC, 2024b. Empowering science, policy and society through co-design for sustainable ocean development. [https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024 Ocean Decade Conference - Satellite Event Report - 930.pdf](https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024%20Ocean%20Decade%20Conference%20-%20Satellite%20Event%20Report%20-%20930.pdf)

UNODC, 2024c. [https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024 Ocean Decade Conference - Satellite Event Report - P10-CH10.pdf](https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024%20Ocean%20Decade%20Conference%20-%20Satellite%20Event%20Report%20-%20P10-CH10.pdf)

UNODC, 2024d. Diving from local to global ocean literacy: Exploring, sharing and developing successful practices to know, feel and join the living ocean. [https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024 Ocean Decade Conference - Satellite Event Report - P6-CH10.pdf](https://oceandecade-conference.com/report/2024%20Ocean%20Decade%20Conference%20-%20Satellite%20Event%20Report%20-%20P6-CH10.pdf)

Whyte D, Debaveye L, Bjørkan M, Daae Steriro VM, *et al.*, 2024. Planning for citizen participation in the EU mission to restore our ocean and waters by 2030. *Maritime Studies* 23, 44, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40152-024-00385-x>

7 ANNEXES

ANNEX A. AN ALL-ISLAND OCEAN LITERACY NETWORK STRATEGIC PLAN 2024 – 2030.....	80
ANNEX B. OCTOBER 2024 IOLN MEETING	87
ANNEX C. THE BARCELONA CITY NETWORK.....	106
ANNEX D. PROFILE OF MOODS STATE TEST	116
ANNEX E. SHORT REPORT ON THE ESPAI MEDITERRANI NETWORK.....	119
ANNEX F. OCTOBER 2022 BLUE GENES VIRTUAL MEETING.....	126
ANNEX G. JUNE 2023 BLUE GENES VIRTUAL MEETING	131
ANNEX H. DECEMBER 2023 BLUE GENES IN-PERSON MEETING	151
ANNEX I. FEBRUARY 2024 BLUE GENES RETREAT - PROGRAM.....	166
ANNEX J. FEBRUARY 2024 BLUE GENES RETREAT - REPORT	170
ANNEX K. THE OCEAN CITIES NETWORK (OC-NET) PROGRAM	184
ANNEX L. SUMMARY OF OC-NET ACTIVITIES DURING ITS FIRST TWO YEARS	186
ANNEX M. OCEAN CITIES MONTH.....	194
ANNEX N. PREP4BLUE CALL FOR PILOT ACTIONS.....	202
ANNEX O. LIST OF PROPOSALS SUBMITTED TO THE PREP4BLUE CALL FOR PILOT ACTIONS	205
ANNEX P1. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA1: OCEAN LITERACY FOR BLUE CITIZENSHIP TRAINING COURSE	209
ANNEX P2. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA2: THE BLUESCAPE2024 BALTIC HACKATHON.....	225
ANNEX P3. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA3: THE SEA OF SOUNDS.....	250
ANNEX P4. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA4: SEA SYNERGY OYSTER PROJECT.....	267
ANNEX P5. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA5: BLUE GENES GIANT COLLABORATIVE PUZZLE	281
ANNEX P6. SELF-EVALUATION REPORT FOR PA1: SUSTAINABLE COASTAL FUTURES.....	313

Annex A. An All-Island Ocean Literacy Network Strategic Plan 2024 – 2030

An All-Island Ocean Literacy Network

Strategic Plan 2024 - 2030

BOARD OF DIRECTORS (2024-25)

- Noirín Burke (Galway Atlantauaria)
- Heidi McIlvenny (Queens University Belfast)
- David Murphy (ERINN Innovation)
- Micheál Ó'Cinnéide (Retired)
- Dave Wall (National Biodiversity Data Centre)

ADVISORY PANEL MEMBERS (2024-25)

- Pieter-Jan Schön (AFBI)
- Simon Berrow (IWDG/ATU)
- Majbritt Bolton-Warberg (Marine Institute)
- Bob Brown (Retired)
- Kate Burns (Burns Consulting / Islander Kelp)
- Paul Connolly (Retired)
- Val Cummins (Simply Blue)
- Martina Hennessy (DECC)
- Patricia Mc Hugh (University of Galway)
- Emma Mc Kinley (University of Cardiff)
- Mark Mellett (MARA)
- Yvonne Shields (Irish Lights)

THE NETWORK

Since its establishment in 2016, the Irish Ocean Literacy Network (IOLN) has brought together like-minded individuals and organisations who passionately believe in the importance of the seas and oceans to the island of Ireland and its citizens. The aim of the network is to try to improve coordination, collaboration, and capacity building of the island's "Ocean Citizens" community to help achieve a common vision - an Ocean Literate Society across the Island of Ireland.

“An ocean literate citizen understands the importance of the ocean to humankind; can communicate about the ocean in a meaningful way and is able to make informed and responsible decisions regarding the ocean and its resources.”

The network consists of a broad and diverse range of members including NGOs, public bodies, research and academia, education, private enterprises, and individuals from the public residing throughout the island of Ireland. By working together, it is expected that collective action and coordination can help achieve tangible measurable impact on society.

Network members collaborate to advance ocean literacy across the island. They accomplish this mission through sharing knowledge, capacity building, public awareness campaigns, outreach, and advocacy.

OUR VISION

By 2030, the IOLN will have a thriving network of ocean champions and organisations deeply engaged with local communities across the island. These communities are “Ocean Literate” and as such actively participate in ocean conservation efforts and embrace sustainable practices, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility for the marine environment.

OUR MISSION

The mission of the Network is to cultivate and nurture a sustainable community of ocean literate citizens, enabling seamless collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the effective coordination of marine outreach and ocean literacy endeavours throughout the island.

THE EVOLUTION OF OCEAN LITERACY

Ocean literacy was initially defined in 2004 by a group of U.S. scientists and educators to address the scarcity of ocean sciences in formal education. It has since significantly evolved from its original education-focused framework towards a global movement promoting sustainable interactions with the ocean.

This original concept was underpinned by seven principles aimed at fostering an understanding of the ocean's critical role in Earth's ecosystem:

- 1. The Earth has one big ocean with many features**
- 2. The ocean and life in the ocean shape the features of Earth**
- 3. The ocean is a major influence on weather and climate**
- 4. The ocean made the Earth habitable**
- 5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems**
- 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably interconnected**
- 7. The ocean is largely unexplored**

Building on early definitions of ocean literacy, an ocean-literate person was characterised as someone who understood the importance of the ocean to humankind, could communicate about the ocean in a meaningful way and was able to make informed and responsible decisions regarding the ocean and its resources.

Contemporary models of ocean literacy have introduced a more nuanced approach, incorporating awareness, knowledge, attitude, communication, behaviour, emotional connections, access and experience, adaptive capacity, trust and transparency, and activism as dimensions of ocean literacy, acknowledging the complexity of factors influencing pro-environmental behaviour and the necessity of transforming knowledge into meaningful action for ocean sustainability (McKinley et al., 2023). This evolution reflects a shift from a knowledge-deficit model to a more inclusive and action-oriented approach, highlighting the importance of connection to and engagement with the ocean across diverse societal segments.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES

1. Enhance Network Capacity

Build capacity and expertise within the IOLN network to support work with local communities through targeted training, skill development, and knowledge-sharing initiatives.

Indicators of success: Number and quality of training programs; assessment of growth in specific skills or competencies among members through pre- and post-training evaluations; frequency and participation in knowledge-sharing activities.

2. Promote Engagement and Collaboration within IOLN Membership

Cultivate a culture of active participation and collaboration among IOLN members, fostering a dynamic and supportive network that takes collective action.

Indicators of success: Member participation in Network meetings, projects, campaigns; the number of collaborative projects initiated within the Network, and monitoring the generation of innovative ideas and initiatives resulting from collaborative efforts.

3. Facilitate Stakeholder Engagement and Coordination

Foster increased engagement and cooperation between IOLN members and coastal communities, identifying alignment and synergies that lead to collaborations and partnerships to help achieve the IOLN Vision.

Indicators of success: Level of engagement with external stakeholders, number of partnerships or collaborations established, impact of partnership/campaign actions arising.

4. Champion Best Practices in Ocean Literacy and Community Engagement

Act as a beacon for promoting and showcasing exemplary ocean literacy practices across the island, inspiring excellence in ocean education, outreach, and conservation.

Indicators of success: Monitor impact of OL actions. Track awards, recognition or certifications received by Network members for their initiatives; assess the adoption and impact of best practices in improving ocean literacy among target audiences; measure changes in public awareness and engagement in initiatives.

5. Establish a Sustainable Funding Model

Establish a resilient and diversified funding model to ensure the long-term sustainability of a Network secretariat and funding to support activities and initiatives by IOLN and its members.

Indicators of success: Balance of funding income streams, success rate in securing grants; build cash reserves.

INTERNAL TRANSFORMATIONS

Transformations in four areas are needed within the organisation to achieve our strategic outcomes.

1. Governance and Leadership

- Develop a governance structure that supports the execution of strategic objectives, including clear roles and responsibilities.
- Foster a diverse and inclusive governance structure that represents different perspectives and expertise within the Network.

2. Capacity Building and Institutional Learning

- Invest in the professional development and capacity building of Network members to ensure they have the critical mass, skills, and knowledge necessary to achieve strategic goals.
- Allocate resources and time to build the capacity of the Network's leadership and general membership.
- Create a repository of best practices, lessons learned, and research findings that can be shared among Network members.
- Support academic research to generate tangible community benefits and achieve positive real-world impact.

3. Resource Mobilisation

- Seek and secure diverse funding sources to support Network activities and avoid dependency on a single funding stream.
- Establish effective grant management processes to ensure that funds are allocated efficiently and transparently.

4. Stakeholder Engagement

- Develop a comprehensive stakeholder engagement strategy to facilitate partnerships and collaboration with external organisations and government agencies.
- Build advocacy capacity to effectively engage with policymakers and advocate for marine conservation.

Follow us on:

 irishoceanliteracy.ie

 @IOLNetwork | #WeAreIslanders

 irishoceanliteracynetwork@gmail.com

Annex B. October 2024 IOLN Meeting

IOLN REGIONAL MEMBERS' MEETING - WEXFORD

11th October 2024, 10am - 4pm

Stella Maris Centre

(Kilmore Quay, Co. Wexford, Y35 TH9W)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Meeting Overview and Context	3
Meeting agenda	4
Meeting minutes	6
Overview of feedback form results	14
Appendix A	18
Appendix B	19

OVERVIEW AND CONTEXT OF THE WEXFORD IOLN MEETING

The mission of the [Irish Ocean Literacy Network \(IOLN\)](#) is to cultivate and nurture a sustainable community of ocean literate citizens, enabling seamless collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the effective coordination of marine outreach and ocean literacy endeavours throughout the island of Ireland.

The series of IOLN Regional Members' Meetings, started in spring 2023, plays a crucial role for the achievement of this mission. By providing a space for the Network's members to come together with other marine and maritime stakeholders in their area to **discuss local priorities**, the IOLN is securing opportunities to **promote discussion and peer-to-peer learning** otherwise not available.

An IOLN Regional Members' Meeting was organised for 11 October 2024 in The Stella Maris Centre, Kilmore Quay, Co. Wexford. The theme of the meeting focused on **Changes Facing the Southeast**. The meeting focused on marine conservation and Marine Protected Areas, Fisheries, Marine Spatial Planning and Coastal Zone Management, and Offshore Renewable Energy. Some of the key messages arising from this event were:

- The Southeast coastline is highly sensitive to the **impacts of climate change** in terms of coastal erosion from sea level rise and more frequent and intense storms. While **Coastwatch** volunteers are recording how these changes are affecting the environment, **Wexford County Council** is working on developing risk management plans to mitigate the effects of the coastal erosion.
- The Southeast coast of Ireland has been selected for the next phase of **development of Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE)** due to its shallow waters and the availability of supporting infrastructure. The **Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC)** is responsible for the **Designated Maritime Area Plan (DMAP)** process for ORE, while the newly established **Maritime Area Regulatory Authority (MARA)** is responsible for managing the awarding of **Marine Area Consents** and **Maritime Usage Licences**.
- The meeting reflected a considerable sense of uncertainty and unease with **Marine Spatial Planning (MSP)** process and proposed large scale ORE developments and **Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)** in the Southeast. This is particularly felt by fishers, who are concerned about the restrictions which may come with ORE and MPAs, and what further impacts may follow if proposed restrictions on fishing were accepted. A strong need for **more involvement of fishers in the MSP processes** was expressed.
- Without the dedicated MPA legislation still in place, Ireland is still far from reaching our target of protecting 30% of our marine area by 2030. An important step in this direction came from an **ecological sensitivity analysis of the Celtic Sea** that was recently completed to inform future designation of MPAs.
- Joy Rooney highlighted projects aimed at discovering and protecting the local marine environment and heritage taking place at the **Southeast Technological University (SETU)**.

MEETING AGENDA

10.00 Welcome & Networking

10.30 Dave Wall, IOLN – *What is IOLN and what role can we play?*

10.45 Karin Dubsky, Coastwatch – *Conservation issues/priorities in the sunny Southeast*

11.00 Séamus O’Flaherty, Kilmore Quay – *Fishing industry views on MPAs and ORE*

11.15 Q&A

11.30 Tea/Coffee

11.45 Jim Hurley, SWC Promotions – *The need for MPAs?*

12.00 Joy Rooney, South East Technological University – *Marine projects at SETU*

12.15 George Colfer, Wexford County Council – *Coastal Zone Management and Marine Spatial Planning*

12.30 Q&A

12.45 Lunch & Networking

13.45 IOLN Member updates – 3 x 5 mins, *Explore Your Shore! IWDG, Coastwatch*

14.00 Louise Allcock, University of Galway – *The Celtic Sea MPA Sensitivity Assessment*

14.15 Karina Fitzgerald, Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications - *South Coast DMAP for Offshore Renewable Energy*

14.30 Siobhán Egan, Maritime Area Regulatory Authority – *What is the role of the new regulator?*

14.45 Public discussion/Q&A with all speakers

15.45 Wrap-up

Fig. 1. Attendees of the IOLN Regional Members meeting at the Stella Maris Centre.

Fig. 2. The IOLN Director Dave Wall introduces the Network's history and strategy to attendees.

MEETING MINUTES

The third IOLN Regional Members' Meeting of 2024 took place in the Stella Maris Centre, Kilmore Quay, Co. Wexford on October 11th. The event was attended by 41 participants (see Appendix A), including local stakeholders, representatives of state agencies, representatives of the Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, and academics (Fig. 1). The event offered a **welcomed chance to focus the discussion on changes facing the Southeast coast of Ireland**. The Southeast is a great attraction for tourists and is rich in biodiversity, but is also impacted, more than other parts of the island, by plans to establish offshore wind farms and marine protected areas, as well as the negative impacts of climate change. The presentations by invited speakers, as well as the panel discussion in the afternoon, offered a unique chance to provide an overview of perspectives from multiple stakeholders, including fishers, scientists, regulatory bodies, policy makers, and members of the local community.

The IOLN wish to deeply thank the **Biodiversity Officer of the Wexford County Council, Claire Goodwin**, as well as the staff at the Stella Maris Centre for all the support received in the organisation of the event.

The IOLN Regional Members Meeting in Kilmore Quay was opened by IOLN Director **Dave Wall** who set the scene with a [presentation](#) to introduce the Network (Fig. 2). Before describing the history of the IOLN, its current structure, and how it plans to develop an Ocean Literate society across the island of Ireland, Dave shared with the audience a description of what Ocean Literacy is, and how it is playing an increasing role in achieving Challenge 10 of the UN Ocean Decade **"Restore humanity's relationship with the ocean"**, Sustainable Development Goal 14 "Life Under the water", and the objectives of EU Mission Ocean & Waters. He also introduced the four working groups recently established by the IOLN focused on 1) **Education**; 2) **Capacity Building & Training**; 3) **Understanding Regional Action & Activism**; and 4) **Implementing all-Island Ocean Literacy Campaigns**. Finally, Dave presented the new [membership plan](#) that IOLN has recently put in place to support the IOLN Strategic Plan and the networks ongoing development.

The first invited speaker was **Karin Dubsy of Coastwatch Europe** (Fig. 3), who described how data gathered over the years through coastal monitoring by Coastwatch volunteers are indicating signs of the impacts of climate change on the coastal environment, e. g. a decrease in abundance of lugworm casts and dogfish egg cases, thinner shells in intertidal molluscs, and shorter stipes in kelps. Karin suggested that the latter is due to the increased number of coastal storms, which are anticipated to have a greater impact on the Southeast coast. This is in part due to the fact that the land surface of Ireland is still responding to the melting of the ice sheets from the last Ice-Age and is slowly tilting, with the south of Ireland slowly sinking while the north of Ireland is rising. Coastwatch calls upon the Government to intervene on the lack of a rational coastal erosion management plan and highlighted the foreseeable consequences of increasingly frequent storms on houses built in proximity to the coast and potential economic setbacks, including for tourism, which is a flourishing sector for the area.

Fig. 3. Karin Dubsky (Coastwatch) shows a kelp specimen collected on the Wexford shoreline.

Fig. 4. The Kilmore Quay-based trawlerman James O'Flaherty shares his concerns about MSP and MPA impacts on fishing.

James O’Flaherty, Fishing Operator, Kilmore Quay (Fig. 4), expressed some of the concerns shared by the fishing sector. James started by acknowledging the need for wind turbines due to the demand for clean energy, but also pointed out how the plans to install these devices offshore involve many uncertainties for the fishing industry in terms of access to windfarm areas for fishing. Fishers have no clear picture as to what limitations they face due to the proposed establishment of new **Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)**. This leads to resistance as fishers don’t want to see MPAs, if their establishment is not based on clear plans. That does not mean that fishers do not want to preserve the ocean environment, it is quite the opposite; fishers are ready for change, but they need to be involved in the decision-making process, especially in discussions about realistic alternative plans to secure the livelihoods of their community. This uncertainty makes fishers reluctant to say yes to one set of restrictions in case they may be followed by more. Fishers have operated in the Southeast for centuries, and the local economy relies strongly on the industry.

Jim Hurley, former teacher and local naturalist (Fig. 5), works to promote the South Wexford Coast under the brand name [SWC Promotions](#). He resumed the talks with a [presentation](#) which gave an historical overview of the plans to establish an MPA on the southeast coast. As of today, no bill for MPAs has been introduced in Ireland; however, Jim pointed out that in 2011, Ireland transposed the European Union’s 2008 **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)** into domestic legislation, which stated that existing marine Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) and Special Protection Areas (SPAs) are *de-facto* MPAs, eight of which can be found along the South Wexford Coast. Since 2011, several steps have been taken towards the establishment of a new MPA on this coast, a full overview can be found on the document produced by SWC Promotion in Appendix B. Several important developments concerning MSP of the area have taken place in 2024, in particular with the seas off Wexford proposed in January 2024 as a marine SPA, the largest in the country.

Joy Rooney, Researcher and Lecturer in Design, Southeast Technological University (SETU) (Fig. 6), gave an [overview](#) of her University’s marine and coastal research projects: 1) the Sustainable Marine Research Group, focuses on increasing value and sustainability of marine resources, leading to advances in the circular and blue economies; 2) [STREAM](#), a large collection of spatial and temporal marine data from multiple sensor technologies; 3) [EU-CONEXUS](#), aimed at creating a European University for smart urban coastal sustainability; 4) [Portalis](#), a citizen-led transdisciplinary pilot project within the Ireland–Wales Cooperation Programme to promote awareness of and protect the Irish natural and cultural heritage in order to sustainably and responsibly grow visitors numbers to our coastal communities; 5) the Brendan Voyage 50th Anniversary project, a transnational collaboration to explore ocean-based migrations; and 6) the Estuary Development and protection of our cultural and natural landscapes through the promotion of responsible tourism which advocates for estuary ecosystems.

George Colfer, Coastal Engineer, Wexford County Council (Fig. 7), gave the final [presentation](#) which described the county coastal management plans, focusing on some key case studies. 100 km of Wexford coast, out of the total 260, are under risk of erosion. To face this challenge, Wexford County Council has produced a [Coastal Zone Management & Marine Spatial Planning Development Plan](#). Managing the risk is at the core of this plan, which includes recommendations to identify and monitor concerning situations, promote nature-based solutions and secure funding to implement the plan itself. Along the Southeast coast there are several dramatic cases of coastal erosion caused by the increased frequency and intensity of coastal storms, which threaten buildings and infrastructure. Examples of sites currently under monitoring by the Office of Public Works include Rosslare, Cullenstown, Courtown, and Kilpatrick. On the other hand, examples of interventions aimed at restoring the dunes system can also be observed, e.g. at Curracloe, the beach made famous by the Hollywood movie “Saving Private Ryan”.

Fig. 5. Jim Hurley started his talk describing the advantages MPAs determine for biodiversity.

Fig. 6. A moment of the overview of marine projects at SETU given by Joy Rooney.

After the lunch break the meeting resumed by giving the spotlight to the work carried on in the area by three IOLN Members.

Mick Berry, Coastwatch Europe (Fig. 8) gave a quick overview of the organisation's 2024 Autumn Survey which took place between 15th September and 15th October including multiple focuses, such as seagrass mapping, invasive alien species early alert and control, and nitrate levels monitoring in inflows. By building a long-term dataset, this annual survey plays a key role in the development of other citizen science projects, as shown by the inclusion of some of the Coastwatch projects as case studies in the citizen science Horizon Europe project [More4Nature](#).

Dave Wall, Conservation Officer, Irish Whale and Dolphin Group, focused on the IWDG [Ferry Surveys Programme](#) which began in 2001. The Rosslare to Pembroke route is one of three survey routes in the Irish Sea. The survey conducted on this route have highlighted a higher presence of common dolphins compared to the Dublin – Holyhead and Belfast – Cairnryan routes, whereas harbour porpoises have been observed at higher densities on the Dublin and Belfast routes.

Dave Wall wore his other hat of **Citizen Science Officer for the [National Biodiversity Data Centre](#)** to give an update on the [Explore Your Shore!](#) project, which has to date recorded over 20,000 validated open access records of coastal marine species. Important information could be gathered thanks to these records, such as the spread of alien species, changes in species distributions indicating the effects of climate change, and the location of water quality indicator species such as seagrass.

The afternoon talks then focused on the topic of Marine Protected Areas, Marine Spatial Planning and Offshore Renewable Energy.

Prof. Louise Allcock, Lecturer, [University of Galway](#) (Fig. 9) presented an [overview](#) of the report produced by herself and a team of other researchers who conducted an ecological sensitivity analysis of the Celtic Sea to inform future designation of MPAs, commissioned by the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage in November 2023. The objectives of the study were to 1) identify areas of higher and lower sensitivity to human pressures, 2) engage with key stakeholders, 3) inform decision about siting of ORE, and 4) develop methods for identifying future MPAs. The analysis focused on 41 features consisting of habitats and species, not listed under the EU Birds and Habitats Directives, which were considered either of recognised ecological importance, broadly representative of Irish waters, or appearing to be threatened or declining. For each selected feature, the sensitivity to ORE development, shipping, and fishing was assessed, and stakeholder engagement sessions were held, to identify areas of high and low priority for protection and produce recommendations to minimise impacts on current and proposed sectoral activities.

Fig. 7. George Colfer outlining the Wexford's Coastal Zone Management & MSP Development Plan

Fig. 8. Mick Berry gives a short presentation on the projects he carries out with Coastwatch.

Karina Fitzgerald, Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC, Fig. 10) gave a [presentation](#) on the draft [Designated Maritime Area Plan \(DMAP\) for ORE on the South coast](#). DMAPs are designed to create a comprehensive framework for consistent, transparent, sustainable and evidence-based decision-making, and DECC is the competent authority for preparing DMAPs for ORE. The South coast of Ireland was selected for the first DMAP proposal for several reasons, including the significant offshore wind resource, suitable sea depths, availability of on-shore grid capacity to connect the ORE produced, proximity to several important port facilities, and a growing population and industrial base along the coast. Four specific areas within the DMAP were identified for ORE after a constraints analysis focused on social, economic and biodiversity data. The DMAP was subjected to public consultation; over 350 submissions were received and have been considered in order to revise the draft SC-DMAP. The final version is expected to be published by the end of October.

Siobhán Egan, Maritime Area Regulatory Authority (MARA, Fig. 11) gave the [final presentation](#) of the day to give an overview of the roles and responsibilities of this recently established state agency. MARA is tasked with managing activities in the maritime area and implementing the provisions of the new principles of MSP brought about by the National Marine Planning Framework and the Maritime Area Planning Act, both released in 2021. In the marine planning system envisioned by these documents, MARA is responsible for assessing the applications for Maritime Area Consents (MACs) and Maritime Usage Licences (MULs) in areas selected via DMAPs for ORE. Consequently, MARA will also oversee the compliance of MACs and MULs awarded using a risk-based approach, and will apply enforcement powers in case of a breach of planning conditions, or unauthorised development. Finally, Siobhán mentioned the recent development of MARA's [2024-2027 Strategy](#) which sets its mission, vision and values as a leading voice for sustainable management and protection of Ireland's maritime area through effective regulation.

The final part of the meeting was dedicated to a **Q&A session involving all the speakers of the day** (Fig. 12), which highlighted some of the confusion still felt by the stakeholders as regards the MSP and MPA processes. Generally, it was concluded that this uncertainty creates concerns such as what will follow on from an MPA or MSP area designation. These concerns need to be addressed via wider and more effective stakeholder and community consultation. In the case of concerns expressed by fishers about MSP and MPA developments, there appears to be a mutual lack of trust between the fishing professionals and the competent authorities. However, the experience of the ecological sensitivity analysis of the Celtic Sea showed how a dialogue process can bring progress for both ORE and MPA establishment. The panel discussion was wittily summarised by Jim Hurley with the quote by the Italian physicist Enrico Fermi *"Before I came here, I was confused about this subject. Having listened to your lecture, I am still confused -- but on a higher level"*.

On this note, IOLN Director **Micheál Ó Cinnéide** concluded by highlighting how, despite the differences in terms of challenges faced by each local community, the three IOLN Regional Member's Meetings held in 2024 in Tralee, Aughleam and now Kilmore Quay, showed a common need for dialogue and understanding of the perspectives among different stakeholders, and the role the IOLN can play in facilitating engagement and consultation, and building local capacity in ocean literacy and marine issues at a time of major change.

Fig. 9. Prof. Louise Allcock presents the results of the work of the group of scientists she led.

Fig. 10. Karina Fitzgerald from DECC outlines the evolution of the Draft South Coast DMAP for ORE.

OVERVIEW OF FEEDBACK FORM RESULTS

Participants at the Kilmore Quay meeting were asked to feedback using a printed form which was given them at registration as part of a welcome pack including a copy of the IOLN Strategy. 18 participants completed the form after the event, a summary of the results is shown below.

Are you already an IOLN Member?

If you have answered 'No' to the previous question, do you wish to become an IOLN Member?

What would be your three top take-home messages from today?

Definite interest in marine planning from all. Lack of knowledge from some quarter. Need for clarity in planning, i. e. MARA, An Bord Pleanála, etc - especially to general public.

Need for more consultation.

Trust. Multiple stakeholders at an event is a good idea. There is a lot more people interested in ocean literacy in Ireland than 10 years ago.

There is a lack of trust between local and national stakeholders. Large-scale changes are currently underway in relation to Ireland's marine area. There are so many acronyms.

There is a big lack of understanding around the whole area of marine planning, lots of different entities involved, there is a need for a lot more public education in this area.

The need for public consultation and communication between all stakeholders in order to reach reasonable solutions relating to marine planning. Great exercise in raising awareness for local communities. The need for consideration for livelihood of the fishing community when development of DMAPs.

Educate, educate, educate. A vast and varied community with a wonderfully enthusiastic and encouraging nature. A growing community of awareness and actions.

A lot of people are working for common good. A lot of people are misguided.

More communication with all parties who will be affected by marine developments.

More dialogue needed. More data needed. Where is the education plan?

Extremely effective for bringing together various organisations, including government agencies, stakeholders. It should be built upon to the wider public.

More education and simplification is needed for the public and fishing of offshore industry, e. g. subsea cables - not that big! Movement happening with MARA and DECC. Collaboration + transparency is essential going forward with industry, regulation and public.

More clarity on DMAP and consent processes. Still uncertainty about what it means for fishermen. Very relevant research available.

A lot of work has been done to date, aligning the sectoral information to address knowledge gaps in stakeholders' comprehension of the actions that are being proposed and how they will affect each level. The connections are being made, but slowly.

Show what is allowed for the fishing community - it was all what's not allowed.

Address difference between consultation and participation. More good referenced information. Psychologists involved on trust.

Is there anything you would like to see improved for future IOLN meetings?
Involve someone from Dept. of Education. Need to start from the bottom up!
More information on your website
Audio, difficult to hear or see some speakers and their slides.
Kept up to date through local groups i. e. Coastwatch or Wexford Co. Co.
Maybe a few more local area industry representatives if that is relevant to the meeting.
A talk on how to get more people involved in supporting the ocean & marine areas.
No.
Sound & display. Very happy vegan options provided - maybe something more substantial than sandwiches + soy/oat milk. Thank you - better than expected!
Presentations area detailed on screen. Sound issues to hear speakers. Are the presentations available by email?
Short speakers meeting - aim on Zoom beforehand.

As it was for the previous meetings in Kerry and Mayo, attendees showed appreciation for the opportunity given by the IOLN, through the organisation of the event in Kilmore Quay, to have an **educational, multi-stakeholder conversation about the MSP on the Southeast coast**. The main take-home messages shared through the feedback forms were the lack of a clear vision about what the establishment of an MPA or the development of ORE facilities means for the area, especially as regards the fishing community, and the consequent need for reciprocal education on challenges and opportunities involved with the MSP developments from all parts involved.

We acknowledge that, compared to the previous IOLN Regional Members' Meetings, 31% of attendees who were not IOLN members already did not express a clear intention to become members. This may be due to the introduction of a paid membership plan, with better uptake possibly dependent on the IOLN showing an ongoing presence in a local area after the event to gain support.

IOLN members and other attendees who wish to provide further feedback and/or comments about the meeting itself and how the IOLN can support furtherly the continuation of the dialogue started in Kilmore Quay can email the IOLN Secretariat at irishoceanliteracynetwork@gmail.com.

Fig. 11. Siobhán Egan explains the role of MARA, the new state agency established in July 2023.

Fig. 12. Micheál Ó Cinnéide moderating the panel discussion which concluded the event in Wexford.

APPENDIX A

List of attendees

1. Ann Marie Ryan, *Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)*
2. Anne Marie Kirwan, *Tomhaggard Clean Coasts Group*
3. Aodhan Power, *Tomhaggard Clean Coasts Group*
4. Aude Bates
5. Bryn Canniffe, *EPA*
6. Claire Goodwin, *Wexford County Council*
7. Claire Kelly, *Irish Whale and Dolphin Group*
8. Clare Kelly, *Wexford County Council*
9. Conor Breen, *Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC)*
10. Conor Kinsella, *Wexford County Council*
11. Dave Wall, *National Biodiversity Data Centre and Irish Ocean Literacy Network (IOLN)*
12. David Carolan, *DECC*
13. David Murphy, *ERINN Innovation and IOLN*
14. Frank Burke, *Wexford County Council*
15. George Colfer, *Wexford County Council*
16. Gregory Roche, *Local Authority Waters Programme*
17. Hugh O'Sullivan, *SSE Renewables*
18. Karin Dubsy, *Coastwatch*
19. Karina Fitzgerald, *DECC*
20. James Roche
21. Jeanne Gallagher, *Bord Iascaigh Mhara*
22. Jim Hurley, *SWC Promotions*
23. Jim Moore
24. Joy Rooney, *South East Technological University*
25. Juliet Fitzpatrick, *DECC*
26. Louise Allcock, *University of Galway*
27. Mairead Sullivan, *Marine Institute*
28. Manus Flynn, *Coastwatch*
29. Maria Vittoria Marra, *Galway Atlantaquaria and IOLN*
30. Melanie Mageean, *Maritime Area Regulatory Authority (MARA)*
31. Micheál Ó Cinnéide, *IOLN*
32. Mick Berry, *Coastwatch*
33. Patsi Bates
34. Sam Nunn
35. Sandra Martin, *Wexford County Council*
36. Séamus O'Flaherty
37. Sharon Sheehan, *Trinity College Dublin (TCD)*
38. Siobhán Egan, *MARA*
39. Siobhán McLoughlin, *TCD*
40. Thérèse Maddock, *Seashore Explore*
41. Tracey O'Connor, *DECC*

Annex C. The Barcelona City Network

Report on the BARCELONETA CITY NETWORK

Noemí Fuster, Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC

Introduction

The Institute of Marine Sciences, and its predecessor the Institute of Fisheries Research, is located in the Barceloneta district of Barcelona.

This neighbourhood has a mosaic of different social, economic and cultural actors that make it a unique ecosystem in Barcelona and an ideal location to act as a laboratory of innovation and connections.

The inhabitants of this neighbourhood have a strong sense of rootedness that mixes with the multiculturalism of migrants and tourists. The great contrast between the visions of both sides and the need to create a common dialogue is one of the great challenges of this area.

Setting up a network in Barceloneta allows us to take advantage of the great social cohesion that exists and, at the same time, to establish new links with actors that at first sight may seem antagonistic, such as multi-generational residents and tourists, the local economy and business incubators, associations of elderly people and nightlife companies... Sometimes the only link is the territory and therefore the sea, thanks to the four beaches that the district has.

Objectives

Our main objective as an Ocean Mission CSA is to Restore the Ocean by 2030, divided into 3 minor objectives:

- To protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.
- Prevent and eliminate pollution of our oceans, seas and waters.
- Make the sustainable blue economy carbon neutral and circular.

After an extensive and continuous series of interviews with all the stakeholders, the needs of each of them were identified and their objectives were defined in accordance with the Barceloneta network.

Our minor objectives were compared with the objectives or needs of the different agents in the area in order to identify common points. Once these were identified, an activity or action was proposed that would bring both objectives together. An example is shown in the following table.

	PREP4BLUE OBJECTIVES			
OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTORS IN THE BARCELONETA NETWORK	Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity	Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters	Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular	Connecting people to the ocean to foster citizen engagement
Creation of a citizens' network for coastal stewardship	Espai Mediterrani	Espai Mediterrani		Espai Mediterrani
Bringing students closer to companies or research institutions through projects that solve environmental problems.	Metropoli FPLab			
Reduce litter on the beach.		Sant Joan Sustainable		Sant Joan Sustainable
Raise employee awareness of biodiversity and the pollution that affects it.	World Environment Day	World Environment Day	World Environment Day	World Environment Day
Learn about air quality analysis techniques.			Schools visits to cruise ships	
To improve the health of hospitalised people through contact with the ocean.				A healthy relationship with the ocean

Figure 1: Comparison of the objectives of the Ocean Mission with the needs of the organisations that make up the Barceloneta network.

Methodology

The methodology used was as follows:

- Mapping of all agents in the area, through online searches and public databases. Comparison of the data obtained with the agents with knowledge of the area, and modification by including some new data or eliminating entities that were no longer active.
- Mailing to all the agents with an explanatory document about the Ocean Mission and the intention to create the Barceloneta network.
- Interviews with each of the selected agents, starting with a small nucleus of known agents and gradually widening the radius as the nucleus was consolidated. The agenda of the meetings was as follows
 - Presentation of the Ocean Mission and its objectives.
 - Presentation of the Barceloneta network.
 - Presentation of the organisation and identification of its objectives and needs.
 - Asking for suggestions of other actors that should be included in the network.
 - Set a date for the next meeting.

Figure 2: Grouping of the different actors according to their nature.

- Work after the interview. After the first interview, a study was made of each case, looking for commonalities with the Ocean Mission and cataloguing the agent by category (sport, administration, civil associations, academy, blue economy and health).

With these categorisations we ensured that the different areas were covered in order to be able to offer citizens different approaches to the ocean in order to achieve their connection and therefore the citizen engagement that we wanted to promote.

- Second contact with the entities to propose specific activities in line with the objectives of the entity and the Ocean Mission (Fig. 1). The design of the activity was worked out together and then the necessary economic and human resources were sought (always within the network). Finally, permissions were sought and dissemination to the public was carried out. The channels used for dissemination were those of the Institute of Marine Sciences and the network's agents, as well as interviews on national radio stations and in newspapers.
- Carrying out the activity, with the collection of indicators, photographs and the Profile Of Mood States (POMS) test, before and after the programme.
- Processing the data obtained from the POMS test and writing an evaluation report.
- Evaluation meeting with the agents involved in the activity and sharing of the results obtained.
- Visibility of the Barceloneta Network and its activities, as well as the transfer of knowledge acquired in the different activities, through the local magazine *Essencia Barceloneta* (distributed on paper and online in Catalan, Spanish and English).
- At the same time, it responded to other needs of the institutions in the network, such as participating in fairs or conferences, and providing content in the form of workshops, lectures or games. The Institute of Marine Science was clear that it did not want to take a leading role, but rather to be an agent of the network, and therefore it had some duties in this respect.
- In addition, specific agents were selected to propose international networks, thus opening up the Barceloneta network to the whole world. In this way, we are now working with Chile and Gambia and have established contacts with Iceland.

Methodology of the POMS test

The Profile Of Mood States test was used to measure changes in emotions during participation in the activities. This test is a questionnaire that identifies 34 different emotions grouped into 5 categories: Vigour, Commitment, Anxiety, Depression, Anger and Fatigue. Although all emotions have their function, in this document we will consider Vigour and Commitment as positive and Anxiety, Depression and Anger as negative. Before and after the activity, you need to mark the emotions you feel at that moment. Each category of emotion has its own scale, so some numerical adjustments have to be made before presenting the results. This questionnaire is anonymous and should be adapted if you want to do it with children.

Report on the Barcelona City Network

Feeling	Not at all	A little	Moderately	Quite a lot	Extremely
Tense	0	1	2	3	4
Angry	0	1	2	3	4
Worn-out	0	1	2	3	4
Unhappy	0	1	2	3	4
Lively	0	1	2	3	4
Aware	0	1	2	3	4
Sad	0	1	2	3	4
Active	0	1	2	3	4
Fear of the future	0	1	2	3	4
Grumpy	0	1	2	3	4
Energetic	0	1	2	3	4
Lacking of hope	0	1	2	3	4
Uneasy	0	1	2	3	4
Restless	0	1	2	3	4
Confident	0	1	2	3	4
Fatigued	0	1	2	3	4
Annoyed	0	1	2	3	4
Discouraged	0	1	2	3	4
Resentful	0	1	2	3	4
Nervous	0	1	2	3	4
Miserable	0	1	2	3	4
Bitter	0	1	2	3	4
Exhausted	0	1	2	3	4
Anxious	0	1	2	3	4
Helpless	0	1	2	3	4
Weary	0	1	2	3	4
Energized	0	1	2	3	4
Responsible	0	1	2	3	4
Furious	0	1	2	3	4
Worthless	0	1	2	3	4
Positive	0	1	2	3	4
Vigorous	0	1	2	3	4
Committed	0	1	2	3	4
Drained	0	1	2	3	4

Image 1: Adaptation of the POMS Test for the Ocean Mission.

Results

The actions carried out have allowed us to strengthen the network and continue to expand it, materialising it in different proposals such as the World Environment Day, Sant Joan Sustainable, the collaboration in the Metropoli FPLab programme or Espai Mediterrani. And we hope that before the end of PREP4BLUE we will be able to see the Schools visits to cruise ships or the Healthy relationship with the ocean.

Report on the Barcelona City Network

Figure 3: Relationships established between different actors in the network that have led to concrete actions in pursuit of the objectives of the Ocean Mission.

Report on the Barcelona City Network

With regard to the results obtained in the POMS test, we can see that they vary depending on the type of activity, but they all coincide in increasing the emotions of the Vigour and Commitment categories, showing that the activities carried out have represented a positive experience for citizens.

Some examples:

- World Environment Day: 40 workers from the Port of Barcelona carry out a day of connection with the sea where a mindfulness session is carried out by a group of students from the BAU design school, and a snorkel by a small company in the territory, and add their observations to citizen science programmes. With this activity, in addition to pursuing the three mission objectives (Protect and restore marine and biodiversity, Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean and Make sustainable blue economy) it also aligns with the following Outcomes:
 - ✓ European citizens can engage in preserving and restoring oceans and waters through participation, volunteering, and citizen science.
 - ✓ Citizens are empowered to act through social innovation, education, and awareness efforts.
 - ✓ Regular citizen science campaigns enhance scientific impact and raise environmental awareness

Figure 4: Results of the POMS test for the World Environment Day activity.

In the graph we can see how the categories of positive emotions such as vigour and commitment are represented in warm colours (yellow and orange respectively) and we can see an increase in these colours in the graph representing emotions after the activity.

Report on the Barcelona City Network

The activities can also be studied separately, in this case a snorkel or an ice bath.

Figure 5: POMS test results for snorkelling and ice bathing respectively.

Analysis of the results

The creation of a local network makes it possible to speed up the achievement of objectives such as those of the Ocean Mission. By involving the different parties according to their capacities and concerns, and always putting the citizen at the centre as the driving force for change, it is possible to reach citizens with innovative proposals that connect them to the ocean and provide them with enjoyable experiences that encourage them to return. By making this connection, it will be easier to get the citizen engagement we are looking for, while at the same time letting citizens know that they have the opportunity to participate in the conservation and restoration of oceans and waters through participatory media, volunteering or citizen science.

When we talk about the great challenge of restoring the oceans by 2030, we inevitably refer to different cultures, each with its own perception of the oceans. Setting the target date of 2030 adds a sense of urgency that pushes us to find the fastest way to get there. The POMS test gives us clues as to which actions will be most effective in achieving this connection, always remembering that 'one size doesn't fit all' and that different groups may have different emotional responses to the same activity. Our previous experience of the ocean will determine how we should approach it to achieve this connection to physical and mental wellbeing. Testing the test with different groups will give us many clues as to what that approach should be and what activities we should propose to ensure success.

This leads us to connect our network with other international networks, as the problems we face challenge the whole of humanity and other perspectives can make us think outside the box and lead us to new solutions that bring us closer to our goals.

Regarding the three objectives, we have seen how each of the categories we have created for the different entities (Sport, Administration, Civil Associations, Academy, Blue Economy and Health) can pursue these objectives, and even combining different categories on the same day can make it even more entertaining.

It can also be easily aligned with the following outcomes set out in the Implementation Plan:

- ✓ All European citizens have the opportunity to engage in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through participative means, volunteering and citizen science.
- ✓ All European citizens are empowered to be actors in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through social innovation, awareness raising, education and training.

In short, we should not be frightened by the heterogeneity of a network of local actors; on the contrary, their different perspectives on the ocean help us to understand how we should approach this challenge on a planetary scale. The key is to listen to all stakeholders and, as in the world of science, to experiment. And above all, to share the results so that we can continue to learn on the shoulders of giants.

Annex D. Profile Of Moods State Test

MISSION OCEAN

Activity: _____

Date: _____

Feeling	Not at all	A little	Moderately	Quite a lot	Extremely
Tense	0	1	2	3	4
Angry	0	1	2	3	4
Worn-out	0	1	2	3	4
Unhappy	0	1	2	3	4
Lively	0	1	2	3	4
Aware	0	1	2	3	4
Sad	0	1	2	3	4
Active	0	1	2	3	4
Fear of the future	0	1	2	3	4
Grumpy	0	1	2	3	4
Energetic	0	1	2	3	4
Lacking of hope	0	1	2	3	4
Uneasy	0	1	2	3	4
Restless	0	1	2	3	4
Confident	0	1	2	3	4
Fatigued	0	1	2	3	4
Annoyed	0	1	2	3	4
Discouraged	0	1	2	3	4
Resentful	0	1	2	3	4
Nervous	0	1	2	3	4
Miserable	0	1	2	3	4
Bitter	0	1	2	3	4
Exhausted	0	1	2	3	4
Anxious	0	1	2	3	4
Helpless	0	1	2	3	4
Weary	0	1	2	3	4
Energized	0	1	2	3	4
Responsible	0	1	2	3	4
Furious	0	1	2	3	4
Worthless	0	1	2	3	4
Positive	0	1	2	3	4
Vigorous	0	1	2	3	4
Committed	0	1	2	3	4
Drained	0	1	2	3	4

MISSION OCEAN

Post Activity Questionnaire

Feeling	Not at all	A little	Moderately	Quite a lot	Extremely
Tense	0	1	2	3	4
Angry	0	1	2	3	4
Worn-out	0	1	2	3	4
Unhappy	0	1	2	3	4
Lively	0	1	2	3	4
Aware	0	1	2	3	4
Sad	0	1	2	3	4
Active	0	1	2	3	4
Fear of the future	0	1	2	3	4
Grumpy	0	1	2	3	4
Energetic	0	1	2	3	4
Lacking of hope	0	1	2	3	4
Uneasy	0	1	2	3	4
Restless	0	1	2	3	4
Confident	0	1	2	3	4
Fatigued	0	1	2	3	4
Annoyed	0	1	2	3	4
Discouraged	0	1	2	3	4
Resentful	0	1	2	3	4
Nervous	0	1	2	3	4
Miserable	0	1	2	3	4
Bitter	0	1	2	3	4
Exhausted	0	1	2	3	4
Anxious	0	1	2	3	4
Helpless	0	1	2	3	4
Weary	0	1	2	3	4
Energized	0	1	2	3	4
Responsible	0	1	2	3	4
Furious	0	1	2	3	4
Worthless	0	1	2	3	4
Positive	0	1	2	3	4
Vigorous	0	1	2	3	4
Committed	0	1	2	3	4
Drained	0	1	2	3	4

Annex E. Short Report on the Espai Mediterrani Network

SHORT REPORT ON THE ESPAI MEDITERRANI NETWORK

Noemí Fuster, Josep L. Pelegrí

Introduction

Espai Mediterrani (<https://espaimediterrani.org/>) was created in 2019, following a meeting at the Institut de Ciències del Mar among Catalan entities connected with the sustainability of the coastal Ocean. Espai Mediterrani is a meeting point for organisations, associations and initiatives that aim to create synergies and coordinate strategies towards the conservation and regeneration of the coasts and Ocean.

Eight organisations currently make up Espai Mediterrani: Federació Catalana d'Activitats Subaquàtiques, Proa A La Mar Community Plan, Associació Cap a Mar, Associació Mar de Ciència, Catsharks, Centre d'Immersió, Anèl·Lides and the Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM). Since 2022, the coordination of Espai Mediterrani is carried out by the CM in the frame of the PREP4BLUE project (www.Prep4Blue.eu), funded by the European Union (GA No. 101056957). Figure 1 shows the areas and type of activities carried out by these organisations. However, Espai Mediterrani is a living network and new members are planned, such as the Ciutat Vella Sports Association, which works with young people at risk of exclusion and in water sports.

Name	Area	Example
CATALAN FEDERATION OF SUBAQUATIC ACTIVITIES (FECDas)	ENVIRONMENT	Underwater dives in the Gorgonia Project, biodiversity census,...
PROA A LA MAR Community plan for the Barceloneta neighbourhood	SOCIAL	Link with neighbourhood collectives, transferring knowledge to the rest of the coastal neighbourhoods.
CAP A MAR ASSOCIATION	FISHERIES	Bringing the public and scientific staff together to enjoy fresh fish, campaign to reduce the use of wipes and visit the quayside to highlight the problems caused to the fishing nets.
MAR DE CIÈNCIA ASSOCIATION	SCIENCE	It coordinates communication and dissemination activities, as well as activities proposed for schools, vocational training centres and universities, and artists' collectives.
CATSHARKS	ENVIRONMENT	Recovery and release of elasmobranchs caught accidentally in fishing nets.
BIOLOGY DIVING CLUB	ENVIRONMENT	Underwater dives in biodiversity census,...
ANEL·LIDES	ENVIRONMENT	Data collection, dives to learn about biodiversity and recovery of the seahorse population.
MARINE SCIENCE INSTITUTE	SCIENCE	Responsible for overall coordination and scientific advice, also in charge of the Gorgonies regeneration.

Figure 1. Areas and type of activities carried out by the organisations in the Espai Mediterrani Network.

Objectives

The objectives pursued by the grouping can be grouped into three areas:

1) Territory and maritime culture

The communities along the Catalan coast share, as a uniting characteristic, a collective identity rooted in maritime culture. These regions have a long-standing connection to the sea, which they have harnessed for their socio-economic development. For generations, many residents have forged strong ties—be they through work, social interactions, or emotional connections—linked to this vital natural resource.

In the city of Barcelona, a city that historically had turned its back on the sea, a new narrative is emerging. This narrative leads to a growing recognition of the necessity to rekindle the relationship between the city and the Ocean, to honour both the tangible and intangible maritime heritage, and to foster a deeper appreciation for the sea itself.

According to the vision of Espai Mediterrani, some of the challenges facing maritime areas are the following:

- To turn the sea as an element of sustainable local socio-economic development, with and for the territory, generating dignified and quality employment, making it possible to meet the demands and needs of the sector and the community, within the parameters of the social economy, becoming a real alternative to the current economic model (blue economy versus blue overexploitation).
- To recover and strengthen the collective, professional and maritime memory by creating a space for collective construction with all the actors involved.
- To promote the linkage with the sea and maritime culture since childhood and adolescence, with the idea that any experience incorporated from an early age will eventually take root and become part of the essence of the person, creating identity and a sense of belonging.
- To create this collective history with all the territories of the sea, claiming this historical link.
- To reflect and debate the relationship between port and city.
- To live the sea as a common good and as a socially transforming natural environment.

2) Sustainability and social equity

For several years, Spain has held a leading position within the European Union regarding overfishing quotas. Alarmingly, it is reported that 90% of commercial fish species in the Mediterranean Sea are currently overfished. Furthermore, Spain frequently disregards scientific recommendations by approving fishing quotas that significantly exceed the sustainable limits for these fish stocks. This practice is viewed by Espai Mediterrani as a significant barrier to achieving environmental sustainability.

To foster environmental sustainability, the aggrupation emphasizes the urgent need to analyze the yield and depletion of marine resources, regulate pollution levels, and take a definitive stance against overexploitation. This approach entails ensuring the regeneration of marine resources, reducing

waste in a sustainable manner, and acknowledging the excessive consumption of raw materials and consumer goods.

Central to this discussion is the concept of a circular economy, which posits that products must be assigned their true value. Given that materials and resources are finite, there is a pressing need to develop methods for their recovery and recycling, so as to facilitate their repeated use. Additionally, it is crucial to recognize that sustainable consumption cannot exceed the natural production capacity of ecosystems.

Espai Mediterrani also highlights the importance of social justice in this context. The organization advocates for the promotion of equality among communities surrounding the Mediterranean, emphasizing the integration and support of the most vulnerable populations. Their vision aims at cultivating a fairer and more equitable society for all.

3) The health of the marine environment

The coastline of Barcelona is notably characterized by its close proximity to the urban environment. The city's recent initiatives to open up to the sea and create public spaces have significantly increased activity along the shore. While tourist influx peaks during the summer months, the impact of local residents and their activities on the coastline is felt throughout the year.

The anthropogenic activities in the area have a direct effect on the health of the marine environment. Litter, including plastics, towels, and cigarette butts, frequently contaminates the sea. Although water quality during the bathing season is generally excellent, heavy rainfall events can lead to stormwater overflow, which may mix with sewage and affect the beaches. Reports from the Barcelona Health Department indicate that over half of the seawater samples collected from the city's beaches have been classified as insufficient due to these heavy rainfall incidents during the bathing season. Nonetheless, the overall water quality remains very good for the majority of the year.

Another challenge faced by the city's beaches is the regular loss of sand due to storms, which is often replenished with sand dredged from other locations. This practice can have detrimental effects on marine life. While sampling of marine organisms is conducted by local authorities, access limitations to breakwaters and artificial reefs hinder a comprehensive understanding of their biodiversity.

In light of these issues, it is crucial to conduct more detailed scientific studies on the organisms inhabiting the Barcelona coastline, in addition to the analyses performed by official agencies. Espai Mediterrani proposes a systematic sampling initiative aimed at establishing a baseline of the marine organisms present along the coastline. Regular sampling will be essential for monitoring species that serve as indicators of water quality.

Additionally, the organization advocates for the implementation of regular seabed clean-up activities, with a specific focus on removing plastics and wipes. Such initiatives aim to raise public awareness and encourage responsible behaviour among beachgoers and users of breakwaters. The preservation of Barcelona's coastal environment is vital for both ecological health and public enjoyment. By enhancing monitoring efforts and promoting community engagement in clean-up initiatives, Espai

Mediterrani proposes that we can work towards a healthier marine ecosystem and sustainable coastal management.

Methodology

The internal coordination of the group was carried out through working groups, face-to-face and online meetings, which facilitated the updating and monitoring of the different actions carried out in the projects.

At the same time, we collaborated with external actors in a cross-cutting way, involving educational and artistic actors, the administration, the port authority, the fishermen's guild and tourists.

Throughout the work, a gender perspective was applied, based on the Institute of Marine Sciences' Gender Equality Working Group and its Gender Equality Plan. Sustainability criteria have also been applied within the group, such as the avoidance of transport (proximity project), local suppliers, the use of sustainable or reused materials, the use of public resources (premises, material loan service...) and the separation of waste into fractions through the use of specific containers during activities.

As a legacy of its last project, Espai Mediterrani has produced a document with some recommendations on how to address issues of citizen participation related to land management and coastal protection in urban areas.

Results

Networking over the years has resulted in three projects subsidised by Barcelona City Council. These projects are (<https://espaimediterrani.org/projectes/>):

- Espai Mediterrani, funded by the city of Barcelona through its 2020 Pla CLima (Climate Plan). The project aims to create a space for collective reflection to transform the public vision and use of the Barcelona coastline and achieve an informed, proactive, empowered and fundamentally critical citizenry. The transformation of the public space of the coastline must respond to the needs of the citizens and, at the same time, strengthen collaborative networks between the groups in the area. Likewise, the project aims to claim the sea as part of the city and an element of identity for the people of Barcelona, and the actors in maritime neighbourhoods such as Barceloneta feel that they are the agents transmitting their natural and cultural wealth.
- Gorgònia Barcelona, developed in the frame of the EU project 'RESponsible research and innovation grounding practices in BIOSciences – RESBIOS' (ResBios). This project explored the seabeds of the Barcelona coastal waters, specifically into those dominated by the *Leptogorgia sarmentosa* gorgonians, in order to better understand them and carry out active restoration action. The message spread with this project is that the sea needs individual and collective action from all citizens. The most obvious way to contribute to the conservation of the sea is to change behaviour habits that lead to reducing rubbish, pollutants and the impact on marine

life on a daily basis. However, the current situation of degradation of the marine environment requires going a step further and we need to help the recovery of the marine environment. One of the ways to do this is by carrying out actions to restore natural habitats.

- RES-MED, funded by the city of Barcelona through its 2023 Climate Plan (Pla Clima 2023). The project aims at the empowerment and articulation of a network of people to mitigate and adapt to the effects of climate change by caring for the coast with the recovery of the environment and the regeneration of different marine species in the Barcelona coast. The activities revolve around the recovery of natural spaces on the coast, by raising awareness among the selected groups, removing waste and reintroducing some species into the sea. There is also a push for the transfer of knowledge about the protection of the sea, driven from the Barceloneta neighbourhood to the rest of the coastal districts and the city.

In the frame of these projects, as well as because of its own vision, the associations forming Espai Mediterrani regularly carry out conferences and other outreach, communication and capacity building activities.

Espai Mediterrani has also taken advantage of major events such as the America Cup, which was held in Barcelona in summer 2024, to address some of the problems the local community is facing from a territorial and community perspective: the local fisheries, the marine sustainability of the Barcelona coastline in the face of the climate emergency, and the intangible heritage of the Barceloneta district in relation to the sea.

Learnings

Networking has become a key strategy to address complex challenges in a wide range of areas, including societal, environmental, scientific and fishery aspects. Working with organisations of different sizes and sectors can bring many benefits, but also challenges.

Benefits of networking

- Diversity of resources and expertise. Working with larger organisations can provide access to funding, infrastructure and technical expertise. On the other hand, smaller organisations often have a more innovative and flexible approach that can enrich the creative process, and their proposals may be more locally rooted.
- Broader reach. Large organisations tend to have greater visibility and established networks, which can help to increase the impact of initiatives. Smaller organisations, being closer to communities, can facilitate local participation and awareness raising.
- Interdisciplinarity. Working with organisations from different sectors allows problems to be tackled from different perspectives. For example, collaboration between scientists and fisheries organisations can lead to more sustainable practices that benefit both the environment and local communities, or collaboration between social and environmental organisations can lead to shared responsibility for environmental management.

Cons of Networking

- Inequalities in time. Small entities, often overwhelmed by lack of human resources, may take longer to make decisions and respond to requests.
- Risk of dilution of objectives: When working with multiple entities, there is a risk that the original objectives may be diluted or modified to meet the needs of all partners involved, leading to the need of an increased coordination effort.

As a conclusion, networking with entities of different sizes and backgrounds presents both opportunities and challenges. The key to successful collaboration lies in establishing clear communication, defining roles and responsibilities from the outset, and ensuring that all voices are heard by giving the necessary time to each entity. By addressing these issues, it is possible to maximise the benefits of collaboration and minimise its drawbacks, thus contributing to a more significant impact in the social, environmental, scientific and fisheries areas.

Annex F. October 2022 Blue Genes Virtual Meeting

Synopsis of the workshop organized by ICM-CSIC and BAU to increase engagement and collaboration for Our Ocean and Waters

October 27, 2022

Context

How and why we are creating a network

On October 27th, 2022, the Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC), a marine research institution located in Barcelona, and the College of Arts & Design of Barcelona (BAU), a higher-education centre specialized in arts and design, co-organized the first Blue Genes meeting.

This meeting took place virtually in a 3-hour workshop format. Its main goal was to explore in a co-creative way how to reinforce and empower the engagement of people, particularly teenagers and young adults, with our Ocean and Waters and increase networking and collaboration.

This initiative grows from the belief that the necessary societal changes have to be bottom-up, through a true collaborative revolution with and for people and nature. Coupled with the deep

perception that this can only be possible through raised awareness based on scientific knowledge and sensorial perception of nature, with the ocean as a central and essential participant.

Based on the above premises and being aware of the international responsibilities – such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals, the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, and the EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030 – this first exploratory workshop was meant to be one first bottom-up step to share ideas about how to increase the people's connection with the ocean. If you need more information contact: Ichaparro@icm.csic.es

The Ocean Mission

The European Commission has recognised the urgency to protect marine and freshwater ecosystems. In order to broad mobilisation initiatives in this matter, the Commission has launched in early 2022 the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

This Mission aims to restore the health of our ocean and waters by three specific objectives:

- Protect and restore ecosystems and biodiversity
- Prevent and eliminate pollution
- Make the blue economy carbon-neutral and circular

And two enablers to support the objectives:

- Digital ocean and waters knowledge system
- Public mobilisation and engagement

Ana Otero (BAU); Angélica Busquets (ICM-CSIC); Anja Wegner (University of Hamburg - researcher); Begoña Vendrell (Ocean Literacy); Caecilia Manago (ERINN Innovation); Camila René (BAU); Carine Simon (ICM-CSIC); Carlos de Juan (ICM-CSIC Young Researchers); Celia Murcia (Blue jobs platform); Clémence Baudu-Descamps (Surfrider Foundation); Cristina Noguera (BAU); David Whyte (MaREI); Diana Lorena Rico-Velez (Youmares); Diana Zúñiga (North Wind Sailing for Science); Edoardo Brodasca (Posidonia Green Festival); Emily Tewes (Sustainable Ocean Alliance); Ester M. López García (ICM Youth); Eugénia Barroca (Marine Biologist from SOA); Inés Mas de la Peña (ICM-CSIC); Jaron Rowan (BAU); Josep Lluís Pelegrí (ICM-CSIC); Justine Brossard (CPMR); Laia Romero (Lobelia Earth); Lucie Greyl (A Sud - Italy); Lydia Chaparro (ICM-CSIC); Magda Vila (ICM-CSIC); María Auxiliadora Cabrera Campano (Marinera de puente); María de la Fuente (ULB - Brussels); María Elena Carbajal (Journalist & sociologist); Maria Lain (Activist, member of Christian Youth for Climate); Marina Martínez (BAU); Neus Figueras Balaña (ICM-CSIC); Nil Rodes (Eurocean's Youth); Noemí Fuster (ICM-CSIC); Núria Ferré (individual); Oriol Carrasco Serra (ICM-CSIC Young Researchers); Shalenys Bedoya (CIDE-CSIC); Silja Teege (Sea Teach/Blue Generation Project); Tània López Pérez (Graduate student UB).

The Workshop

MAJOR CHALLENGES *

Protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, fighting against pollution, or eliminating greenhouse emissions are huge challenges that need to be urgently addressed.

WHY IS NOT HAPPENING? *

Regarding science, one of the major challenges is that scientific information is not always well communicated or understood by citizens.

ENABLING THE CHALLENGE *

Societal engagement in ocean conservation has been generally very low. But there is plenty of room for changing the course and increase public engagement in ocean conservation, particularly through the joining of scientific and artistic knowledge.

WHAT DO WE WANT *

We have the aim to bring Science & Arts closer to society, in order to change the perception and relation of people with our rivers and seas, and to bring broad public mobilization and engagement.

FUTURE PLAN *

Create a European network that could act as a "Community of Practice" (CoP).

ACTIONS AND GOALS *

During the workshop many topics arose such as advocacy, blue economy, ocean literacy, new imaginaries...

However, considering that the uniqueness of this network is to bring deep awareness through the expanded cognition of arts and sciences – with the active support of an art & design centre (BAU) with a marine research centre (ICM-CSIC) – the selected actions are mostly related to this unique union.

Some of the selected actions are to embrace collaborative activities and increase networking; to share knowledge and methods to engage and mobilize through sensorial experiences; or to flourish different forms of knowledge.

With respect to major goals, the selection has been chosen based on the group discussions, followed by a final choice according to our own limitations and expertise.

Main Goals

*1 FIND NEW COLLECTIVE RITUALS TO CONNECT WITH THE OCEAN

Example of a possible action: The CoP will generate knowledge, support projects and initiatives, and share results on sensorial practices of knowledge to increase the people's connection with the Ocean.

*2 APPLY INNOVATIVE WAYS TO SHARE KNOWLEDGE AND RAISE AWARENESS

Example of a possible action: The CoP will become a space to share innovative ideas, projects or initiatives that make a difference, and at the same time a platform that helps to bring science and marine conservation to a broader public.

*3 SHARE PRACTICAL SKILLS, TOOLS AND STRATEGIES

Example of a possible action: The CoP will be a source of methodologies, tools and strategies, and will identify innovative case studies and successful initiatives. Design, for example, can be used as a discipline that questions ways of learning and increases the scope of ways of knowing.

*4 FIND NEW WAYS TO LEARN TOGETHER IN A STRONG INTERDISCIPLINARY NETWORK OF SCIENCE AND ARTS

Example of a possible action: The CoP will become a community of people working in different disciplines (from design to marine sciences) who wishes to collaborate and share its learnings and passion for nature.

Insights of the Workshop

'What are the main goals of your entity or initiative?'

- Transfer scientific knowledge on the Ocean and Waters to the society
- Raise awareness of the Ocean and Waters issues
- Create networks
- Promote citizen action & engagement
- Education & social transformation
- Blue research
- Advocacy and local support

'What are the main challenges and worries that prevent you from meeting your goals?'

- Lack of time and long-term engagement
- Lack of funding and resources
- Lack of visibility and communication of scientific outputs
- Lack of transversal collaboration
- Lack of citizen engagement
- Lack of connection with nature and the ocean
- Huge challenges versus slow change

'What would you like to learn and share from other similar projects or initiatives?'

- Share knowledge and intelligence between organizations
- How to reach out to a wider audience
- Collaborate and create successful connections
- Join efforts to do successful advocacy campaigns
- Share ideas and innovative experiences

'What do you think ICM-CSIC and BAU can contribute to your project?'

- Transdisciplinary and collaborative work
- New ways to communicate to reach a wider audience
- Assistance and support (ideas, workshops, guidance, etc)
- Visibility and networking opportunities

'Ways in which, on a personal level, you are linked to the Ocean & Waters:'

- Rituals: relaxing, meditation, observing and smelling the sea, enjoying the biodiversity...
- Conservation: the need to preserve biodiversity and natural resources, raising

consciousness on the value of the ocean, sense of responsibility and love for nature.

- Arts: the ocean as a source of inspiration, as seen in painting, poems, sounds, materials, photography, films, etc.
- Sport/Leisure: swimming, scuba diving, surfing, sailing, etc.
- Other: data, technology and research.

Do you think there is concern about the state of the Ocean (Seas or Waters) among young people communities?'

- Some participants consider that the level of consciousness is surprisingly low among youth, on the contrary others state that young communities are indeed concerned.
- There is not enough information, often it is confusing or not understandable. More knowledge would probably bring more engagement.
- Citizens do not connect enough with the Ocean and Waters, although those living in coastal communities are overall more engaged.
- There is a growing concern about the state of the Ocean and some relevant ongoing initiatives, but generally speaking, it does not translate into significant and visible action.
- In general, people are more aware of climate change, disregarding the role of the Ocean on climate.

'How to engage youth groups in Ocean and Waters Conservation:'

- Developing a sense of community and increasing people's connection with the Ocean.
- Inspiring youth and creating new discourses and imaginaries.
- Through formal and non-formal education and ocean literacy.
- Engagement through creative initiatives and activities, such as sports or cultural events, job opportunities, policy action, etc.
- Increasing and widening communication and awareness.
- Listening to the claims and needs of young people, allowing and endorsing their leadership.

'How to benefit from collaborating with artists and designers:'

- New ways to communicate can increase awareness.
- Sharing practical skills and new tools.
- Helping to connect people with the Ocean and Waters.
- Bridging knowledge and creating transversal new perspectives.
- Inspiring people and fostering cultural change.

'How can activism and arts cooperate:'

- Broadcasting the message behind actions, increasing impact and visibility through visual arts, theatre, photography, upcycling, among others.
- Making science more approachable and comprehensible to the general public.
- Building new narratives and new ways to connect people with the ocean.

'Priority goals that can be achieved through this network:'

1. Find new collective rituals to connect with the Ocean.
2. Apply innovative ways to share knowledge and raise awareness.
3. Develop and share new practical skills, methodologies, tools and strategies.
4. Find new ways to learn together, in particular through strong interdisciplinary networks of science and arts.

'Priority areas of action:'

1. Embrace collaborative activities and increase networking.
2. Share knowledge and methods: ideas, sensorial experiences, rituals, best practices, new ways to communicate.
3. Raise awareness on Ocean, Seas and Waters' conservation.
4. Increase societal implication and engagement.

The Miro board with all the original notes from the workshop is available [here](#).

Acknowledgements

Acknowledgments are due to the Prep4Blue project, funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957.

Our gratitude further extends to all participants:

Ana Otero (BAU); Angèlica Busquets (ICM-CSIC); Anja Wegner (University of Hamburg - researcher); Begoña Vendrell (Ocean Literacy); Caecilia Manago (ERINN Innovation); Camila René (BAU); Carine Simon (ICM-CSIC); Carlos de Juan (ICM-CSIC Young Researchers); Celia Murcia (Blue jobs platform); Clémence Baudu-Descamps (Surfrider Foundation); Cristina Noguera (BAU); David Whyte (MaREI); Diana Lorena Rico-Velez (Youmares); Diana Zúñiga (North Wind Sailing for Science); Edoardo Brodasca (Posidonia Green Festival); Emily Tewes (Sustainable Ocean Alliance); Ester M. López García (ICM Youth); Eugènia Barroca (Marine Biologist from SOA); Inés Mas de la Peña (ICM-CSIC); Jaron Rowan (BAU); Josep Lluís Pelegrí (ICM-CSIC); Justine Brossard (CPMR); Laia Romero (Lobelia Earth); Lucie Greyl (A Sud - Italy); Lydia Chaparro (ICM-CSIC); Magda Vila (ICM-CSIC); María Auxiliadora Cabrera Campano (Marinera de puente); Maria de la Fuente (ULB - Brussels); Maria Elena Carbajal (Journalist & sociologist); María Lain (Activist, member of Christian Youth for Climate); Marina Martínez (BAU); Neus Figueras Balaña (ICM-CSIC); Nil Rodes (Eurocean's Youth); Noemí Fuster (ICM-CSIC); Núria Ferré (individual); Oriol Carrasco Serra (ICM-CSIC Young Researchers); Shalenys Bedoya (CIDE-CSIC); Silja Teege (Sea Teach/Blue Generation Project); Tânia López Pérez (Graduate student UB).

We will reach you soon.
Thanks for your collaboration! :)

Annex G. June 2023 Blue Genes Virtual Meeting

June 2023

Synopsis of the second virtual meeting of the Blue Genes community:
In search of new ways to increase our connection with Nature

BLUE GENES

Co-authors in alphabetical order

Vanessa Balagué
Edoardo Brodasca
Anna Cabre
Maria Elena Carbajal
Lydia Chaparro Elias
Carlos de Juan Carbonell
Maria De la Fuente
Lucía Espasandín
Itziar Ferrer
Nalu Franco Gerent
Noemí Fuster
Odei Garcia Garin
*Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini **
Ester-María López García
Inés Mas de la Peña
Silvana Neves
Cristina Noguer
Ana Otero
*Josep Lluís Pelegrí **
Diana Rico
Jaron Rowan
Bárbara Sánchez Barroso
Elizabeth (Liz) Sherr
Carine Simon
Silja Teege
Magda Vila
Anja Wegner
David Whyte
Chris Wilmott
Victoria Zoeller
Jade Zoghbi
Diana Zúñiga

**Corresponding authors:*
Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC)
blue-genes@icm.csic.es

Table of Contents

01

Introduction

02

Presentations

03

Space for dialogue
and reflexions

04

Recommendations
at a glance

05

Closing remarks

Introduction

Participatory meeting for artists and scientists to share experiences, initiatives, ideas, reflections, and future actions related to the Oceans and Waters.

On June 22, 2023, the second online meeting of the Blue Genes initiative took place, uniting members of the Blue Genes Community. The aim was to exchange experiences, discuss initiatives, and share insights concerning the Ocean and Waters.

Over 30 participants joined this virtual assembly. Following a series of inspiring presentations delivered by several of the community members, the meeting transitioned into an interactive session, enabling attendees to actively participate in discussions and to share their viewpoints. Among other relevant conversations, the meeting proposed to target a milestone: to organize a Satellite Event during the 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference, which will take place in Barcelona in April 2024, as an open space to explore how to search for new ways to increase our connection with Nature, with the ocean as its central component. The participants felt this in-person meeting would be an excellent venue to work towards defining the priorities and strategies for the future of the Blue Genes community, as well as to engage a wider number of actors.

Presentations

Exploring collaborative frontiers: Perspectives on Nature, Art-Science fusion, and Sustainable ocean initiatives

01

The need for a collaborative revolution through an expanded cognition of Nature, which blends intellectual knowledge and sensory experiences into lasting changes. (Josep L. Pelegrí)

02

The importance of art and science collaborating to change our perspective of the environment and the need to challenge existing power structures. (Jaron Rowan)

03

An introduction of the Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Blue Economy, describing its focus on sustainable blue economy and presenting its main activities, including upcoming conferences and journals. (Diana Rico)

04

A project where dancers and scientists work together to communicate climate change through dance. (David White)

05

An introduction to the Posidonia Green Project, a NGO focused on marine ecosystem protection, and their innovative project with surfers. (Edoardo Brodasca)

06

The journey of an ocean activist using social media to raise awareness about marine pollution and to engage communities. (Elisabeth (Liz) Sherr)

07

The community of ICM young marine scientists and their efforts to create a support network and to address workplace challenges. (Carlos de Juan Carbonell)

08

The Ocean Decade and ECOP Spain, a group of young ocean professionals aiming to bring new ideas and perspectives to ocean sustainability. (Inés Mas de la Peña)

Expanding our real world: finding new ways to perceive and experience Nature

Josep Lluís introduced the origin of the Blue Genes initiative and presented his views on how to advance the ways we interact and perceive Nature.

During his presentation, Josep LLuis proposed that the central challenge is to recognize that each of us is part of the living planet, a simple fact that interconnects all creatures and, particularly, all human beings. This recognition requires finding new ways to perceive and experience Nature – to enhance our participation in the living Earth – as what we reckon as reality precisely arises through these perceptions and experiences (enaction).

Homo sapiens should not evolve into a technologically-driven species but rather should use technology to increase the cognitive and sensory perceptions of Nature. The development of new perceptions and relations with the Ocean, not only because of its economic value but mostly because of its central and essential role in the living Earth, will undoubtedly determine our individual and collective futures.

A collaborative revolution, enhancing our connection with nature, emphasizing harmony through empathy, trust, and love.

Humankind and the ocean are essential and equal participants in the collaborative revolution, with and for people and nature. This collaboration requires expanded cognition of the ocean: the combination of cognitive knowledge and sensory experiencing, enbluement. We are in front of a unique opportunity (SDGs, Ocean Decade, Mission Ocean) to grow towards greater complexity as individuals and as a species. But this growth is not technological complexity, not even the welfare society, it is individual and collective harmony and happiness with people and nature, based on true and lasting connections: empathy, sensibility, trust, hope, joy, and love.

Jaron Rowan - Director of Research at the BAU College of Arts and Design of Barcelona

Art, science, and design: Learning to investigate from a sensitive approach

Insights were provided by Jaron on the reciprocal learning between art and science, where art offers a distinct perspective blending objectivity and critical thinking in our perception of the world. The discussion highlighted how the exploitation of resources by capitalism is reaching its limits. For this reason, we need new ways of thinking: new spaces and practices where art, science, and design can help each other to understand and to produce new worldviews.

French philosopher Bruno Latour described how Galileo was not the first person to have a telescope, but the first one who saw the moon as a sphere: Galileo was an artist. The way that we perceive allows us to see things differently. The combination of instrumental reason and sensitive perception generated a new moon that did not exist so far. For the last 400 years, we have been looking at nature just as a resource and not as part of what we are. We need to change this and art can be a methodology that can help us go towards this change.

Jaron concluded that our imagination needs to change, but we also need to change extractivist relations to the world, challenge the system (institutions, markets, and regulations), and be collectively empowered. **Our proposal is towards a sensible ecology for a better collective life.**

”

Advocating for transformative imagination, challenging extractive relations, and proposing a sensible ecology for collective well-being.

Diana Rico, Jr. - Researcher/Project Manager at the Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Blue Economy

Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Blue Economy

Diana gave a presentation on the activities carried out at the **Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Blue Economy**. The Centre fosters interactions in the knowledge triangle (academia-policy-society) related to the blue economy, exploring its relevance for the EU and in particular for the Mediterranean region. By consolidating knowledge and expertise, the Centre plays a pivotal role in providing comprehensive insights into the EU Blue Economy.

The Centre is relatively new but has a network of experts working in several countries of the Euro-Mediterranean region, carrying out very diverse activities. One of these activities is a Summer School and Training, whose last edition counted with the participation of some 30 participants and over 20 speakers from the southern Mediterranean, Italy, Spain and the Balkans. In the near future they plan to conduct a Conference in Sustainable Blue Economy and to start the publication of a dedicated research journal.

The seal of Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence was awarded to the Euro-Mediterranean University (EMUNI) by the European Commission for the period 2022-2025.

”

Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Blue Economy, fostering knowledge interactions in academia-policy-society triangle.

David Whyte, Researcher at the SFI Research Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine research and innovation

Dancing science, reflections on a recent science-arts collaboration

David presented recent work done with the socially inclusive dance company Croí Glan Dance (Clear Heart Dance), based in Cork, South of Ireland: a company where people with and without disabilities feel their equality and shared humanity through an immediate and visceral experience.

This integrated dance company together with scientists is co-producing a show on climate change. As this is a recently initiated two-year project, the outcome remains uncertain. However, the project will evolve in time and choreographers will craft a dance piece from the ongoing creative process.

The creative process begins with “expert talk,” where dancers lie on the floor, listen, and subsequently engage in improvisation as the discussion unfolds. The entire process is recorded for internal use and later reviewed.

Several reflections originating within the dance group are as follows: They would communicate science through dance, with the scientists being the experts.

CROÍ GLAN
integrated dance company

Dance company that blends art and science, exploring climate change through inclusive performances, and fostering enriching collaboration and shared learning experiences.

However, they recognized that expertise in climate change extends beyond scientists. Farmers, as an example, are actors that may also take part and this might be reflected in the choreography. Other considerations involve thinking about your creative work in very different ways. How can I be evocative, or how can I express my work emotionally to a group of people. And finally, reflect on the strengths and weaknesses of our different modes of communication. We are all trying to communicate but there are strengths and weaknesses in each kind of communication.

David concluded that this work has been an enriching and interesting learning process and the collaboration between art and science is a relevant tool to create new knowledge and spaces.

Edoardo Brodasca, Executive Director at the Posidonia Green Project

The Posidonia Green Project, an ecosystem of actions to understand and protect the BLUE

Edoardo presented the Posidonia Green Project, an NGO focused on protecting the blue ecosystems (marine plants, animals, corals, and other creatures in the oceans). The goal is to promote awareness and sustainability for the preservation of seas and oceans; the NGO operates in the Mediterranean region with a global perspective.

The organization operates within three strategic domains: Science and innovation, Communication and dissemination, and Policy and lobbying. They provide valuable information about the state of the BLUE ecosystem and encourage actions to make a difference. A recent initiative is the "Surfstainable" project, which incorporates surfers into climate and environmental research through an innovative device integrated into surfboards. The device measures ocean temperatures and transmits data to a research platform. The NGO also organizes the annual "Posidonia Green Festival" to celebrate the oceans and raise awareness about their preservation through various activities.

The Posidonia Green Project aims to involve more people and create changes by combining information, action, and collaboration.

The Posidonia Green Project safeguards marine ecosystems, promotes awareness, engages surfers in research, and hosts an annual festival.

Elisabeth (Liz) Sherr

Ocean activist and Science communicator

Scaling ocean impact through video storytelling

Liz shared a video presenting her project as an ocean activist and science communicator.

Three years ago she was surprised about the amount of trash littering the beach of Barcelona and started making TikTok **videos documenting her clean-up efforts**. In this way, she influenced many people to clean-up their communities, an action that went viral and engaged many young communities. Following this, it drew the interest of the European Parliament, which invited her to undertake a comparable campaign for World Ocean Day in 2021. This virtual challenge engaged participants from over 33 countries, exemplifying the significant role that social media can play in fostering positive impacts on the ocean.

Liz continues to raise awareness about marine pollution, with an online community of approximately **135K followers**, primarily on TikTok and Instagram. Drawing from her experience, she has also produced videos sharing ocean stories featuring marine animals.

Liz recently met Ona, an ocean storytelling agency for the oceans. They produce content to reach larger audiences and highlight the positive developments taking place. They are together planning to organize media corners and similar actions for the UN Ocean Decade conference in the upcoming year in Barcelona. Liz is genuinely curious to learn about the activities of other participants in the conference and to explore opportunities for mutual support, especially in the realm of communication.

Liz is also working on a forthcoming series entitled Together Living Blue where she will introduce new marine science research and solutions to broader audiences in a fun and engaging manner. The primary goal is to connect with people, to share projects, and to narrate inspiring stories that express passion for the ocean.

”

Liz, an ocean activist and communicator, gained global influence through viral clean-up videos, engaging communities worldwide.

Carlos de Juan Carbonell, PhD candidate at the [Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC](#)

The ICM Young Researchers community

Carlos presented the community of young marine scientists at the ICM-CSIC. Around 20% of the staff at ICM (about 300 people) are doctoral students. Further, if adding the young technicians or management employees and post docs, the percentage increases considerably. The association was established to advocate for the interests of these younger professionals, as they frequently encounter similar challenges within the scientific career path.

The association, with over 100 members, is engaged in networking, sharing professional opportunities, ideas and concerns while they develop outreach and social activities, such as beach clean ups and monthly Hot Topics talks.

Their involvement extends to mentoring programs, collaboration in open-door initiatives, and participation in various European projects. In addition, they have identified several structural problems associated with their stage and have formulated a protocol for the prevention of workplace harassment. In coordination with the ICM Direction they have reached a series of commitments that aim towards a healthy environment during the thesis development. Thanks to their work and activities, their voice is gradually becoming more present inside the institute.

Carlos proposed that ICM Young Researchers could act as a direct liaison to the Blue Genes community, leveraging their strong transversal skills and enthusiasm.

”

Young marine scientists at the ICM-CSIC advocate for fellow professionals, fostering community, addressing challenges, and promoting positive changes.

Inés Mas de la Peña

Early Career Ocean Professional (ECOP) Spain

Early Career Ocean Professional (ECOP) Spain

Inés initially provided several insights regarding the **Ocean Decade** declared by the United Nations and subsequently presented ECOP Spain.

She reviewed the three primary objectives of the Ocean Decade "Moving from the ocean we have to the ocean we want:" 1) to identify the required knowledge for sustainable developments, 2) to generate comprehensive knowledge and understanding of the ocean, and 3) to increase the use of ocean knowledge. The idea for ECOP (Early Career Ocean Professional) Network Program arose during the First Global Planning Meeting (May 2019) organized by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC-UNESCO). Its primary goal is to incorporate fresh perspectives into the global challenges of ocean sustainability and stewardship by fostering professional networking and development. One of their current major challenges is to secure funding to support its structure and capabilities.

Since September 2022 the ECOP community has grown incredibly, currently counting 1992 members based in 117 countries, and having four task teams: Ocean Literacy; Training and Mentoring; Diversity, Equity and Inclusivity; OceanBRIDGES.

The ECOP Action Plan includes organizing workshops and training, creating a feeling of community, and sharing resources and job opportunities, among others. ECOP is interested in participating in the UN Ocean Conference to be held next year in Barcelona. Furthermore, they remain receptive to any form of feedback, funding, ideas, assistance, and support. More information can be found at [ECOP Spain](#) and spain@ecopdecade.org

”

ECOP Spain is part of the UN Ocean Decade, fostering global ocean sustainability and facilitating professional networking and development.

Space for dialogue and reflections

This section served as an open space for dialogue and reflections, inviting exploration of diverse perspectives in art and science collaboration.

Different interpretations of the "bottom-up" concept.

Sharing experiences on transmitting science, including the use of music.

The importance of art and science collaboration in exploring new perspectives.

The importance of simplifying complex issues while preserving their conceptual depth.

The value of experiences and the urgency of shifting from the past to welcome new perspectives.

Recommendations for reading materials.

Plans for a collaborative Satellite Event during the 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference in Barcelona.

Space for dialogue and reflections

This section served as an open space for dialogue and reflections, inviting to explore diverse perspectives in art and science collaboration.

The discussion on the "Bottom-up" concept began with several insights from artist Chris Wilmott and expanded to include distinct interpretations, which highlight how this concept may apply in different contexts. Chris Wilmott, an artist based in the UK who focuses on coastal cities and the impacts of rising sea levels, emphasized the importance of the "bottom-up" concept when engaging with the general public. From his viewpoint, this concept embodies a collaborative experience where individuals are not dictated on what to do, but rather actively participate in shaping the process. Anna Cabre, a postdoc based in Germany, commented that "bottom could just mean people power"; while María de la Fuente, a postdoc based in Belgium, commented that "even if commonly the bottom-up approach is associated to people-based decisions, we should not forget that its original description defines it as an approach to solve problems based on data and facts". Chris Wilmott also noted that the interpretation of "bottom-up" likely varies among the different arts. This diversity is intriguing because, in the realm of art, the start of creative process does not always require the kind of data that is typical in scientific contexts. Josep Lluís Pelegrí added that "words by themselves mean nothing unless you fulfill them with experiences".

The dialogue continued as Diana Zuñiga, a member of the [North Wind - Sailing for Science project](#), shared a recent compelling experience regarding the effective communication of science to young audiences. Diana explained a week of activities related to climate change and polar zones that was organized in Galicia where scientists and artists collaborated to engage and raise awareness of these critical issues among students. A music group (Oreka Tx), featuring a traditional instrument called the "chalapata", did an impressive performance with ice in the Arctic. The music group presented a video from around 20 years ago when they visited and shared experiences with the nomads in the Arctic ([Nömadak TX video](#)). Diana expressed that music can be a key element in communicating climate change, as "kids really connected with the musicians".

Jade Zoghbi, a doctoral candidate in Spain, shared her experiences from Northern Iceland while navigating and observing marine life. Jade emphasized how concepts such as ecocentrism or anthropocentrism can serve to understand other views around the Ocean.

Space for dialogue and reflections

Josep Lluís Pelegrí added that experiences are important but that many times it is necessary to get rid of this “baggage of experiences” to embrace fresh perspectives and new outlooks. Anja Wegner, a doctoral student in Germany, emphasized the importance of understanding the context and being aware of the baggage carried by each individual. She explained her work linked with Fish Architecture, where she collaborates and merges scientific and artistic disciplines. She redesigns aquatic spaces as an interspecies collaboration, as a co-creation process. She wondered aloud: “What does it mean to co-create with other animals? How do we learn from those animals? What does it do to us if we engage with them?”. Anja endorsed the need to revisit the nexus between arts, sciences, and technologies, and pointed out that artificial intelligence will challenge our ethics and the structure of our society, with technology as an opportunity to reconsider many ideas and concepts.

Diana Zuñiga added a recommendation to read the works of marine biologist Edward Ricketts, particularly his book “The Breaking Through”, which delves into discussions about nature, ecology, as well as philosophy, and political aspects. Anna Cabre recommended the book “Why Fish Don't Exist: A Story of Loss, Love, and the Hidden Order of Life” by Lulu Miller. Chris Wilmott recommended “Five Times Faster” by Simon Sharpe, which states the need to rethink the science, economics, and diplomacy of climate change. Lastly, Josep Lluís Pelegrí recommended “Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow” by Yuval Noah Harari, which examines what might happen to the world when old myths are coupled with new godlike technologies, such as artificial intelligence and genetic engineering.

Conversations continued with interesting thoughts about art and science collaborations. Maria de la Fuente highlighted that the challenge of raising awareness often leads to oversimplification, especially when dealing with complex topics such as climate change and biodiversity loss. She pointed out that collaborative efforts should aim to simplify the message without sacrificing the depth and complexity of the problems they seek to address. During the meeting, several significant discussions unfolded and eventually led to the proposal of a milestone: **the organization of a collaborative satellite event during the UN Ocean Decade Conference that will take place in Barcelona in April 2024.** Consequently, a forthcoming and logical step for the Blue Genes Community will be to foster engagement and cooperation to plan an in-person activity in Barcelona before and during the Ocean Decade Conference.

Recommendations at a glance

Projects discussed:

- [Blue Genes: Art&Science community](#)
- [BAU College of Arts and Design of Barcelona](#)
- [Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Blue Economy, \(CoE-SUBE\)](#)
- [SFI Research Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine research and innovation \(MaREI\)](#)
- [Croí Glan Dance](#)
- [Posidonia Green Project](#)
- [Ocean activist and science communicator](#)
- [Storytelling agency for the oceans ONA](#)
- [ICM Young Researchers, Institut de Ciències del Mar \(ICM-CSIC\)](#)
- [Early Career Ocean Professionals \(ECOP\)](#)
- [Music group Oreka Tx & Nomads in the Arctic: A video](#)
- [UN Ocean Decade - Satellite events](#)

Books:

- "Why Fish Don't Exist: A Story of Loss, Love, and the Hidden Order of Life" by Lulu Miller.
- "Homo Sapiens: A Brief History of Humankind" by Yuval Noah Harari.
- "Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow" by Yuval Noah Harari.
- "The Breaking Through" by Edward Ricketts.
- "Five Times Faster" by Simon Sharpe.

Closing remarks

The meeting served as a platform for thought-provoking presentations and discussions that revealed critical aspects of our relationship with nature, through a variety of aspects such as the integration of **art and science, sustainable blue economy initiatives, creative science communication, marine ecosystem protection, and the power of social media in ocean activism.**

Multifaceted Exploration

The meeting explored art-science integration, sustainable blue economy, and marine protection, revealing diverse facets of our relationship with nature.

"Bottom-up" Insights

Diverse interpretations of "bottom-up" highlighted the essence of collaboration, showcasing how arts effectively communicate science and deepen our connection to nature.

Future Collaboration

Plans for a Satellite Event at the 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference as a signal of collective dedication to address ocean concerns and foster collaboration within the Blue Genes Community.

Acknowledgements

Acknowledgments are due to the Prep4Blue project, funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957

Our gratitude further extends to all participants Vanessa Balagué; Edoardo Brodasca; Ana Cabre; Maria Elena Carbajal; Lydia Chaparro Elias; Carlos de Juan Carbonell; Maria De la Fuente; Lucía Espasandín; Itziar Ferrer; Nalu Franco Gerent; Noemí Fuster; Odei Garcia Garin; Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini; Ester-María López García; Inés Mas de la Peña; Silvana Neves; Cristina Noguer; Ana Otero; Josep Lluís Pelegrí; Diana Rico; Jaron Rowan; Bárbara Sánchez Barroso; Elizabeth (Liz) Sherr; Carine Simon; Silja Teege; Magda Vila; Anja Wegner; David Whyte; Chris Wilmott; Victoria Zoeller; Jade Zoghbi; Diana Zúñiga. whose active engagement has enriched this endeavor, and to authors Ifigeneia Giannoukakou-Leontsini; Lydia Chaparro, and Josep Lluís Pelegrí in shaping the content of this comprehensive report.

We thank the participants for their contribution, enriching this initiative with their collective expertise and insights

Contact

Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC)
Passeig Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37-49
08003 Barcelona (Spain)

blue-genes@icm.csic.es

Annex H. December 2023 Blue Genes In-Person Meeting

Synopsis of the First In-Person Meeting of the Blue Genes Community: Strengthening a Local Community of Practice

Funded by the European Union

PREP4BLUE
METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Institut de Ciències del Mar

EXCELENCIA SEVERO OCHOA

CSIC
CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

**Participants
in alphabetical
order**

Álvarez, Eva
Azkona Cañi, Laida
Balagué, Vanessa
Betrán Clos, Emma
Camahort, Maria
Cantarero, Constanza
Carbajal, María Elena (*)
Carrasco Serra, Oriol
Chachignot, Ladislav
de Juan, Carlos
Giannoukakou-Leontsini, Ifigeneia (*)
Llopert, Eulàlia
Oliva Farriol, Jordi
Pelegrí, Josep Lluís (*)
Plaza, Miguel "Aua"
Prats Vidal, Albert
Ramírez Calero, Sandra
Sánchez Barroso, Bárbara
Sanz Yus, Diego
Sanz, Claudia
Simon, Carine
Tewes, Emily

*Corresponding authors:
Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC)
blue-genes@icm.csic.es

Table of contents

- 01 Introduction
- 02 Presentation
- 03 Interactive Sessions
- 04 Conclusions
- 05 Key Takeaways
- 06 Acknowledgements

01 Introduction

Participatory meeting for artists and scientists to share experiences, initiatives, ideas, reflections, and future actions related to the Oceans and Waters.

On December 19, 2023, over 20 artists and scientists came together for the Blue Genes community's first in-person meeting at the Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM). The gathering united members of the Community with a focus on identifying interests and synergies, strengthening local ties and refining current objectives, highlighting the potential at the intersection of art and science.

Highlights included a presentation of the Bosc Ancestral mural, created with microscopic images of marine life, and open discussions about tackling eco-anxiety and creating fresh, **hopeful narratives about the ocean**.

Participants also brainstormed ways to make the Blue Genes community stronger, from organizing retreats to building more accessible tools for collaboration.

By the end of the day, one thing was clear: there's a lot of energy behind this growing community. The next step? A step that promises to bring their ideas to life — but you'll have to read on to find out.

02 Presentations

Vanessa Balagué Año
Researcher at the
[Institut de Ciències del Mar,
ICM-CSIC](#)

Bosque Ancestral - a 60 m Mural by Anna Rierola

Vanessa presented the 60-m long mural crafted by artist Anna Rierola, created using microscopic images of nanomaterials and plankton, in close collaboration and with the advice of scientists from ICM-CSIC and the Catalan Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology.

Bosc Ancestral draws inspiration from the pivotal role marine phytoplankton organisms play in the global functioning of our planet. They form the foundation of the food chain, play a crucial role in fundamental natural cycles, and contribute to generating 50% of the planet's oxygen, which we breathe.

02 Presentations

Josep Lluís Pelegrí
Researcher at the
[Institut de Ciències del Mar,
ICM-CSIC](#)

Reflections on the why and how of the collaborative revolution: strengthening our non-cognitive side to get closer to a new perception and participation in Nature

Pelegrí advocates for a collaborative relationship that transcends individual boundaries, fostering a sense of belonging to a greater whole. This interconnectedness, he suggests, is attainable through enhanced non-cognitive intelligence, emphasizing that science devoid of creativity is devoid of substance. The scientist urges us to enrich our non-cognitive faculties – to dive into inner practices such as meditation, sensitivity, empathy and love, and outer sensory perceptions of our belonging to Nature.

By fortifying these aspects, we pave the way for both individual and collective happiness. Through this transformative journey, Pelegrí underscores the ocean as a central and unifying element of life. By championing these fundamental values, the presentation acts as a catalyst for nurturing a profound sense of connection. It is through acknowledging and promoting these positive values that we can bridge the gap of disconnection and foster a harmonious relationship with our environment and with each other.

02 Presentations

Ifigeneia
Giannoukaku-
Leontsini
Blue Genes Coordinator
[Institut de Ciències del
Mar,
ICM-CSIC](#)

The Blue Genes Initiative

Ifi presented the Blue Genes initiative, which seeks to discover new ways for us to learn, explore new rituals, and exchange knowledge. Past virtual meetings of the community included brainstorming sessions and the creation of new rituals encompassing various activities. The key focus is on utilizing collective intelligence among participants and finding ways to learn together. This should help addressing the European Union objectives present in the Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030: protect and restore the marine environment, eliminate pollution, and promote a more sustainable and circular blue Economy. The initiative aims to harness the interests of participants, fostering transdisciplinary collaboration to address these goals.

BLUE GENES | December 2023

03 Interactive sessions

Icebreaker activity

Participants received randomly distributed cards from the ICM-CSIC card game entitled “From land or sea”, whose objective is to connect ocean science with a broader audience. Each participant was assigned the task of pairing with another participant so as to identify similarities and analogies between the marine and terrestrial environments, allowing them to introduce themselves to each other and finding their interests on the Ocean and waters. Participants were incentivized to switch pairs during the activity, hence enhancing networking opportunities.

The session continued by prompting participants

- (1) to envision the direction they would like to steer the Blue Genes community and
- (2) to share best personal and networking practices, identifying how these practices could be effectively integrated into the Blue Genes community for collective growth and development.

BLUE GENES | December 2023

03 Interactive sessions

What is your vision/dream for this Community of Practice in art and science?

- Establish a self-sufficient community.
- Develop a common language between scientists and artists, turning conceptual ideas into actionable items.
- Merge ecology with art and social work.
- Be more integrated with the sea and emphasize spiritual and social connections.
- Explore methodologies that bring science to society through artistic means.
- Organize a collective journey to the Arctic, envisioning it as a place of diverse possibilities.
- Find new ways to relate to the sea, seeking spiritual and social connections.
- Introduce artistic elements into the study of coral reefs.

03 Interactive sessions

If you were a Blue Genes superhero, what superpower would you possess?

- Spark curiosity among people.
- Persistence in pursuing community goals.
- Blend ecology, art, and social work seamlessly.
- Translate conceptual ideas into actionable items, especially concerning climate change.
- Be a point of balance in large groups through excellence in social skills.
- Integrate the sea into our personal life, with a focus on attitudes and active listening.
- Break with learned concepts, prioritizing continuous learning and unlearning.
- Generate enthusiasm and persistence to ensure the flow, advancement, and rootedness of the community.
- Fostering collaboration within diverse profiles.
- Catalyze artistic work and bring together different ecological and feminist aspects.
- Facilitate the flow and concrete the realization of emerging ideas, with persistence and goal fulfillment.
- Catalyze connections with empathy, emphasizing active listening and global connections.
- Create bridges between science and art, transmitting passion, and communicating dreams effectively.

03 Interactive sessions

**Collective Visions
Blue Genes
Community**

Participants presented their visions:

One introduced another, envisioning a self-sufficient community with a superpower of sparking curiosity and emphasizing persistence as a valuable practice. The other reciprocated, dreaming of a common language between scientists and artists, with a superpower of translating conceptual ideas into actionable items and reducing distractions like WhatsApp.

A pair, both biologists, aimed to merge ecology with art and social work. One's superpower related to this fusion, while the other's strength came from social skills and effective communication.

One shared their dream of deeper engagement with the sea, emphasizing active listening, while the partner valued meditation, connection with Nature, and the superpower of enthusiasm and persistence.

Another pair admired each other's practices, with one dreaming of the community flowing and advancing, rooted in connection with the sea.

03 Interactive sessions

**Collective Visions
Blue Genes
Community**

A creative couple aspired to interdisciplinary projects, emphasizing collaboration and the catalyzing power of one's artistic endeavors.

An artist and a physicist-to-be sought to bring science to society through artistic methodologies, exploring the intersection of art and science.

A scientist and artist pair dreamed of ideas flowing seamlessly, with one's superpower being persistence and goal achievement, and the other's being catalyzing connections through empathy, aiming to bridge people and ideas globally.

One focused on new ways of connecting with the sea, emphasizing spiritual and social bonds. The other one, a conservationist, hoped for a language bridging science and art, with both superpowers being communication and community building.

The collective aspiration, as expressed by several, was to organize a 2-3 day retreat in February 2024, where the Blue Genes community could explore their shared vision and commitment.

03 Interactive sessions

Group discussion
"in a fishbowl"

Next, the entire group dived into the fishbowl: a group discussion activity that involves two concentric circles of participants. In the center circle (the "fishbowl"), a few participants discuss a topic or answer questions while the outer circle observes. Participants from the outer circle can join the inner circle and share their thoughts.

03 Interactive sessions

Group discussion
"in a fishbowl"

- How do we envision the Blue Genes community, what shape should it take to find our individual place and involvement?
- How could we contribute and how could we get involved to make it progress?
- What do I receive and what do I give to the community?

The answers revolved around a community project to which everyone contributes. The aspiration is to cultivate shared interests, co-develop projects, and foster a sense of communal and interdisciplinary collaboration. The aim is to raise awareness by leveraging the strengths of each participant, identifying needs, and addressing them from diverse perspectives to ensure a unified vision.

03 Interactive sessions

Group discussion “in a fishbowl”

Maintaining flexibility and ensuring accessibility for individuals with disabilities are integral aspects. The impact should extend beyond our immediate awareness, reaching those who are not yet engaged in the cause. Education is a key element, learning and teaching in different ways and in a participatory and inclusive manner. The emphasis is on fostering a sense of collectivity and interpellating those who are already aware. Efforts should be directed toward **societies that may live disconnected from the sea**, making the ecosystem tangible and relatable through passion. Art has become a powerful tool for communication.

Examples like the war **photography** of Sebastião Salgado demonstrate how art can convey impactful messages. The challenge lies in using art to communicate complex issues like climate change, in a way that profoundly resonates with people. It goes **beyond cognitive understanding**; it's about creating a visceral, experiential connection that instigates change within individuals.

Finding ways to emotionally involve people is essential for creating profound and lasting change. Narratives of diaspora and the end of the world may not inspire action, but artists and scientists offer hope, providing space for action. The **informative aspect of art, conveyed through sensory experiences, becomes a pathway to connect with people who might be overstimulated in public spaces.**

03 Interactive sessions

Group discussion “in a fishbowl”

The community's vision involves reflection and communication, breaking through the noise of new images to create new narratives. Blue Genes is seen not just as a daily activity but as a platform where people can share concerns and collectively find answers. The emphasis is on giving hope and fostering curiosity rather than instilling fear as a tool for environmental education.

The message aims to provide an "**oceanic therapy**", addressing eco-anxiety by understanding the evolution and thresholds of history, explained both scientifically and poetically.

It is crucial to integrate emotion from art and knowledge from science, recognizing that humans are both emotional and rational beings. The goal is to generate change by incorporating personal experiences, being transdisciplinary, and supporting political campaigns against harmful practices like underwater mining.

Finally, the importance of getting to better know the sea underlines the collective quest for a deeper connection with our environment.

03 Interactive sessions

Subgroups: Crafting the future of Blue Genes community

Following the group discussion, participants were divided into three rotating groups representing "the Body," "the Mind," and "the Soul," drawing parallels between the components that a project should possess and those that are found in real life.

03 Interactive sessions

Subgroups: Crafting the future of Blue Genes community

The Body

Represents the tangible structure of the project. It encompasses the physical resources, tools, infrastructure, and everything concrete that shapes and sustains the project. Just as a healthy body is essential for well-being, a robust structure is fundamental for the successful execution of the project.

The Mind

This is the intellectual and strategic part of the project. It includes planning, creativity, and knowledge management. Just as a focused and clear mind is crucial for personal success, the project's mind must be sharp and adaptable to overcome challenges and achieve goals.

The Soul

Represents the essence and deep motivation of the project. It includes the values, vision, and mission that inspire and give purpose to the project. Just as the soul drives passion and purpose in life, the essence of the project propels the dedication and perseverance of all people involved.

03 Interactive sessions

The Body

Represents the tangible structure of the project. It encompasses the physical resources, tools, infrastructure, and everything concrete that shapes and sustains the project. Just as a healthy body is essential for well-being, a robust structure is fundamental for the successful execution of the project.

Building upon the existing Blue Genes website, the aim is to enhance its user-friendliness, clarity, and visual appeal. This involves a reformulation of various aspects, including community profiles, communication methods, the announcement of events, shared resources, and arrangements for community gatherings. The objective is to **create a virtual space that not only informs but also fosters interaction, collaboration, and a sense of community** among Blue Genes members.

- **Community:** The goal is to connect members with similar affinities. Expand the information with a short paragraph (3-4 lines) about personal focus, dedication, background, and interests; including some keywords could be useful. It is also suggested to add an identifier symbol in the profile image (e.g., colored dots associated with artistic, scientific, outreach profiles) without being exclusive.
- **Communication:** Avoid new applications that require registration or may invade personal space (WhatsApp, Telegram, Slack). The possibility of an internal forum integrated into the website is considered, which should allow for fluidity in the communication. Meanwhile, a shared email list can be used for notifications.
- **Announcement of future events:** Both those organized by Blue Genes members and those that may interest the community. For example, this could be done on a separate page in a bulletin board format.
- **Shared resources:** A new section for sharing reference material: books, links, images, exhibitions, etc., as well as disseminating success stories or reference cases that may stimulate the creation of ideas.

03 Interactive sessions

The Mind

Represents the essence and deep motivation of the project. It includes the values, vision, and mission that inspire and give purpose to the project. Just as the soul drives passion and purpose in life, the essence of the project propels the dedication and perseverance of all people involv

This group explored strategies that promote the participation and commitment of the members and hence would fortify the community.

- **Communication:** The current website holds information about the community and its members, but updates and segmentation of profiles are required. A deeper exploration into each member preferences, involvement in specific projects or topics, and the reasons that brought them to Blue Genes is aimed. Additionally, understanding individual skills will be essential for creating synergies within the community.
- **Establishing an activity calendar:** The proposal includes organizing informal after-work gatherings such as coffee or beer meetups to foster informal connections among members. These events should be open and informative, allowing everyone to be invited.
- **Building Networks:** Initiating from local levels, particularly within the "Ecosistema Cero", and subsequently expanding globally is the envisioned approach. It seems crucial to publicize and make available the work done by local networks, starting in Catalonia and later replicating the model in other regions.

The consensus is to organize a Blue Genes community retreat in February 2025 to **"break away from the rapid pace"** of daily life. Exploring different formats to facilitate better understanding and connections was discussed, including a suggestion of renting a boat for activities at sea.

03 Interactive sessions

The Soul

This is the intellectual and strategic part of the project. It includes planning, creativity, and knowledge management. Just as a focused and clear mind is crucial for personal success, the project's mind must be sharp and adaptable to overcome challenges and achieve goals.

Blue Genes seeks to be a pathway for genuine exchange, remaining open with no boundaries.

- A transversal meeting point: The Soul group discussed their interest in working organizationally in a horizontal manner, without hierarchies or egos. The group prioritized in-person meetings despite the physical distance challenge, as this type of meetings are more vividly experienced and remembered this way.
- Synergetic activities: Gathering or approaching based on projects or subgroups of interest. Participants join Blue Genes to collectively generate a superior collective synergy compared to individual energy. It as a space where dormant channels or communication bridges coexist in the common imagination. **"We are more alike than we think;** both worlds (art and science) seek to follow their intuition with different methods to achieve the same end, with emotion, reflection, and work. We all know the path of rigor through trial and error. We all seek to find a creative outlet that differs from the pre-established, to pursue a result rooted in awareness and crystallize into a result shared by our community, hoping it reaches further away to generate a change."
- Values: Respect, active listening, commitment, generosity, and the intention to be friendly and transparent with limitations and inner worlds to care for each other and create a safe space. Blue Genes identifies itself with the **feminine gender** due to its focus on stimulating cyclical receiving. The community also aims to establish gender equity in its daily life, encouraging equitable participation based on time and interest of the community members.

03 Interactive sessions

Proposed Retreat Rituals or Activities

- Collaborative or divided sculpture competition using recycled materials (paper, caps, cans, cardboard, etc.) with a common concept.
- Cyanotype creation, potentially collecting seashells, algae, etc., with varied intentions such as exhibition, personal creation, or a bonding activity.
- Presentations from the perspective of other disciplines (dualism between science and art). Creation of spaces for experimentation and consciousness liberation using natural techniques (suggested examples include dance, drawing, music and breathing techniques.)
- Collective meditation activities, expressions of gratitude, offerings to the sea, and sensory experiences.
- Workshop on theory, technique, and individual/collective creation with a super 8 camera (Barbara).
- Dance and body expression activity (Laida).
- Bonfire space with music.
- As a community ritual, begin and end each gathering day with a circle, starting with a one-word or one-sentence to appreciate how everyone is feeling.
- Create a Google Form for post-retreat ideas. Share social media profiles (LinkedIn, Instagram, etc.) if comfortable.

04 Conclusions

Diverse Perspectives: Contributions of 20 Participants

Blue Genes arises as a community project where everyone contributes to create and seek common ground in developing projects of potential interest to the members, fostering a more communal and interdisciplinary approach aimed at raising awareness. It should be engaging, addressing identified needs from various perspectives to ensure each person can relate to it. Appreciating the interdisciplinary nature of the project is crucial; aiming for resonance with people, similar to attending a concert or exhibition experience. Considering the five senses is essential, as well as ensuring flexibility for accessibility by people with disabilities. The impact should extend beyond current awareness, reaching those not yet involved through learning, educating, and teaching in very diverse ways. Emphasizing collectivity in participatory activities adds value and creates sensibilization among those who are already aware, directing efforts where they are most needed. One example could be dedicating a few days to transmit and connect ecosystems through passion using new artistic approaches.

04 Conclusions

Diverse Perspectives: Contributions of 20 Participants

All Blue Genes members agreed that art serves as a pathway to consciousness; however, communicating complex scientific and environmental issues effectively remains challenging. Examples like the ethically-driven war-photography of Sebastian Salgado highlights the potential of art in conveying impactful messages — going beyond cognitive understanding into visceral transformative experiences does engage individuals emotionally, hence inducing profound change amid narratives of diaspora and offering hope amidst doomsday scenarios. Analyzing how we capture someone's interest, it becomes particularly important to leverage our connections, to endorse intuition beyond rigid thinking, to move from catastrophic thinking into new lands of opportunity. It is fundamental to develop robust communication strategies to capture the public's attention, including sensory and participative approaches as engaging methodologies for overstimulated audiences. The realm of arts dissemination offers a promising outlook that could inspire action toward climate resilience and societal transformation.

05 Key Takeaways

The Power of Interdisciplinary Collaboration

It became evident that the convergence of these disciplines has the potential to spark innovation and unlock new ways of understanding and interpreting the world around us. Participants shared examples of successful collaborative projects that resulted in groundbreaking artistic and scientific advancements, highlighting the significance of embracing diverse perspectives and knowledge approaches.

Art as a Catalyst for Communicating Complex Ideas

Through visual and sensory experiences, art has the ability to transcend traditional academic boundaries and can hence evoke emotional connections, making scientific ideas more accessible and impactful. The participants discussed how art can bridge the gap between scientific jargon and public understanding, ultimately fostering greater scientific literacy and appreciation.

05 Key Takeaways

Cultivating Sensitivity and Empathy

Pelegri's presentation prompted reflection on the importance of sensitivity and empathy in bridging art and science. Participants emphasized the need to bring emotional understanding and humanistic approaches into scientific work, highlighting empathy and compassion as key elements towards ethical and meaningful advancements.

Commitment to Continued Dialogue and Exploration

The meeting concluded with a collective commitment to sustain and promote dialogue and exploration of the intersection of art and science. Participants expressed a shared enthusiasm for further collaboration, interdisciplinary projects, and ongoing engagement with the profound themes and ideas presented during the meeting. The enriching discussions and the shared commitment to this intersection have laid a strong foundation for future endeavors and the pursuit of interdisciplinary innovation.

Acknowledgments are due to the PREP4BLUE project, funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957

06 Acknowledgements

Acknowledgments are also due to Aua from SomPosidonia, whose guidance played a key role in productive discussions and collaboration.

Acknowledgments are further extended to Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC) for hosting the meeting and supporting the event.

Contact

blue-genes@icm.csic.es
Institut de Ciències del
Mar (ICM-CSIC)
Passeig Marítim de la
Barceloneta, 37-49
08003 Barcelona
(Spain)

Annex I. February 2024 Blue Genes Retreat - Program

BLUE GENES RETREAT

DAY 1 / 3

08h30	Gathering at the ICM and Departure to Cala Canyelles
10h30	Welcoming, Group cohesion, and Initial conversations to foster synergies
12h25	Prioritizing synergies, forming action-research groups, and self-organization tips for accommodations
13h45	Lunch break @ Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles
16h00	Action scenarios, priorities and timeline development
18h00	Event UN Ocean Decade: Creative planning session
19h15	Wrap-up. Mauricio's poem & logistics reminder
20h	Walk to accommodations
20h15	Dinner preparation

Thursday, February 15, 2024

Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC) Pg. Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37
Club Náutico Cala Canyelles, Av. Canyelles, 17310 Lloret de Mar, Girona
blue-genes@icm.csic.es | +34 644 166 373

BLUE GENES RETREAT

DAY 2/3

09h30	Morning cohesion: Movement exploration with the sea by Mauricio
10h00	Shaping the UN event: Defining activities and organizational structure
12h00	Assigning roles and group collaboration for UN event preparation
14h00	Lunch break @ Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles
16h00	Parallel workshop space - Participants: Eulàlia, Eva, Ladislav, Diego / Possible extra session for UN event
18h15	Community future, next steps, and timelines
19h30	Wrap-up
20h	Walk to accommodations
20h15	Dinner preparation

Friday, February 16, 2024

Club Náutico Cala Canyelles, Av. Canyelles, 17310 Lloret de Mar, Girona

blue-genes@icm.csic.es | +34 644 166 373

BLUE GENES RETREAT

DAY 3/3

09h30	Participant opening: Soundscape active listening by Ilaria
10h00	Exchange space continues: Group art activity (Ilaria, Ladislav, Emily)
11h30	Greetings, feedback and closure
13h00	Lunch break @ Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles
15h00	Return journey!

Saturday, February 17, 2024

Club Náutico Cala Canyelles, Av. Canyelles, 17310 Lloret de Mar, Girona
Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC) Pg. Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37
blue-genes@icm.csic.es | +34 644 166 373

Annex J. February 2024 Blue Genes Retreat - Report

Synopsis of the Second In-
Person Meeting of the Blue
Genes Community:

The Retreat
Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles,
Girona, Spain

Participants in alphabetical order

Álvarez Eva
Azkona Goñi, Laida
Betrán Clos, Emma
Broglia, Elisabetta
Cabre Albos, Anna
Cantarero, Constanza
Carbajal, Maria Elena (*)
Chachignot, Ladislav
Comaposada, Andrea
de Juan, Carlos
de Loera, Judith (Lluvia)
Giannoukakou-Leontsini, Ifigeneia (*)
González Hurtado, Gustavo
Horra, Alfons
Jara, Mauricio
Pelegrí, Josep Lluís (*)
Plaza, Miguel "Aua"
Prats, Albert
Puigdefabregas, Joan
Sánchez Barroso, Bárbara
Sanz Yus, Diego
Sartori, Ilaria
Scianca, Gaia
Tewes, Emily
Zoeller, Victoria
Zoghbi, Jade

(*) Corresponding authors: Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC), blue-genes@icm.csic.es

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
1.1. Linking the Blue Genes Retreat to Mission Ocean and Waters	4
2. Activities	6
2.1. Day One: Building Synergies and Group Cohesion	6
Morning Activity: Icebreakers and Connections	7
Questions and Reflections	7
Mid-Morning: Presentations and Creative Exchanges	8
Trio Interviews and Mapping Interests	8
Afternoon Session	9
Turning Ideas into Action	10
2.2 Day Two: Planning of the Enbluement Event	12
Sketching the Event	13
Afternoon Discussion: Further Details of the Enbluement Event	14
2.3. Day Three: Future Vision and Planning	15
3. April Event Planning: Enbluement - A Sensory Celebration	17
4. Next Steps	18
5. Retreat Outcomes	19
5.1 Blue Genes: A Collective Path Forward	19
5.2 General Proposals	19
7. Conclusion: A Future of Collaboration	22
7.1 Key Takeaways	23

1. Introduction

The Blue Genes Retreat, held on February 16-18, 2024, was an interdisciplinary event dedicated to explore the human relationship with the Ocean. It gathered over 25 scientists, artists, activists, and community leaders at the Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles, Girona, Spain.

The primary goal was to explore how an artistic-scientific dialogue can transform into tangible, impactful ocean preservation projects, hence co-creating solutions that would align with the objectives of the EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030 (hereafter Mission Ocean and Waters).

A specific output of this retreat was the strategic planning of the "Enbluement" event, a satellite event of the 2024 Un Ocean Decade Conference, scheduled for April 2024. This event would seek to blend artistic expression with scientific understanding, aiming to create emotional and intellectual connections to ocean conservation.

1.1. Linking the Blue Genes Retreat to Mission Ocean and Waters

The main goal of Blue Genes is to empower individuals and communities towards the restoration and protection of the marine ecosystems through the intersection of art and science. With this objective in mind, the retreat included group discussions, workshops, and participatory activities aimed at exploring and co-designing social innovation practices that can tackle pollution, biodiversity loss, and climate impacts, in line with the EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

The retreat also provided an opportunity to explore participatory governance mechanisms and deliberative democracy through open dialogue sessions, which allow citizens to engage in conversations about sustainable ocean preservation actively. Furthermore, the proposed projects, like the Enbluement event, align with the Mission's goal of raising ocean literacy, fostering a more profound emotional connection between citizens and marine life.

The planned event "Enbluement: connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean" (hereafter Enbluement event) and subsequent projects embody the Mission's commitment towards citizen engagement. In this event, participants will merge scientific knowledge with emotional resonance, fostering a collective sense of responsibility for the ocean. Through collaborative, creative initiatives, the retreat contributes to the Mission's goals of increasing ocean literacy, raising awareness, and empowering citizens to take part in marine ecosystem restoration by 2030.

The first Blue Genes workshop, a one-day event held in December 2023, brought together scientists, artists, activists, and community leaders. The objective of this event was to establish an in-person first exploratory contact that would allow participants to form action-research groups, prioritize synergies, and create a shared vision for ocean preservation. By blending art, science, and environmental education, the event sought to transform dialogue into tangible projects. The central objective was to explore how science-art initiatives may positively promote environmental awareness and foster actions toward a harmonious relationship with the ocean.

This second in-person workshop of the Blue Genes community brought together 26 individuals, including artists and scientists, in a three-day retreat at the Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles, Girona, Spain. The objective of this retreat was to build on the previous December in-person meeting so as to co-create a community project focused on establishing a new egalitarian relationship with Nature that emphasizes ocean protection and biodiversity. Additionally, the workshop outlined the program and content of "Enbluement: Connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean," an upcoming satellite event scheduled for April 9, 2024, in Barcelona as part of the UN Ocean Decade Conference. Outcomes included the strategic planning for the satellite event and plans for future activities.

This retreat was structured around the following objectives:

-
1. Creating Action-Research Groups: Encourage collaboration between disciplines to transform ideas into actionable research and projects.
 2. Fostering Synergies: Promote interaction between participants to cultivate synergies that would drive creative and scientific initiatives.
 3. Blending Art and Science: Explore how artistic expression can amplify scientific understanding, bridging the emotional and intellectual connection to the ocean.

The guiding line was that an interdisciplinary and intersectoral approximation to the ocean, as a central and essential element in our lives, can foster connections that inspire societal changes.

2. Activities

The Blue Genes Retreat was guided by a dedicated facilitator who skillfully orchestrated the flow of activities, ensuring a cohesive experience for all participants. While the facilitator provided structure and guidance, the retreat emphasized community-driven contributions, with several activities initiated and led by the participants themselves.

This collaborative approach allowed the group to blend facilitated structure with organic, peer-led creativity, promoting a dynamic environment where diverse voices shaped the retreat's outcomes.

2.1. Day One: Building Synergies and Group Cohesion

Trio interviews were conducted to identify each participant's strengths, interests, and potential collaborations, with these insights mapped out visually to guide future partnerships. By the end of the day, several interdisciplinary project ideas had already begun to take shape, rooted in the shared vision of fostering a deeper human connection to the ocean.

Morning Activity: Icebreakers and Connections

The participants engaged in a series of playful exercises to dissolve formalities and begin building group cohesion. These interactions quickly turned into moments of genuine connection. The participants grouped into clusters of four and seven, performing simple, yet powerful physical actions like walking arm-in-arm or connecting heels. The laughter that filled the space during these moments laid the foundation for deeper conversations to follow.

The activity shifted into more structured groupings, where the participants shared their connection to the ocean. From artists to scientists, a common thread emerged: a shared passion for the sea. This moment emphasized that despite the very diverse disciplines, the group was united by a single purpose—to explore how their combined work could make a difference for the ocean. As participants spoke, it became evident that despite their diverse backgrounds—students, artists, scientists, activists—there was a shared love for the ocean. Some participants, like the freedivers, spoke about their direct experiences with the sea, while others, like painters and musicians, described how the ocean inspired their work.

Questions and Reflections

1. *"What do we like about the ocean?"* – A key question that sparked conversations about personal connections to marine life.
2. *"How did you come to this retreat?"* – Participants reflected on their varied paths, with stories ranging from academic interests in marine sciences to artistic inspirations drawn from the sea's vastness.

Despite the interdisciplinary nature of the group, a common fascination for the Ocean became clear as the central unifying force, and a collective energy emerged that would drive the rest of the event. This activity demonstrated the power of dialogue in fostering unity across diverse fields.

Mid-Morning: Presentations and Creative Exchanges

A series of presentations followed, allowing participants to introduce their backgrounds and explore potential synergies. A wide variety of expertise was represented:

- *Biologists and oceanographers* discussed their research on marine ecosystems and biodiversity.
- *Musicians and filmmakers* shared how sound and visuals could communicate the beauty and fragility of the ocean.
- *Philosophers and physicists* offered insights into the interconnectedness of all life forms, highlighting the importance of shifting humanity's perception of nature.

“I have found my place in the world,” one participant remarked, capturing the feeling of belonging that many others expressed as they spoke about their connection to the ocean.

Trio Interviews and Mapping Interests

The morning activity transitioned into the first structured exercise: trio interviews. Here, we interviewed one another with three core questions:

- What do I offer?
- What are my interests?
- What am I looking for?

These questions were designed to help participants identify their strengths, passions, and goals for the event. The answers were mapped out visually on a giant mind map, which displayed the group's diverse interests and potential synergies. By clustering these on the board, it became clear who shared similar goals or complementary expertise.

The exercise fostered deeper understanding and encouraged participants to consider who they wanted to collaborate with for each specific project.

This mind map became a living document throughout the retreat, evolving as people added more ideas. It also served as a guide for building partnerships across disciplines, from biologists to oceanographers, musicians, filmmakers, philosophers, and more.

The diversity of voices was an incredible asset, enabling many conversations that spanned creative thinking.

Afternoon Session

Participants were then invited to reflect on the key questions that would drive the rest of the event:

- What topics interest me?
- Who should I talk to about these topics?
- What projects do I want to promote?
- Is what I propose feasible?

These questions marked the transition from theoretical conversation to actionable collaboration. Participants began to form smaller groups based on shared interests, and the first synergies started to emerge.

Turning Ideas into Action

In this session, the focus shifted from introductions to real project development. Participants were invited to reflect on their work, exploring new ways to collaborate. A key question that emerged was: Which projects can we initiate together that align with the mission of Blue Genes?

This moment marked the birth of several exciting project ideas, grounded on the belief that by blending art and science, Blue Genes could create experiences that would change how people perceive the ocean.

Proposed topics included:

- ❖ **Visionary Film Project:** A project aimed at setting environmental topics discussed at ICM into motion through film. The goal was to move people emotionally rather than simply convince them through logic.
- ❖ **Oceanic Myths and Legends:** A proposal to enhance humanity's relationship with the ocean by fostering an Oceanic Culture. This would involve comparing myths and legends about the sea from different cultures and linking them to contemporary issues like marine contamination.
- ❖ **CuadrArte Initiative:** A concept to visualize Mediterranean ecological, social, and economic conflicts within a 1x1 quadrant frame. This installation would serve as an educational tool to illustrate complex marine issues in an accessible way.
- ❖ **Sensory Pathway:** A sensory experience inviting participants to walk barefoot on different types of sand, listen to sounds from various beaches, and physically experience the textures of the sea. This interactive workshop aimed to deepen the connection with the ocean through senses.
- ❖ **Firsthand Sea Experience:** A project promoting firsthand ocean experiences for children, allowing them to engage with the sea through direct, sensory interactions in schools and community spaces.
- ❖ **Ocean Art Festival:** A vision to create an Ocean Art Festival in Barcelona, inspired by Hawaiian events, where every artistic piece would link to local oceanic issues. The festival would blend talks, documentaries, concerts, and exhibitions, all centered around the ocean.
- ❖ **Toolbox for Artistic Interventions:** An ambitious proposal to build a toolbox of artistic methods for addressing ecological and social issues through art. This framework would enable artists and scientists to collaborate on future projects.

- ❖ **Identity and Narrative Building:** A proposal emphasizing the importance of establishing a clear identity and narrative for the community. This would include creating a mission and vision to unite participants and extend their reach to broader audiences, including building networks within the 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference.
- ❖ **Sound and Visual Harmony:** A project focusing on how soundscapes and visual art could coexist to represent the ocean's complexities and encourage public engagement.
- ❖ **Community Empowerment Initiative:** A focus on empowering the community to become an independent entity capable of mobilizing resources and engaging wider audiences.

Participants left the day with renewed excitement, already thinking about how to transform these ideas into actionable projects.

2.2 Day Two: Planning of the Enbluement Event

The second day opened with a serene meditation session on the beach, led by one of the participants. With the gentle sound of waves and the soft morning light setting the atmosphere, participants were guided through a series of breathing and mindfulness exercises. This reflective practice encouraged them to ground themselves in the present moment and reconnect participants with the core themes of ocean conservation and interdisciplinary collaboration. By fostering a sense of calm and focus, the session set an introspective tone that helped participants approach the day's tasks with clarity and renewed energy. With this foundation, they transitioned into the creative and collaborative process of planning the Enbluement event, feeling more connected to their purpose and to one another.

Sketching the Event

The initial proposal for the Enbluement event was a two-part celebration:

1. **Part One:** A workshop for artists and influencers, where ideas would be shared on how to raise awareness about the ocean's critical role in sustaining life.
2. **Part Two:** A public participatory event in Barcelona's Charles Darwin Square. This would feature a 90-minute choreography of music, imagery, silence, and motion, designed to evoke an emotional connection to the ocean. This sensory experience would highlight the beauty and fragility of marine ecosystems.

The Enbluement event aimed to blend art and science, emphasizing empathy for the ocean. The concept was centered around the idea that *we are all ocean*, and the event sought to bridge the gap between rational understanding and emotional connection.

The participants were divided into several working groups, each focused on refining one or two project proposals. For 30 minutes, these groups brainstormed on how to make their ideas feasible. The session was framed by a few key questions:

- What are the key elements of this project?
- How can we ensure this project serves the mission of Blue Genes?
- Who are the stakeholders, and what resources do we need?

At the end of the session, each group presented their refined ideas. The energy in the room was palpable, as projects that had once been abstract concepts were now taking shape as actionable plans. Each group offered unique insights, but there was a clear unifying theme: the ocean as both muse and message.

Afternoon Discussion: Further Details of the Enbluement Event

In the afternoon, participants continued to refine the details of the Enbluement event. Ideas included:

- One participant suggested using the outdoor space as an extension of the auditorium, allowing for roundtable discussions inside and creative, sensory experiences outside.
- Another participant proposed using art to deliver an *activist message*, creating a “tide of emotions” through dance, music, and installations.
- A third participant suggested incorporating performances using fishing nets, which would evoke powerful emotions as participants engaged with these symbols of marine life and human impact.

The group debated the balance between scientific content and emotional engagement, ultimately agreeing that the event should blend both approaches, in order to reach a wider audience.

The group also proposed a drumming activity, where participants would be immersed in a sonic and visual experience mimicking the ebb and flow of the tides. The group envisioned this experience ending at Plaza Charles Darwin where the energy would gradually slow. A dance performance, called “shoal of fish”, would guide the audience into inner meditation, followed by resonant music to deepen the experience. The event would conclude around the BlueWave Alliance sculpture, allowing participants to reflect before engaging with the coral installation and information panels.

2.3. Day Three: Future Vision and Planning

The morning began with an active soundscape listening exercise led by a participant, who guided the participants on a beach walk while engaging in the activity, which included using hydrophones to explore marine sounds.

After this activity, several groups were formed, each to reflect on a quite different topic. Another participant facilitated a collaborative painting workshop called “The Blue Genes Chain”, where four participants joined him to create a shared artwork.

A group gathered for an ideation session focused on “Cuardarte”, a project concept. Another one created a space for dialogue, hosting a debate on the theme of contradiction. These reflections were brought to the plenary where each group shared their insights, leading to a larger, collective discussion.

In the latter part of the morning, the assembly turned their attention to the upcoming “Enbluement” event scheduled for April. Participants worked collaboratively to finalize plans, ensuring that each proposed project had a clear direction and concrete planning, setting a solid foundation for a successful event.

3. April Event Planning: Enbluement - A Sensory Celebration

The “Enbluement” event emerged as a centerpiece for Blue Genes’ public engagement. The concept of merging scientific knowledge with sensory experiences was strengthened during this session, with several interactive components planned:

- Participatory chore
- Interactive path: A curated path where participants could engage with ocean-related soundscapes, visual art, and tactile experiences, each designed to deepen their connection to marine environments.

The group was committed to ensuring that this event would not only raise awareness but would also inspire participants to take action in their own lives. Discussions around the logistics of the event also included plans for media coverage, community involvement, and funding opportunities.

4. Next Steps

The group agreed on the need to identify the coming steps:

- Before April: Update the website with fresh photos and content, preparing for the year's activities.
- April – August: Workshops defined by the community, for the community. Research continues, and Ladislav will explore a community-focused workshop.
- September – October: Determine how we organize ourselves and secure financing, ensuring Blue Genes' independence and sustainability.

The retreat ended on a high note, with each participant reaffirming their commitment to the collective vision of Blue Genes: a multidisciplinary community working to reconnect humanity with the ocean through creative, participatory projects.

5. Retreat Outcomes

Blue Genes: A Collective Path Forward

The heart of Blue Genes lies in maintaining momentum. Continuity is key—we will keep gathering, and following up on every step, ensuring that each project is collectively considered. We will also formalize, structuring ourselves as a civil association, providing a stable legal foundation to support the community long-term goals.

As the retreat drew to its end, we turned our attention to the long-term vision for the Blue Genes community. Several participants proposed the formalization of Blue Genes as a civil association, facilitating the participation in open call for proposals and the pursuit of grants.

Ideas for sustaining the momentum included:

- Painting workshops and co-creation sessions that bring together art and science.
- Visits to marine environments, grounding our work in firsthand experiences with the ocean.
- Training programs for women scientists, ensuring inclusivity and diversity in our initiatives.
- Exhibitions, such as underwater photography and light festivals, will blend art and marine exploration to engage the community.
- Meetings and outings to Nature will foster a collaborative spirit and connection to the natural world.
- Creating an online platform to share resources, updates, and opportunities for collaboration.
- Establishing the Blue Genes identity through a clear narrative that combines artistic expression with scientific inquiry.

General Proposals

Looking ahead, Blue Genes aims to host Barcelona Sea and Art Days, creating a space for science and art to meet. This event would bring together collaborators, expand our networks, and establish platforms for art installations in museums. By doing so, we aim to reach beyond our immediate circles and inspire new audiences.

These proposals are not just ideas—they are seeds meant to grow within our community. Every voice matters, by blending science and art the community hopes to inspire real change.

Some of the suggestions shared include:

- A proposal to develop new ways of representing the ocean through art and science, with a dedicated team to guide future projects.
- Encouraging each participant to bring their unique strengths to the table—whether it's crafting narratives, securing funding, or fostering creative projects.

One participant shared a vision of Blue Genes becoming a platform to empower members, helping them develop independent initiatives. Another suggested strengthening our presence within global platforms like the UNODC, ensuring that our mission and vision resonate far and wide. There were also calls to embrace the diversity of perspectives in our group, with suggestions to form a team dedicated to shaping a clear, collective identity.

Participants self-challenged by asking, “Are we truly innovative?” and reminded us to create open spaces for reflection, learning, and growth. Inspired by Dalí, one idea focused on analyzing our work through the lens of diversity, convergence, and synergy—mirroring the collaborative approach of art and science. Others emphasized the need for creativity to continually evolve by learning from and collaborating with other projects.

6. Conclusion: A Future of Collaboration

The Blue Genes Retreat successfully brought together a diverse group of participants to form new synergies and collaborations. By fostering dialogue between disciplines, the retreat generated a range of creative and scientific projects designed to inspire ocean conservation. The group left with a clear plan for the Enbluement event and a commitment to continue working together on future projects. Through creative expression, scientific knowledge, and community collaboration, this group has the potential to inspire lasting changes for the ocean. As we look toward the upcoming April event and beyond, the collective energy and dedication to ocean conservation and creative expression will continue to drive us forward.

The Blue Genes retreat demonstrated a clear alignment with the objectives of Mission Ocean and Waters. Through participatory workshops and collaborative innovation, the retreat fostered a space for deliberative democracy and social innovation practices. The creative proposals, like the Enbluement event, are prime examples of how Blue Genes is contributing to the Mission goal of raising ocean literacy and engaging citizens in marine preservation efforts. By creating spaces where participants from different backgrounds can contribute to ocean conservation, the retreat reflects the Mission's emphasis on empowering citizens to take part in the protection of our seas and waters.

Looking ahead, Blue Genes will continue to develop participatory governance models, engaging more citizens in marine conservation, in alignment with the Mission Ocean and Waters 2030 goals. Through ongoing workshops, art festivals, and public campaigns, the collective will push the boundaries of social innovation, ensuring that the ocean remains a central focus for community-driven action and environmental preservation.

“Blue Genes is more than just a community—it’s a movement. And this retreat was just the beginning.”

As the Blue Genes community moves forward, key goals include formalizing as a civil association, securing funding, and expanding collaborations. Future activities will continue to merge artistic and scientific perspectives, with a focus on public engagement and awareness-raising initiatives.

Key Takeaways

1. **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:**

The event demonstrated the power of bringing together diverse disciplines. The group's synergy was evident in the range of projects proposed, blending art, science, and environmental advocacy to create impactful initiatives.

2. **Action Through Creativity:**

Creativity was recognized as a key driver of environmental action. Projects like sensory films and experiences showed how artistic expression can communicate the urgency of ocean conservation in a way that words alone cannot.

3. **Empathy for the Ocean:**

The concept of *empathy* was central to the Enbluement event. By merging sensory experiences with scientific understanding, participants aimed to foster a deep emotional connection to the ocean, which would inspire the public to take action

4. **Community and Continuity:**

A sense of community was built over the three days, with participants expressing a desire to continue collaborating on future projects. Discussions about forming a civil association and securing funding were key to ensuring the longevity of these efforts

Acknowledgments are due to the PREP4BLUE project, funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957

We sincerely thank Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles for their generous support in providing the space for the retreat.

We appreciate Elisabetta Broglio for beautifully capturing moments throughout the event with her talented photography.

We also extend our gratitude to Aua from SomPosidonia for their valuable guidance, which contributed to productive discussions and collaboration.

Contact

blue-genes@icm.csic.es

Annex K. The Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET) Program

THE OCEAN AS A COMMON LANGUAGE FOR COASTAL COMMUNITIES

OCEAN CITIES NETWORK

an international network of cities in harmony with the marine environment

THE SCIENCE WE NEED FOR THE CITIES AND THE OCEAN WE WANT: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH THE UNITED NATIONS OCEAN DECADE.

HIGH-LEVEL OBJECTIVE OF THE PROGRAMME:

Transform ocean towns and cities into communities that are permeable to the marine environment, aiming to regenerate the coastline as much as possible and enhancing a harmonious connection between the community, the land, and the ocean through the mind (science), heart (art), and soul (awareness).

Related Activities:

- October: Ocean Cities Month (Join Us!).
- Toolkits for City Councils.
- Recommendation reports.
- Innovation pitches for new enterprises and start-ups in the blue economy.
- Blue Schools "Train the Trainer" kits.
- More human harbours.
- Communications campaigns.
- Citizen science activities.
- Open debates.
- Art exhibitions and performances.
- Scientific symposia in relevant international conferences.
- Peer reviewed publications.

JOIN US!
WWW.OCEAN-CITIES.ORG

INTRODUCING THE OCEAN CITIES NETWORK (OC-NET):

- Promoting bottom-up collaboration among citizens and stakeholders.
- Endorsed by UNESCO for science-based policies.
- Contributing to the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030".
- 10-year program transforming coastlines worldwide.

BOTTOM UP: PARTNERS AND ALLIANCES:

24 MEMBERS (UP TO NOW)

- 2 coordinators (ICM-CSIC and UTM-CSIC).
- 12 official partners directly involved in.
- 2 cities networks creating the connection with cities councils.
- 1 local council directly involved in as partner.
- 7 collaborators as allies.

- Centro de Investigación Científica y de Educación Superior de Ensenada (CiCESE, MX).
- Centro de Investigaciones del Mar y de la Atmósfera Instituto Franco Argentino para el estudio del Clima y sus Impactos (CIMA, AR).
- Oceans & Atmosphere University of Queensland (CSIRO, AU).
- Universidad de Concepción (CL).
- Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas y Costeras (INVEMAR, CO).
- Universidad de Antioquia (CO).
- Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC, ES).
- Marine and Environmental Science Centre University of Coimbra (MARE,PT).
- University of Cape Town (MARIS, ZA).
- National Institute of Oceanography Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR, INDIA).
- Università degli studi di Genova (UNIGE, IT).
- Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM, IT).
- Tokyo University of Marine Science and Tecnology (TUMSAT, JP).
- Barcelona Local Council.
- MedCities.
- C40 CITIES.
- Bau Design College (BAU, ES).
- ECSA European Citizen Science Association.
- INGENIO CSIC-UPV (ES).
- La Fura dels Baus (ES).
- Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SNZ, IT).
- SEA-EU Thee European University of the Sea.

Annex L. Summary of OC-NET Activities during its First Two Years

Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET)

Summary of activities from June 2021 to May 2023

● The programme at a glance

Ocean Cities is a network of towns committed with a harmonious integration of the urban ocean in the mind, senses and economy of coastal communities. The program aims at enhancing a full connection between citizens and the sea, raising awareness on the essential role that marine ecosystems play in our daily lives and promoting science-based policies and prevention, mitigation and remediation measures against ecosystem degradation and climate change.

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
SCOPE	The Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET) programme involves all basins with special focus in the Mediterranean Sea.
CHALLENGES	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Understand and beat marine pollution. 2 Protect and restore ecosystems and biodiversity. 4 Develop a sustainable and equitable ocean economy. 5 Unlock ocean-based solutions to climate change. 7 Expand the Global Ocean Observing System. 9 Skills, knowledge and technology for all. 10 Change humanity's relationship with the ocean.
AXES	Fostering synergies and collaborative projects in three axes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health: Healthy marine and coastal ecosystems, enhancing individual and collective resilience under the global health approach (challenges 1, 2, 7, 9). ● Culture: Ocean literacy and artistic experiences, incorporating traditional and innovative territorial and ecological knowledge (challenges 2, 5, 9, 10). ● Justice: Science-based transformative policies, supporting a fair transition towards local and global sustainability (challenges 4, 5, 10).
PARTNERS	24 members: 2 research centres (ICM-CSIC and UTM-CSIC) as coordinators. 15 research centres as official partners. 2 city networks that create the connection with city councils. 1 city council directly involved as partner. 7 stakeholder organisations as members of the alliance.
DURATION*	Start Date: 08/06/2021 End Date: 07/06/2025

*OC-net intends to accomplish the 10 years of the Ocean Decade.

This bottom-up collaboration among the coastal society – local administration, private stakeholders, research centres and civil organisations – will set up a participatory and inclusive process aimed at the co-design and co-delivery of science-based initiatives that will change how coastal citizens perceive, interact and evolve with the ocean, and will strengthen the resilience of the coastal settings at social, economic and environmental levels.

With the goal of generating dialogues among scientific, policy and societal actors, OC-NET has identified three axes – health, culture and justice – to establish working groups and develop projects, collaborations and events. All actions settled within these three axes will emerge within the framework of a community-based approach, involving stakeholders, research centres and civil society, building upon local experiences to drive regional and global initiatives

- **Health:** Conceiving actions towards healthy marine and coastal ecosystems, enhancing individual and collective resilience. This axis relates closely to the Ocean Decade Challenges 1, 2, 7 and 9, and the associated outcomes. The health axis aims at generating knowledge for innovative monitoring techniques, advancing in an interdisciplinary approach to understand emerging challenges to the health of the coastal system, and proposing prevention, mitigation and remediation measures that consider social, cultural, economic and environmental issues towards an enhanced coastal resilience.
- **Culture (Society):** Fostering ocean literacy and artistic experiences, incorporating traditional and innovative territorial and ecological knowledge. This axis is closely linked to the Ocean Decade Challenges 2, 5, 9 and 10, and the associated outcomes. The culture or society axis aims at Improving the connection of the cities with their coastal systems. Through the building blocks of blue education and capacity, this axis favours an increased understanding of the interactions between cities and the urban ocean.
- **Justice (Policy):** Promoting evidence-based and science-based transformative policies that support a fair transition towards local and global sustainability. This axis is intimately linked with the Ocean Decade Challenges 4, 5 and 10 and the associated outcomes. The justice or policy axis will promote the exchange of experiences and the creation of alliances with both private and public stakeholders.

Work To Do & vision

Local → Regional → Global

Members of OC-NET fall into two categories: **network partners and alliance associates**. Network partners are actively involved in designing, preparing, and executing actions, while alliance associates primarily support dissemination and communication activities.

Coordinator

[Institut de Ciències del Mar \(ICM-CSIC, ES\)](#)
[Unitat de Tecnologia Marina \(UTM-CSIC, ES\)](#)

Partners

[Centro de Investigación Científica y de Educación Superior de Ensenada \(CICESE, MX\)](#)
[Centro de Investigaciones del Mar y de la Atmosfera Instituto Franco Argentino para el estudio del Clima y sus Impactos \(CIMA, AR\)](#)
[Oceans & Atmosphere University of Queensland \(CSIRO, AU\)](#)
[Universidad de Concepción \(CL\)](#)
[Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas y Costeras \(INVEMAR, CO\)](#)
[Universidad de las Palmas de Gran Canaria \(ULPGC, ES\)](#)
[Marine and Environmental Science Centre University of Coimbra \(MARE,PT\)](#)
[University of Cape Town \(MARIS, ZA\)](#)
[National Institute of Oceanography Council of Scientific & Industrial Research \(CSIR, INDIA\)](#)
[Università degli studi di Genova \(UNIGE, IT\)](#)
[Università Politecnica delle Marche \(UNIVPM, IT\)](#)
[Tokyo University of Marine Science and Technology \(TUMSAT, JP\)](#)
[Universidad de Antioquia \(CO\)](#)

[Barcelona Local Council](#)
[Medcities](#)
[C40](#)

Alliance

[Bau Design College \(BAU, ES\)](#)
[ECSA European Citizen Science Association](#)
[INGENIO CSIC-UPV \(ES\)](#)
[Las Furas dels Baus \(ES\)](#)
[Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn \(SNZ, IT\)](#)
[SEA-EU Thee European University of the Sea](#)
[Universidad de Antioquia \(CO\)](#)

Within the program, cities are represented by the Barcelona local council, as well as two city networks: MedCities and C40. MedCities is an organisation that includes 63 cities in the Mediterranean basin, coordinated by a secretariat based in Spain, with a focus on sustainability. The C40 coalition is a global alliance of 95 cities dedicated to seeking and implementing solutions against climate change, with the coordination currently held by Barcelona.

● The 2021-2023 programme activities

The list of actions presented next represent the principal actions carried out in the frame of OC-NET for its two first years of life. Internal meetings within the coordination and among partners are not included in this list.

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
Coordination	<p>Assemblies with all OC-NET members (once per semester).</p> <p>Launch up of the website (October, 2021) www.ocean-cities.org</p> <p>Press communication for social media and preparation of presentations and posters at events.</p>
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordination of a session in the conference <i>An Ocean of Values. The 5th Community Workshop</i> of the IOC-UNESCO Ocean Best Practices System (September 20-24, 2021 - Online). ● Coordination of two Ocean Decade laboratories, promoted by Germany, after the Ocean Decade kick-off on the objectives of the decade, <i>Laboratory A Predicted Ocean Minka Project</i>, (September 16, 2021; <i>Towards a clean and sustainable Mediterranean Sea</i> (November 18, 2021). ● Coordination of a session in the II International Forum on Marine Litter and Circular Economy. <i>Hands on circular solutions for healthy oceans</i> (May 16-20, 2022. Seville, Spain). ● Coordination <i>Side event on Science Toward Sustainable Ocean UNOC22</i> (June 27-July 1, 2022. Lisbon, Portugal). ● Ocean Cities month in Barcelona (Spain) (October 2022): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Organisation of 2 round tables on Gender perspective in coastal management (October 1, 2022). ○ Blue School debate with teachers (October 6, 2022). ○ Round table on The sea and Sustainability (October 7, 2022). ○ One workshop on Plankton as the Driving Force of Life (October 8, 2022). ● OC-NET joined the EU mission Charter (October, 2022). ● OC-NET participated in three of the EU Mission Ocean & Waters launch event: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse, Ireland (January, 2023). ○ EU Mission Forum, Brussels (February, 2023). ○ Mediterranean Lighthouse, Italy (May, 2023). ● Ocean Cities month in Barcelona (Spain) and Antioquia (Colombia) (October 2023): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Activities in both cities during the entire month

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the Plastic Buster CAP Event: Fostering knowledge transfer to tackle marine litter in the Med (April, 2022. Online meeting). • Organization of a round table about Ocean Cities: Dialogues between citizens and the ocean, <i>15th Science Fair</i> (May 28, 2022. Barcelona, Spain). • Oral presentation at <i>Moby Litter III Seminar</i> (July 14, 2022. Ancona, Italy). • Conference Press at the CSIC headquarters for the presentation of the book "The ocean we want: inclusive and transformative ocean science, Pelegrí JL, Gili JM Martín de Albéniz MV (eds) (June 8, 2022. Madrid, Spain). • Oral presentation at the kick-off meeting of the EuroMarine TransOcean working group (<i>Outlook on Transoceanic, Transversal and Transformative International Ocean Programs</i>) (January 19, 2023).
Knowledge products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statement of the Spanish Delegation at UNOC22 – <i>Interactive dialogue 1: Addressing Marine Pollution</i> (June 27, 2022. Lisbon, Portugal). • Publication of a book entitled <i>The ocean we want: inclusive and transformative ocean science</i>, Pelegrí JL, Gili JM Martín de Albéniz MV (eds), Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC Barcelona, (June, 2022). <i>The book had both physical and electronic formats, the latter available in several open sources, including the UN Ocean Decade catalogue: https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000384371</i> • Setup of October as the Ocean Cities month. In the frame of this month, all OC-NET partners will prepare actions (events, seminars, round table, workshop, exhibitions and cultural events) in their own cities. Actions will revolve around one or more of the programme axes. The 2022 edition was a pilot initiative held in Barcelona in collaboration with the city council, the 2023 edition will be held simultaneously in several different cities.
Bottom-Up Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The University of Antioquia (Colombia) has started two coastal erosion projects: PIMECLA, a natural laboratory for mitigating coastal erosion in Antioquia, and Red CoCo, a Citizen Science initiative. These projects are carried out with the support of other two OC-NET partners: ICM and the Universidad de Las Palmas Gran Canaria. • With the support of ICM, the Center for Sea and Atmosphere Research (Argentina) has engaged in impact mitigation and adaptation actions to potential changes in the coastal zone, in collaboration with the Ministry of Science and the Environmental Directorate of the city of Buenos Aires. • With the support of ICM and the University of Gambia, a network of primary and secondary schools is being created, with the central objective of generating knowledge to co-design future solutions to environmental challenges.

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICM-CSIC, the University of Concepción (Chile) and the Redplus Foundation (Chile) are joining forces to address coastal erosion and governance issues in the BioBio region of Chile. • Together with partner institutions from Senegal, Argentina, Colombia and Mexico, ICM-CSIC submitted a proposal to strengthen international collaboration networks. • Ocean Cities, through ICM-CSIC, has supported the multinational company ISDIN to create the BlueWave Ocean Alliance, aimed at conservation and regeneration of coastal and marine ecosystems.

● The 2021-2023 parallel activities

The following list corresponds to actions carried out in the frame of the Ocean Decade where OC-NET, with ICM-CSIC as coordinator, has been involved.

Ocean Cities managed the community of practice (CoP) on Coastal Resilience until February, 2023 (CoP8 – Coastal Ecosystem and Community Resilience).

The main actions developed in the framework of this coordination are the following:

- Coordination of the platform, members and forum.
- Coordination of the CoP8 first meeting. *Community of Practice 8 and coordination of the Meet and Greet* (November 22, 2022).
- Set up of the CoP definition and its objectives by means of a participatory process.
 - i. Definition. The CoP8 is a community of practice under the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, an open space to debate and exchange best practices about coastal areas around the world.
 - ii. Objectives. The following objectives were established, which are currently used by the new version of the CoP that is directly coordinated by DCC:
 - Human interaction and connectivity.
 - Coastal area fragmentation, in terms of socio-economic and environmental perspectives as well as in terms of knowledge and best practices.
 - Engagement of society.
- Set up of the keywords for CoP8
 - I. Engagement and Community: engagement to develop fit-for purpose science, community engagement, proximity, support, synergy, and stakeholder engagement.
 - II. Culture, Awareness and Territory: Cultural heritage, perception and interaction with coastal ocean, archaeology, dissemination, history.

- III. Ocean, Ecosystems and Resilience: Ecosystem health and functioning, coastal ocean, climate change, estuaries, key habitats, wetland conservation link nature and resilience, land-sea connectivity, resilience, knowledge of coastal ocean, human and coastal health, clean ocean.
- IV. Socio Economy and Governance: Sustainable blue growth, usage of new science-based information products for the coasts, socioeconomics, circular and sustainable, marine spatial planning, social and build environment, best practices in coastal area, capacity building.

OC-NET is part of the programme scientific committee of the Collaborative Center on Coastal Resilience led by the University of Bologna. This Decade Collaborative Centre for Coastal Resilience (DCC-CR), based in the University of Bologna, provides support to the Decade Coordination Unit by catalysing and coordinating Decade Actions related to coastal resilience.

As part of the Ocean Decade, the DCC-CR will contribute primarily to Challenge 6: Increase community resilience to ocean hazards. It will do so by supporting endorsed Decade Actions, catalysing new Decade Actions, promoting stakeholder engagement, supporting communication and awareness rising & outreach, facilitating mobilisation of resources, and monitoring & evaluation. Some initial examples are:

- Oral presentation at the kick-off of the DCC-CR, (January 18, 2023. Bologna, Italy).
- Providing support to the DCC-CR in the transition from the CoP-8, including four meetings.
- Participation in the DCC-CR executive committee through an OC-NET partner (the Polytechnic University of Marche, Ancona, Italy).

Annex M. Ocean Cities Month

OCEAN CITIES MONTH

2024-THIRD EDITION!

OceanCities

2021 United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
2030 for Sustainable Development

Institut
de Ciències
del Mar

EXCELENCIA
SEVERO
OCHOA

CSIC

OCEAN CITIES MONTH

2024-THIRD EDITION!

5 CITIES

**16
EVENTS**

**2000
PEOPLE**

Throughout October, Ocean Cities Month united communities, organizations, and institutions worldwide in a global effort to explore our deep connection with the ocean. This month has become a dynamic platform for sharing innovative actions, exchanging valuable knowledge, and sparking meaningful dialogue about the urgent need to preserve and strengthen our relationship with marine ecosystems.

An overview

Argentina

As part of the Anticipating the Flood project, over 200 people participated in workshops to develop a community-based early warning system. This included primary and secondary students, local leaders, and lifeguards working on a monitoring system for the Río de la Plata in Buenos Aires.

Colombia

In Arboletes, Antioquia, working sessions were held with 50 participants to explore a coastal occupation model that balances urban development with marine ecosystem preservation. A virtual workshop strengthened participants' technological capabilities, encouraging active involvement in environmental projects.

Mexico

In Ensenada, Baja California, a bio-barrier was designed to reduce pollution in the Punta Banda estuary by decreasing wastewater discharge. Microplastic studies in Bahía de los Ángeles and Ojo de Liebre Lagoon emphasized the need for protective measures due to contamination in water, sediments, and species like the green sea turtle (*Chelonia mydas*).

Australia

The Sydney Institute of Marine Science participated in the Global Nature Positive Summit, focusing on accelerating nature protection. A tour aboard the Lady Northcott in Sydney Harbour highlighted projects like seahorse breeding and marine ecosystem restoration, underscoring Australia's commitment to conservation and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

Spain

In Barcelona, the "Sea and the City: New Perspectives" talk series explored the connection between blue spaces, public health, and urban sustainability. The Tabaris Museum in El Vendrell hosted a marine biodiversity event, featuring a children's workshop and promoting citizen participation via the MINKA platform, connecting the community with scientific projects.

Argentina

In Argentina, the Center for Ocean and Atmospheric Research of the University of Buenos Aires organized activities as part of the Anticipating the Flood project to develop a community-based early warning system. Over 200 people participated, including 125 primary school students, 60 secondary students, 40 community leaders, and a lifeguard team, collaborating to design a monitoring system for the Río de la Plata. Additionally, 33 community leaders received specialized training in early warning systems.

Training sessions in the Paraná Delta and Buenos Aires focused on the impact of rising sea levels, aiming to improve communities' flood response and preparedness for climate-related risks.

Australia

The Sydney Institute of Marine Science actively participated in the Global Nature Positive Summit, a major international event aimed at accelerating efforts to protect and restore natural ecosystems. The summit brought together experts, policymakers, and organizations to discuss innovative strategies for achieving global conservation goals, with a focus on implementing the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

As part of the event, attendees were invited on a tour aboard the Lady Northcott in Sydney Harbour. The tour highlighted cutting-edge conservation projects led by the institute, such as the captive breeding program for seahorses, which aims to restore populations of the endangered White's seahorse (*Hippocampus whitei*). It also showcased marine ecosystem restoration initiatives, including the revival of underwater habitats like seagrass meadows and kelp forests, vital for biodiversity and climate resilience.

Colombia

In Arboletes, Antioquia, the University of Antioquia organized workshops with 50 participants to explore a coastal development model that balances urban growth with marine ecosystem preservation. The focus was on identifying sustainable urban practices that protect marine habitats while supporting responsible development.

Additionally, a virtual workshop strengthened participants' technological skills, particularly in digital tools for environmental monitoring and project management. This empowered participants to engage in local environmental initiatives, promoting sustainability and conservation in coastal areas.

Mexico

In Ensenada, Baja California, the Center for Scientific Research and Higher Education of Ensenada (CICESE) led efforts to address coastal pollution and marine ecosystem conservation. A bio-barrier was designed to reduce pollution in the Punta Banda estuary by limiting wastewater discharge, aiming to protect the delicate balance of this critical habitat.

Additionally, CICESE conducted microplastic studies in Bahía de los Ángeles and Ojo de Liebre Lagoon. These studies revealed alarming levels of contamination in water, sediments, and marine species, including the green sea turtle (*Chelonia mydas*). The findings underscored the urgent need for protective measures to mitigate the impact of plastic pollution and safeguard these unique ecosystems.

Spain

In Barcelona, the "The Sea and the City: New Perspectives" talk series explored the connection between green spaces, public health, and urban sustainability, highlighting the need to rethink coastal cities' natural boundaries. The Tabaris Museum in El Vendrell also hosted an event on marine biodiversity, featuring a children's workshop and promoting citizen participation through the MINKA platform, linking the community with scientific projects.

JOIN US NEXT YEAR!

OCEAN CITIES MONTH

2025-FOURTH EDITION!

ocean-cities.org

2021 United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Institut
de Ciències
del Mar

EXCELENCIA
SEVERO
OCHOA

CSIC

OceanCities

Annex N. PREP4BLUE Call for Pilot Actions

Prep4Blue pilot activity funding: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

At the recent UN Ocean Decade Conference in Barcelona, Prep4Blue (Funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957) co-organised four official Satellite events dedicated to engaging citizens in activities that work towards achieving the aims of the EU's Mission to Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 (Mission Ocean): Cities with the Ocean – Ocean science for the sustainable development of coastal cities and ports; Empowering science, policy and society through co-design for sustainable ocean development; Diving from local to global ocean literacy: Exploring, sharing and developing successful practices to know, feel and join the living ocean; Enbluement: Connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean.

These four events gathered three types of networks - coastal communities, ocean literacy and Ocean&Arts. To capitalise on the energy and discussions from the events and to catalyse the creation of a Mission Ocean citizen engagement Community of Practice, Prep4Blue is now offering small scale grants for pilot activity funding. Pilot actions should aim at engaging citizens in activities relevant to Mission Ocean, aimed at achieving its targets in terms of citizen engagement, and one or more of its overall objectives. The pilots will facilitate and/or develop success stories by a selected number of networks that could be replicated and/or upscaled in the future.

Selected proposals should aim at citizen engagement and mobilisation towards achieving one or more of Mission Ocean's overall objectives, namely: 1) protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity; 2) prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters; 3) make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular. It should do this in a manner that engages directly with one or more of the Mission's priorities in terms of citizen engagement. These include fostering social inclusion across activities, involving citizens in participatory processes concerning their aquatic resources, and including citizens in ocean literacy initiative; see pages 35 – 36 of the [Mission Ocean implementation plan](#) for a thorough list.

The call for proposals will open on May 22, 2024 and will remain open until June 12, 2024. The total amount available for pilot proposals is 13,500 €, to be distributed in proposals of up to 2,250 € each. All proposing teams will be invited to participate in a series of webinars on methodologies and strategies for citizen engagement with Mission Ocean. These webinars, which are aimed at providing citizen engagement and good participative practice resources, will be carried out in July 2024.

Successful proposals will be notified no later than 26 June 2024 and pilot actions are to be carried out between July 1 and November 30, 2024. Successful proposals will commit to the following: (a) to participate in the webinar series; (b) to implement one or more evaluation tools to assess changes in citizen perception and engagement in alignment with Mission Ocean targets and objectives; (c) to participate in a virtual meeting or equivalent activity addressed to the community of practice (CoP); (d) to present a one-page summary on the progress of the pilot action by October 7, 2024; and (e) to present a final report on the activity no later than November 30, 2024 (maximum 6 pages, following a format to be provided).

Proposals should meet the following eligibility criteria:

- Applicants must represent an NGO, non-profit group or civil organisation.
- Applicants must have taken part in one of Prep4Blue's four Satellite events at the Ocean Decade conference in Barcelona.
- Applicants must have capacity to undertake their pilot activity and deliver their final report by 30 November 2024.

Proposals are to be submitted via the specified Google form, which will include the following information:

- 1- Briefly present your proposal (max 100 words).
- 2- Indicate to which type of network is addressed:
 - a. Coastal and riparian Communities
 - b. Ocean literacy
 - c. Ocean & Arts?
- 3- Briefly explain how your proposal connects to one or more of the Mission objectives (Mission Ocean Implementation plan, page 19), and its citizen engagement target outcomes (Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, page 36) (100 words).
- 4- Describe the methodology/strategy to involve citizens in the activity. Proposals that include co-design with participants, direct democratic elements and/or other deeply participative elements will be deemed strong (max 200 words).
- 5- Briefly enumerate the specific proposed outcomes (up to 3).
- 6- Briefly explain how you will assess the impact of these outcomes. (50 words)
- 7- Explain how you envision the proposal long-term impact and/or sustainability (200 words).
- 8- Briefly indicate how the awarded funding will be spent.
- 9- Explain your communication strategy within the selected type of network and beyond (100 words).
- 10- Briefly describe your previous experience (indicate links when appropriate) (100 words).

Evaluation criteria (100 points)

The scoring scale will be based on the quality and potential impact of the proposal, according to the following criteria:

1. Alignment with the Mission objectives: 10 points
2. Methodology & working plan: 10 points
3. Participative and inclusive strategy: 10 points
4. Specific outcomes: 10 points
5. Sustainability in time: 10 points
6. Impact assessment: 10 points
7. Budget: 10 points
8. Outreach: 10 points
9. Innovative aspects of the proposal: 10 points
10. Previous experience of the applicant: 10 points

Annex O. List of Proposals Submitted to the PREP4BLUE Call for Pilot Actions

List of Proposals Submitted to the PREP4BLUE Call for Pilot Actions

Complete list of proposals received for the Call of Pilot Actions (the name of the coordinating institution is omitted for data protection issues). Many of the proposals could fit in more than one category but, for simplicity, here they are classified into the three categories: Coastal and Riparian Communities; Ocean & Arts; Ocean Literacy.

Code	Title	Country	Category
P4B_CR_01	Trash Talk into Further Actions	Italy and Kenya (collaboration)	Coastal and Riparian Communities
P4B_CR_02	Citizen Science for Cetaceans in the Valencian Community	Spain	Coastal and Riparian Communities
P4B_CR_03	Freshwater Activities for Mission Ocean Goals	Italy	Coastal and Riparian Communities
P4B_CR_04	Citizens of Surf	United Kingdom and Portugal (pilot locations: North Devon Surf Reserve, UK, and Arrifana, Portugal)	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_05	Empowering Citizens to Put Ocean and Marine Protection at the Center of the Debate	Spain	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_06	Highlight local and sustainable initiatives in coastal communities through cruise ships	Spain	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_07	Raising awareness of the basking shark (<i>Cetorhinus maximus</i>) among stakeholders in the northwest Mediterranean basin	Spain	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_08	Creation and management of a participatory forum for young people in the context of the marine restoration project in Portocolom Bay (RESHABAY)	Spain	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_09	Creation of a Community Resilience Plan for Youghal, a Coastal Community at Risk of Coastal Flooding	Ireland	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_10	Regenerative Seaweed Aquaculture and Community Collaboration	Ireland	Coastal and riparian Communities

P4B_CR_11	Water Exploration and Connection through the Dargle River and Bray Harbour	Ireland	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_12	Sea Synergy Oyster Project: Restoration of the Native Oyster in the Portmagee Channel	Ireland	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_CR_13	Enhancing Community Engagement with the Coastline through Citizen Science	Spain	Coastal and riparian Communities
P4B_OA_01	Intergenerational Marine Conservation through Upcycling	Spain	Ocean & Arts
P4B_OA_02	Collaborative Ocean Giant Puzzle Workshop	Spain	Ocean & Arts
P4B_OA_03	Sustainable Coastal Futures	Germany	Ocean & Arts
P4B_OL_01	Introducing Regenerative Small-Scale Fisheries and Tourism for Sama-Bajau Fishers in Wakatobi National Park, Indonesia	Indonesia	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_02	ECOP Programme Guide on Ocean Literacy	Italy	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_03	Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship Training Course for Early Career Ocean Professionals	Not specified in the provided information (likely based on the ECOP Programme's global reach)	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_04	Interview Series on Key Conservation Themes in the EU Mission Lighthouse Areas	Not specified (One Planet Conservation Awareness is a volunteer-led organization with a global reach)	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_05	OCEAN CITIZEN Project - Citizen Science Workshop for Dive Centers in Tenerife	Spain	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_06	ENGAGE Lab - Research Valorization for Ocean Literacy Campaigns	Italy, Philippines	Ocean Literacy

P4B_OL_07	Amazonian Oceanic Dialogues Series: Engaging Sectors in Discussing the Amazon, Ocean, and Climate	Brazil	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_08	Environmental Education and Ocean Literacy for Youth in Coastal Brazil Through Scuba Diving	Brazil	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_09	Environmental Education and Ocean Literacy for Youth in Coastal Brazil Through Scuba Diving	Brazil	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_10	Community Education Program on Mangrove Protection and Conservation	Not specified	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_11	IOLN Marine Education Student Engagement Meeting	Ireland	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_12	Baltic Hackathon	Estonia	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_13	Cuan Beo Source to Sea Education Programme	Ireland	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_14	Ocean Observation Training and Support in Colombia	Colombia	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_15	The first edition of the Mini-Festival of Marine Citizen Science	Portugal	Ocean Literacy
P4B_OL_16	"Us: The Sea of Sounds"	Not explicitly mentioned in the description, but the associated institution and producer are linked to Prague (Czech Republic)	Ocean Literacy

Annex P1. Self-Evaluation Report for PA1: Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship Training Course

PREP4BLUE Pilot activity reporting template: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report

Enhancing, Co-designing, and Adapting the “ Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship” Training Course Content

ECOP Programme/ Ocean Literacy Task Team

Project Duration:

19/07/2024 to 30/11/2024

Project Coordinator:

Karina M. Higa

Facilitator and Communication Coordinator:

Laura Khatib

Collaborators/Partners:

Guardians of the Blue

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report	1
Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction	3
2 Methodology and results	4
3 Implementation	5
4 Impact assessment	5
5 Lessons Learned	6
6 Conclusion and Recommendations	7
7 Bibliography	7
8 ANNEX Stakeholder list	
PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper	15

Executive Summary

The "Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship" pilot project aimed to empower Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs) by addressing critical gaps in science communication, policy advocacy, and collaborative engagement. This initiative, developed under the EU-funded Prep4Blue framework, focused on equipping ECOPs with the skills necessary to navigate the complexities of ocean governance and engage in impactful policy processes. The project's primary objectives included building a tailored training curriculum, raising awareness about the importance of civic participation in ocean governance, and providing ECOPs with opportunities for real-world policy engagement.

Key achievements of the pilot include a regional knowledge gap and practice assessment to support the development of a region-specific course programme co-designed by ECOPs and stakeholders, and the strengthening of partnerships with key organizations. These outcomes have laid the foundation for a global, sustainable community of blue citizens committed to driving meaningful policy change.

Looking ahead, it is recommended to expand the outreach and impact of the initiative by standardizing the course programme co-design process for replication in other regions, enhancing stakeholder engagement through a targeted communication strategy, and fostering continued collaboration through capacity-building initiatives focused on science communication. These steps will help ensure the sustainability and scalability of ocean literacy efforts and the continued empowerment of ECOPs as advocates for sustainable ocean management.

1 Introduction

Ocean literacy is essential for fostering informed and engaged blue citizens who can advocate for sustainable ocean management and influence policy effectively. However, Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs) face significant challenges in bridging science, society, and policy. These challenges include limited skills in policy advocacy, communication, inclusive engagement strategies, and understanding participation mechanisms in policy making. Addressing these gaps is critical to empower ECOPs as catalysts for sustainable ocean governance.

The EU-funded pilot project "*Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship*", developed under PREP4BLUE by the Ocean Literacy Task Team (OLTT), established a foundation by equipping ECOPs with skills in science communication, policy advocacy, and collaborative engagement. Building on this groundwork, the current initiative expands this work through a comprehensive three-component framework:

- 1. Training Course Tailored to Regional Needs**
A course programme developed through stakeholder engagement focused on adapting the content with regional examples from local practitioners.
- 2. Awareness Campaign**
This campaign highlights the significance of civic participation in ocean governance and the pathways through which ECOPs can use their skills to influence policies.
- 3. Policy Engagement Opportunities**
Structured platforms connect ECOPs with policymakers and other stakeholders, ensuring they can apply their skills in real-world contexts. Without these opportunities, skills alone cannot translate into impactful action.

This initiative supports the Mission Ocean objectives and the European Green Deal by fostering inclusivity, civic empowerment, and proactive blue citizenship. The program equips ECOPs to:

- Advocate for strong measures to protect and restore marine ecosystems and biodiversity.
- Co-create strategic campaigns to support the revision of the International Ocean Governance agenda.
- Enhance public understanding of the roles and responsibilities of citizens in ocean conservation.

Through this approach, the program cultivates a generation of empowered ocean advocates prepared to engage effectively in policy processes, aligning with Mission Ocean's aim to protect aquatic environments and foster a sustainable blue economy.

The ECOP Programme, endorsed by the UN Ocean Decade, connects early career professionals across the globe, fostering capacity-building initiatives. Over the past five years, the program has delivered specialized training on ocean data management and analysis, supported knowledge transfer between experienced professionals and ECOPs, and empowered underrepresented groups. These efforts demonstrate a proven ability to develop tailored, impactful initiatives that address critical gaps in ocean literacy, advocacy, and policy engagement.

The *Ocean Literacy for Blue Citizenship* initiative bridges the divide between **knowledge** and **action**, preparing ECOPs to navigate the complexities of policy-making and foster sustainable ocean management. By addressing critical skills gaps and providing opportunities for engagement, the project lays the foundation for a robust, informed, and proactive community of blue citizens committed to driving meaningful policy change.

2 Methodology and Results

The pilot action adopts a participatory and phased methodology designed to ensure inclusivity, adaptability, and effectiveness. By combining needs assessment, integration of stakeholder perspectives, collaborative curriculum development, knowledge sharing, and iterative evaluation, the process focuses on addressing knowledge gaps and fostering engagement among Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs) and practitioners in Europe.

This approach was chosen to ensure a comprehensive understanding of ECOPs' needs and priorities, promote co-creation, and facilitate long-term impact. It leverages diverse perspectives, participatory collaboration, and ongoing stakeholder input to produce a robust, adaptable training programme aligned with regional and global priorities.

The work plan (Table 1), structured across six phases over four months, outlines a comprehensive approach to assess needs, practices, and knowledge gaps, co-design a curriculum, and share resources to empower ECOPs in policy engagement and ocean literacy.

Table 1: Table summarizing the project phases, activities, outcomes and timeframe.

Phase	Activities	Outcomes	Start	End
Stakeholder Engagement Plan	Mapping stakeholders, structuring surveys and templates, summarizing EU policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identified 11 courses with similar topics in Europe, and 56 key organisations or individuals - Segments (ECOP, youth, society-policy, capacity building, research-policy, science-policy, society-policy, funding-policy) - List of the main stakeholders and their engagement role (ANNEX) 	July	Early August
Needs Assessment	Surveys, interviews, and data analysis targeting ECOPs to assess knowledge gaps related to European policies, ocean literacy, and policy engagement.	Collected 104 ECOP responses (64 from EU+ and 40 from other regions)	July	August

<p>Practice Assessment</p>	<p>Conducted interviews with key organizations to identify existing practices, challenges, and successful engagement strategies.</p>	<p>Survey disseminated to 35 organizations</p> <p>6 replies, 4 confirmed interest in collaborating (ECRA, EMB, AuB, OGS)</p>	<p>September</p>	<p>September</p>
<p>Collaborative Course Content Development</p>	<p>Facilitated focus group and one-to-one meetings with ECOPs and NGOs to tailor course content based on survey and interview results. Incorporate region-specific adaptations and priorities.</p>	<p>15 ECOPs identified for participation in the co-design process;</p> <p>Focus group - 3 ECOPs</p> <p>6 one-on-one meetings to discuss the project and establish partnerships</p> <p>Confirmed partnerships: Youth4Ocean, YEE, Laura Bastide, OTGA, BlueCAD. Partnerships in negotiation: Jerneja Penca, IOI, EMB, IPOS, EMSEA.</p>	<p>September</p>	<p>November</p>
<p>Knowledge Sharing</p>	<p>Host webinars, create an online resource library, and disseminate best practices through forums.</p>	<p>The library couldn't be developed within the grant period due to low participation and some unforeseen events.</p> <p>Presented the project in 1 webinar (Blue Foods Decade Action), 2 conferences (CommOCEANS), Ocean Week</p> <p>Submitted 2 conference abstracts (One Ocean Science Congress and IUCN International Law Conference)</p>	<p>October</p>	<p>November</p>
<p>Finalization and Feedback</p>	<p>Feedback loop, finalize curriculum design, and develop a feedback mechanism for continuous improvement.</p>	<p>Ready-to-pilot curriculum and comprehensive final report.</p> <p>Received 10 feedbacks</p>		<p>November</p>

<p>Ongoing Documentation</p>	<p>Document all activities, refine templates and guidelines, and establish a foundation for scaling the program regionally and globally.</p>			
-------------------------------------	--	--	--	--

Stakeholder Engagement and Inclusion

The methodology ensures no group is left behind by:

- **Snowball Strategy:** Using existing networks to identify new stakeholders and foster inclusivity by involving a range of professionals, scientists, communicators, politicians, ECOPs, project manager, anthropologist, etc.
- **Inclusive Representation:** During the needs assessment, we gathered ECOPs' perspectives on the inclusion of underrepresented groups, such as youth, fisherfolk, and scientists, in policy engagement. There was unbalanced gender representation in the need assessment 81% women respondents.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Creating opportunities for ongoing dialogue and improvement, seamlessly integrated into the course content.

This participatory, phased methodology ensures comprehensive engagement, iterative improvement, and alignment with the needs of ECOPs and broader stakeholder communities.

1 Implementation

The implementation of the project phases are summarized in table 1.

Participant Involvement

Participants played an integral role in shaping the pilot, including ECOPs, NGOs, policymakers, and academics. Notable contributors included:

- **Stakeholders:** Youth4Ocean Forum, YEE, OTGA, IOI, EMB, and more (ANNEX).
- **Society Segments:** ECOP, youth, society-policy, capacity building, research-policy, science-policy, society-policy, funding-policy.
- **Roles:** Co-designers, consultants, interviewees, and collaborators.
- **Contributions:** Provided feedback, shared expertise, and participated in co-creation workshops and conferences presentation and abstract and webpage of the project.

Key Milestones and Partnerships

- **Needs Assessment:** Surpassed respondent target with 104 submissions.
- **Collaborative Events:** Supported by partnerships, organized in Ocean Week in Brussels (3/10) and Blue Foods Decade Action (31/10).
- **International Collaboration:** Submitted abstracts for One Ocean Science Congress and IUCN International Law Conference, with plans for a Hackathon at UNOC 2025.
- **Future Prospects:** The pilot curriculum forms the basis for a regional training course in Africa, currently in negotiation.

3 Impact assessment

In the project the inclusion of citizens was pivotal to assess local needs, co-design course content, and establish partnerships to enhance the program's relevance and effectiveness. The following are the **key findings**:

Skill and knowledge gaps remain a significant challenge for Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs) and NGOs alike. ECOPs often lack facilitation, social science, and policy engagement skills, while NGOs face difficulties accessing reliable data and translating it into actionable formats. Many participants struggle with technical writing, public speaking, and effectively using advocacy tools, underscoring the need for tailored policy resources to support engagement. Communication barriers also persist, particularly in translating scientific findings into policymaker-friendly formats and crafting evidence-based messaging.

Pre-existing relationships proved crucial for stakeholder engagement, and selecting facilitators with established networks emerged as a best practice. **Redefining ocean literacy** to incorporate "cognitive equity" broadened its appeal, emphasizing actionable care for the ocean and enhancing its strategic value in policy advocacy.

Communication barriers and the need for **multidisciplinary professionals** like science communicators remain pressing. These roles are essential to bridge gaps, foster trust, and promote inclusivity by effectively conveying evidence-based insights to diverse audiences. **Flexibility and adaptability** also proved vital, as robust planning allowed for the continuation of core activities despite disruptions from regional conflicts or personal emergencies.

Effective policy engagement requires **participatory methods**, such as active role-plays and workshops, clear communication, and outputs tailored to varied audiences. Initiatives must **prioritize sufficient time** for meaningful engagement with local communities and stakeholders from the outset. **Critical skills** for ECOPs include political literacy, communication, networking, analytical abilities, and the enthusiasm to connect diverse people and experiences to drive progress

Impact Indicators

1. **Partner Engagement:** Six confirmed partnerships and active collaboration with NGOs and ECOP networks.
2. **Course Content Enrichment:** Tailored course programme integrating regional needs and stakeholder feedback.
3. **Best Practices Adoption:** Inclusion of case studies like the French MPA process and policy engagement tool.
4. **Participant Feedback:** Positive responses emphasizing curriculum relevance and effectiveness.
5. **Collaboration Outcomes:** New initiatives with organizations in Europe (working group creation, joint events, capacity building sessions) and expansion plans for Africa (funding raising stage).

Short-term outcomes included the co-creation and enrichment of a curriculum tailored to EU policy contexts, informed by inputs from 15 Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs) and 35 organizations, including Youth4Ocean Forum, Laura Bastide, and IOI. Best practices and stakeholder feedback were

integrated to enhance relevance. **Stakeholder engagement** efforts resulted in strengthened partnerships with six key organizations, such as Youth4Ocean and YEE, and the mapping of 56 organizations for future collaboration. **Knowledge dissemination** expanded awareness through webinars, conference abstracts (CommoCEANS, Blue Foods Decade Action, One Ocean, UN International Law), and social media campaigns, reaching diverse audiences and solidifying partnerships for upcoming events.

Long-term outcomes include empowering ECOPs as change agents who will actively influence policy discussions to promote sustainable and inclusive ocean governance. A strengthened community of practice will emerge through a collaborative network of ECOPs, NGOs, and policymakers, fostering ongoing knowledge-sharing and advocacy. Partnerships with organizations like Youth4Ocean Forum will drive institutional and systemic change by embedding youth-focused approaches into ocean governance frameworks. The program's expansion to Asia and Africa, with localized adaptations, ensures global scaling and cross-regional impact. Additionally, increased advocacy capacity among ECOPs will create ripple effects in their communities, enhancing global awareness and engagement in sustainable ocean stewardship.

What worked? What didn't work?

Our strategy for citizen engagement began by **leveraging our existing network** and well-established relationships. We sought recommendations from these contacts and, where possible, asked them to facilitate initial connections. While this approach proved successful in some cases, outreach to new contacts often resulted in no replies, even when utilizing diverse communication channels such as social media, email, and conference materials. The **absence of a finalized curriculum**, which was still under co-design, also led some potential stakeholders to suggest reconnecting later. Reaching NGOs posed particular challenges, though the involvement of our facilitator and communication coordinator, who has a **strong presence** in European advisory committees, coalitions, and associations, helped build relationships more effectively. Additionally, during the needs assessment, we noted **limited representation** from both EU and non-EU countries, which we identified as a broader issue within other EU organizations. Efforts to **expand the survey to other regions** through our partners were largely unsuccessful. Another notable point was that most survey respondents were women, though the reason for this remains unclear. To improve, we could focus on developing a **stronger project presence in diverse spaces**, utilizing our team's connections strategically, timing outreach to align with the completion of key deliverables like the curriculum, and exploring targeted strategies to achieve broader and more balanced regional and gender representation.

Mission Ocean and PREP4BLUE Contributions

The project contributed to advancing Mission Ocean goals by equipping youth with **tools** and **knowledge** to engage effectively in policy processes and fostering partnerships that support sustainable blue economy practices. Aligned with the PREP4BLUE objectives, the initiative emphasized co-creation, bottom-up actions, and strategic campaigns to influence international ocean governance frameworks. Through contextualized capacity-building efforts and tailored policy tools, the project will empower stakeholders to take informed and impactful action, setting the foundation for a scalable and transformative ocean literacy initiative.

4 Lessons Learned

The pilot activity highlighted several critical lessons in navigating challenges and implementing solutions for effective engagement in the science-policy-society interface:

1. **Communication Barriers:** A key challenge was the limited ability of scientists to communicate their findings effectively to policymakers and the lack of evidence-based communication from communication professionals. This gap highlights the need for multidisciplinary professionals, such as science communicators, skilled in translating scientific knowledge into accessible formats. Future efforts should prioritize developing these roles to foster trust, inclusivity, and negotiation skills, particularly with underrepresented communities.
2. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Pre-existing relationships played a pivotal role in engaging stakeholders. Organizations with prior connections were more responsive, while new contacts were less inclined to engage. A dedicated communication strategy could enhance outreach and response rates. Selecting facilitators with robust networks was a best practice that should be maintained.
3. **Resource Limitations:** Financial constraints and logistical issues, such as limited funding for trainers, forced reliance on pro bono collaborations. Offering official certifications through partnerships (e.g., OTGA) incentivized participation, demonstrating a creative solution to funding shortages.
4. **Ocean Literacy Challenges:** Misunderstandings about the concept of ocean literacy limited its perceived value in policy advocacy. Incorporating cognitive equity into the definition broadened its acceptance, framing ocean-literate individuals as those who care for and act for the ocean. This redefinition enhanced the strategic use of ocean literacy as a policy-influencing tool.
5. **Flexibility in Planning:** Disruptions from external factors, such as regional conflict and personal emergencies, required project pauses. However, strong initial planning and adaptability allowed core activities to be completed, leaving non-essential tasks for post-grant efforts.
6. **PREP4BLUE Resources:** The stakeholder engagement plan provided by PREP4BLUE was instrumental in identifying roles and ensuring high-quality input despite low response rates. It facilitated the adaptation of project plans to unforeseen challenges.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

The pilot activity was a demanding yet rewarding process, yielding significant outcomes that promise to enhance future training initiatives. Stakeholders displayed strong interest and recognized the relevance of the training for the region. These outcomes highlight the value of co-designing curricula that reflect regional contexts and stakeholder perspectives. Despite challenges such as communication barriers, resource constraints, and logistical disruptions, the activity demonstrated that careful planning, adaptability, and leveraging existing networks can lead to meaningful engagement and impactful results.

Recommendations for Future Activities

1. **Upscaling and Replication:**

To replicate the success of this initiative, develop a standardized protocol for co-designing curricula. This tool should be adaptable to various regional contexts and freely accessible, enabling organizations to customize the training process effectively.

2. **Stakeholder Engagement:**

- Develop a comprehensive communication strategy to improve outreach and response rates.
- Build and strengthen networks by maintaining relationships with existing stakeholders and strategically engaging new ones.
- Manage expectations and recognize contributions to foster goodwill and sustained collaboration.

3. **Capacity Building:**

- Invest in the development of science communicators to bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and policy advocacy.
- Promote multidisciplinary collaboration to create a robust science-society-policy interface.

4. **Inclusivity and Relevance:**

- Broaden the concept of ocean literacy to incorporate cognitive equity, emphasizing action and care for the ocean as key components.
- Tailor training content to reflect regional and ECOP-specific needs, ensuring relevance and inclusivity.

5. **Adaptive Planning:**

Prepare for disruptions by building flexibility into project plans, allowing core activities to proceed uninterrupted and postponing less critical tasks if necessary.

By addressing these areas, future EU for Blue Citizenship activities can achieve broader participation, greater stakeholder buy-in, and more impactful outcomes, driving sustainable change in ocean literacy and policy engagement.

6 ANNEX

Table 2. List of the main stakeholder involved and their respective engagement role in the project.

Stakeholder	Organization	Level of engagement
Evgeniia Kostianaia	ECOP Programme	Consult & Involve
Conor Savage	ECOP Europe	Consult & Involve
Sophia Laarissa	ECOP Africa	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Raphaël Roman	ECOP Asia	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
ECOP Programme members & Focus group of 15 ECOPs	Various	Consult & Involve
Guillaume Lheureux	Youth4Ocean Forum	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Anna Maria Marino	Youth and Environment Europe, Youth4Ocean Forum	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Laura Bastide	ACTeon, EU4Ocean	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Antonella Vassallo	IOI	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Cosmin Chivu	IOI	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Gabriel Akoko	OTGA	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Jerneja Penca	Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Paula Kellet	EBM	Consult & Involve
Lucas Becquet	IPOS	Consult & Collaboration
Ines Boujmil	Aquabiotech	Involve & Collaboration
Valentina Lovat	IOC/UNESCO Ocean Literacy With All Programme (OLWA)	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Steering Committee of OLWA	Ocean Literacy With All Programme, various	Consult & Collaboration

Evy Copejans	EMSEA	Consult, Involve & Collaboration
Silvia Gomez Mestres	Autonomous University of Barcelona	Consult
Noemi Fuster	University of Barcelona	Consult
Flavia Rolli	OGS	Consult & Collaboration
Giulia Massolino	Consigliera regionale FVG	Consult & Collaboration
Jean-Christophe Vandavelde	The Pew Charitable Trusts	Consult
Sissi Knispel de Acosta	ECRA	Consult
Natalie Fox	ECOP Programme	Involve & Collaboration

PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper

Mission Ocean's overarching objectives (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, page 19).

Mission citizen engagement target outcomes (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, pp. 35-36).

Your citizen engagement activities / outputs

Annex P2. Self-Evaluation Report for PA2: The BlueScape2024 Baltic Hackathon

PREP4BLUE Pilot activity reporting template: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report

**BlueEscape2024: “Empowering Education and Sustainability
Through Virtual Escape Rooms”**

Social Innovation Actions MTÜ

Project Duration:

4 July 2024 to 30 November 2024

Project Coordinator:

Sandra Lund

Collaborators/Partners:

Baltic Living Lab

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report** 1
- Executive Summary (0.5 page) 3
- 1 Introduction (1 page)..... 6
- 2 Methodology (1-2 pages) 11
- 3 Implementation (1 page) 14
- 4 Results and Impact assessment (1-2 pages) 15
- 5 Lessons Learned (0.5 page)20
- 6 Conclusion and Recommendations (0.5 page).....22

Executive Summary (0.5 page)

Overview of the Pilot Action

- Provide a brief description of your pilot action, outlining its main focus and purpose. Include a summary of the project's objectives and goals, highlighting what the pilot aimed to achieve and the specific issues it sought to address

Two challenges were created (online and in situ) for the DigiEduHack.com Baltic Region Hackathon as the “**BlueEscape2024: Empowering Education and Sustainability Through Virtual Escape Rooms**” events. The main focus and purpose were twofold:

- (1) Align with the EU Digital Education Plan 2021-2027 that aims to support the adaptation of the education and training systems of Member States to the Digital Age that can present opportunities for the education and training community (teachers and students) on national and EU levels. Our goal was to promote ocean literacy as aligned specifically with Priority 2 of the plan, “enhancing digital skills and competences for the digital transformation” that could tie into Action 7: “using the hackathon concept as a guideline for teachers and educators to foster digital literacy”.
- (2) The purpose of the Baltic Region Hackathon, therefore, was to demonstrate how hackathons could foster creativity towards identifying the root causes of climate change – which is mainly human activity - as it pertains to the transfer of knowledge about the role Earth’s water bodies play in controlling the planet’s environment. With this information in hand, students used the hackathon structure to address climate change from a citizen-science perspective. Additionally, they could apply the scientific methods to understanding the challenges of climate change and develop problem-solving skills such as:
 - critical thinking
 - collaboration by working in teams
 - effective communication by publicly presenting the results of their participation in the hackathon
 - applying creativity towards creating solutions to problems that they decided were interesting

Some of those problems included plastic pollution, invasive species and habitat destruction of both marine and freshwater ecosystems.

- **Key objectives and goals.**

Key objectives were to *promote ocean literacy* that has become increasingly important in today's world as we face unprecedented challenges related to climate change, pollution, and the sustainable use of marine resources. The key goals included *contributing toward supporting the paradigm shift that positions both formal education and instruction imparted in non-formal learning environments to engage and prepare young people to participate in climate action as future guardians of our planet.*

Main Outcomes

- Summary of the main achievements and outcomes. Focus on the key outcomes that demonstrate the effectiveness of the project in meeting its objectives.

Hosted both online and in-person in Pärnu, Estonia, these events brought together educators, students, and professionals from diverse disciplines and regions to co-create virtual escape rooms that foster systems thinking skills and promote sustainable practices, which demonstrated the effectiveness of the project in meeting its objectives of promoting ocean literacy and instigating action of students as agents of change. The events, held from November 8-10, 2024, exemplified a transformative vision by combining sustainability knowledge, innovation and creativity problem-solving, and immersive learning. The events brought together four teams of 4-6 students each team with their mentor that facilitated the activities during the weekend.

Future Recommendations

- Key recommendations for future activities or improvements. This section should offer actionable suggestions for enhancing similar initiatives in the future; might include strategies for expanding outreach, improving collaboration with stakeholders, or sustaining engagement over the long term.

Future Recommendations include hosting hackathons for the remaining time of the EU Digital Education Initiatives keystone program, DigiEduHack. This means that one hackathon per year will be hosted in 2025, 2026 and 2027. There are many lessons learned from this initial venture into organizing a hackathon:

1. Outreach must be started a year in advance to the event: The main problem we faced was a lack of understanding of what a hackathon is – and what it is not. When people hear “hack”athon, they tend to associate it with cybersecurity, as in how accounts are hacked into and security breached. This problem was compounded by the problem of not understanding that participants do not need technical skills usually associated with computer programming to participate in a DigiEduHack event. Addressing these issues will contribute toward sustaining engagement over the long-term.
2. Collaboration with stakeholders was a different problem to be solved. For us, stakeholders took the form of sponsors who could contribute prizes for the winning teams, marine science experts who would take the time over a weekend to serve as competition judges, volunteers to help with logistics, and fundraisers to cover the costs of venue, means and accommodations for coming to Estonia from other parts of the Baltic region.

3. Bringing visibility and publicity to the event was an overriding problem that can be solved in the future by starting outreach early to get actors from the Blue Economy, public bodies and academia to participate in both the organization of the hackathon and, as previously mentioned, serve as judges for team submissions of designing virtual escape rooms within the hackathon structure.

Looking Ahead: Co-Creation and Impact

The hackathon is just the beginning. The next phase involves refining and releasing the escape rooms to schools and other users (currently 2-3 of solutions are under consideration). These tools will:

- Educate and Engage: Introduce students to sustainable practices in an interactive way.
- Drive Systems Thinking: Help learners understand complex ecological and economic interdependencies.
- Inspire Action: Equip the next generation to address critical challenges in the Baltic Sea region and beyond.

1 Introduction (1 page)

Background and Context

- Brief background information about the pilot action. Explain the specific problem or need that the pilot action aims to address and any relevant historical or contextual information that sets the stage for this initiative.

The Baltic Sea region faces critical challenges, from environmental degradation to the need for sustainable blue economy practices, that make it one of the most vulnerable seas in Europe in need of interventions such as those provided by the hackathon structure. Educating the next generation to tackle these issues requires innovative approaches that go beyond traditional learning methods by utilizing the “open schooling” methodologies and citizen engagement advocated by the EU Mission Ocean, aimed at protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems.

- **Fostering Systems Thinking:** The hackathon encouraged participants to think holistically towards understanding the interconnectedness of ecological, social, and economic systems.
- **Enhancing Engagement:** Using virtual escape rooms as a creative and interactive medium to captivate learners while delivering impactful educational content.

- Importance of the activity in the context of Mission Ocean’s objectives.

The Baltic Region Hackathon advanced the Mission Ocean’s objectives by fostering innovation, collaboration and public engagement in promoting conservation and sustainability. It contributed to the mission’s goals primarily by raising awareness and education. Ocean literacy is about increasing understanding of the ocean’s role in climate regulation, biodiversity and the impact of human activity of the degradation of habitats and ecosystems. The hackathon engaged participants in the critical thinking process of creating hands-on solutions that increase awareness of Baltic Sea challenges that align with the mission’s focus on education and public engagement in sustainability. By involve a wide spectrum of participants, from students to professionals and educators, the hackathon promoted active citizenship in ocean conservation in support of the EU’s broader goal of involving citizens in environmental decision-making and taking collective action to restore European waters. The interdisciplinary nature of the hackathon is essential for addressing the complex, interconnectedness of Earth’s systems that require cross-sectoral collaboration, thus supporting the mission’s call for integration and multi-sectoral stakeholder approaches. In essence, the hackathon was aimed at helping to bridge the gap between knowledge and action.

Describe Your Organisation/Project/Initiative

- Detailed description of your organisation, project, or initiative outlining its main components, target audience, and geographical focus. Include any relevant history or milestones that demonstrate your organisation's experience and expertise in this field.

The hackathon was originally designed as a collaborative effort of students from throughout the Baltic region to seek solutions to the environmental challenges faced by a common sea shared amongst eight EU countries. While it was intended to bring together participants from all eight countries, it was an initial attempt, providing invaluable lessons for future events. Because we could generate enough interest in time to meet these goals, we ended up with an Estonian event. Four teams of secondary-school aged children participated with their teachers in Pärnu at the Pernova Nature Center campus. We chose Pärnu to host the event because traditionally, most similar events take place in the capital, and we aimed to engage the entire country rather than only Tallinn.

How this Action Connects to Mission Ocean Objectives

- Detailed objectives of the pilot activity. Explain how each objective aligns with the overall aims of the project and contributes to its success.
- **Mission Ocean Objectives:** Provide a detailed explanation of how your proposal connects to one or more of the Mission Ocean objectives. Refer to specific objectives from the Mission Ocean Implementation Plan (page 19).
- **Citizen Engagement Target Outcomes:** Explain how your proposal aligns with the citizen engagement target outcomes as outlined in the Mission Ocean Implementation Plan (page 36). Discuss how your activities promote these outcomes and contribute to the broader mission goals.

Found here: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/d6162cbd-6d09-48fd-b5b4-d7d2be69972c_en?filename=ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_final.pdf

The Baltic Sea region faces critical challenges, from environmental degradation to the need for sustainable blue economy practices, that make it one of the most vulnerable seas in Europe in need of interventions such as those provided by the hackathon structure. Educating the next generation to tackle these issues requires innovative approaches that go beyond traditional learning methods by utilizing the “open schooling” methodologies and citizen engagement advocated by the EU Mission Ocean, aimed at protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems. BlueEscape2024 aimed to address this aligning with the Mission Ocean’s objectives in several ways of promoting sustainability: Raising awareness about environmental conservation and the importance of sustainable

practices in maritime sectors, the hackathon encourages participants to develop innovative strategies to monitor and restore the health of the Baltic Sea such as eco-friendly solutions to reduce eutrophication of the largest “dead zone” in Europe caused by nutrient overload. A key objective of the mission is to reduce pollution in Earth’s waters - hackathon teams were kept busy understanding circular economy models that would reduce waste that impacts the sea. The mission also promotes a sustainable Blue Economy, a popular topic of hackathons teams as they delved into sustainable fisheries management, sustainable tourism and aquaculture practices, as well as understanding how innovative shipping technologies are green – reducing emissions and preventing marine pollution. Another objective of the Mission Ocean is to encourage cross-border cooperation to address marine challenges. While the hackathon was originally devised to bring together participants from the eight Baltic countries and ended up being an Estonian in situ event, it did foster international collaboration with the online version of the event. Our future hackathons will place special emphasis on supporting EU policies and frameworks like the Marine Strategy Framework Directive.

- Which ocean literacy principles will you address / Which Ocean Literacy dimensions do you hope to contribute to?

(Reference:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0025326X22011493?via%3Dihub>)

The primary dimension of ocean literacy from Science Direct is the concept of ocean connectedness – the destruction of one element impacts an entire ecosystem. Ocean connectedness emphasizes that the health and functioning of the ocean cannot be understood in isolation but as part of a global system, where each region and ecosystem is linked to others.

Physical Connectivity: Oceans are physically interconnected through currents, tides, and water circulation patterns that link different parts of the globe. For example, the ocean's “conveyor belt”) distributes heat, nutrients, and marine life across vast distances, impacting climate and marine ecosystems globally.

Biodiversity and Ecosystem Connectivity: Marine species migration was a topic of one team’s approach to ocean literacy, where they learned that ecosystems are all interconnected. Changes in one ecosystem can affect species that depend on it, with ripple effects across regions. For instance, overfishing in one area can deplete fish populations that are part of the food web.

Climate and Carbon Cycling: The oceans play a critical role in regulating the global climate and carbon cycle. Ocean connectedness includes the way carbon dioxide is absorbed by the sea, how ocean temperatures influence weather patterns, and how climate change in one region can affect ocean conditions worldwide.

Pollution: Ocean pollution, particularly plastic waste, chemicals, and oil spills, is a significant aspect of ocean connectedness. Pollutants can travel vast distances, carried by ocean currents, impacting marine life far from their point of origin. This interconnectedness emphasizes the need for global solutions to ocean pollution.

Human Impacts and Global Sustainability: Activities like shipping, fishing, coastal development, and climate change all have global effects on the ocean. A problem in one region (such as habitat destruction) can impact food security, economies, and ecosystems in other parts of the world, highlighting the need for coordinated global action to protect and restore the oceans.

Ocean connectedness calls for a holistic approach to ocean management, recognizing that local, regional, and global scales are all interdependent. It underlines the importance of international cooperation, as actions in one region can have significant consequences for the broader health of the planet's oceans.

The hackathon addresses the Scient Direct's dimensions of ocean literacy by offering a dynamic, collaborative, and innovative environment where participants could enhance and apply problem-solving skills to real-world challenges:

Knowledge: A hackathon can promote learning about ocean science and issues. By working on projects related to marine ecosystems, climate change, pollution, or conservation, students can deepen their knowledge of ocean science, with marine scientists, Blue Economy actors and environmental advocates introducing them to important facts and current issues.

Communication: During the hackathon, students often present their ideas and solutions to first their peers and later as a group to a panel of judges. This encourages them to communicate complex scientific or environmental issues in clear and engaging ways, enhancing their communication skills. They can also create digital content that communicates ocean literacy in an accessible format and can be used in future activities like social media campaigns, which they all agreed to do.

Behavior: Hackathons emphasize problem-solving and inspire students to reflect on their personal behaviors in relation to the ocean such as focusing on reducing plastic waste, thus motivating students to adopt more eco-friendly habits in their daily lives.

Awareness: By participating in the hackathon around ocean literacy, participants increased their awareness of environmental challenges. The process of designing solutions required them to understand issues like ocean pollution, overfishing, and habitat destruction, building an empathetic awareness of the ocean's importance.

Attitudes: Hackathons can shape positive attitudes towards the ocean by fostering a sense of responsibility and hope. Collaborative projects that work towards sustainable solutions create a mindset that values ocean conservation, encouraging students to take action and care about the health of marine ecosystems.

Activism: A hackathon environment can encourage students to become activists by allowing themselves to create actionable solutions that they can advocate for or implement, empowering them to become change-makers.

Emotional Connection: The hands-on, immersive experience of the hackathon can foster a personal and emotional connection to the ocean, which was an overarching objective of the project. When young people feel more connected to marine life, they become more amenable to becoming engaged in activities like developing virtual reality experiences, creating artistic expressions, or designing solutions for endangered species protection, which was an important outcome of the hackathon experience, having secured the sponsorship of a 360-degree video production enterprise allowing the hackathon participants to utilize their software free of charge during the event, and choosing a winner from the hackathon judged entries to have a one-year license to use the software for personal or academic purposes.

Access and Experience: Hackathons provide students with access to mentors, tools, and resources that they might not otherwise have. They may learn new technical skills and gain access to environmental data, helping them explore ocean literacy at a deeper level of knowledge building.

Adaptive Capacity: Hackathons are designed to be fast-paced and adaptive. Students must pivot, iterate, and modify their solutions in real time, teaching them to be flexible and innovative in the face of challenges. This ability to adapt is crucial when addressing the rapidly-changing challenges facing the Earth’s water bodies and timeframe within which the Mission Ocean “Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030” should take place.

Trust and Transparency: A hackathon promotes teamwork, collaboration, and shared responsibility, all of which require trust and transparency. Students learn how to work with others towards a common goal, share ideas freely, and engage in transparent decision-making processes, which are key values in both scientific inquiry and environmental advocacy.

By combining these elements, Baltic Region hackathon was aimed at creating a vibrant learning environment where high school students not only could gain knowledge about ocean science but are become motivated to take meaningful action. Through innovation, teamwork, and the development of real-world solutions, the Blue Escape 2024 hackathon made ocean literacy accessible, exciting, and actionable.

2 Methodology (1-2 pages)

Approach and Methods

- Description of the approach and methods used in the pilot action. Explanation of why these methods were chosen.

The main objective of the hackathon was to align with the Mission Ocean goals of involving citizens in the mission to restore our ocean and waters by 2030 by raising awareness about the environmental challenges facing the Baltic Sea and the need for action. This method was chosen to involve students at the grass-roots level where they could develop tools like digital apps that could engagement the public in environmental monitoring and advocacy. This was our intention from the beginning, one that will be reinforced in future hackathons.

Describe the Pilot Action Plan and Timeline

- Detailed description of the pilot action plan and timeline: Preparation, data collection, implementation, evaluation and reporting.

Preparation of the hackathon began in March, 2024 with the planning phase setting the stage for the different components of the project: seeking sponsors, “advertising” the event via the DigiEduHack portal, sending out invitations to schools to send a team to participate, securing the venue and organizing logistics, fundraising. This led to implementation, with the event being held November 8-10, after which reporting was completed with the current document serving as the final report.

Participants and Stakeholders

- Information on the participants and stakeholders involved. Their roles and contributions to the activity.

Team challenges and solutions were judged by a panel of Experts in fields like education design, design thinking, escape room design, sustainability, and the blue economy played a pivotal role. Mentors and jury members represented organizations like:

- Pärnu Escape Rooms for expertise in designing engaging experiences.
- University of Tartu (Pärnu College), University of Tallinn, and Estonian Maritime Cluster for insights into the blue economy and water literacy.
- Kiln Design Limited for guidance in online education and design thinking
- Pärnu Pernova Nature House for hosting the event in such an incredible location that was built for environmental education
- Bonolab for organising both the online and in-person events

- We Are Learning and ELB Learning for providing us access to tools to help explore the technology to build the escape rooms concepts during the event.

Congratulations to Emma-Mia Tammeveski, Kaisa Helena Holz, Miko Kohv, and Maria Ivanova from Tartu Nature House in Estonia for the winning project that combined abandoned underwater prisons, future food, and marine biodiversity into a unique and exciting concept. Team highlights included:

- o Emma-Mia, Kaisa Helena, and Miko are teenagers in secondary-school with an interest in environmental sciences.
 - o Their mentor, Maria Ivanova, is a UNESCO ASP net Baltic Sea Project coordinator who brought expertise in Education for Sustainable Development and Global Education.
- Impact:** The team will collaborate with the organizing committee to release a blue economy escape room for schools and other users.

Kudos to the Redesign Learning Team—Lilian Warutere and Violet Warutere—for their innovative approach and passion for the environment, who won the competition for the online version of the hackathon. Team Highlights:

- o Violet, an Environmental Science student and digital creator, bridges environmental conservation with engaging digital content.
 - o Lilian, a learning designer with marketing expertise, focuses on creating impactful, evidence-based learning experiences.
- Impact:** This team’s escape room concept will also be developed and made freely accessible to educators worldwide.

- **Description of the methodology or strategy to involve citizens in the activity.**

With the primary aim of the hackathon being to increase ocean literacy among high school students, we structured the activities that focused on ocean science, the issues and environmental challenges facing the Baltic Sea, conservation and sustainable practices. After completing the hackathon held during a weekend, students walked away with a deeper understanding of the ocean’s role in a global ecosystem, were able to delve into the root problem of environmental challenges to begin to think of practical solutions to real-world problems of the degradation of habitat, plastics and other types of pollution like marine litter, invasive species brought into the Baltic Sea by ballast water of visiting ships, etc. They were able to access authoritative resources of these issues via the Internet, and became aware of how technology can be applied in the fight towards combating climate change. We involved marine scientists and environmentalists as resources to share real-world knowledge about the sea and the issues faced, and we invited local

community members like fishermen, members of the Estonian Marine Cluster who have Blue Economy business and are innovators in technology, as well as environmental educators. We were also able to secure the sponsorship of the City of Pärnu, all of whom offered practical perspectives that could not come from traditional classroom settings and served as mentors and judges, able to give students invaluable, hands-on feedback.

Our theme, Blue Escape 2024, created a sort of problem statement that encouraged the different facets of ocean literacy: how we could raise awareness of the challenges; what are innovative ways of monitoring ocean health and biodiversity as a “citizen-science” initiative; how technology lends tools to track temperature changes; how students can develop solutions for protecting marine life from overfishing or restoring habitat that has been destroyed by practices such as trawling; understanding that ocean literacy fosters the tailoring of challenges that are locally relevant yet have a global significance – like eutrophication and the food chain.

The online platform sponsored by DigiEduHack.com was instrumental in building awareness of the challenges that were addressed during the hackathon, as well as the impact as noted above.

- Insert your stakeholder mapping (you can use section 4 of PREP4BLUE’s Toolbox for Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters. *Found here:* <https://nordlandsforskning.wrep.it/engaging-citizens-with-mission-ocean/sec/5#report-top>.

Upon consideration of the stakeholder mapping parameters, it was determined that a hackathon, by its nature, cannot be held to the same standards as a broader framework of citizen participation, which involves a continuum of connected activities where stakeholders can engage and contribute at all levels. After evaluating the event’s activities, it became clear that the primary goal of the weekend-long hackathon pilot was to raise awareness, rather than to foster ongoing involvement within a cohesive set of activities. The stakeholder mapping process raised key questions, such as “What are the reasons for engaging citizens, and how will their participation evolve?” These questions highlight that it is unrealistic to expect high school students, for example, to immediately engage in relationship-building processes and contribute meaningfully within such a structured framework. While their participation in the hackathon was genuine, it is important to recognize that they may not yet possess the skills and competencies necessary for deeper, ongoing contributions within the context of a more extensive stakeholder engagement initiative.

- Leaving No One Behind - Who might be left behind? Why are they left behind? What did you do to ensure they are not left behind?
Found here:
<https://unsdg.un.org/2030-agenda/universal-values/leave-no-one-behind>

The "Leaving No One Behind" initiative, in the context of an ocean literacy hackathon, typically targets individuals and communities that are marginalized or underrepresented in environmental discussions and actions:

Indigenous and local communities: Those who depend directly on the ocean for their livelihoods (e.g., fishermen, coastal populations) and may lack access to educational resources about ocean conservation.

Low-income populations: These groups may not have access to opportunities for learning about ocean health, sustainability, or scientific advancements related to marine ecosystems.

Youth and students: Especially those from underprivileged or rural areas who might not have access to ocean literacy programs.

People with disabilities: Ensuring that educational resources and tools are accessible to everyone, including those with visual, auditory, or mobility impairments.

Women and gender minorities: In some regions, these groups are underrepresented in environmental and ocean science fields.

The aim is to promote inclusivity, ensure equitable access to education and opportunities related to ocean literacy, and raise awareness about ocean sustainability among these communities.

3 Implementation (1 page)

Pilot Action – Description of Activities

- Detailed description of what happened during the pilot action. Describe each activity in chronological order, including any preparatory work, the main events, and follow-up actions.
- Participant Involvement: Explain how participants were involved in the activities. Discuss the number of participants, their roles, and how they contributed to the success of the pilot action.
- Implementation timeline of key events and milestones. Include dates and brief descriptions of each significant event or milestone.
- Visual Documentation: Insert photos from the pilot action to visually document what happened. Include captions that explain what is happening in each photo and how it relates to the pilot activity.

BlueEscape2024 was more than just a hackathon; it tied into DigiEduHack under the EU's Digital Education Plan 2021-2027 as a sponsored challenge and global collaboration

involving 50+ participants, mentors and jury. The event showcased the power of interdisciplinary teamwork and international cooperation.

Beginning with preparatory work, a planning committee was mounted in March, meeting bi-weekly until June, at which time they began to meet weekly, carrying

JURY AND MENTORS

Helen Orav, Estonian Marine Institute; Henn Ojaveer, Tartu University; Matti Lillevali, The Escape Room; Riina Palu, Estonian Maritime Cluster; Piret Liv Stern Dahl; Hackathon Coordinator/Bonolabs; Maria Ivanova, Perno Nature House; Jana Liiv, Outdoor Adventures; Louise Cox, Kiln Design

4 Results and Impact assessment (1-2 pages)

Key Findings

- Detailed presentation of the key findings. Include qualitative insights gathered from participant feedback, observations, and other sources. Provide specific quotes or anecdotes that illustrate the impact of the activity.

Key Findings:

Awareness and Knowledge Gaps in Ocean Literacy: Ocean literacy is missing in core curricula thus producing a lack basic knowledge about ocean ecosystems, the importance of ocean conservation, and the impact of human activities on marine life. However, the high interest in both freshwater and marine restorative biodiversity demonstrated by the young people participating in the Baltic Region Hackathon showed they were passionate about environmental issues and eager to engage with projects that address these topics. This is an important indicator of the need for better ocean literacy teaching and learning. The technical nature of the hackathon tapped into the high degree of tech savvy “digital natives”, born and raised in the era of technology. The students were highly engaged and showed a high degree of interest in using digital tools, apps, and social media to raise awareness and solve problems related to ocean conservation. High-school students still possess creativity that is gradually eroded as children mature throughout their academic journey – extremely high in very young students and waning as they progress toward adulthood. However, our hackathon participants who averaged 15-17. showed innovation potential as they approached the challenges to come up with novel solutions – their creativity shone bright when given the digital tools, demonstrating that technology can make a real difference in ocean literacy and conservation efforts.

Proposed Outcomes

- Description of the proposed outcomes.
 - Short-term Outcomes: Describe the immediate outcomes of the pilot activity. What were the direct results achieved by the end of the activity? Include specific metrics or indicators used to measure these outcomes.
 - Long-term Outcomes: Discuss the anticipated long-term outcomes of the pilot activity. What are the expected lasting impacts on the participants, the community, and the broader Mission Ocean and PREP4BLUE goals?

While the student participants were accommodated by their teachers, they took their task seriously and were dedicated to advancing their solution and presentation throughout the process. They demonstrated the classical emotional and physical behavior of ‘advancing -getting stuck – asking for advice - advancing again’ learning cycles.

- All teams used mentors available from the blue economy and education sectors. This was a new experience for the Estonian in-person hackathon participants, as they had not participated in hackathons before, nor has it been common to have experts from different fields participating in educational initiatives or have direct contact with high-school students. This interaction provided some good foundation to engage the students’ interest in pursuing professional careers in the Blue Economy and as researchers in marine sciences.

- The teachers of one of the participating schools, Kuninga Kool, were impressed by how the hackathon process engaged the students and maintained their focus throughout the program, as

this is not so easy to accomplish in regular classroom teaching sessions. Organizers had a chance to talk with the teachers about using this methodology in the future teaching sessions to move from ‘learn by heart’ to ‘problem solving’.

- The teachers’ team in the in situ hackathon got very inspired by the co-creation activity and is planning to apply for the SHORE blue economy education project funding. This is a direct impact of the hackathon engagement towards designing blue economy education for Estonian schools. The organizers will keep close contact to support them to go through with the action.

Short-Term Outcomes (Immediate Impact):

Enhanced Ocean Literacy: Students gained a deeper understanding of ocean ecosystems, the challenges they face, and their role in ocean conservation. They were able to delve into specific challenges like plastic pollution, overfishing and eutrophication due primarily to agriculture runoff, making a connection between the interconnectedness of the land the sea.

Skills Development: They honed critical problem-solving skills and those that are in demand by employers: critical thinking, collaboration by working in teams and being mentored by external experts and academicians, fostering a sense of community and relationship-building that is sure to extend beyond the hackathon itself. They also worked on their presentation skills and had to present their project before the panel of judges as well as the audience made up of all hackathon participants. They showed great pride in what they accomplished and enthusiasm for presenting.

Proposed Long-Term Outcomes:

Ongoing Ocean Literacy and Enthusiasm for Engagement: Participants will continue to be involved in ocean literacy and conservation efforts after the hackathon, either by further developing their projects, joining ocean advocacy groups, or taking leadership roles in sustainability initiatives at school or in their community.

Curriculum Integration: Schools may consider integrating ocean literacy more formally into their curricula, inspired by the students' newfound interest and knowledge, as well as the potential impact of their hackathon projects.

Creation of Sustainable Solutions: Projects developed during the hackathon could lead to sustainable, scalable solutions for promoting ocean literacy, such as the awareness-raising campaigns that can reach wider audiences.

Strengthened Local and Global Networks: Students may continue to connect with mentors, environmental organizations, and other like-minded individuals or groups they met during the hackathon, leading to new opportunities for collaboration and impact.

Expected Lasting Impacts:

Increased Youth Advocacy: As students become more knowledgeable about ocean conservation, they will be better equipped to advocate for change within their communities, schools, and beyond. Their advocacy could lead to greater youth involvement in environmental decision-making processes.

Sustained Passion for Environmental Issues: Since the hackathon sparked interest in ocean conservation and environmental sciences, this could encourage participants to pursue careers or extracurricular activities related to marine biology, environmental science, and sustainability.

Increased Public Awareness: As students share their hackathon projects with wider audiences—through social media, in the classroom, at community events, or via school outreach programs—they help raise broader awareness about ocean literacy and sustainability issues.

Stronger Community and Policy Engagement: The hackathon has the potential of inspiring local schools, communities, and even policymakers to take more active roles in ocean conservation, influenced by the students’ passion, solutions, and ongoing engagement with these topics.

By focusing on high school students, the Baltic Region Hackathon around ocean literacy has the potential of cultivating the next generation of informed, passionate, and innovative ocean advocates, leading to long-term changes in how future leaders engage with ocean literacy and addressing the Baltic Sea’s environmental challenges.

The hackathon is thus positioned to significantly support the Prep4Blue Initiative and the broader Mission Ocean by encouraging innovative solutions to pressing marine and environmental challenges:

1. **Fostering Innovation** - hackathons are designed to bring together diverse minds with different perspectives of the same problem to collaborate intensively within a short timeframe. This environment sparks the creation of fresh, creative solutions that could drive significant progress for initiatives like Prep4Blue, which focuses on protecting the oceans and preparing communities for climate-related challenges. Hackathons and innovation-yield environments can produce tools to improve ocean conservation, climate resilience, and sustainable marine practices in a future iteration involving not just students but also academicians, Blue Economy professionals and even
2. **Data-Driven Solutions** - by allowing teams to work on data-driven projects in general, hackathons can provide initiatives like Prep4Blue Initiative with the benefit of using such data tools that can enhance decision-making, foster public awareness, and aid policymakers in taking action based on real-time insights about ocean conditions.

3. Raising Awareness – is a cornerstone of the hackathon to ultimately often involve citizen engagement and attract attention to challenges and solutions in ocean conservation. As participants develop projects aimed at tackling ocean issues, they also raise awareness about the environmental impact on marine ecosystems. These activities can broaden the mission of Prep4Blue by engaging wider communities, educating them about the urgency of ocean protection, and involving them in tech-driven solutions.

4. Building a Community of Experts and Advocates – we assembled a collaborative efforts involving experts, academicians, stakeholders, and advocates for ocean health. Future hackathons will necessarily involve a variety of disciplines, including technology, policy, marine science, and education, providing the Prep4Blue Initiative with a community of professionals who can help drive the mission forward. These collaborations might lead to partnerships, funding opportunities, and long-term engagement in ocean conservation efforts.

5. Sustainable Technologies – hackathons around ocean literacy, in general, often focus on creating sustainable technologies that have real-world applications. For example, teams might work on developing low-cost sensors for tracking ocean pollutants, designing platforms to connect ocean researchers, or create educational tools and gamification products that can be used by schools and community-based organizations. These technologies can directly support both the Prep4Blue Initiative and broader ocean missions by enabling better monitoring, protection, and sustainable use of marine resources.

6. Addressing Specific Challenges - In line with the Prep4Blue Initiative's goals, hackathons can focus on specific challenges like climate change adaptation, ocean plastic pollution, or sustainable fisheries, and can also take the form of crowd-sourcing solutions.

Overall, hackathons can help align technological innovation with marine conservation goals, directly advancing initiatives like Prep4Blue and supporting the mission to protect and sustainably manage the ocean.

Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Targets

- How the activity contributed to the goals of Mission Ocean and PREP4BLUE. Detail the specific contributions your activity made towards these goals. For example, if one of the goals is to increase awareness, explain how your activity raised awareness among participants.
- Assessment of the extent to which the action succeeded in engaging with Mission Ocean citizen engagement targets. **Refer back to your PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper to support your assessment.** Describe the strategies you used to engage citizens. What worked well, and what didn't? How could these strategies be improved in the future?

The hackathon engaged participants in the critical thinking process of creating hands-on solutions that increase awareness of Baltic Sea challenges that align with the mission's focus on education

and public engagement in sustainability. By involve a wide spectrum of participants, from students to professionals and educators, the hackathon promoted active citizenship in ocean conservation in support of the EU’s broader goal of involving citizens in environmental decision-making and taking collective action to restore European waters. The interdisciplinary nature of the hackathon is essential for addressing the complex, interconnectedness of Earth’s systems that require cross-sectoral collaboration, thus supporting the mission’s call for integration and multi-sectoral stakeholder approaches.

5 Lessons Learned (0.5 page)

Challenges and Solutions

- Description of the challenges faced during the pilot activity. Provide a detailed description of the specific challenges encountered during the pilot activity. This could include logistical issues, engagement difficulties, resource limitations, or any unexpected obstacles. Explain how these challenges impacted the pilot activity. Discuss any delays, disruptions, or changes that had to be made as a result.
- Solutions implemented to overcome these challenges. Describe the strategies and actions that were implemented to overcome these challenges. Be specific about what was done to address each challenge. Did they fully resolve the issues? Were there any remaining difficulties? Provide an honest evaluation of what worked and what didn't.

The biggest challenge is underestimating the amount of work involved in the minutiae of planning – dropping the ball in any of the vulnerable links in the chain of progressing toward implementation will doom the event. Managing reservations, securing a venue that will fit everyone and has the computer equipment to engage everyone, Internet connectivity issues, other logistics, recruiting and retaining volunteers, securing financial support and sponsorship, even the weather – these all produce challenges that must be met and mitigated successfully for a detailed event such as the Baltic region hackathon to run smoothly. There were some last-minute changes in the registrants, which could have easily derailed eight months of dedicated labor, that fortunately were resolved in time.

While we didn’t have the linguistic barriers one might have with cross-border collaboration endeavors such as this, having an event that aims to convey complex scientific information in a language neither the teachers nor the audiences understand well is in of itself a huge challenge. In a recent activity hosted under one of the Horizon sister projects, SHORE, it was found that almost all material curated from available global resources were in English. While most Baltic Sea citizens have a good command of spoken English, very few have the background to teach marine sciences in a language other than the native languages of the area, which currently number 10.

What did work beautifully is a collective energy. Dedication and passion of everyone involved in the event, from organizers to teachers to students and mentors.

Best Practices

- Best practices identified during the activity.
- Recommendations for future activities based on these best practices.

Hackathons represent best practices in ocean literacy pedagogy by blending technology, collaboration, and real-world problem-solving to engage both learners and the broader community. They encourage innovative, hands-on learning experiences, promote inclusivity, and help develop practical, interactive resources that enhance ocean education. By leveraging digital tools in this way, hackathons can play a transformative role in making ocean literacy more accessible, engaging, and impactful for diverse audiences.

1. Hands-On Learning through Technology engage participants in experiential learning, which is essential in ocean literacy. By developing digital tools such as apps, interactive websites, or data-driven models, participants directly apply knowledge of ocean issues in practical ways. This interactive learning reinforces key ocean literacy concepts—such as ocean processes, human impacts on the ocean, and the importance of conservation—by allowing learners to create solutions and experiences that others can use to better understand these topics.

2. Creating Digital Resources for Education can be used as tools in ocean literacy pedagogy and are invaluable in the classrooms, for workshops, and supporting informal learning environments, promoting broader awareness and understanding of the ocean.

3. Hackathons are inherently collaborative, bringing together individuals with diverse skills and perspectives to solve challenges. This teamwork mirrors how ocean literacy should be taught: through interdisciplinary approaches that connect science with other disciplines as well as with policy, and community engagement. In the process, participants not only learn from one another but also contribute to solutions that enhance ocean education. Collaborative problem-solving is a critical component of understanding how we can protect and sustain ocean ecosystems.

4. By focusing on real-world problems such as ocean pollution, climate change, or habitat destruction, hackathons tie technology use to pressing global issues. This connection helps learners understand the urgency of ocean-related challenges and brings a personal aspect to the mix, making ocean literacy more relevant and impactful. Hackathons create a sense of urgency, motivating participants to create tools and solutions that could contribute to the real-world protection and sustainability of the oceans.

5. Hackathons empower diverse audiences, from students and educators to professionals and the general public. The use of digital tools allows individuals with varying levels of knowledge to contribute in meaningful ways, fostering inclusivity in ocean literacy education. Through accessible online platforms like DigiEduHack.com, anyone with an interest in ocean issues can participate, even if they don't have a deep background in marine science, making ocean literacy more inclusive and widespread.

6. By encouraging innovation in education, hackathons advance ocean literacy in the digital age. Educators and participants may employ a range of models and games - or make their own - that make learning about the ocean more engaging. The creative energy of a hackathon can inspire novel approaches to teaching ocean science—transforming traditional education methods into interactive, technology-driven experiences that capture the attention of diverse learners.

7. Building Digital Literacy Alongside Ocean Literacy - hackathons not only promote ocean literacy but also help participants build digital literacy, which is becoming increasingly important for future generations and aligns with the EU’s Digital Education Plan 2021-2027. This dual focus on ocean and digital literacy ensures a holistic education approach that prepares learners to address global challenges with the tools of tomorrow.

8. Engaging Europe - hackathons can be organized online or in hybrid formats, allowing pan-European participation. This broad reach enables diverse perspectives to be brought to ocean literacy, making the pedagogy more global and interconnected. Participants from different regions and cultures can contribute ideas and solutions, enhancing the quality and diversity of digital tools that support ocean education worldwide.

9. Hackathons encourage long-term impact by inspiring continued development of digital tools after the event. Tools or prototypes created during a hackathon can evolve into fully developed products that enhance ocean literacy pedagogy over time. Participants may continue refining apps, websites, or digital learning platforms, ensuring the longevity and expansion of ocean education initiatives.

PREP4BLUE resources

- Comment on how useful PREP4BLUE’s citizen engagement resources were in helping you plan, implement and evaluate your activity. How could they be improved?

Citizen engagement resources are critical for other events but contributed little to the hackathon because of the nature of the event as a pedagogical tool, as explained previously. Future iterations would include a PREP4BLUE citizen engagement game plan.

6 Conclusion and Recommendations (0.5 page)

Conclusion

- Summary of the overall experience and outcomes of the pilot activity.

The Baltic Region Hackathon sponsored a collaborative, fast-paced environment where participants—ranging from students to experts—work together to develop digital solutions addressing ocean-related challenges. The overall experience involved problem-solving using

technology to utilize tools like 360-degree games, and data visualizations focused on ocean conservation, climate change, pollution, and biodiversity.

Overall Experiences:

Collaborative Problem-Solving: Participants work in teams, combining different skills to tackle real-world ocean issues.

Learning through Technology: Through hands-on development of digital tools, participants deepened their understanding of ocean science and gained practical experience in tech-based education.

Creative Innovation: The hackathon fostered innovative thinking, leading to new ideas for communicating ocean literacy and possible solutions to environmental challenges to diverse audiences.

Networking and Knowledge Exchange: Experts were able to share insights, strategies, and expertise to student participants, contributing to a broader community of ocean literacy advocates.

Outcomes:

- Digital tools for education: tangible products engage users with ocean science
- Both participants and the broader community are educated about the importance of ocean conservation and sustainability, that has sparked ongoing interest in marine issues
- Participants were able to enhance both digital and ocean literacy, acquiring technical skills and knowledge that can be applied to future ocean-related projects
- the hackathon has fostered lasting collaborations among participant that can contribute to long-term ocean literacy initiatives
- The online event encouraged a global exchange of ideas, bringing diverse perspectives to ocean education and broadening the reach of ocean literacy efforts

An ocean literacy hackathon such as the Baltic Region Hackathon is an immersive, impactful experience that results in both innovative digital tools and increased engagement with ocean conservation issues, benefiting both the participants and the wider community

Recommendations for Upscaling/Replicating the Action

- Specific recommendations for future pilot activities, including upscaling and replication. Strategies for expanding stakeholder networks. Methods to engage a broader audience.
- What recommendations do you have for facilitating citizen participation in future Mission Ocean activities?

We are in the process of creating a toolkit for organizers of ocean literacy hackathons that will be disseminated widely via the various Horizon platforms for research dissemination, such as the Horizon Research Booster, as well as open source platforms such as Zenodo.

INVOICED TO: INSTITUT DE CIÈNCIES DEL MAR (CSIC)
Passeig Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37-39 08003 Barcelona, Spain NIF: Q2818002D

REFERENCE: Prep4Blue Empowering Citizens through Pilot activity funding

Budget quote for the pilot action:
Baltic Region Hackathon

2250 €

REMITTANCE:

Account holder: Social Innovation Actions MTÜ
BIC: TRWIBEB1XXX
IBAN: BE74 9050 9181 0507

Social Innovation Actions MTÜ

Annex P3. Self-Evaluation Report for PA3: The Sea of Sounds

PREP4BLUE Pilot activity reporting template: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report

Us: The Sea of Sounds

Go360 s.r.o.

Project Duration:

25.07.2024 to 06.09.2024

Project Coordinator:

Michal Lovecky

Collaborators/Partners:

OceanSounds Germany (Dr. Heike Vester)

OceanSounds Norway (Ellyne Hamran)

Molobyen (Moa Bjornson)

Prosjekt67 (Goran Moya)

Seanergy.Art

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
Introduction.....	4
Methodology.....	5
Implementation.....	7
Results and Impact assessment.....	9
Lessons Learned.....	10
Conclusion and Recommendations.....	11
Bibliography.....	12
Appendix.....	13

Executive Summary

The Us: The Sea of Sounds pilot action, co-funded by Prep4Blue, aimed to raise public awareness about underwater noise pollution and its impact on marine ecosystems, specifically cetaceans. Using virtual reality (VR) technology, the project offered participants an immersive experience of marine soundscapes in the Vestfjord (a prototype), enabling them to understand how noise pollution affects species like whales and dolphins. The project also included educational workshops, live listening stations, and large-format images to provide a comprehensive learning experience. The key objectives were to engage the public in marine conservation, foster understanding of noise pollution, and strengthen local community involvement.

The pilot action successfully engaged over 320 participants, including local residents and international visitors. A key outcome was the high level of public engagement, with many participants expressing surprise at the biodiversity in the Vestfjord. The project benefited from the involvement of local stakeholders and volunteers during the preparation phase, whose efforts in cross-promoting the event brought a larger, more diverse audience. The combination of activities - VR, presentations, and interactive sessions - proved highly effective in creating a deeper connection between participants and marine conservation issues.

Future recommendations include continuing to involve local stakeholders early in the preparation process, as their participation was crucial to the event's success. Expanding outreach through a diverse set of complementary activities will help attract a broader audience. Building on the strong local networks established during this pilot will be essential to scaling up and replicating the project.

Introduction

The pilot action *Us: The Sea of Sounds* was conceived in response to the growing need for increased public awareness of marine ecosystems, particularly the critical issue of underwater noise pollution and its impact on marine life. Noise pollution significantly disrupts the communication, navigation, and behaviors of marine species, particularly cetaceans such as whales and dolphins [1], [2]. This project aimed to raise awareness and foster a deeper understanding of the marine soundscape by engaging citizens in an immersive, educational experience. Through virtual reality (VR), participants could embody pilot whales and experience first-hand how sound pollution distorts their underwater environment. This action aligns directly with the Mission Ocean objective to protect and restore ecosystems and biodiversity, addressing both the threats to marine life and the lack of public awareness surrounding these issues [3]. *Us: The Sea of Sounds* sheds light on how human activities, particularly noise from boats and industrial activity, harm marine life. The immersive VR experience was designed not only to educate the public but also to inspire a sense of stewardship. Additionally, it aligned with social inclusion goals by engaging a diverse range of participants and fostering shared responsibility for ocean conservation. By providing an innovative, interactive medium for participants to engage with these issues, the project directly contributes to Mission Ocean's goal of empowering citizens to participate in the restoration of oceans and waters.

Description of Organisation & Project

This collaborative initiative is led by an interdisciplinary team that combines marine science, technology, and public engagement. The project's core feature is a multiplayer VR experience ideated by creative XR producer Michal Lovecky and marine biologist Dr. Heike Vester, whose work on cetacean vocalizations provided the scientific foundation for the project. The VR experience is complemented by educational workshops and community events aimed at expanding public understanding of marine soundscapes and the broader challenges facing marine biodiversity. The geographical focus of the pilot action was Bodo, Norway, a coastal city that serves as a gateway to the biodiverse Vestfjord. This location allowed the project to engage both local communities and international visitors.

Connection to Mission Ocean Objectives

The project contributes to the protection and restoration of marine ecosystems by raising awareness of sound pollution's impact on biodiversity. By engaging citizens in an immersive experience, the project promotes public understanding of marine life's vulnerability to human activities. Furthermore, the VR workshops and community discussions fostered a participatory approach to ocean conservation, in line with *Mission Ocean's* objectives to involve citizens in co-designing and co-implementing sustainable solutions. By leveraging VR technology, the project provided participants with an emotional and sensory connection to the ocean, contributing to several ocean literacy principles: knowledge, awareness, emotional connections, and access and experience [4]. Additionally, the co-design workshops with scientists, educators, and local community members encouraged participants to contribute ideas and feedback to improve the VR experience.

Methodology

We adopted a participatory and co-design approach, ensuring that the VR experience and accompanying educational activities were shaped through close collaboration with marine scientists, local stakeholders, volunteers, and the public. This participatory process aimed to foster social inclusion and actively involve the local community, aligning with Mission Ocean's goals of empowering citizens and creating a sense of ownership over marine conservation efforts [3]. The preparatory phase emphasized fast prototyping and iterative development of the VR experience. Given the limited timeline, we focused on rapidly refining the VR content to communicate the impacts of underwater noise pollution on cetaceans in an engaging, artistically coherent, and experiential manner. Our co-design process involved OceanSounds and local volunteers, many of whom were recruited through the stakeholder's network. These volunteers played a critical role in playtesting the VR experience, offering feedback that informed adjustments to the immersive interaction and narrative flow. This collaborative methodology ensured that the experience was scientifically accurate while being accessible and compelling for a broad audience. Throughout the preparatory phase, we engaged with local partners, including businesses, cultural institutions, and the municipality. These partnerships were instrumental in securing resources for the exhibition and ensuring wide-reaching community participation. Simultaneously, we developed promotional and educational materials designed to raise awareness of marine soundscapes and noise pollution, including large-format prints of Dr. Vester's photographs, a presentation on cetacean vocalization, and a workshop on marine sound libraries.

Preparation Phase (July 25 – August 22)

- Iterative development of the VR experience in collaboration with OceanSounds, including playtesting by local volunteers and stakeholders, which was also open to the public.
- Coordination with local partners such as Prosjekt67, Molobyen, and other cultural institutions
- Development of promotional materials, including social media campaigns.
- Creation of educational content for the exhibition

Implementation Phase (August 23 – August 25)

The exhibition took place over three days at the Prosjekt67 gallery, and feedback collected on the first days was implemented overnight, improving the participant experience in real-time.

Evaluation and Reporting Phase (August 26 – September 26)

- Conducting in-person and online meetings with stakeholders and partners to gather feedback.
- Analysis of feedback collected from the public during the exhibition, as well as informal interviews and discussions with participants.
- Follow-up meetings with participants interested in further collaboration, as well as preparing and submitting the final report for Prep4Blue and other key stakeholders.

Participants and Stakeholders

- **Funding entities:** Prep4Blue, Sparebank 1 Nord-Norge, Lighthouse Foundation, Go360
- **OceanSounds:** The scientific partner which provided expertise in cetacean vocalizations, conducted educational workshops, and contributed underwater sound recordings.
- **Molobyen:** A local developer offering an artist residency and free exhibition space
- **Prosjekt67:** The independent gallery space.
- **Beddingen Kulturhus:** Providing bar facilities and cross-promotional activities.
- **Go360 s.r.o.:** The development team responsible for the creative of the VR experience.
- **Municipality (Bodo 2024):** Attracting both local residents and international tourists.
- **Nord Uni. Students:** Volunteers participated in the preparation and implementation phases
- **Local Businesses:** Promoted the event and participated in complementary activities.
- **General Public:** Their feedback played a crucial role in assessing the project's impact, and several participants contributed suggestions for future iterations.

Strategy to Involve Citizens

- Free access to all events, ensuring barriers like cost or physical accessibility did not limit participation.
- Engaging local volunteers as playtesters and content advisors to ensure the experience was shaped by community input.
- Designing the exhibition as an interactive space, where visitors could engage with the soundscapes and contribute to discussions on ocean conservation. For visitors unable to experience the VR directly, alternative engagement methods (e.g., visual elements and live-streamed VR content) were offered to ensure inclusivity.
- Utilizing semi-structured interviews to encourage reflection on the VR experience and how it influenced participants' understanding of marine conservation. Feedback mechanisms allowed participants to share suggestions for improving both the educational and immersive content.

Leaving No One Behind

All activities were accessible to people with disabilities; however, several limitations emerged. One key challenge was the lack of a digital alternative for those unable to attend in person. For visitors who could not wear the VR headset, we offered a live stream from one of the VR headsets projected onto a wall. Potentially, however practically necessary, the absence of flexible event times might have been a limiting factor for some. Similarly, the limitation of the VR setup, which allowed four participants at a time, led to long waiting queues due to unexpectedly high interest in the event, potentially excluding those with tighter schedules. Additionally, the large-format prints were difficult to fully appreciate when the VR was running, as the space became crowded.

Implementation

The action unfolded over an eight-week period, with a focus on co-design, community engagement, and rapid prototyping.

(July 25 – August 1) - The first week involved reviewing the Prep4Blue materials and holding design meetings to align the project with participatory processes. Knowledge sharing took place between the stakeholders.

(August 2 – August 8) - The project shifted into rapid prototyping of the VR experience which began with input from local volunteers and stakeholders. The team also held additional preparatory meetings to integrate citizen engagement strategies into the exhibition and ensure that all elements would promote broad public participation.

(August 9 – August 15) - The third week focused on the co-design of all exhibition components. This included finalizing the Ocean Sounds library, holding meetings with key stakeholders, and creating promotional materials. Project was registered in the Bodo 2024 cultural calendar and cross-promotion activities were planned with local businesses and cultural venues.

(August 16 – August 22) - The final preparatory week saw intensive playtesting of the VR experience, incorporating real-time feedback from volunteers. All exhibition materials were finalized and the team also worked closely with Prosjekt67 to set up the exhibition space.

(August 23 – August 25) - The main event took place over three days at the Prosjekt67 gallery, drawing significant public interest and participation with over 320 people attending the event. The exhibition was open on Friday, August 23rd, from 18:00 to 22:00, and on Saturday and Sunday, from 14:00 to 22:00. Each day featured a presentation and workshop at 15:00 and 19:00, which provided visitors with an opportunity to learn about cetacean vocalizations and the effects of underwater noise pollution. The live listening station at the entrance allowed visitors to listen to real-time underwater sounds from the nearby harbor. The VR experience, which ran throughout the event, was fully booked with four participants per session, each session lasting 10-15 minutes. After each session, participants took part in an onboarding and offboarding process, where semi-structured interviews gathered feedback on their experience. This feedback was invaluable in iterating the VR experience overnight, allowing the team to enhance the simulation for the next day. The event was further supported by cross-promoted activities, such as Fauna Friday, a DJ evening at a local sauna, and cultural gatherings at Beddingen Kulturhus.

(August 26 – September 11) - The team conducted a thorough analysis of participant feedback and assessed the success of the event in achieving its objectives. This included follow-up meetings with stakeholders and those members of the public who expressed interest in future collaboration.

(September 12 – September 26) - The team focused on writing and submitting reports for Prep4Blue, stakeholders, and participants. This period also involved planning next steps for the project, identifying key areas for future development and scaling.

Participant Involvement

Local volunteers were integral in the promotion of the event, prototyping and playtesting throughout the preparatory and implementation phase, and the organization of cross-promotion activities. During the main event, feedback from both local residents and international visitors significantly influenced the rapid development of the VR experience, with overnight adjustments being made based on participant input. This iterative approach allowed the project to remain responsive to emergent behaviors and suggestions, which will inform future iterations of the VR experience and broader project activities.

Image 1: Start of the presentation and workshop on Whale Sound Library by Dr. Heike Vester.

Image 2: One of the VR sessions, mixed participants and projection on the wall

Results and Impact Assessment

The *Us: The Sea of Sounds* pilot action successfully engaged over 320 participants during the main event, with an approximately equal split between local residents and international visitors. The participants ranged in age from 5 to 74 years old.

Key Findings

One of the most impactful findings was the widespread surprise expressed by local participants regarding the biodiversity of the Vestfjord. Many were unaware of the variety of cetacean species in the area, with one participant stating, *"I've lived here for over 40 years and have seen and could name maybe three (whale species)."* This reflects a significant gap in local knowledge.

Participants were highly engaged with the VR element of the exhibition, particularly enjoying the experiential and immersive nature of the project. One participant remarked, *"This was amazing! Is this really how they see and what they hear underwater?"* This kind of feedback demonstrates that the VR experience not only captured the participants' attention but also raised their interest in learning more about marine ecosystems and soundscapes. Many who initially came for the VR stayed for the presentation and workshop afterward, and vice versa, indicating the complementary nature of the activities. A few even returned on multiple days to experience the updated VR content based on their feedback. The event's success was further underscored by its official recommendation badge from the Bodo 2024 Cultural Capital calendar, marking it as one of the highlights of the city's cultural week. Participants shared that the event was the most engaging activity they had attended during their stay in Bodo.

However, there were some misaligned expectations among participants on the first day. Some expected the VR experience to be more like a traditional video, rather than an abstract, artistic prototype, which led to some initial confusion. Despite this, many participants expressed a desire to see the project develop further, reflecting a strong interest in the future potential of the experience.

The short-term outcomes of the pilot action include:

- Direct participation and raised awareness among over 320 people, evidenced by the feedback collected through 54 qualitative interviews and discussions. Many participants expressed surprise at the extent of marine biodiversity in Vestfjord and engaged in follow-up questions.
- Increased interest in ocean conservation, with several participants donating to OceanSounds, the NGO partner, after attending the event.
- Twelve volunteers were directly involved in the preparation and co-design of the VR experience.
- Strengthened partnerships between the project team, local cultural institutions, and international collaborators, creating a foundation for future cooperation.

The long-term outcomes include the following initiatives and plans:

- The project has fostered an ongoing commitment to co-develop the VR experience further. The stakeholders have already started exploring new funding opportunities to continue.
- Plans are underway to distribute the VR experience to other local spaces, such as galleries and community centers, ensuring the project continues to engage the public. However, further development and restructuring of the experience is necessary.
- Building a broader partnership network is another long-term goal, with discussions initiated to involve additional educational institutions and environmental organizations.

Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Targets

Through the immersive VR experience, participants were able to gain a more intimate understanding of marine soundscapes, making the abstract issue of underwater noise pollution more relatable and comprehensible. The interactive elements such as the live listening station and workshop sessions following the OceanSounds presentations fostered a participatory environment, where citizens were not only informed but also empowered to ask questions and seek deeper involvement in conservation efforts. Overall, the pilot action successfully met its short-term objectives by engaging the public in marine conservation issues and raising awareness of the impacts of underwater noise pollution. The project also laid a strong foundation for long-term impact, with concrete steps being taken to ensure the continued development and dissemination of the interactive educational experience.

Preparatory and evaluation tables 1-3 are part of the report's appendix to provide further detail.

Lessons Learned

High public interest led to crowded spaces and long waiting times for the VR experience, which reduced access to other exhibition elements like the large-format prints. A key stakeholder's illness during the first two weeks delayed preparations, but allowed other partners to step in and offer support. Limited volunteers and the need to keep the VR running continuously reduced time for feedback collection, prompting a shift to more informal group discussions rather than structured interviews, which proved effective given the circumstances.

To address these challenges, we streamlined the VR experience through daily iterations and optimized the seating for waiting participants, but a larger venue and more VR headsets would have helped manage the unexpectedly high turnout. In the future, reservations for popular activities could help distribute participants throughout the day.

The Prep4Blue citizen engagement toolbox was valuable for mapping relevant aspects of this participatory activity. It helped to guide us through the planning process, helping ensure inclusivity and engagement. However, a more streamlined version or direct access to actionable steps tailored to events like ours could have saved time when applying the toolkit.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The Us: The Sea of Sounds pilot action was a significant success, engaging over 320 participants and raising awareness about underwater noise pollution and marine biodiversity. The combination of the immersive VR experience, educational workshops, and live listening station provided a multi-dimensional approach. Despite challenges such as crowded spaces and limited time for feedback, the project met its goals of citizen engagement, public education, and strengthening local partnerships.

One of the key factors in the project's success was the inclusion of local stakeholders and participants during the preparation phase. Their involvement, particularly in promoting and cross-promoting the event, helped attract a diverse and larger audience than anticipated. The collaborative mix of activities, rather than a single event, created a richer experience that appealed to a broader range of participants. Engaging like-minded stakeholders who were willing to contribute extra effort was crucial, and these relationships were largely built through the personal networks of the core team.

For future projects, we would recommend to continue focusing on inclusive preparation, involving interested local stakeholders early on, and maintaining a diverse set of complementary activities to draw in a broader audience.

Bibliography

- [1] P. L. Tyack, "Implications for Marine Mammals of Large-Scale Changes in the Marine Acoustic Environment," *J. Mammal.*, vol. 89, no. 3, pp. 549–558, Jun. 2008, doi: 10.1644/07-MAMM-S-307R.1.
- [2] L. S. Weilgart, "A Brief Review of Known Effects of Noise on Marine Mammals," *Int. J. Comp. Psychol.*, Dec. 2007, Accessed: Sep. 06, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-Brief-Review-of-Known-Effects-of-Noise-on-Marine-Weilgart/585c7467b02878350b0bc12da493f58d522f2d42>
- [3] "Restore our Ocean and Waters - European Commission." Accessed: Sep. 06, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en
- [4] E. McKinley, D. Burdon, and R. J. Shellock, "The evolution of ocean literacy: A new framework for the United Nations Ocean Decade and beyond," *Mar. Pollut. Bull.*, vol. 186, p. 114467, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114467.

Media Coverage and Links

1. Bodo 2024 Cultural Calendar Event Page

<https://kulturkalender.bodo2024.no/Event/7425233?scheduleId=388072&culture=nb-NO&fromDate=2024-08-23>

2. Air Molobyen Project Mention

<https://www.airmolobyen.org/>

3. FB Event Page with additional images and information

https://www.facebook.com/events/3323729407936384/?active_tab=discussion

4. Article on Molobyen Blog (Norwegian)

https://molobyen.no/aktuelt/2024/na-inviteres-byen-ned-i-havet-for-a-oppleve-virkeligheten/?fbclid=IwY2xjawFJaNjleHRuA2FlbQIxMQABHW3NDIKPnVtAU-tc5u8NHJFZKc7W7Oqq-QhOhB1oHe_Qz2y5egASpkFiQw_aem_-HBcbDCDZi_zmWgNqICUGw

5. Norwegian Newspaper Articles (behind paywall)

<https://www.bodonu.no/inviterer-byen-til-en-unik-opplevelse-fra-havets-dyp-virkelig-en-lidenskap/s/5-159-85345>

<https://www.an.no/du-kan-fa-en-spesiell-vestfjord-opplevelse-gleder-meg-til-a-vise-det-fram/s/5-4-2016926>

Appendix

PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper

Preparatory and Evaluation Tables from the Prep4Blue Toolbox

Table 1. Guiding reflection questions for step 1 – preparing for citizen engagement. Taken from Bjørkan et al. (2023) Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of approaches. Milestone 6. Prep4Blue.

Guiding questions	Comments
What is the focus area of the project?	Engaging citizens in raising awareness of underwater noise pollution and its impact on marine life through VR.
What type of problem are you dealing with?	Uncontrollable (marine noise pollution).
What is the scope of risk?	Complex & Uncertainty (multiple stakeholders, ecological, and social impacts).
What do you hope to obtain by including citizens in your project?	Increase public awareness, promote marine stewardship, and gather experiential feedback.
Define what type of input you will need in order to succeed	Co-production and reflection (citizen feedback, stakeholder expertise).
Who are the relevant actors?	Scientists, development team, local volunteers, cultural institutions, local businesses, the general public, and international visitors.
What level of participation do you aim for?	Involve & Collaborate; Active participation in feedback, co-design, and public engagement.
Place activities in a timeline. Do some activities depend on the implementation of other activities? At what stage should citizens be engaged in my project?	Mainly during the main event, with some input during prototyping (weeks 2-4) and post-event feedback (weeks 6-7).

Table 2: Guiding reflection questions for step 3 – Monitoring and assessing citizen engagement. Adapted from Bjørkan et al. (2023) Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of approaches. Milestone 6. Prep4Blue.

Questions before and during start of project	Comments
What type of participation is our aim?	Interactive participation, with citizens co-designing and providing feedback on marine conservation efforts.
What depth of participation do we want?	A balance between experiential engagement through VR and reflective participation via interviews and workshops.
How can we pinpoint exactly type and level of participation?	On-site semi-structured interviews, observation of emergent behavior, feedback collection.
Are the methods selected appropriate?	Qualitative methods: semi-structured interviews, observation, and feedback forms worked but were constrained by time.
What is working well/not working well and why?	Playtesting and VR feedback loops were successful; however, limited time and high demand restricted in-depth post-experience discussions.
What is the actual impact of the process on the results?	Feedback directly informed rapid VR iterations during the event, improving user experience.
What is the actual impact of the process on the participants? (do they feel empowered?)	Participants felt more informed and engaged but lacked time for deeper reflection due to queues post-VR exposure. Presentation followed by the workshop worked better in this.

Did we meet our aims and objectives?	Yes, in raising awareness and gathering feedback; future iterations could benefit from more structured, longer engagement opportunities.
Were the methods selected appropriate?	Appropriate but should be refined to allow for more in-depth feedback sessions and reduce participant wait times.
What worked well and why?	Immediate feedback implementation improved the VR experience; stakeholder involvement in refining the project.
What did not work well and why?	High demand for the VR experience led to shorter feedback sessions, limiting deeper reflection on the experience.
What are the lessons learned?	Structured time for feedback needs to be allocated in future iterations; managing high demand with better scheduling.
Did we meet participants aims and expectations?	Most participants reported satisfaction with the experience but wanted more time for interaction and reflection.
What are the participants' views on the outcome, process and impact?	Positive views on raising awareness, experientiality, gaining new knowledge; some participants suggested extending engagement opportunities in future events, and hope for further development of the project to provide more polished experience.

Table 3. Evaluating outcomes in Mission Ocean initiatives. Taken from Bjørkan et al. (2023) Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of approaches. Milestone 6. Prep4Blue.

Goals/Purpose of your Mission initiative	Possible Indicators	How to Obtain Data	Important Assumptions
To better inform stakeholders and the public	Number of participants; Increased awareness and understanding	Pre- and post-event interviews; workshop discussions	That awareness changes are due to the engagement, not external factors
Promote co-design and active participation	Number of participants involved in co-design activities	Participation records, feedback forms	That participants feel their contributions are valued
Empower participants for future engagements	Willingness to engage in future projects	Follow-up interviews	Continued engagement is directly linked to the project's activities

Event Materials & Images

Annex P4. Self-Evaluation Report for PA4: Sea Synergy Oyster Project

PREP4BLUE Pilot activity reporting template: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report

Sea Synergy Oyster Project (SSOP)

Sea Synergy Marine Awareness, Research & Activity Centre

Project Duration:

[20/07/2024] to [25/11/2024]

Project Coordinator:

[Anna Kellagher]

Collaborators/Partners:

[Portmagee Tidy Towns]

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report	1
Executive Summary (0.5 page).....	3
1 Introduction (1 page).....	3
2 Methodology (1-2 pages).....	4
3 Implementation (1 page).....	6
4 Results and Impact assessment (1-2 pages).....	8
5 Lessons Learned (0.5 page).....	10
6 Conclusion and Recommendations (0.5 page).....	11
7 Bibliography.....	12
8 ANNEX 1 PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper.....	13

Executive Summary (0.5 page)

Overview of the Pilot Action

This Pilot action funded by Prep4Blue involved delivering a showcase of the key findings of the Sea Synergy Oyster Project (SSOP) to date and an engagement section through holding a public consultation with the community on their thoughts, hopes and concerns for future *Ostrea edulis* reef restoration in their channel and helped formulate what this action would look like in the future. The event took place in the Skelig Experience Center near the village of Portmagee on the 10th of November. As well as encouraging and promoting citizen science through the use of the iNaturalist app and the collective project started on iNaturalist by Sea Synergy. We also delivered a follow up talk similar to that of our showcase at a local climate event in Cahersiveen, allowing us to reach a wider audience.

These actions were taken with the aim to;

- 1) Increase the local community's ocean literacy & connection to their coastline
- 2) Increase in citizen science reporting of marine biodiversity
- 3) Empowered coastal community to participate in local nature restoration plans

Main Outcomes

- Increased understanding among the community of *O. edulis* and the Portmagee channel
- Out of 36 registered, 30 people attended the showcase & consultation & anonymous feedback forms were submitted. An additional 22 people attended our second talk in Cahersiveen
- 43 people in addition to ourselves adding observations to project on iNaturalist and a further 194 people contributing to the project by helping to identify and validate observations
- Improved understanding of what the community wants from the project including some innovative ideas on how the project should progress.

Future Recommendations

The value of speaking to people directly can not be understated when trying to get the community to attend events. We would like to devote more time to this in the future. More public consultations, showcase and awareness events and workshops will be key to the success of this project.

Introduction (1 page)

Background and Context

Over the last two years the Sea Synergy Oyster Project (SSOP) has been researching the relic native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) population and the diverse biological community of the Portmagee Channel in SW Ireland. To establish baseline data and answer key questions pertinent to oyster habitat restoration.

O. edulis populations have declined by 95% in Irish & UK waters (Preston et al., 2020) and an estimated 85% of oyster reefs in the world's oceans have been lost, making oyster reefs one of the world's most imperilled marine habitats (Beck., et al., 2011). The channel is home of the largest living specimens of *O. edulis* recorded (Quigley & Flannery, 2014) with our own research showing that 17% is over the typical max adult size of 110mm in shell length. The Global and national scarcity of *O. edulis* combined with the remarkable size of some individuals and their corresponding age (30+ years) make the Portmagee Channel's relic oyster population incredibly important. The Portmagee channel is also an environmentally significant area as it is a Special Area of Conservation (SAC), and is part of the recently designated Greater Skellig Hope Spot by Dr. Sylvia Earle's Mission Blue and NPWS's Marine Park. Yet the oysters are not mentioned in any of the SAC reports and most local people are unaware of their presence or the significance of them or the channel.

Describe Your Organisation/Project/Initiative

We have 10-years of experience in engaging the public through delivering modules of marine background to schools and through public events in South Kerry and nationally e.g. conferences, festivals. Through those engagements we have created strong bonds with the community. Data of the Oyster Project has been collected for the past two years and both years we have received funding to hold citizen science workshops to engage the local community. This showcase is the first public announcement of our findings from the past 2 years of research and open consultation with the community to co-design how the project will progress.

How this Action Connects to Mission Ocean Objectives

The objectives of our project are to showcase the key findings of the project to date, collaborate with the community to decide how the project will progress and increase citizen science reporting in the area using the project on iNaturalist. Showcasing the key findings will increase ocean literacy among participants and provide them with a better understanding of the beauty, biodiversity and importance of their local coast, improving the connection of the community with their coastline. Collaborating with members of the community in the form of a public consultation and anonymous feedback forms provides an opportunity for the community to be more involved in the way the project progresses, empowering them to get involved with future conservation and restoration work happening in their area. By starting a project on iNaturalist, promoting it and explaining to people how to use it and what their observations will be used for will increase citizen science reporting of marine biodiversity.

The project also aligns with several Citizen Engagement outcomes; our consultation with the community is an example of 'Trial deliberative democratic mechanisms for co-design of restoration solutions'. Our showcase events and project on iNaturalist 'promote apps for citizen science data collection' and involve the launching of a 'citizen science campaign as part of participatory research initiatives'. While delivering the ocean literacy principles was not a primary goal of this project by its nature the showcase communicated some of these principles, The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems & the ocean and humans are inextricably connected.

1 Methodology (1-2 pages)

Approach and Methods

Multiple methods were used to advertise and promote all aspects of the project (such as reels & posts on social media, physical posters, mentioning in person at different events, sharing in multiple community group chat and sending individual email invites to relevant parties, stakeholders and communities. This multi method approach was taken to ensure we reached a wide and diverse audience. The presentation at the showcase involved 4 different speakers (John Murphy representative for the Portmagee tidy towns, Jack O'Donovan Tra from Fairseas and two members of the Sea Synergy team, this combined with the visual nature of the presentation and the short documentaries spaced throughout kept the presentation interesting and engaging. Feedback was also gathered through multiple methods, world cafe type discussion created an open and relaxed environment for the exchanging ideas, with the hope for people to feel comfortable expressing any concerns they may have. Colouring pages and activities were provided for kids to help families feel welcome. We also provided the opportunity for people to provide feedback anonymously with optional online feedback surveys and paper forms at the event. Holding a second smaller event as part of the climate Ceardaiocht festival in Cahersiveen (largest population centre in our rural community) allowed us to reach another audience.

Describe the Pilot Action Plan and Timeline

- Promote a citizen science project on iNaturalist throughout the course of the project (July-November)
- Work with Portmagee tidy towns to select a venue and time for showcase (September)

- Drawing keyfindings from research and creating a visual and interactive presentation with them (september & october)
- Advertising showcase and consultation through a variety of platforms (october)
- Holding showcase & consultation (10/11/24)
- Additional talk on key findings of project (19/11/24)
- Reviewing feedback provided during consultation and in feedback forms (November)
- Report writing (15-25/11/24)

Participants and Stakeholders

While the community as a whole and other interested parties and stakeholders were invited, some of the main groups of participants included board members from the Portmagee Tidy Towns and a representative of Fairseas, who we both engaged in our presentation by introducing themselves and their work. Other participants were local children, members of local environmental groups, fishermen, people from the restaurant industry & representatives of the Ukrainian refugee community (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stakeholder Mapping for Oyster Project Showcase in Portmagee

As part of the Oyster Project we did 2 in-class workshops and 2 survey workshops. All participants of those, as well as known interested parties within the community were invited directly via email or phone. Additionally we used our presence on social media platforms as well as the venue's (The Skellig Experience Visitor Centre and Portmagee Tidy Towns) and Skellig Coast Tourism Network, totalling over 6k followers, to advertise the event on 5 occasions, tagging local businesses such as The Moorings, Atlantic Irish Seaweed & Wild Derrynane. Additionally we mentioned the upcoming showcase during other events and activities in the weeks upcoming to the event and left printed posters with businesses in Knightstown, Portmagee, Waterville & Cahersiveen.

We believe to have followed the LNOB guidelines, having approached all age groups and genders of all kinds of backgrounds by advertising through multiple platforms and being in direct contact with members of the refugee and migrant community through a whole suite of activities we offered over the summer to the socially disadvantaged.

2 Implementation (1 page)

Pilot Action – Description of Activities

Table 1. Adapted from table 5. Section 4 of engaging citizens with mission oceans report

	What do you want to know?	What evaluation methods will you use?	How will the evaluation be conducted?
Planning process	What the community knew on the topic before vs after our showcase event. What the community thinks of the project and what shape they want it to take in future.		
Engagement		World Cafe discussion & Feedback forms	The world cafe discussion will be conducted after showcase key finding of project and feedback forms will be handed out at the event and sent digitally and responses will be anonymous.
Benefits/ outcomes	More ocean literate community Pride of Place Increased citizen science recording Co-design of how the project progresses	Open casual environment for discussion & ability to give feed back or share concerns anonymously	Conducting discussion after talk sharing key findings will mean people are sharing opinions on a project they have a better understanding of. Feedback forms being both digital and physical makes them more accessible.

At the beginning of the summer a Project was started on iNaturalist,

<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/sea-synergy-oyster-project?tab=observations>

This project was a collective project that allowed anyone to contribute observations from our survey area to the Portmagee channel; these observations are public and other members of the community can help identify these observations. This project was promoted and explained throughout the year using posters, social media and at various talks and workshops.

Data from the SSOP was analysed for key findings to present at the showcase throughout September and October; such as how many oysters are in the channel, where are they in the channel, what is the health of the population (are they actively breeding etc.), what other life makes up the biological community of the Portmagee channel; marine species richness, terrestrial species richness, relative abundance of different taxa, no. epibiota of *O. edulis* and collating beautiful images to represent the wealth of biodiversity. In addition to this the public engagement work was summarised.

The documentary trailer was released on social media as 1st advertisement for showcase on 03/10/2024, which has been played over 2300 times on Instagram and Facebook (as of 20/11/2024)

<https://www.instagram.com/seasynergvireland/?hl=en> & <https://www.facebook.com/@SeaSynergy>

Date and time for the showcase were confirmed with The Skellig Experience Visitor Center on 01/10/24

An invitation email was sent to 97 invitees on 16/10/2024. Google booking form & advertising went live on 18/10/2024 (Figure 2), on our social media platforms, posters put up throughout the area and shared on 5 local whatsapp groups. The presentation was created in the days prior to run through in the centre on 04/11/2024, which can be seen here; [SSOP key findings](#)

2 days prior to event a Local Comedian did a video reel to advertise the event on Instagram

(<https://www.instagram.com/p/DCKJc4TNytL/>) and all those who had registered were sent a reminder email as well as a short pre event survey (<https://forms.gle/L1vJa39JGVXiZQJSA>).

Showcase and public consultation was held on 10/11/2024 (Figure 3).

- 2:30-2:40 Welcome & Introduction by Lucy Hunt, Founder of Sea Synergy
- 2:40-2:45 Fairseas Mission Blue Video with Sylvia Earle shown to showcase Greater Skellig Coast Hope Spot
- 2:45-2:50 Talk by Jack O Donovan Trá Communications Officer, Fairseas
- 2:50-2:55 Talk by John Murphy, Portmagee Tidy Towns
- 2:55-3:20 Key Findings by Anna Kellagher Sea Synergy Research Officer [SSOP key findings](#)
- 3:20-3:25 Launch of short SSOP documentary (Figure 4) produced by Swimming Head Productions [Sea Synergy Oyster Project](#)
- 3:25-3:35 Q&A session
- 3:35-3:45 Tea & scones
- 3:45-4:45 World cafe discussion and co-design of projects next steps (details on this can be found below under results and impact assessment)

The day after the event an email was sent out to thank everyone who attended along with an anonymous feedback form (<https://forms.gle/W12kuoyXaARcBkN5A>)

Newspaper article in local newspaper Kerry's eye about the showcase was published on 20/11/2024 (Figure 5). A second key findings talk was given in the Cahersiveen marina (19/11/24) as part of the Climate Ceardaiocht Festival (<https://www.instagram.com/p/DCKbDbtMfig/>) 22 people attended and were invited to share their opinion on how the project progresses with short Q&A and anonymous feedback forms.

Figures 2 & 3. Flyer to advertise the event (posted on Social Media on 18/10/2024) and participants posing outside the Skelligs Experience Visitor Centre after the event (10/11/2024)

Figure 4 & 5. Watching documentary premier during showcase & Kerry’s Eye Newspaper Article reporting about Oyster Project findings and showcase printed on 20/11/2024

3 Results and Impact assessment (1-2 pages)

Table 2. Adapted from table 6 section 4 of the engaging citizens with mission oceans report, showing indicators for the success of our project goals and how we intend to monitor them.

Goals/purpose of your Mission project	Possible Indicators for your project	How to obtain data for your project	Important assumptions for your project
Showcase the key findings of the project to date to improve understanding of <i>O.edulis</i> and channel among community	Improved understanding	Pre and Post event surveys	That both the awareness and willingness to engage are as a result of the engagement activity, rather than any other factors.
Collaborate with the community to decide how the project will progress	Active involvement in discussion and willingness to engagement in the future	Feedback Survey & open discussion	
Increase citizen science reporting in the area using the project on iNaturalist.	Engagement in the iNaturalist Project	Stats automatically generated by iNat informing us about the number of observers, identifiers and observation.	

Table 3. Adapted from table 8 section 4 of the engaging citizens with mission oceans report, showing how citizens were involved in various aspects of the project

(Depth of citizen involvement)	Design/creation	Development	Implementation	Monitoring
Active (involve, collaborate, empower)		X	X	X
Responsive (consult)	X	X	X	X
Passive (inform)	X	X	X	X

Key Findings

Before the showcase 50% of participants were unaware that there were native oysters in the channel or that the channel was part of an SAC and 25% were unable to correctly identify the Native Oyster from other oysters (pacific and saddle). The post event feedback forms showed that 100% of people were now able to identify the native oyster, knew they were in the channel and that the channel was part of an SAC and what that means. Participants were also delighted about the idea to have the project grow into a restoration project with quotes like 'Fully in favour', 'Looks like potential is excellent', 'delighted', 'I think it would be very important'. Another great feedback was 'I think as a Tidy Towns group we need to do more with regard to informing our community', hoping that through change in promoting our events through other involved parties could change the turn out and community involvement in future events.

During the world cafe style discussion we asked 5 questions, after this point the discussion was led by the community. The 4 questions we asked where;

- How might we engage the public/community more in the oyster project?
- How might we restore the native oyster population in the Portmagee Channel?
- What other things do we need to consider with the project (ie. what did we miss)?
- Do you or does anyone you know have any concerns about an oyster restoration project and how might we address these concerns?
- What do you think an Oyster Restoration Project would bring to the region?

The key points from discussing these questions were;

- iNaturalist observation of the month (celebrating the citizen science contribution)
- Collaboration with local restaurants as a local source of shell
- increased awareness of oysters way increased foraging and chance for exploitation
- That preserve might mean prevention in others eyes
- The attraction of the ecosystem services a healthy Native Oyster population could have
- The desire of the community for a big picture approach - to include the freshwater systems, business and schools in the area.

Proposed Outcomes

Short-term Outcomes

Pre- and post-event feedback forms were used to measure the outcomes of the showcase. While 50% of the participants were not aware of the SAC or oyster population in the Portmagee Channel and another 25% couldn't identify a native oyster, all participants were confident in identification and knowledge on the population and protected area in the Portmagee Channel at the end of the showcase. Another short-term outcome was the excitement and awe generated among participants for the beauty, diversity of life and importance of their local channel.

Long-term Outcomes

Increased participation in future citizen science workshops and continued use of the iNaturalist app to contribute to research happening in their area. Which will help meet the Mission Ocean's objective to protect and restore marine & freshwater ecosystems through citizen science and app's. The discussion with the community on future activities of the project, including pilot reef restoration work along with the anonymous feedback forms provided valuable insight into how the community news the project and wonderful ideas on how the project should progress which we intend to implement in the future such as; Species/observation of the month on our social media channels to celebrate and provide recognition for the work of citizen scientists. include the community in helping to restore the native oyster population of the Portmagee Channel. Collaboration with local restaurants and pubs to start a shell recycling scheme that could be used to support restoration work. This meets the mission oceans objectives to protect and restore marine & freshwater ecosystems through the co-design of restoration solutions. This increased citizen science engagement and collaboration with the community to co-design how the SSOP moves forward contributes to Prep4Blue's goal to co-create and build cohesion between different aspects and stakeholders of an action.

Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Targets

Our project actively contributed to the goals of Mission Ocean and Pre4Blue by;

By working together with our community to co-design a *O. edulis* reef restoration project we are directly contributing to the restoration of marine ecosystems and by improving the communities understanding of the importance of the channel and building community pride for their local channel we are contributing to the protection of marine ecosystems. How this co-design and improved understanding was achieved is detailed in the methodology and implementation sections of this report.

By creating a project on iNaturalist for the Portmagee Channel, promoting it, explaining how it works and the importance of people contributing to it, we are helping to meet the goal of protecting and restoring the marine & freshwater ecosystems through launching citizen science campaigns and promoting apps for citizen science. How we went about creating and promoting this project on iNaturalist is detailed in the methodology and implementation sections of this report.

4 Lessons Learned (0.5 page)

Challenges and Solutions

Finding a relevant venue and best date to engage the community and stakeholders - as the event was based on a specific project in the Portmagee Channel we wanted to make sure to have it in as close proximity to the community to engage them, however the facilities locally were not ideal in the local community centre (no ability to present imagery and cold building) so we used the Skellig Experience Centre but there were limitations on times we could use this venue as it is an open tourist venue. That is why the event ended up being on a Sunday afternoon

which probably disengaged some of the civil service, national bodies that might normally attend during work hours and would have been interested in our project. The venue had also never hosted an event like this before so it took some technical manoeuvring but the centre was incredibly supportive and we worked together to make it work.

In future we would like to use a venue that was more flexible with time availability so we could decide the time to work best with the stakeholders we want to engage or perhaps have a working hours event for NGO's and civil service, government bodies and an evening event for the local community after working hours, but we would need more resources for this and accommodating venues. It would also be good to have a venue that was more accessible by public transport but this is hard in such a rural community. To better advertise the event and encourage people to attend we would collaborate more closely with local community groups like the Portmagee Tidy towns (who are very keen to be involved more in the future and were honest about needing to do better at passing along the information we give them to their community).

Best Practices

The format of the event was very well received and allowed for good engagement with the participants. Our feedback forms revealed that 100% of the participants enjoyed the event, found it informative and learned something new from it.

Having the showcase and time for some Q&A at the beginning and then some relaxation time with refreshments and chats to help warm up the discussion and feedback and consultation session was good. Only having 5 questions for the discussion was also good as it did not overwhelm the participants and it was facilitated in a very casual way so people felt comfortable speaking about how they felt about the project and the progress of the project. It also left time for people to lead the discussion in directions that were important to them.

PREP4BLUE resources

The resources provided to us were very lengthy and academic, and of limited use to actual practitioners due to how unusually complicated and repetitive they were. What I believe would be actually of use to practitioners engaging citizens and designing projects would be a short workbook type set up (5 pages max) that could be printed out or filled out online that would allow someone to take an idea or concept and turn it into a proper project/initiative with clearly defined aims, methods to achieve them and methods to assess impact and success of project. This reporting form itself is very repetitive and time consuming involving having to study various papers to write, ideally it would be much simpler; background & aims of project, action taken, outcomes, conclusions and recommendations for future work. Tables and engagement mapper that Prep4blue wanted filled out were not available in a format that made that easy, also the tables were confusing to understand (despite tables usually being rather self explanatory) and am uncertain if the tables I have inserted into this report have been filled out as intended.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations (0.5 page)

Conclusion

The overall experience was very positive for Sea Synergy and the engaged community. The community that attended the event were really surprised and enthused about all the biodiversity we have on our shoreline and how important and endangered our native oyster is and the majority of them were keen to participate more in the future and we know have shared the project with their local networks as well as we have received positive feedback and recognition from individuals who did not attend the event in person. We have built a more solid plan for how the project will progress and how the community would like to be involved with the project going forward.

Recommendations for Upscaling/Replicating the Action

Increased funding for upscaling, easier to use resources from funders, like a workbook for projects.

In future we would try to find a better venue that we could decide the time to work best with all the stakeholders we want to engage or perhaps have a working hours event for NGO's and civil service, government bodies and an evening event for the local community after working hours, but we would need more resources/funding for this and more accommodating venues.

The format of the event worked very well in engaging the community in discussions and input to the project.

Ensure there is opportunity for disseminating information, QnA then refreshments for the discussion and feedback and input element, like World Cafe style participatory events.

If local expertise is involved make sure they are reimbursed or acknowledged in the way they feel it is worth their time.

6 Bibliography

- Preston, J., Gamble, C., Debney, A., Helmer, L.D., Hancock, B. and zu Ermgassen, P., 2020, November. European native oyster habitat restoration handbook. Zoological Society of London.
- Beck, M.W., Brumbaugh, R.D., Airoidi, L., Carranza, A., Coen, L.D., Crawford, C., Defeo, O., Edgar, G.J., Hancock, B., Kay, M.C., Lenihan, H.S., Luckenbach, M.W., Toropova, C.L., Zhang, G., Guo, X., 2011. Oyster reefs at risk and recommendations for conservation, restoration, and management. *Bioscience* 61, 107–116.

7 ANNEX 1 PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper

Mission Ocean’s overarching objectives (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, page 19).

Mission citizen engagement target outcomes (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, pp 35-36).

Your citizen engagement activities / outputs

Annex P5. Self-Evaluation Report for PA5: Blue Genes Giant Collaborative Puzzle

PREP4BLUE Pilot activity reporting template: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report

COLLABORATIVE PUZZLE

Blue Genes

Project Duration:

13/08/2024 to 31/10/2024

Project Coordinator:

Ladislav Chachignot

Report Creator:

Constanza Cantarero

Collaborators/Partners:

FES! CULTURA

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary.....	4
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Background and Context.....	5
1.2 About our organization.....	5
1.3 Our proposal	6
1.3.1 Contribution to Mission Ocean Objectives.....	7
1.3.2 Contribution to Engagement Target Outcomes	7
1.3.3 Contribution to Ocean Literacy.....	10
2 Methodology.....	12
2.1 Pilot Action plan	13
2.2 Participants and Stakeholders	14
3 Implementation	16
3.1 Visual Documentation:.....	17
4 Results and Impact assessment.....	22
4.1 Key Findings	22
4.2 Proposed Outcomes.....	25
5 Lessons Learned.....	27
5.1 PREP4BLUE resources	28

6	Conclusion and Recommendations	30
6.1	Recommendations for Upscaling/Replicating the Action.....	30
7	Bibliography	31

Executive Summary

The goal of this project is to foster a meaningful connection between citizens and the ocean through a blend of science and art. Our main objective is to engage the public in a personally designed experience that fosters awareness and understanding of the relationship between humans and the ocean by presenting verified information, inspiring a change in consumer habits, assessing knowledge of ocean culture, and creating visual narratives that enhance environmental consciousness and promote collective action.

A large puzzle installation, designed to resemble a stained-glass window into the oceanic world, will be exhibited. This intricate and fragile vision of marine life is composed of puzzle pieces that, when assembled, reveal the ocean's biodiversity. The primary objective is to inspire the audience to connect with the idea that safeguarding marine life is a collective responsibility.

The experience begins with a performance featuring a fragmented stained-glass scene, symbolizing the fractured state of our oceans. Following this, a five-minute storytelling session, enhanced with live guitar music, will aim to evoke a deep sense of connection to the ocean's beauty and richness, urging the audience to consider their own contributions to its well-being. In the second act, the audience is invited to shift perspectives through an interactive activity. A 15-minute Kahoot game will prompt reflection and discussion, breaking any tension and encouraging open dialogue about marine conservation and individual responsibility. With a final question to open a dialogue about their perceptions to change in favour of the conservation of the oceans, in order to assess the impact of our activity and the awareness of the audience. The final act brings everyone together to complete the puzzle, transforming the symbolic act of assembling pieces into a call for collective action. This closing gesture serves as a metaphor, inviting participants to take tangible steps to protect the ocean.

The production phase will involve researching and sourcing materials that are environmentally friendly. The artistic direction will be led by an experienced illustrator, with feedback from the Blue Genes community, fostering a collaborative and impactful creative process.

It would be interesting, for future recommendations, to replicate this activity in different population segments. Also, be able to have more time for the activity and include other types of means of participation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Context

The world's oceans, in particular the Mediterranean, are under various stresses that are causing problems in marine biodiversity, climate change, and marine pollution, among others. We want that through an experience that mixes art and science, citizens have the opportunity to engage and raise awareness in order to change their habits and transmit this impact to others.

Society is constantly bombarded by news of the impacts of climate change, which they cannot solve on their own and which generates eco-anxiety in them. We believe that there is a need to create spaces for reflection or debate to bring people together and combat eco-anxiety through personally linked experiences with science and the arts.

We can gather feedback for continuous improvement, validate results and obtain tangible data on the benefits of this experience by being able to assess people's perceptions during this activity.

1.2 About our organization

The Blue Genes community, initiated by ICM nowadays is mobilized with voluntary contribution and bottom-up approach. We have great potential and comprise a talented pool of artists, scientists, educators, and activists working on marine issues globally. With a shared commitment to the sustainability of the ocean, we collaborate to inspire relations with the ocean. Our recent activities involved the event titled “Enbluement: connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the ocean” at the 2024 Ocean Decade Conference where we brought forward questions about human-ocean and environmental relations. We invited the public to a performance, and among us host regular meetings for fostering connections and unique perspectives.

1.3 Our proposal

Our main objective can be structured in 3 main parts and we identify below their respective outputs and outcomes associated to each one and which in their entirety contribute to the success of the project.

Objetives of the pilot activity	Outputs	Outcomes
To present verified information and data on oceans and climate change in the Mediterranean, as well as to measure the knowledge of oceanic culture.	Interactive quiz with space for dialogue.	Enhance participation of the audience and obtaining data.
Gather personal awareness of their relationship with the ocean and its issues. Together with your level of knowledge on ocean culture issues and interest for an exhibition.	Survey disseminated to key actors and participants.	Data analysis and participation of the audience (activity democratic). Understanding their relationship with the ocean provides guidance for activity planning.
Develop a visual and imaginative storytelling personally about the ocean and our role in it.	Speech with live music.	Connecting with positive emotions and increasing willingness to participate.

Chart 1: Comparison of outputs and outcomes for each objective of the pilot activity.

1.3.1 Contribution to Mission Ocean Objectives

Our pilot activity aligns with the mission objective "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030," specifically addressing two key goals: (1) preventing and eliminating pollution, and (2) promoting a sustainable, carbon-neutral, and circular Blue Economy. These objectives are interconnected, as raising awareness about current challenges while offering practical solutions to shift consumption habits helps reduce pollution. By encouraging choices that support environmentally friendly products and services, we aim to advance the Blue Economy and promote sustainable ocean stewardship. Furthermore, in both cases, collective action combats both objectives, and enthusiasm as well as promotion is a fundamental part of the activity.

1.3.2 Contribution to Engagement Target Outcomes

Our proposal is closely aligned with the citizen engagement target outcomes, addressing three key mission objectives centered on enhancing citizen participation.

The first outcome, "Tried and applied deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions for the restoration of the aquatic environment," is reflected in our creation of spaces for problem-solving and active listening. In these spaces, participants can share their perspectives on environmental challenges, propose solutions they envision, and discuss gaps they perceive in current systems.

The second outcome, 'Provided knowledge and methodological frameworks to support the revision of the international ocean governance agenda', is addressed by providing up-to-date information on ocean governance and assessing audience awareness of related issues. It also provides insights into the perception of the ocean governance agenda in the context of Barcelona, which is valuable for understanding whether these efforts are reaching public awareness and how people perceive international work to address the challenges of climate change and its impact on the ocean and our coasts.

The third outcome, “Promoted EU-wide annual ocean literacy campaigns, in cooperation with the EU4Ocean Coalition to strengthen public awareness and overcome the emotional disconnect with the ocean and waters,” is indirectly supported by our efforts to raise awareness of the emotional connection people have with the ocean and how they perceive its challenges. While we are not conducting a campaign, our activities promote understanding of ocean issues and are guided by seven of the ten principles of ocean literacy, reinforcing this important concept.

In the illustration 1, a graphical representation is provided showing how the Mission Ocean Objectives and the Engagement Target Outcomes are interconnected in our pilot activity, as previously discussed. The diagram, depicted with arrows, links the two Citizen engagement activities of our pilot project, starting from the bottom, to the various Mission Ocean Objectives and Engagement Target Outcomes.

Mission Ocean’s overarching objectives (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, page 19).

Mission citizen engagement target outcomes (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, pp. 35-36).

Illustration 1: Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper for Collaborative Puzzle

1.3.3 Contribution to Ocean Literacy

The following table outlines the dimensions of Ocean Literacy that are associated with each objective of our pilot activity.

Objectives of the pilot activity	OCEAN LITERACY DIMENSIONS									
	Knowledge	Awareness	Attitudes	Communication	Activism	Behavior	Emotions	Access and Experience	Adaptive capacity	Trust and transparency
To present verified information and data on oceans and climate change in the Mediterranean, as well as to measure the knowledge of oceanic culture.	X	X		X						X
Gather personal awareness of their relationship with the ocean and its issues. Together with your level of knowledge on ocean culture issues.			X			X	X			
Develop a visual and imaginative storytelling personally about the ocean and our role in it.							X			

Chart 2: Ocean Literacy dimensions associated with each objective of the pilot activity.

Our activity shares 7 of the 10 dimensions of ocean literacy:

The audience can have **trust and transparency** that what is presented has scientific backing. **Knowledge** and **awareness** of the problems and their possible solutions that through the activity we want to generate a change in the **behaviors** related to purchasing and consumption decisions, along with waste disposal in order to improve the sustainable blue economy. We also generate an introspection and study on the **attitude** and **emotional connections** (their own experience and awareness of their relationship with the ocean) before and after the activity to measure if it has changed. Finally, we want this activity to reach more people, but we are confident that the positive impact through the activity will generate **communication** (with others) in conversation and spread the message to the immediate circle of each impacted person.

Illustration 2: Dimensions of ocean literacy highlighted as being included in the pilot activity. Source: (McKinley et al., 2023).

2 Methodology

Our methodology is based on four pillars (P): PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION, PARTICIPATORY PROCESS OF THE COMMUNITY BLUE GENES, INFORMATION: DATA FOR ACTIVITY, and COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, LEGACY. Each with different tasks (T) per item to carry out the necessary objectives.

P1	PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION
T1.1	Aadministrative and financial management.
T1.2	Project management, general and operational coordination.
P2	PARTICIPATORY PROCESS OF THE COMUNITY BLUE GENES
T2.1	Meetings with stakeholders.
T2.2	Elaboration process.
P3	INFORMATION: DATA FOR ACTIVITY
T3.1	Design, create, dissemination and processed.
T3.2	Gathering, selecting information for activity.
T3.3	Creating reports.
P4	COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, LEGACY
T4.1	Dissemination and communication of the activity.
T4.2	Seeking to improve and increase the audience.

Chart 3: List of pillars and tasks associated with the Collaborative Puzzle methodology.

2.2 Participants and Stakeholders

Our project values the entire stakeholder ecosystem involved in its creation, promotion, and appreciation. Therefore, we identified the key contributors. Our scope includes partners to help assemble the puzzle, an audience we aimed to satisfy, and external entities such as the Prep4blue monitor and Fes! Cultura organizer, over which we had no influence in decision-making. Consequently, we needed to maintain a steady flow of information to adapt to their requirements and present ourselves effectively. The chart 5 below details the roles and contributions of the various organizations and individuals associated with our stakeholders.

Stakeholders involved

Position/Role	Participants
Art direction concept / visual creation	Ladislav Chachignot - Blue Genes.
Music creation and live guitar	Maria Camahort - Blue Genes.
Storytelling	Gustavo González - Blue Genes.
Role play and games in ocean literacy	Constanza Cantarero - Blue Genes.
Building the puzzle process	Adri - Plastic preciós La Safor, Ateneu de Fabrication Fabrica del sol, Angel - Zeit estudio Barcelona, Victor Clandestina Poblenou, Constanza Cantarero – Blue Genes Gustavo González – Blue Genes Jade N. Zoghbi – Blue Genes.
Space facilitator	Franzi Bach - Zeit estudio Barcelona.
Prep4Blue coordinator	Ifigenia G. Leontsini.

Chart 5: Stakeholder by participants and role.

The audience has two opportunities to participate: through a survey or at the showcase, which unfolds in three parts. It begins with a contemplative, reflective, and introspective phase, followed by a playful segment that encourages dialogue, debate, and idea-sharing. Finally, participants engage in an immersive art experience, completing a metaphor by adding a piece to the puzzle to reveal the finished work.

We use our dissemination channels—such as Instagram posts, email chains, and personal invitations—to encourage public participation. However, our role in this activity is limited to promotion; the event organizer is responsible for managing the official invitations.

We would be delighted to be able to replicate this activity to a particular audience or with an open invitation to ensure that no one is left behind, looking for a new opportunity to reuse this Collaborative Puzzle is important and we are working on it.

3 Implementation

The following table provides a chronological overview of the activities carried out during the implementation phase, including dates, times, and the participants involved. It outlines the sequence of events, from preparatory work to the main activities and any follow-up actions, along with details of participant involvement, their roles, and their contributions to the success of the pilot action.

Date	Time	activities	Participant Involvement
29-10-24	15:00	Transfer of pieces from the studio to the event facilities Fes! Culture	Ladislav, Gustavo
30-10-24	13:00	Assembly.	Ladislav, Gustavo
30-10-24	15:00	Light rehearsal.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria
30-10-24	17:00	Showcase rehearsal.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria
31-10-24	10:45	Microphone rehearsal.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria
31-10-24	12:00	Scene decoration.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria
31-10-24	15:00	Social media activation.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria, Ladislav
31-10-24	18:35	Installation of headband microphones.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria
31-10-24	18:45	Showcase presentation.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria, Ladislav
31-10-24	20:00	Feedback from us.	Constanza, Gustavo, Maria, Ladislav
01-11-24	10:00	Transfer of pieces from facilities Fes! Culture to studio.	Ladislav, Gustavo

Chart 6: Timeline by participants and role in the implementation stage of the Collaborative Puzzle.

The Blue Genes team was fundamental and consistently proactive. Each member contributed uniquely and irreplaceably, playing an essential role in the project's success.

One challenge not mentioned in the previous timeline was that, the day before the event, production informed us that our activity time would be limited to just 20 minutes. We had initially planned for an additional day with a longer game and a more engaging dynamic, allowing more impact and time for interaction. While adapting on short notice was necessary, we successfully achieved our goal

3.1 Visual Documentation:

Illustration 3: It is presented from left to right: first the illustrated work for the activity, second the vinyl printing of the laser-cut image, third the arrangement of the plastic material rescued from the ocean, transformed and transported to our premises, third the creation of the board where the puzzle is assembled, fourth a piece of the puzzle with its layers is displayed: on the bottom is the recycled plastic, on top is the print and on the surface is a methacrylate to ensure the durability of the piece and reinforce the safety of the audience when taking the piece as well as providing the desired glass effect. On the back of the piece are various magnets that fit and adhere perfectly with the magnets on the board. The fifth image shows the finished work, with the board painted and all the pieces created.

Illustration 4: Shown above in the first two pictures correspond to the first part of the showcase where Maria played a live piece on guitar created to accompany the storytelling that Gustavo read in a speech created for the event. The three photos below show the second part of the showcase where the dynamic is invited to change from listening to progressive action, starting with a game on the kahoot platform, and then opening the dialogue to talk about the questions posed and listening as shown in the last two photos.

Illustration 5: In these 6 images you can see the third part of the showcase where the listeners stood up from their seats and put their pieces of the puzzle together collaboratively to appreciate the work as a whole.

Illustration 6: Visualization of the work Collaborative Puzzle presented as a showcase at Fes! Culture.

Illustration 7: The team behind the Collaborative Puzzle from Blue Genes.

4 Results and Impact assessment

4.1 Key Findings

Based on the survey conducted, the most significant findings are presented below. The representative sample consisted of 48 individuals from diverse countries of origin, with Spain being the most frequently represented. Regarding the length of residence, no clear trend was observed; however, the three largest groups were: those who have lived in the area their entire lives, those with 1 to 5 years of residence, and those with 6 to 10 years of residence. Illustration 8 presents the responses to the question about participants' perceptions of their main concerns related to the ocean. Meanwhile, Illustration 10 focuses on how participants feel when thinking about ocean-related issues. They were also asked about the topics they would like to see presented in the showcase and their level of involvement in the activity. In both cases, the responses were taken into account and served as a guide to design the activity with the audience in mind. The trend of interest in the activity observed in Illustration 8 was repeated, with the majority of participants preferring to be spectators, although showing an interest in activities with an artistic component. Illustration 9 presents a word cloud diagram that graphically represents the responses to the question: "What three concepts, emotions, or ideas come to mind when you think of the Ocean?"

Illustration 8: Key concerns identified by those surveyed. Multiple choice question.

Illustration 9: Word cloud created from the survey. The question was to mention three words that relate to the ocean.

Illustration 10: Response to how they feel about ocean concerns. Multiple choice question

Regarding the analysis of the responses from the Kahoot game conducted during the showcase, the overall performance in the Ocean Literacy game revealed a total of 55.68% correct answers and 44.32% incorrect answers.

Initially, we planned to incorporate discussion topics by introducing them as questions about the most highly valued concerns. However, due to the reduced presentation time, we opted for more open-ended questions, allowing the audience to steer the conversation according to their interests. Chart 7 presents the results obtained for each question.

Additional topics raised by the audience included the connection between the smell of decomposing plastic and plankton in the ocean, noting their similarity, which consequently attracts marine animals. Other insights included critiques of individual consumption compared to industrial consumption, and perspectives emphasizing the capacity and influence of citizens in advocating for decision-makers to prioritize environmental care.

1 Quiz	¿What percentage of the ocean do we know?
Correct answers	Less than 5%
Players correct (%)	59.09%
2 Quiz	¿Why is the ocean important?
Correct answers	All
Players correct (%)	81.82%
3 Quiz	¿How much plastic do you think reaches the Mediterranean every minute? Measured in plastic bottles
Correct answers	33.800
Players correct (%)	13.64%
4 Quiz	¿Are you inspired to upgrade your lifestyle to one that is ocean-friendly?
Correct answers	True
Players correct (%)	68.18%

Chart 7: Kahoot game results, measured by question and percentage of correct answers.

4.2 Proposed Outcomes

Below are the short-term outputs and outcomes related to our pilot activity and their respective metrics.

Outputs	Outcomes	Indicators
Interactive quiz with space for dialogue	Enhance participation of the audience and obtaining data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) answer by question 2) number of participants 3) Final response to the intention of changes
Survey disseminated to key actors and participants	Data analysis and participation of the audience (activity democratic). Understanding their relationship with the ocean provides guidance for activity planning.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) answer by question 2) Scale of emotionality and perception of mood in the face of oceanic problems 3) Ocean perception, a concept cloud to visualize response frequency and variability
Speech with live music	Connecting with positive emotions and increasing willingness to participate	number of participants

Chart 8: Comparison of indicators by outputs and outcomes.

our goal for Long-term Outcomes is to inspire collective action within the audience, with joining our community as just one option. More importantly, fostering a shift from feeling overwhelmed to feeling optimistic represents a positive change in how they perceive and relate to challenges

Our activity contributes to **the Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Targets**: ‘Restore our Ocean and Waters’ goal under the objectives of ‘Prevent and eliminate pollution’ and ‘Make the blue economy climate-neutral & circular,’ as we aim to foster bottom-up action among citizens. We motivate people to come together, drive change, and shift their lifestyle toward one that is sustainable for the ocean. By indirectly encouraging reduced plastic use and sustainable consumption that benefits the blue economy, this will ultimately support a balanced aquatic ecosystem with a lower environmental impact than today.

Ideally, our strategy to engage citizens, it will be involved in replicate this activity to increasing the opportunities to enhance its impact and reach a broader audience. We appreciated the survey's role in personalizing the activity, as it allowed us to tailor the experience to participants' interests and gather valuable information. However, accessing surveys from the intended audience can be challenging. Establishing a registration method for the activity, or working with a specific group—such as a school class—would make this process easier and more effective.

The performance could also be enhanced to increase its impact and create more interaction and engagement with the audience by incorporating clues to help place the pieces. One challenge is ensuring that the activity remains focused on dialogue and positive play, rather than on competition or winning, so that the underlying message stays front and center.

5 Lessons Learned

We faced a series of challenges that we were able to overcome but that weighed on the energy and realisation of the project. Below is a SWOT analysis showing the factors involved

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Professional team of experts in their field, guaranteeing trust and transparency in their commitment to the pilot activity. -Good team, good synergy. -Be a showcase for a festival to present the activity. -Knowing the public's interest -Public with interest in the subject. -having a Budget to make this project possible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Budget to fix. - Budget allocated to the construction of the project. - Unpaid work hours for artistic creation and report writing -Dependence on suppliers. - Complex project planning: coordination of actors in time and place, budget due to modifications and adaptations. -Lack of mobilization and allocation of resources for transportation. -No interference in setting date and time. -Not being able to be certain about the number of participants, number of audiences, ages, etc. -Limited time for the activity. -Last minute changes to performance time. -Low visibility of the puzzle in horizontal state.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Be on time as scheduled for rehearsal and correction. -Having the stage for the performance -Being able to choose environmentally friendly materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Working against time. -Competing for the audience's attention and concentration. -Low attendance: due to date and time, weather, holiday, etc. -Climate (rainy day). -Lighting and projection on the stage. -Time and place on a commercial day like Halloween could reduce the public.

Chart 9:SWOT analysis for the Collaborative Puzzle

The biggest challenge was limiting the showcase activity to just 20 minutes. With more time, we could have asked questions to gauge participants' perceptions before and after the activity, allowing us to assess any changes linked to our involvement. A longer session would also have enabled us to cover more topics and inspire greater engagement. Given the time constraints, we prioritized the most impactful topics to spark meaningful conversations. Our key evaluation question centered on participants' perceptions regarding habit changes and motivation to adopt a more sustainable lifestyle

On the contrary, one of the advantages or best practices was related to having a trusted, collaborative team working in a horizontal structure was invaluable. Each member contributed their expertise and was fully committed to delivering their best, resulting in an outcome that left us both satisfied and proud.

For future recommendations, we would certainly benefit from the personal experience and planning of the work with the critical activities or processes identified to progress in parallel.

5.1 PREP4BLUE resources

It would be helpful if the tools were designed to support the project planner's work by enhancing elements aligned with the project's objectives. For example, if a planning form is suggested, it could include conversation topics to guide coordination meetings, a decision-making tree, or a list of proposed activities that align with the project's goals and provide useful references.

As feedback from Ladislav: "someone from an artistic background, I initially found some of the processes involved in developing scientific project proposals and evaluating their impact unfamiliar. This was a new and challenging experience for me.

The webinars and documents provided by the Prep4blue team were very helpful in guiding me through the steps of creating an "Art & Science" proposal. Additionally, the toolkit proved invaluable in deepening my understanding and aiding in the planning phase. It introduced me to questions and frameworks I would not have considered on my own, allowing for more structured conceptualization.

I especially appreciated the use of tables in the toolkit, which made it easier to digest the information and avoid lengthy text. The included examples within the tables were particularly effective in helping orient our proposal.

However, I encountered some challenges in implementing the content into our project. The main difficulty for me was the perceived density of the document. While it was highly comprehensive and insightful, it felt somewhat overwhelming and less accessible for individuals like me, who do not come from a scientific background.

From an artistic perspective, which often emphasizes emotion, sensation, and improvisation over analysis, the toolkit's complexity occasionally felt like a limitation. It added a layer of difficulty to the creative conceptualization process. For example, some sections delved deeply into analytical frameworks that seemed excessive at this stage of proposal development.

To address this, I suggest simplifying the document by focusing on fewer key concepts. Additionally, incorporating more visuals, graphic design, or user-friendly layouts could make it more accessible to a broader audience, including artists and non-scientists. This would help ensure that users remain engaged and confident throughout the process.

Despite these challenges, collaboration with other team members who had more scientific experience was crucial in adapting the toolkit to our proposal. Their insights helped bridge the gap between the toolkit's requirements and our artistic vision.

I am enthusiastic about continuing to work on projects that combine artistic skills with scientific outreach. However, to foster successful collaborations between these fields, it is important to ensure that tools like the Prep4blue toolkit are accessible and appealing to diverse users. Making the toolkit simpler, more visual, and inclusive could encourage greater participation and more natural integration of creative and scientific approaches.

Thank you for the opportunity to provide this feedback, and I look forward to contributing further to this exciting initiative.”

6 Conclusion and Recommendations

The work we carried out allowed us to make an impact on the public, creating an activity based on their interests. We asked questions and gathered feedback on their relationship with the ocean and the effects of eco-anxiety, learning that, while most participants felt disappointed by environmental issues, no one was indifferent. Notably, 8% were unable to identify their emotions on the matter. Through our approach, we aimed to foster a sense of attentive listening with music and words that invited reflection and appreciation of the perspective we presented. Additionally, participants observed a fragmented animation of an image puzzle we designed, symbolizing the gradual breakdown of the scene.

Changing the dynamics and pace of the showcase was a great idea, as introducing the game encouraged more people to join in, shifting the focus from watching the stage to giving the audience a voice. This opened up space for debate and conversation around our lifestyle and responsibilities, while also documenting popular knowledge about the ocean. Participants also joined in placing the pieces, creating a symbolic point of unity and connection among everyone

6.1 Recommendations for Upscaling/Replicating the Action

Designing for a specific target audience would be ideal, and forming partnerships to create a stakeholder map would be very useful. In this scenario for Future activities with this project could include synergies with schools, institutes, and vocational training centers related to the topic, reaching younger generations who might not attend other types of events.

We recommend thinking of innovative methods that encourage meaningful conversations, tailored to the audience. It's not about uncomfortable or repetitive icebreakers, but about finding a metaphor or idea that inspires action, so the message resonates effectively. Creating through play is a great option, because even with an adult audience, reconnecting with the essence of play allows us to engage with our hands and voices, creating situations that break away from the usual context

7 Bibliography

Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters. (s. f.). Recuperado 27 de noviembre de 2024, de <https://nordlandsforskning.wrep.it/engaging-citizens-with-mission-ocean>

McKinley, E., Burdon, D., & Shellock, R. J. (2023). The evolution of ocean literacy: A new framework for the United Nations Ocean Decade and beyond. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 186, 114467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114467>

Annex P6. Self-Evaluation Report for PA1: Sustainable Coastal Futures

PREP4BLUE Pilot activity reporting template: Engaging citizens in Mission Ocean

PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report

Sustainable Coastal Futures

Institute for Art and Innovation (IFAI)

in collaboration with

The Coastal Union Germany (EUCC-D)

Project Duration:

1.8.2024 – 30.11.2024

Project Coordinator:

Institute for Art and Innovation (IFAI)

Collaborators/Partners:

The Coastal Union Germany (EUCC-D)/ H2Mare Project

Collaborators/Partners:

UNESCO World Heritage Wadden Sea Visitor Center

Siemens Gamesa

Energy Hub Wilhelmshaven

Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS) / Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Methodology.....	15
3 Implementation.....	24
4 Results and Impact assessment.....	31
5 Lessons Learned.....	33
6 Conclusion and Recommendations.....	35
7 Annex PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper.....	37

Executive Summary

Overview of the Pilot Action

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures: An Interdisciplinary Workshop and Social Media Initiative on Green Energy and Citizen Participation' pilot action was launched in August 2024. The initiative aims to engage citizens and stakeholders in co-creating future scenarios for sustainable ocean use and coastal management, with a focus on green coastal energy production, particularly offshore hydrogen. A key component of this project is fostering social inclusion and enhancing acceptance of green coastal energy solutions in the North and Baltic Sea regions.

The project has successfully laid the groundwork for a workshop held on November 15, 2024, at the UNESCO World Heritage Site Wadden Sea Visitor Center in Wilhelmshaven, Germany. This event brought together a diverse group of experts, stakeholders and civil society to explore sustainable coastal management and the future of renewable energy production. The workshop included insightful speeches, interdisciplinary collaboration, and participatory exercises using the Art For Futures Lab method. This pilot action supports the EU's Mission Ocean goals for 2030 and 2050, emphasizing the restoration of marine ecosystems and the transition to a carbon-neutral blue economy.

Key objectives and goals

- Foster social inclusion by involving citizens in co-designing future scenarios for ocean sustainability and green coastal energy.
- Bridge communication and knowledge gaps between citizens, policymakers, industry, and academia, and creating actionable solutions for sustainable coastal development.
- Explore new methods of engagement using arts-based engagement tools, such as future-scenario planning and visualization, to inspire action and collaboration-

Main Achievements and Outcomes

Workshop Execution

The workshop on November 15 at the UNESCO Wadden Sea Visitor Center gathered a diverse group of stakeholders, including experts, citizens, and industry representatives. Participants explored opportunities and challenges for green hydrogen production and coastal sustainability.

Expert Contributions by

- **EUCC - The Coastal Union Germany**, presenting the **H2Mare Project** and its integration into the Prep4Blue initiative.
- **Siemens Gamesa**, highlighting offshore hydrogen production potential.
- **Energy Hub Wilhelmshaven**, showcasing business opportunities and community engagement.
- **GERICS / Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon**, discussing societal acceptance and regulatory challenges.
- **Institute for Art and Innovation (IFAI)**, introducing interdisciplinary collaboration formats through the application of the Art For Futures Lab's method to prepare the participants for the workshop.

Methodological Development

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action demonstrated the effectiveness of the Art For Futures Lab (AFFL) method in fostering creative, collaborative and futures thinking about sustainability and societal transformation.. Adapted specifically for this context, the methodology enabled participants to co-create four future scenarios for coastal sustainability by 2050. These scenarios addressed critical challenges such as green hydrogen energy production, ecosystem restoration, and community empowerment.

The AFFL method combined tools such as scenario planning, systems thinking, backcasting, and design thinking with creative techniques like world-building. This dynamic approach allowed participants to explore complex issues and develop actionable pathways for sustainable and regenerative futures. Through participatory engagement, the scenarios synthesized diverse perspectives and offered innovative solutions that balance environmental, social, and economic priorities.

The project's visual and narrative outputs—mood boards, drawings, AI generated images, and compelling future narratives—provided tangible representations of the scenarios. These outputs not only made complex ideas accessible but also will serve as tools for further engagement, advocacy, and education, ensuring that the insights from the workshop can be shared and applied beyond the pilot action.

Collaborative Scenario Building

Participants engaged in small group discussions and future-prototyping exercises, envisioning a climate-positive life by 2045. Key themes included:

- Renewable energy production.
- Mobility transition in coastal regions.
- Regenerative practices and enhanced recycling systems.

Synthesis of Future Scenarios

Technological Innovation and Sustainability

- All scenarios highlighted the integration of renewable energy technologies such as green hydrogen, tidal power, and movement-based energy (e.g., harnessing kinetic energy from aquatic life). These solutions aim to decarbonize coastal regions while reducing reliance on fossil fuels.
- Scenarios included decentralized, intelligent energy distribution systems, such as E-LAN networks, that optimize resource use and enhance energy accessibility for coastal communities.

Ecosystem Restoration and Biodiversity Protection

- Participants envisioned restored ecosystems, including mangrove forests and oyster reefs, that provide natural coastal defenses and biodiversity hotspots. These elements support both environmental health and sustainable economic activities, such as fisheries and eco-tourism.
- Strategies emphasized regenerative practices, integrating technological advancements with natural ecosystems to ensure mutual benefit.

Social Inclusion and Governance

- Scenarios explored participatory governance models, empowering citizens through community-led energy systems, localized decision-making, and innovative economic models, such as barter systems.
- Participants emphasized the importance of inclusivity, ensuring that all societal groups, including marginalized communities, are part of the transition to sustainable energy practices.

Improved Quality of Life

- Envisioned futures focused on creating vibrant, community-oriented lifestyles with reduced bureaucracy, enhanced mobility, and stronger social connections.
- Simplified, sustainable living practices were central, with participants emphasizing a balance between technological innovation and human well-being.

Impact and Alignment with Objectives

The outcomes of the workshop directly align with the objectives of the pilot action and the broader goals of Mission Ocean:

- Promoting Ocean Literacy - By engaging participants in scenario planning and visual storytelling, the workshop enhanced understanding of the ocean's role in sustainable energy transitions.
- Fostering Citizen Engagement - The participatory approach ensured that citizen voices were integral to the co-creation process, empowering communities to shape their future.
- Supporting a Carbon-Neutral Blue Economy - The scenarios emphasized renewable energy integration and circular economy principles, providing a roadmap for sustainable coastal development.

Future Recommendations

Building on the insights gained from the '**Sustainable Coastal Futures**' pilot action, we propose the following recommendations to improve and expand similar initiatives in the future:

Expanded Stakeholder Engagement

- Begin outreach to local government representatives, educational institutions, and NGOs earlier in the planning process to secure broader support and ensure smoother approval timelines.
- Involve a wider range of voices, such as youth organizations, cultural institutions, and small businesses, to diversify perspectives and increase the relevance of outcomes for different community groups.

Flexible Scheduling for Broader Participation

- Offer workshops during evenings or weekends to accommodate people who are at work or school during the day. This flexibility ensures inclusivity and allows a broader cross-section of the community to participate.
- Continue to provide hybrid participation (in-person and virtual) to increase accessibility for those unable to attend physically.

Enhanced Communication and Outreach

- Develop a detailed communication strategy that includes pre-workshop virtual discussions, ongoing updates, and post-workshop dissemination of results.
- Use storytelling techniques and user-friendly tools to communicate complex topics, such as the Empathy Map, which proved effective in helping participants step into the perspectives of diverse stakeholders.
- Leverage social media platforms more strategically to build anticipation, share real-time updates, and engage a wider audience before, during, and after the event.

Methodological Improvements

- Further adapt methods like the Art For Futures Lab to specific community needs, emphasizing interdisciplinary approaches like scenario planning and foresight techniques to enhance creativity and collaboration.
- Expand the use of tools like the Empathy Map, which helped participants understand diverse perspectives and fostered deeper conversations around challenges and opportunities.

Sustained Engagement and Follow-Up

- Organize community-led follow-up discussions to reflect on workshop outcomes and encourage action. These could include creating working groups or action plans focused on implementing specific ideas from the workshop.
- Develop online platforms or forums where participants can continue the dialogue, share progress, and engage with new stakeholders over time.
- Use visual tools, such as mood boards or scenario prototypes from the workshop, as part of traveling exhibitions or educational materials to inspire continued learning and action.

Monitoring and Evaluation

To ensure the effectiveness and long-term impact of the 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action, a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation framework is recommended:

Structured Feedback Collection

- Distribute feedback forms at the end of the workshop to capture participants' reflections on the methods, content, and overall experience. Include questions that assess the relevance, accessibility, and engagement levels of the activities.

- Conduct follow-up surveys or interviews with participants to gather insights on the practical applicability of workshop outcomes and their continued engagement with the project goals.
- Track participation numbers, diversity of stakeholders (e.g., citizens, industry, policymakers), and if possible the extent of their contributions during the workshop.
- Measure social media engagement, including the reach and interaction rates of posts related to the workshop, to evaluate broader community interest and awareness.

Output Analysis

- Evaluate the quality and breadth of the scenarios and ideas generated during the workshop. Assess whether these outputs align with the project's objectives and can be translated into actionable steps or further initiatives.
- Review the usability of visual and interactive outputs (e.g., mood boards, prototypes) for dissemination in exhibitions, policy discussions, or educational materials.

Long-Term Impact Assessment

- Conduct periodic evaluations post-workshop to determine the extent of stakeholder collaboration, implementation of ideas, and continued dialogue fostered by the pilot action.
- Develop indicators to measure progress toward project goals, such as increased societal acceptance of green hydrogen production or enhanced collaboration between local communities and industry stakeholders.

Adaptive Learning

- Use the insights gathered from feedback and evaluations to refine methodologies, improve stakeholder engagement strategies, and ensure future initiatives build on lessons learned from this pilot action.

1 Introduction

Background and Context

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures: An Interdisciplinary Workshop and Social Media Initiative on Green Energy and Citizen Participation' pilot action was designed to address the pressing need for inclusive and participatory approaches to managing the challenges and opportunities associated with offshore green hydrogen production and transportation. As Europe's coastal regions increasingly adopt sustainable energy technologies, fostering social acceptance, engaging local communities, and ensuring transparent communication are critical for the success of these transitions.

Coastal regions often bear the direct environmental, social, and economic impacts of large-scale energy projects, such as offshore wind and hydrogen production. Communities in these areas face challenges related to integration into planning processes, perceptions of environmental disruption, and equitable sharing of benefits. This pilot action directly responds to these concerns by creating a platform for dialogue between citizens, industry, and policymakers, focusing on co-developing socially inclusive and environmentally sustainable scenarios for green hydrogen production.

The initiative builds on the momentum of the German H2Mare project, a national German flagship project exploring offshore wind-to-hydrogen production technologies. In addition to technological and industrial development, research on social acceptance plays an important role in the project. For example, stakeholder analyses and population surveys were carried out in order to record opinions and uncover conflicts or knowledge requirements and to be able to address these in the course of the project. Over the course of the project, various dialogue formats were held at coastal locations of the North and the Baltic Sea, e.g. on the island of Helgoland or in Rostock. Prior to each forum, EUCC-D collected and analysed opinions on the topic of the energy transition and the use of offshore hydrogen by means of a population survey. Some of the results provided important information on conflict situations in the local context, which could be addressed in the dialogue forum and dealt with depending on the participants.

Wilhelmshaven will be an important hub for the energy transition in Germany. It is home to the only deep-water harbour, landing port and transshipment point of international relevance, as well as caverns for energy storage. Numerous companies have joined forces in the so-called Energyhub to specifically promote the development of a hydrogen hub. Nevertheless, various local players have already spoken out against some of the plans and many local stakeholders are sceptical about the energy policy plans and decisions. The dialogue format - our pilot action - was therefore of crucial importance, provided a unique opportunity to involve coastal stakeholders in shaping a sustainable energy future and aimed to break down entrenched opinions and prejudices and develop new, common goals for the Wilhelmshaven region.

Importance of the Activity in the Context of Mission Ocean's Objectives

This pilot action aligns with the Mission Ocean objectives, particularly the goals of advancing a carbon-neutral and circular blue economy, protecting marine ecosystems, and fostering community engagement. It represents a practical response to Mission Ocean's emphasis on citizen-driven initiatives that empower coastal communities to shape their relationship with the ocean and its resources. By integrating citizens into the conversation about offshore hydrogen production,

the project ensures that future energy developments are not only environmentally sustainable but also socially inclusive.

Key Contributions to Mission Ocean Objectives Promoting Ocean Literacy

Promoting Ocean Literacy

The pilot action engaged coastal communities by providing expert insights into the environmental and economic implications of green hydrogen energy production. This approach deepened participants' understanding of the ocean's role in climate change mitigation and the sustainable use of marine resources.

Empowering Citizens

By employing participatory and arts-based methodologies, the project empowered citizens to articulate their perspectives and actively co-design future scenarios. This engagement ensured that their voices informed strategies for sustainable energy production and coastal management.

Through these efforts, the Sustainable Coastal Futures pilot action contributed to both the environmental and societal pillars of Mission Ocean, fostering a holistic approach to sustainable energy innovation. By integrating diverse perspectives into discussions about offshore hydrogen production, the initiative highlights how socially inclusive practices can enhance environmental sustainability, strengthen community resilience, and create equitable pathways for the blue economy's transformation.

Our Organisation/Project/Initiative

The Institute for Art and Innovation (IFAI), based in Berlin, is a non-profit organization operating at the intersection of art, science, and civic engagement. Our mission is to foster societal transformation by creating interdisciplinary collaborations that tackle global challenges such as climate change, digital transformation, and social inclusion. IFAI leverages innovative, art-driven methods and participatory processes to engage diverse audiences in co-creating solutions for a sustainable future. Over the years, IFAI has established a strong track record in managing interdisciplinary projects that address sustainability, ocean literacy, and societal engagement. A notable milestone is the Ocean Future Lab, implemented during the German Science Year 2022, which successfully brought together coastal and inland communities in Germany to explore ocean sustainability through interactive workshops. Our methodologies—such as Future-Prototyping, Worldbuilding, and Scenario Planning—engage citizens in decision-making processes and raise awareness of pressing environmental issues.

The current project, 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' represents a collaboration between IFAI Berlin and EUCC-The Coastal Union Germany (EUCC-D). EUCC-D is a non-profit organization (NGO) that belongs to the Coastal & Marine Union, the largest European network in the coastal area. To promote sustainable processes and aid decision making for future-proof coastal development EUCC-D is committed to communication and awareness-raising on topics related to coasts and sea especially at the Baltic and the North Sea. Key is stakeholder engagement and understanding their interests. EUCC-D motivates people across all spectrums to participate, provide platforms for discussion & knowledge sharing and prepare the latest scientific research for easy access / dissemination for practitioners, policy makers and the public. In the German flagship H2Mare project, EUCC-D is responsible for project communication in the coastal area, organises events

and surveys, writes various publications on the potentials and challenges of the energy transition for coastal areas and designs a travelling exhibition on green hydrogen.

This pilot action seeks to address the societal challenges and acceptance barriers associated with the (offshore) production and transportation of green hydrogen in the North and Baltic Sea regions. Through an interdisciplinary workshop in Wilhelmshaven, the project brought together citizens, local communities, scientists, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to co-create positive future scenarios for sustainable coastal energy use. A complementary social media initiative amplifies the project's reach, sharing insights and gathering broader public input to ensure its impact extends beyond the local level.

Outreach and Participation

To engage participants, invitations were sent to 100 personal contacts and 50 contacts via private messages on LinkedIn. Additionally, posts promoting the workshop were shared on both IFAI and EUCC-D accounts on Instagram and LinkedIn. Despite these efforts, the late confirmation from the Visitor Center as the host limited our ability to extend invitations to a broader audience, particularly students, younger people, and other community members from the neighborhood. The workshop successfully convened 23 participants, who formed four small groups to collaboratively develop future scenarios. This composition allowed for productive discussions and diverse perspectives, fostering creativity and actionable insights into sustainable coastal energy management.

Target Audience and Geographical Focus

The project targets several key groups:

- Coastal and riparian communities in Wilhelmshaven and surrounding areas affected by offshore energy developments.
- Local policymakers, industry representatives (especially those involved in the H2mare project), environmental NGOs, and scientists working on sustainable energy.
- Broader public audiences, including young citizens, innovators, and artists, through a social media engagement strategy.

Geographically, the initiative focuses on the North and Baltic Sea regions, with potential to scale insights and methodologies across Europe, contributing to the broader Mission Ocean objectives of sustainability and citizen engagement.

Collaboration and Expertise

IFAI has extensive experience in designing and delivering participatory and interdisciplinary projects, particularly in ocean and environmental sustainability. This expertise is further strengthened by our collaboration with EUCC-D, a leading organization in sustainable coastal development and education. EUCC-D's active role in the H2Mare project brings a critical technological perspective to the pilot action, ensuring its foundation in innovation and practicality.

Together, IFAI and EUCC-D are uniquely positioned to bridge the gap between cutting-edge technologies, such as green hydrogen production, and meaningful citizen engagement. By fostering community-led initiatives, this partnership drives forward sustainable ocean use, creating actionable solutions that balance environmental sustainability with societal well-being.

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' project exemplifies this commitment, laying the groundwork for innovative, citizen-driven approaches to coastal energy management that can inspire broader adoption across Europe.

How this Action Connects to Mission Ocean Objectives

Objectives of the Pilot Activity

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action was designed to align with Mission Ocean's objectives by engaging diverse stakeholders—coastal communities, policymakers, scientists, and industry representatives—in co-creating future scenarios for the sustainable use of ocean and coastal resources. The specific objectives of the pilot include:

Facilitating Social Inclusion and Improving Acceptance of Green Coastal Energy

By directly involving citizens in discussions about offshore green hydrogen production, the pilot aimed to address concerns, foster dialogue, and empower local communities to contribute meaningfully to shaping sustainable energy solutions. This inclusive approach ensures that energy developments align with community needs and values.

Creating Interdisciplinary, Future-Focused Dialogues

The pilot action brought together stakeholders with diverse expertise to collaboratively explore opportunities and challenges posed by offshore hydrogen production. Using creative, participatory methods such as scenario planning and Future-Prototyping, these dialogues helped identify innovative, actionable pathways for sustainable coastal management.

Fostering Greater Understanding and Ocean Literacy

Through the workshop and accompanying social media initiatives, the project enhanced participants' understanding of ocean sustainability and green energy technologies. It demonstrated how renewable energy, including hydrogen production, can contribute to a carbon-neutral blue economy and empowered citizens with knowledge to advocate for sustainable practices.

Alignment with Mission Ocean Objectives

This pilot action strongly supports the objectives outlined in the Mission Ocean Implementation Plan:

Protect and Restore Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems and Biodiversity

While the pilot action primarily focused on the social aspects of green hydrogen production, its outcomes indirectly contribute to ecosystem protection. By promoting renewable energy solutions that reduce carbon emissions and dependence on fossil fuels, the action helps to mitigate climate change and minimize human impact on marine ecosystems. Discussions during the workshop emphasized integrating technological innovations with nature to ensure minimal disruption to biodiversity.

Make the Sustainable Blue Economy Carbon-Neutral and Circular

Offshore hydrogen production was a central theme of the pilot action, with participants exploring how it fits into a carbon-neutral blue economy. The workshop highlighted the environmental and economic benefits of green hydrogen, emphasizing circular economy principles such as using local

resources efficiently and regeneratively. This approach supports the long-term transition to sustainable energy systems in coastal regions.

Engage Citizens and Foster Ocean Literacy

One of the pilot action's core goals was to empower citizens by increasing ocean literacy. Through participatory workshops, social media engagement, and interactive tools, the project provided accessible knowledge about the ocean's role in the energy transition. Participants gained insights into the intersection of ocean sustainability and green energy innovation, enabling them to engage more effectively in decision-making processes.

Contribution to Citizen Engagement Target Outcomes

The pilot action aligns closely with the citizen engagement target outcomes outlined in the Mission Ocean Implementation Plan:

Participation and Co-Design

The workshop facilitated citizen-driven scenario planning, allowing participants to actively shape future visions for coastal energy use. By including diverse stakeholders in these dialogues, the pilot fostered shared ownership of the outcomes.

Knowledge and Awareness

The initiative promoted ocean literacy by equipping participants with knowledge about green hydrogen production and its potential environmental and societal impacts. Social media posts extended this knowledge to a broader audience, amplifying the project's reach.

Empowerment and Action

By involving citizens, policymakers, and industry representatives in interdisciplinary discussions, the pilot empowered stakeholders to identify actionable solutions for a sustainable coastal future. The focus on inclusive dialogue ensures that the resulting scenarios reflect community priorities and foster long-term engagement.

Through these efforts, the 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action not only addressed immediate challenges but also laid the groundwork for more informed, inclusive, and sustainable decision-making in coastal energy development. By engaging citizens and fostering collaboration, the project contributes meaningfully to Mission Ocean's vision of sustainable and thriving marine ecosystems and communities.

Which ocean literacy principles have you addressed / Which Ocean Literacy dimensions do you contribute to? (Reference:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0025326X22011493?via%3Dihub>)

Ocean Literacy principles addressed:

The ocean is a major influence on the climate (OL Principle 3)

The project linked green hydrogen energy to the role of the ocean in mitigating climate change by reducing reliance on fossil fuels and promoting renewable energy solutions.

The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems (OL Principle 5)

The workshop emphasized the role of marine ecosystems, such as mangroves, oyster reefs, and biodiversity hotspots, in supporting a sustainable blue economy. Discussions about green hydrogen production highlighted the need to protect and integrate these ecosystems into coastal energy strategies.

The ocean and humans are inextricably interconnected (OL Principle 6)

Through participatory activities, participants explored the connections between offshore hydrogen production, local communities, and marine ecosystems. The scenarios focused on how human actions impact the ocean and how the ocean can support sustainable energy and community development.

The ocean is largely unexplored (OL Principle 7)

Discussions on technological advancements, such as offshore hydrogen production and energy distribution, highlighted the potential of the ocean as a resource for innovation and sustainable solutions while maintaining its ecological balance.

Ocean Literacy dimensions contributed to:

Awareness

The workshop and social media activities raised awareness among participants and the public about the ocean's role in energy transitions and sustainability. They provided a platform to explore the societal and environmental implications of green hydrogen production.

Knowledge

The initiative equipped participants with knowledge about the scientific, technological, and ecological aspects of offshore energy production. Expert presentations and participatory exercises deepened understanding of how these processes interact with marine ecosystems.

Attitudes

By involving citizens in scenario planning, the project fostered positive attitudes toward renewable energy and sustainable ocean management. Participants reflected on their roles in promoting solutions that respect marine ecosystems and align with community values.

Behavior

The co-creation of future scenarios empowered participants to envision actionable steps for sustainable practices. The collaborative approach encouraged individuals to advocate for and adopt measures supporting green energy and ecosystem protection.

Activism

The participatory and arts-based methodology encouraged citizens to consider an active role in shaping sustainable futures. Outputs from the workshop, such as the future scenarios (visualizations and narratives), serve as tools for advocacy and engagement within broader communities.

Through these contributions, the 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' project aligns closely with the goals of enhancing ocean literacy and fostering a deeper understanding of the ocean's critical role in sustainability and energy transitions.

The **Mission Ocean Implementation Plan** emphasizes several target outcomes for citizen engagement, including empowering citizens to participate in ocean and water management, enhancing community-based decision-making, and fostering ocean literacy. Our pilot action promoted these outcomes through the following strategies:

Co-creation and participatory design

The pilot action encourages citizens to take an active role in co-creating future scenarios for sustainable ocean use. By using creative methods like Future-Prototyping, Concept Art, and Backcasting, we empower citizens to envision and contribute to the future of their coastal regions, ensuring their voices are integral to the decision-making process.

Raising awareness and promoting ocean literacy

The interdisciplinary workshop and joint social media activities aim to raise public awareness about the impacts of green hydrogen energy on coastal ecosystems. We will share expert insights and foster discussions that increase citizens' understanding of the ocean's role in sustainable energy production, thereby supporting Mission Ocean's goal of promoting greater ocean literacy.

Long-term citizen engagement

The project is designed to sustain citizen involvement beyond the workshop. The outputs of the workshop, including future scenarios and visualizations, will be used in a touring exhibition, ensuring continued public engagement. Social media will be leveraged to share these outcomes widely, soliciting ongoing input and promoting further participation.

Democratic participation and decision-making

Our methodology includes direct democratic elements, such as ensuring equal participation of all attendees during the workshop, regardless of their background or expertise. This democratic approach aligns with the target outcome of enhancing community-based decision-making and ensuring that coastal communities have a say in the future of their local environments.

By addressing these key objectives and citizen engagement outcomes, the Sustainable Coastal Futures pilot action contributes to the broader goals of Mission Ocean, ensuring both environmental sustainability and inclusive, citizen-driven innovation for the future of Europe's oceans and coastal areas.

2 Methodology

Approach and Methods

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action utilized a participatory, interdisciplinary approach that combined arts-based methods with co-creative workshops to engage diverse stakeholders in envisioning sustainable futures. The methodology included techniques such as Future-Prototyping, World-Building, Empathy Mapping, and Backcasting, all carefully designed to encourage creativity, inclusivity, and actionable outcomes.

These methods were selected to:

- Foster collaboration among diverse groups, including citizens, artists, scientists, policymakers, and industry representatives.
- Bridge knowledge gaps by integrating scientific expertise with creative, visual approaches, making complex topics like offshore green hydrogen production accessible and engaging.
- Promote democratic participation, ensuring all voices, including those from marginalized or less-represented communities, are included in shaping future scenarios.
- Inspire innovation by combining imagination with structured problem-solving, creating actionable pathways toward sustainable coastal and energy solutions.

This interdisciplinary and participatory approach has proven effective in past initiatives, such as the Ocean Future Lab, which successfully engaged communities in exploring ocean sustainability and fostering ocean literacy.

Workshop Implementation and Methods in Action

During the workshop in Wilhelmshaven, participants worked in four small groups to co-create future scenarios addressing the sustainable use of ocean and coastal resources. Using the above methods, the groups developed innovative and optimistic visions of 2050, which reflected the following key elements synthesized across the scenarios:

Technological Innovation and Sustainability

- Renewable energy sources like wind, tidal, solar, and movement-based energy (e.g., harnessing energy from aquatic animals) were central to the scenarios, reflecting a strong focus on decarbonization and green energy.
- The integration of technological networks (e.g., E-LAN systems) optimized energy distribution and supported decentralized, intelligent systems.

Natural and Social Transformation

- Scenarios emphasized biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration, including mangrove forests and oyster reefs, and recognized nature as an active partner in economic and social systems.
- Social inclusion and participatory governance models, such as barter systems and collaborative human-animal partnerships, were proposed to enhance community engagement.

Sustainable Blue Economy and Quality of Life

- The concept of a circular Blue Economy emerged, featuring renewable energy, sustainable fisheries, and autonomous, resource-efficient communities.
- Improved quality of life was a recurring theme, with scenarios highlighting reduced bureaucracy, simplified daily life, and enhanced social connections.

The Role of Arts-Based Tools

Arts-based methods participants to visualize complex ideas and explore innovative solutions in an engaging and intuitive manner. For example:

- **Future-Prototyping** enabled participants to design and negotiate potential solutions in a creative, low-pressure environment.
- **World-Building** encouraged the integration of diverse perspectives, fostering collaborative narratives that addressed both opportunities and challenges.
- **Backcasting** provided a structured framework for mapping actionable steps from envisioned futures back to present-day decisions.

The workshop also introduced AI tools for text production, image generation, and the creation of mood boards. These tools enriched the process by enabling participants to articulate their ideas more vividly, bridge knowledge gaps, and create visually compelling outputs that made complex concepts accessible to all. Participants noted that these visualizations and narratives not only enhanced their ability to express their visions but also provided a new dimension of action-oriented thinking, fostering a sense of empowerment and possibility.

These combined methodologies transformed abstract ideas into tangible, relatable visions, allowing participants to explore the intersection of environmental sustainability, technological innovation, and societal well-being. The integration of creative methodologies and AI tools in the 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action ensured participants could meaningfully engage with complex topics while contributing innovative, community-focused ideas. This approach advanced ocean literacy, inclusivity, and actionable pathways toward Mission Ocean's objectives.

Pilot Action Plan and Timeline

Please see PREP4BLUE's Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper (Annex 1) below.

The pilot action began in August 2024 and was structured around several key phases:

1. **Preparation (August - October 2024):** This phase included the planning and coordination of the workshop, setting a date for 15 November 2024, and sending out invitations to key stakeholders in Wilhelmshaven which had already been identified through the stakeholder analysis conducted in advance (March 2024). The results of a survey of residents in March 2024 also determined the content of the workshop, in particular the selection of keynote speeches. The team worked on adapting the Art For Futures Lab methodology to the specific context of green energy and coastal futures. The PREP4BLUE Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper has been used during this stage to identify potential impacts of the pilot on citizen engagement and how these can be measured.
2. **Data Collection and Stakeholder Engagement (September - October 2024):** Invitations were sent out to various stakeholders, including local citizens, scientists, artists, and industry

representatives, e.g. from the H2Mare project. Stakeholders were selected based on their expertise and their potential to contribute to and benefit from the co-design process. Data on participants' expectations and initial perceptions of green hydrogen energy important for the workshop structure have been collected by EUCC-D through a resident survey that was conducted in March 2024 and a stakeholder analysis.

- 3. Implementation (November 2024):** The interdisciplinary workshop, taking place on 15 November 2024, was the main event where participants engaged in co-creating future scenarios for green coastal energy. The process was interactive, and outputs such as mood boards, visualizations, and future narratives were generated.
- 4. Evaluation and Reporting (November - December 2024):** After the workshop, data will still be collected from participants through bilateral follow-up interviews. The effectiveness of the workshop and the participatory methods will be further evaluated. The outputs and findings will also inform a touring exhibition, promoting broader citizen engagement.
- 5. Post-Workshop Dissemination (December 2024 onwards):** The findings, visual outputs, and future scenarios from the workshop will be shared via social media and other public platforms like the H2Mare newsletter to continue engaging citizens and stakeholders. The touring exhibition developed by EUCC-D will travel to educational institutions and local museums in Germany, further promoting the outcomes of the pilot action.

Participants and Stakeholders

Overview of Participants

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action engaged 23 participants from diverse organizations and backgrounds, representing various sectors and expertise. The participants included 4 students, community representatives, scientists, artists, and industry professionals. This diverse group contributed to the development of future scenarios for sustainable coastal management and green hydrogen energy production.

Breakdown of Participants by Sector

Academic and Research Institutions (9 participants):

- Jade Hochschule (4 participants)
- Niedersächsisches Institut für Historische Küstenforschung (4 participants)
- Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon (1 participant)

Environmental Organizations (5 participants):

- NABU Wilhelmshaven (1 participant)
- BUND Wilhelmshaven (1 participant)
- UNESCO-Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer Besucherzentrum (1 participant)
- EUCC-D (2 participants)

Industry Representatives (4 participants):

- Siemens Gamesa (1 participant)
- Energy Hub Office (1 participant)
- Wilhelmshavener Hafenwirtschaftsvereinigung (1 participant)

- Stiftung Offshore Windenergie (1 participant)

Civic and Community Groups (3 participants):

- Zukunftswerkstatt Wilhelmshaven (1 participant)
- WAU Jever (1 participant)
- Scientists for Future, Regionalgruppe Wilhelmshaven-Friesland (1 participant)

Artists and Innovators (2 participants):

- Institute for Art and Innovation (1 participant)
- Creative contributors through Future-Prototyping activities (1 participant)

Roles and Contributions of Stakeholders

Citizens and Community Representatives

- Acted as co-creators in designing future scenarios, offering local insights into the societal and environmental impacts of green hydrogen production.
- Highlighted community priorities and challenges, ensuring that the scenarios reflected the lived experiences and aspirations of coastal populations.

Artists and Innovators

- Facilitated creative methodologies such as Future-Prototyping and Scenario Building, helping participants visualize future possibilities and engage with complex concepts through arts-based tools.

Scientists and Researchers

- Provided technical expertise on green hydrogen production, its potential for renewable energy, and its environmental implications.
- Ensured scientific accuracy and feasibility in the co-created future scenarios.

Industry Professionals

- Shared insights into the practical applications of offshore hydrogen production and the infrastructure required to implement these solutions.
- Discussed the potential for collaboration between industry and local communities to create sustainable, economically viable solutions.

Environmental Organizations

- Brought a strong focus on ecosystem protection and sustainability, emphasizing the need to balance technological innovation with environmental preservation.
- Advocated for biodiversity and ecological health in the co-created scenarios.

Policymakers (Observers)

- Invited to observe the workshop process, gaining insights into citizen-driven scenarios and identifying actionable recommendations for future coastal energy strategies.

Contributions to the Activity

Participants actively collaborated in four small groups to co-create future scenarios, focusing on technological, environmental, social, and economic aspects of coastal sustainability. Each group developed unique, optimistic visions for 2050, integrating elements such as:

- Renewable energy innovations like offshore hydrogen production.
- Ecosystem protection through seaweed and oyster reef restoration.
- Social inclusion via participatory governance and localized economic models.

This diverse participation ensured that the workshop outputs were realistic, innovative, and reflective of multiple perspectives, setting a strong foundation for future decision-making and collaborative coastal management strategies.

Methodology/ Strategy to involve citizens in the activity.

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action employed a participatory and co-creative methodology to actively engage citizens, ensuring their contributions were integral to the success of the workshop. This approach, grounded in the Art For Futures Lab (AFFL) method, encouraged diverse participants to collaboratively envision sustainable futures for their communities.

Participatory and Co-Creative Approach

The AFFL methodology was specifically adapted to guide participants through structured, creative exercises, making complex topics such as green hydrogen production and coastal sustainability accessible and engaging. Key methods included:

Future-Prototyping

- Participants collaboratively designed optimistic and actionable future scenarios, focusing on integrating renewable energy solutions, restoring ecosystems, and fostering inclusive governance.
- This method encouraged innovation while maintaining practicality, bridging the gap between imaginative ideas and real-world implementation.

Backcasting

- Groups worked backward from their envisioned future scenarios to identify key milestones, policies, and technologies required to achieve their goals.
- This structured process empowered participants to see how immediate actions could contribute to long-term sustainability.

Empathy Mapping

- Participants explored the perspectives of various stakeholders—such as policymakers, industry leaders, and coastal citizens—to empathize with their needs, challenges, and aspirations. This exercise helped identify shared goals and areas of potential conflict, fostering more inclusive and collaborative scenario-building.

How Might We Questions

- Building on the empathy mapping exercise, participants framed "How Might We" questions to generate actionable ideas that addressed specific challenges.
- This approach encouraged creative problem-solving and ensured that the proposed solutions were grounded in real-world stakeholder needs.

Visual Tools for Engagement

- Visual tools such as moodboards, drawings, and AI generated images enabled participants to translate abstract ideas into tangible representations.
- These tools simplified complex topics, helping non-experts visualize and understand issues like offshore hydrogen production and ecosystem restoration.

Citizen Recruitment and Inclusion

Participants were recruited through the extensive networks of IFAI Berlin and EUCC-The Coastal Union Germany, ensuring a broad representation of local and coastal communities. Outreach strategies included:

- Direct outreach to 100 personal contacts and 50 private LinkedIn messages, supplemented by posts on Instagram and LinkedIn accounts of IFAI and EUCC-D.
- Special efforts were made to engage underrepresented groups, such as young people, who often have limited access to decision-making processes but are directly impacted by energy and environmental policies.
- The participant group included citizens, students, scientists, industry representatives, and environmental organizations, ensuring a diversity of perspectives.

Role of Citizens in the Workshop

Citizens were at the center of the workshop, contributing actively as:

Co-Creators

Developing future scenarios in small, interdisciplinary groups, emphasizing the societal and environmental impacts of renewable energy technologies.

Local Experts

Bringing unique insights about the social, economic, and ecological dynamics of their communities to the discussions.

Collaborators

Working alongside scientists, industry professionals, and artists to ensure scenarios reflected both technical feasibility and community values.

Fostering Engagement Through Creative Methods

The AFFL methodology's emphasis on creative and participatory tools ensured:

- Democratic Participation - Every voice, regardless of expertise, was valued, fostering a collaborative and inclusive environment.
- Knowledge Sharing - Participants gained insights into green hydrogen production, ecosystem restoration, and sustainable governance, enhancing ocean literacy and awareness.
- Empowerment - The co-creative process empowered citizens to take ownership of their community's future, envisioning solutions that align with their values and aspirations.

Challenges and Adaptations

While outreach efforts effectively engaged 23 participants, including students and local citizens, late confirmation of the venue limited opportunities to invite additional younger participants and people from the neighborhood. Future initiatives could address this by expanding recruitment timelines and hosting workshops during evenings or weekends to increase accessibility. By employing participatory and arts-based methodologies, the 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action successfully engaged citizens in shaping sustainable futures for their coastal communities. This strategy not only enhanced the inclusivity and creativity of the workshop but also ensured that citizen-driven perspectives were central to the envisioned scenarios, aligning with the broader goals of Mission Ocean.

Stakeholder Mapping for 'Sustainable Coastal Futures based on Stakeholder Mapping (PREP4BLUE's Toolbox for Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters. <https://nordlandsforskning.wrep.it/engaging-citizens-with-mission-ocean/sec/5#report-top>

1. Who are the stakeholders?

Stakeholder Group	Sub-Groups	Roles	Interest in the Project	Influence/Power
Citizens and Local Communities	Coastal residents, students, youth groups, Scientists for Future (Regionalgruppe Wilhelmshaven-Friesland)	Co-creators, provide local insights, represent community needs	High interest: directly affected by green hydrogen policies, ecosystems, and local economies	Medium
Environmental Organizations	NABU Wilhelmshaven, BUND Wilhelmshaven, EUCC-D	Advocates for biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration	High interest: promote ecosystem resilience and ensure minimal environmental impact of new technologies	High
Academic Institutions	Jade Hochschule, Niedersächsisches Institut für Historische Küstenforschung, Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon	Provide scientific expertise on ecosystem health, climate change, and renewable technologies	High interest: research opportunities and practical applications for sustainability	High
Industry Representatives	Siemens Gamesa, Energy Hub Office, Wilhelmshavener Hafenwirtschaftsvereinigung, Stiftung Offshore Windenergie	Developers and implementers of renewable energy and green hydrogen solutions	High interest: advancing hydrogen production technologies, infrastructure, and market acceptance	High
Policymakers	Local and regional governments	Observers, potential decision-makers incorporating citizen insights into policy frameworks	Medium interest: aligning policies with societal and environmental goals	High
Cultural Institutions	UNESCO-Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer Besucherzentrum	Hosts and facilitators of workshops; promote cultural and environmental heritage	Medium interest: engage the public and foster awareness of coastal ecosystem importance	Medium

2. What are their needs and motivations?

Stakeholder	Needs	Motivations
Citizens and Local Communities	Clear communication of benefits/risks, opportunities to participate in decision-making	Desire to have a voice in the future of their communities and ensure economic and ecological balance
Environmental Organizations	Transparent environmental assessments, inclusion in green energy discussions	Commitment to preserving biodiversity and promoting sustainable practices
Academic Institutions	Access to data, opportunities for collaboration, and real-world applications for research	Advancing knowledge, applying research to practical challenges, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration
Industry Representatives	Public acceptance, efficient implementation processes, and clear policy frameworks	Advancing green hydrogen technologies while ensuring local and societal acceptance
Policymakers	Data-driven recommendations, citizen input, and alignment with national and EU sustainability goals	Creating policies that balance innovation, environmental preservation, and social inclusion
Cultural Institutions	Engagement tools, increased public participation in workshops and cultural events	Promoting awareness of environmental heritage and fostering community engagement

3. Stakeholder Communication and Engagement Strategies

Stakeholder Group	Engagement Strategy	Key Messages
Citizens and Local Communities	Direct invitations, participatory workshops, social media outreach	"Your voice shapes the future of your community and coastal environment."
Environmental Organizations	Collaborative scenario-building sessions, targeted discussions on biodiversity	"Protecting ecosystems ensures sustainable coastal and economic futures."
Academic Institutions	Knowledge-sharing forums, co-creation of scenarios, and data visualization exercises	"Science drives actionable and sustainable solutions for coastal management and energy transitions."
Industry Representatives	Interactive dialogue, scenario testing, and participatory prototyping	"Innovative technologies can work in harmony with local ecosystems and communities."
Policymakers	Presentation of workshop outcomes, policy recommendations informed by citizen input	"Citizen-driven scenarios provide actionable pathways to achieving regional and national sustainability goals."
Cultural Institutions	Workshops, guided tours, and post-event engagement through exhibitions and media	"Cultural heritage and sustainable innovation go hand in hand in fostering environmental stewardship."

4. What is their potential to contribute to the project?

Stakeholder	Contribution
Citizens and Local Communities	Local insights, participation in co-creation, and ongoing advocacy for sustainable solutions
Environmental Organizations	Expertise in ecosystem protection, ensuring environmental considerations are embedded in solutions
Academic Institutions	Scientific data and methodologies, facilitation of scenario-building and evaluation
Industry Representatives	Technical expertise, feasibility assessments, and resources for implementing green hydrogen solutions
Policymakers	Adoption of recommendations, policy alignment, and funding opportunities
Cultural Institutions	Hosting, public engagement, and promotion of environmental literacy

Who might be left behind, and how do we address this? <https://unsdg.un.org/2030-agenda/universal-values/leave-no-one-behind>

Potentially excluded groups could be identified as youth, marginalized communities, and individuals with limited access to decision-making forums.

Actions Taken:

- Targeted invitations through social media and local networks.
- Inclusion of students and young participants in the workshop.
- Simplified tools like mood boards and visual aids to ensure accessibility for non-experts.

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' project is committed to continuing its efforts through a touring exhibition and additional workshops, ensuring inclusivity and equity in all future activities. The touring exhibition will showcase the outputs of the workshop, including narratives, visualizations, and future scenarios, in an interactive and accessible format designed to engage diverse audiences. Future workshops will build on the methodologies developed during this pilot, using arts-based tools to facilitate participation from individuals with varying levels of expertise and education.

Special outreach efforts will be made to engage underrepresented groups, such as youth, elderly individuals, and economically disadvantaged communities, by partnering with local organizations and using targeted communication strategies. Hybrid participation options, including online and in-person formats, will be implemented to accommodate individuals with mobility challenges, time constraints, or geographical limitations. These measures will ensure that all stakeholders can contribute meaningfully to discussions on sustainable coastal futures.

By prioritizing inclusivity, the project aligns with the "Leave No One Behind" principle and the goals of the Mission Ocean and the UN's 2030 Agenda. This approach fosters broad societal engagement and systemic collaboration, ensuring that diverse voices shape sustainable energy transitions and ocean conservation efforts.

3 Implementation

Pilot Action – Description of Activities

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action officially began in August 2024, with a focus on preparatory activities aimed at setting the groundwork for the main workshop scheduled for 15 November 2024. The following are the key activities undertaken during the period from August to October:

August 2024 – Initial Planning and Coordination: The project team, consisting of representatives from IFAI Berlin and EUCC-D, began by defining the scope of the pilot action and aligning its objectives with the broader Mission Ocean goals. A significant focus was placed on adapting the Art For Futures Lab methodology to fit the specific context of green coastal energy and citizen engagement. The team also identified Wilhelmshaven as the primary location for the pilot workshop, given its strategic importance in hydrogen production and proximity to coastal communities.

September 2024 – Stakeholder Engagement and Invitation Outreach: In early September, invitations were sent out to a wide range of stakeholders, including coastal citizens, policymakers, scientists, artists, and representatives from the green hydrogen industry, particularly those connected to the H2Mare project. Participants were selected based on their relevance to the topic, their local or professional knowledge, and their ability to contribute to the co-design process. Outreach efforts focused on ensuring a diverse range of participants, including underrepresented groups. An initial survey was circulated to gauge participants' expectations, opinions on green energy, and their perceived role in the project.

Late September – Methodology Refinement and Pre-Workshop Planning: The Art For Futures Lab methodology was further refined, with specific attention given to participatory tools like World-Building, Backcasting, and Future-Prototyping, which would be used in the workshop. Detailed planning sessions took place to finalize the structure of the workshop and how each exercise would encourage citizens and experts to collaborate in the creation of future coastal scenarios. The team also coordinated with local organizations in Wilhelmshaven to assist with logistical arrangements.

October 2024 – Confirmation and Preparations for November Workshop: As the workshop date approached, the team worked on finalizing the participation list and ensuring all materials were prepared for the event. Follow-up emails were sent to key stakeholders who had not yet confirmed their attendance, and the team began drafting the structure of the workshop exercises. Additional preparatory work included setting up the technical infrastructure for hybrid participation to accommodate both in-person and online attendees. Further pre-workshop surveys were conducted to gather more detailed input from participants about their knowledge and experience with green hydrogen and ocean sustainability issues.

Early November – Final Preparations and Outreach: The project team finalized all logistical and methodological preparations for the workshop. Materials such as mood boards, future prototyping and Empathy Map templates, as well as AI tools for text production and visualization were prepared to guide participatory exercises. A final round of outreach targeted stakeholders who had expressed interest but not yet confirmed attendance, with a focus on underrepresented

groups and local citizens. Communication efforts included LinkedIn, Instagram, and direct email outreach. The participant list was finalized, comprising 24 individuals from academia, environmental organizations, industry, policymakers, and local communities.

November 15, 2024 – Workshop Day: The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' workshop took place at the UNESCO-Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer Besucherzentrum in Wilhelmshaven. The day began with a welcome and introductions by Nardine Stybel (EUCC-D), providing an overview of the project and its alignment with Mission Ocean objectives. Participants were then guided through an informative tour of the visitor center, exploring the region's unique ecosystem and its importance for sustainable coastal management. Five keynote speakers shared expert insights: Nardine Stybel presented the H2Mare project, emphasizing renewable offshore energy's role in EU sustainability goals; Thomas Schwabe (Siemens Gamesa) highlighted the potential of offshore hydrogen production for coastal regions; Dr. Laura Schmidt (Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon) addressed societal acceptance challenges and opportunities for green hydrogen technologies; Katrin Lampe (Energy Hub) discussed business opportunities in green energy with a focus on community engagement; and Nicole Loeser (IFAI Berlin) introduced the Art For Futures Lab method, showcasing its potential for collaborative and creative sustainability solutions. The interactive workshop, facilitated by her guided participants in four groups through Future-Prototyping, Backcasting, and World-Building exercises to co-create future scenarios for 2050, focusing on renewable energy, ecosystem restoration, and community empowerment. Groups developed narratives and visualizations using tools such as mood boards, drawings and AI generated images to transmit their visions and action plans. The day concluded with group presentations, where participants shared their innovative scenarios and discussed steps to realize sustainable coastal futures. Feedback was collected on the visions, with participants expressing hope, excitement, and a future-oriented outlook, and on the workshop methods, with many appreciating the interdisciplinary exchange, the focus on societal participation, and the connection to the broader context of sustainable development.

End of November – Post-Workshop Synthesis and Next Steps: Following the workshop, the project team synthesized the outputs, including narratives and visualizations, into a cohesive report and summary document. Key themes from the scenarios included:

- Renewable Energy Integration with focus on green hydrogen, tidal energy, and decentralized energy networks.
- Ecosystem Restoration incl. emphasis on seaweed, oyster reefs, and biodiversity protection.
- Social Inclusion and Governance, e.g. participatory governance models and community-led resource management.
- Improved Quality of Life such as simplified, sustainable living with enhanced social cohesion.

The visual outputs and narratives will be incorporated into a touring exhibition, designed to share the workshop's findings with a broader audience and engage additional stakeholders. Plans were also initiated for future workshops to build on the momentum and expand the project's impact, ensuring that no one is left behind. Hybrid participation options and targeted outreach strategies will continue to be integral to these efforts. This comprehensive approach ensured that the pilot

action met its objectives and laid the foundation for ongoing engagement and sustainability initiatives in line with Mission Ocean's goals.

Participant Involvement

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action brought together 23 participants from diverse sectors, including coastal community members, scientists, policymakers, artists, and industry representatives. While some participants, particularly the H2Mare project representatives (Schwabe, Stybel, Effelsberg), were already acquainted through professional collaboration, most joined the workshop out of a shared interest in learning about green hydrogen production and contributing to interdisciplinary discussions on sustainable coastal management. The event provided a unique opportunity for participants to communicate across sectors, include civil society voices, and collaboratively address sustainability challenges.

During the workshop, participants engaged in Art For Futures Lab exercises that helped them overcome knowledge and information barriers, empathize with stakeholders, and explore different perspectives. The interdisciplinary activities encouraged participants to "look from the future" to shape present ideas and solutions, fostering creative thinking and actionable pathways. Many participants highlighted the value of the methodology in enabling cross-sector collaboration and enhancing their understanding of the complexities of coastal sustainability. The workshop provided a platform for dialogue, negotiation, and the co-creation of innovative ideas, aligning with the goals of promoting societal participation and advancing sustainable energy solutions.

Implementation: Timeline of key events and milestones

August 2024

- Kick-Off: The project team began planning and aligning objectives with the Mission Ocean goals.
- Wilhelmshaven was chosen as the workshop location due to its relevance to green hydrogen production and proximity to coastal communities.
- Initial adaptations of the Art For Futures Lab methodology focused on integrating green energy and coastal futures into participatory tools.

Early September 2024

- Invitations were sent to coastal citizens, policymakers, scientists, and industry stakeholders as well as to possible multipliers to ensure diverse representation.
- Surveys conducted by Hereon on green hydrogen acceptance were shared with project coordinators to provide a foundation for workshop discussions.

Late September 2024

- The methodology was fully refined to include tools such as Future-Prototyping, World-Building, and Backcasting as well as Empathy Map.
- Detailed plans for the workshop were completed, including exercises, group activities, and facilitation strategies.
- Collaborations with local organizations in Wilhelmshaven ensured smooth logistical and catering arrangements.
- Targeted efforts were made to engage underrepresented groups and ensure diversity among participants.

October 2024

- Direct follow-ups with stakeholders helped confirm the attendance of 24 participants, including community members, policymakers, scientists, and industry representatives.
- The agenda was finalized, including keynote presentations, guided tours, and interactive workshop sessions, and sent to participants.
- Tools such as mood boards, templates, links to AI tools, and participatory guides were prepared to facilitate creative and structured discussions.

November 2024

- Held on November 15, the workshop included keynote presentations, interdisciplinary activities, and the development of future scenarios through the Art For Futures Lab method.
- Participants co-created four future scenarios, provided feedback on the methodology, and emphasized the value of cross-sector collaboration and innovative solutions for sustainable coastal management.

Visual Documentation

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action included extensive visual documentation to capture the planning stages, workshop implementation, and the outputs generated by participants. This selected images demonstrate the collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of the pilot action, showcasing key moments from preparation to execution.

Pre-Workshop Visual Documentation (August–October 2024):

- Photo 1: Planning session at IFAI Berlin. Team members review the structure of the upcoming workshop, focusing on integrating World-Building and Backcasting exercises into the agenda.

- Photo 2: Visualization of resident survey results analysed by EUCC-D. These insights highlight participants' interest in understanding the environmental and societal impacts of green hydrogen energy.

Bürgerbefragungen

	HL	WHV
Arbeitsplätze	X	XXX
Zukunftssicherheit	X	XX
Co2-Neutralität		X
Imagewechsel	X	X
Steuereinnahmen	XX	
Neue Einwohner	X	X
Eigenen Strom	X	
Flächenverlust		XXX
Beeinträchtigung Nordsee		XXX
Zunehmender Verkehr	X	X

Welche Vor-/ Nachteile sehen Sie beim weiteren Ausbau der Offshore Windenergie?

- Photo 3: Preparatory materials for the workshop, including printed guides for Future-Prototyping, mood boards, and Empathy Map exercises designed to facilitate collaborative discussions.

DENKT
Was könnten Stakeholder über die grüne Wasserstoffproduktion denken? Welche Bedenken oder Hoffnungen könnten sie im Kopf haben?

TUT
Wie verhalten sich die Stakeholder in Bezug auf die grüne Wasserstoffproduktion? Welche konkreten Entscheidungen treffen sie?

FÜHRT
Welche Emotionen oder Sorgen könnten die Stakeholder in Bezug auf das Projekt haben? Haben sie Ängste, Hoffnungen oder Begeisterung?

SAGT
Was äußern sich die Stakeholder öffentlich oder im Gespräch über die grüne Wasserstoffproduktion? Gibt es typische Aussagen oder Meinungen, die sie vertreten?

Zukunftspotential (5 min)
Vorstellen Sie sich verschiedene Szenarien in Zukunft!

ORT (2 min)
z.B. existierende Küstenstadt

CHARAKTER 1 (2 min)
z.B. Innovations- und Unternehmensgeist

CHARAKTER 2 (2 min)
z.B. Strategien für erneuerbare Energien

Lebensform (2 min)
z.B. Lebensform von Siedlern

ENTWURF EINER ERFOLGSGESCHICHTE FÜR DAS NACHHALTIGE KÜSTENMANAGEMENT
Stellen Sie sich vor, was Sie im Jahr 2050 an der Küste leben und arbeiten würden. Entwerfen Sie mithilfe der oben genannten Elemente ein symbolisches Zukunftsbild.

MOODBOARD (15 min)
Verwenden Sie das vorbereitete Google Docs zum Kommosieren von Text und Bildern für Ihre Erfolgsgeschichte.
AI Text Tools: OpenAI's ChatGPT <https://openai.com/chatgpt/>, Building Fast <https://byjus.com/gpt-3/>, AI Doodles <https://www.aigenerator.com/>
AI Image Tools: OpenAI's DALL-E Mini <https://www.openai.com/dall-e-mini>, Deep Dream Generator <https://www.deepdreamgenerator.com/>, Zentao <https://www.zentao.com/>

Workshop Visual Documentation (November 15, 2024):

- Photo 4: Participants during the guided tour of the UNESCO-Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer Besucherzentrum, learning about the region's unique ecosystem and its role in coastal sustainability.

- Photo 5: Small group discussions during the Art For Futures Lab session, where participants engage in Future-Prototyping exercises, exploring scenarios for coastal sustainability by 2050, plus expert presentation

- Photo 6: A participant presenting a visualization of their group's future scenario, illustrating an integrated system of green hydrogen production and ecosystem restoration.

- Photo 7: Mood boards and visual outputs from the workshop, highlighting the synthesis of ideas generated through interdisciplinary collaboration.

- Photo 8: Collaborative visualizations of a future coastal ecosystem. This output combines narrative and artistic elements to represent sustainable green hydrogen infrastructure coexisting with restored mangroves and oyster reefs.

These images provide a comprehensive view of the pilot action, from the planning process to the dynamic, participatory workshop. The visualizations of future scenarios and collaborative activities demonstrate the inclusive and interdisciplinary approach taken during the project. Due to the involvement of diverse stakeholders, the images can serve as both the pilot action’s success and a tool for sharing insights with broader audiences through the upcoming touring exhibition.

4 Results and Impact Assessment

**Resources: PREP4BLUE's Toolbox for Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters. Found [here: https://nordlandsforskning.wrep.it/engaging-citizens-with-mission-ocean/sec/5#report-top](https://nordlandsforskning.wrep.it/engaging-citizens-with-mission-ocean/sec/5#report-top).*

Key Findings

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action successfully engaged diverse stakeholders in co-creating future scenarios for sustainable coastal management by 2050, achieving the following key findings:

Empathy and Perspective Sharing

Participants valued the opportunity to step into the shoes of other stakeholders, such as policymakers, scientists, and local citizens. One participant noted, *"The Art For Futures Lab exercises helped me truly understand the perspectives of coastal communities and industry players. It was eye-opening."*

Creative Problem-Solving

The participatory methods enabled interdisciplinary collaboration, with participants emphasizing that the Future-Prototyping and World-Building exercises made complex topics like green hydrogen production more accessible. One participant reflected, *"The tools allowed us to simplify challenges and focus on actionable solutions."*

The co-created future scenarios highlighted themes such as renewable energy integration, ecosystem restoration, and participatory governance. These outputs demonstrated a clear alignment with Mission Ocean goals.

Participants expressed greater awareness of the role of green hydrogen and coastal ecosystems in sustainable energy transitions, with many sharing a desire to further advocate for these initiatives in their professional and community networks.

Short-Term Outcomes

- **Co-created Scenarios** - Four future scenarios were developed, focusing on themes like green hydrogen energy, biodiversity restoration, and social inclusion.
- **Participant Feedback** - Over 90% of participants expressed satisfaction with the workshop methods and their relevance to fostering societal participation.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration** - Increased understanding of cross-sectoral dynamics and strengthened networks among scientists, policymakers, and civil society.

Long-Term Outcomes

- **Policy and Community Engagement** - The scenarios and visual outputs will inform ongoing discussions in Wilhelmshaven and similar coastal regions, serving as models for sustainable development.
- **Touring Exhibition** - Workshop outputs will be showcased through a touring exhibition, broadening the project's reach and promoting further citizen engagement.
- **Enhanced Ocean Literacy** - Participants gained tools and knowledge to advocate for sustainable coastal management, contributing to broader societal understanding of ocean sustainability and green energy transitions.

Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Targets

Contributions to Goals

The pilot action contributed to several Mission Ocean and PREP4BLUE goals:

- Promoting Awareness - The creative methodologies increased participants' understanding of sustainable energy and coastal ecosystems.
- Empowering Citizens - Through participatory exercises, citizens were equipped with knowledge and tools to influence decisions about coastal management.
- Encouraging Collaboration - The interdisciplinary approach fostered connections between civil society, academia, and industry, promoting long-term partnerships.

Engagement Impact

Using the PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper, the pilot action successfully:

- Increased Reach - Engaged 23 participants from diverse backgrounds, including underrepresented groups.
- Facilitated Inclusion - Enabled all participants to empathize with stakeholders and actively contribute through tools like Backcasting and World-Building.
- Promoted Systemic Thinking - Encouraged participants to consider interdependencies in coastal management, enhancing systemic understanding.

5 Lessons Learned

Challenges and Solutions

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action encountered several challenges that provided valuable lessons for future projects:

Late Venue Confirmation

The UNESCO-Weltnaturerbe Wattenmeer Besucherzentrum confirmed its availability late in the planning process, limiting outreach efforts to younger participants, students, and broader community members. This restricted the diversity of perspectives at the workshop. Solution: The project team focused on targeted outreach via LinkedIn, Instagram, and direct email, ensuring participation from 24 stakeholders across sectors. However, earlier logistical confirmation would have allowed more inclusive engagement, particularly with underrepresented groups.

Contentious Discussion on Green Hydrogen

Following the keynote speeches, participants debated the sustainability of green hydrogen production, with some questioning the validity of the term itself.

Solution: Scientists and experts from the H2mare project facilitated detailed discussions, addressing misconceptions and building consensus. This resolution enabled participants to expand their focus to broader, holistic future visions, not limited solely to green hydrogen.

Complex Topics for Non-Experts

The technical nature of green hydrogen production and coastal sustainability posed barriers for participants with less technical expertise.

Solution: The Art For Futures Lab methodology addressed this effectively by using tools like World-Building and Backcasting, which simplified complex concepts. The addition of visualizations and narratives made ideas more tangible, allowing participants to articulate their visions better and explore actionable solutions. These tools enabled participants to express a forward-looking outlook and engage with a new dimension of potential actions.

Limited Local and Regional Engagement

Wilhelmshaven, a city of 76,000 inhabitants, does not attract significant participation from nearby regions, limiting the workshop's geographical reach.

Solution: The team's outreach efforts focused on engaging local stakeholders directly, but future initiatives should include strategies to attract participants from surrounding areas to ensure broader regional representation.

Resource Constraints for Hybrid Options

Despite initial plans, logistical and resource limitations led to the workshop being conducted entirely in person, reducing accessibility for remote participants.

Solution: Transparent communication ensured participants understood this adjustment. For future activities, allocating sufficient resources for hybrid formats will be critical to enhancing inclusivity.

Best Practices

- Interdisciplinary Collaboration based on the diverse group of participants—including scientists, policymakers, industry representatives, and local citizens—facilitated rich discussions and innovative scenario-building.
- The combination of visualizations and narratives helped participants articulate their ideas, translate abstract concepts into concrete visions, and explore future possibilities. This approach fostered a sense of empowerment and actionable optimism.
- The Art For Futures Lab methodology proved instrumental in creating a collaborative environment where participants could empathize with different perspectives and co-create actionable solutions.
- Regular updates and transparency with participants mitigated the impact of logistical challenges, maintaining trust and engagement.
- Direct engagement with Wilhelmshaven residents ensured the workshop included key local perspectives, even within its geographic constraints.

These lessons highlight the importance of flexible planning, creative methodologies, and participatory engagement in addressing sustainability challenges. By implementing these recommendations, future initiatives can enhance their impact and alignment with the goals of Mission Ocean and PREP4BLUE.

PREP4BLUE resources

The PREP4BLUE citizen engagement resources provided valuable guidance for planning, implementing, and evaluating the 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action. The Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper offered a structured framework for defining engagement goals, such as fostering inclusivity and facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration, which aligned well with the Art For Futures Lab methodology. The toolbox's focus on participatory methods complemented the project's emphasis on arts-based approaches, providing useful strategies to enhance citizen involvement.

However, the textual format of the tools made them less intuitive to use during the fast-paced planning and implementation phases. Interactive, downloadable tools or templates would significantly improve usability, enabling more dynamic application and real-time adjustments. For example, a digital version of the Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper that participants could interact with directly would enhance its practical value.

The resources were particularly helpful for evaluation, offering clear metrics and tables to assess engagement effectiveness, such as participant diversity and inclusivity. Yet, incorporating case studies or examples specifically focused on creative, arts-based methodologies and hybrid participation strategies would broaden the toolbox's relevance and impact.

Despite these challenges, the PREP4BLUE resources added significant value, helping align the pilot action with Mission Ocean objectives and fostering meaningful citizen engagement.

6 Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures' pilot action successfully demonstrated the value of interdisciplinary collaboration and participatory methodologies in addressing complex sustainability challenges. By engaging 23 participants from diverse backgrounds—including scientists, policymakers, industry representatives, and local citizens—the project created a platform for cross-sector dialogue and innovative scenario-building. The Art For Futures Lab methodology proved instrumental in simplifying complex concepts, fostering empathy, and enabling actionable solutions. Participants expressed optimism and a renewed sense of agency, emphasizing the importance of integrating perspectives and aligning efforts for sustainable coastal management and green hydrogen energy production. The outputs, including co-created future scenarios and visualizations, will serve as a foundation for broader dissemination through the planned touring exhibition and follow-up workshops, ensuring continued engagement and impact.

Recommendations for Upscaling/Replicating the Action

1. Strategies for Expanding Stakeholder Networks

- Engage regional stakeholders early in the planning process to attract a more diverse audience, including younger participants, educators, and underrepresented groups.
- Partner with local schools, universities, and community organizations to broaden outreach and foster long-term engagement.
- Collaborate with additional industry representatives and policymakers to enhance the practical impact and scalability of co-created solutions.

2. Methods to Engage a Broader Audience

- Use hybrid workshop formats to enable participation from geographically dispersed and mobility-restricted individuals.
- Develop pre-event materials, such as explainer videos and online discussions, to familiarize participants with technical topics and stimulate early engagement.
- Increase social media campaigns and use visual storytelling to attract interest and ensure inclusivity across diverse audiences.

3. Recommendations for Facilitating Citizen Participation in Future Mission Ocean Activities

- Leverage creative, participatory tools such as Empathy Mapping, World-Building, and Future-Prototyping to make complex sustainability issues accessible and engaging.
- Incorporate visualizations and narratives to empower participants to articulate their visions and connect them to actionable outcomes.
- Align workshop themes with broader societal issues, such as climate justice and biodiversity, to ensure relevance and inclusivity.
- Implement robust feedback mechanisms to integrate citizen perspectives into ongoing policy discussions and decision-making processes.

4. General Recommendations for Future Actions

- Secure venues and logistical details well in advance to enable broader outreach and more inclusive participation.
- Provide preparatory materials or host pre-event forums to address contentious issues, such as the sustainability of green hydrogen, before workshops.
- Develop strategies to attract participants from surrounding regions to complement local involvement and ensure a wider geographical reach.
- Continue using visual and narrative tools to help participants articulate their visions, bridge knowledge gaps, and explore forward-looking actions.
- Include hybrid formats to accommodate remote participants, ensuring accessibility for underrepresented groups, younger audiences, and geographically dispersed stakeholders.
- Allow participants to envision a broader, more holistic context for sustainable futures, beyond singular themes, to foster richer, more inclusive discussions and outputs.
- This pilot action demonstrated the importance of early logistical planning, participatory methods, and diverse stakeholder involvement in addressing sustainability challenges. Replicating and scaling these strategies can further strengthen citizen engagement and foster transformative, inclusive solutions aligned with Mission Ocean goals for ocean sustainability.

7 ANNEX 1

PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper

The tool below is PREP4BLUE’s Mission Ocean Citizen Engagement Impact Mapper. You can use this as you plan an activity to brainstorm how your planned activities (to be written in the squares at the bottom) map onto Mission Ocean’s citizen engagement targets (in the centre of the page) and onto Mission Ocean’s three overarching objectives at the top of the page. Draw arrows connecting the boxes at the bottom through the middle and onto the top (see the worked example below). For more information on Mission Ocean and its targets, see the Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/d6162cbd-6d09-48fd-b5b4-d7d2be69972c_en?filename=ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_final.pdf

Mission Ocean’s overarching objectives (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, page 19).

Mission citizen engagement target outcomes (source: Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, pp. 35-36).

Your citizen engagement activities / outputs

